

InGRID

Integrating expertise in inclusive growth

www.inclusivegrowth.be

Working paper

WHAT DO WORKERS DO?

Measuring the intensity and market value of tasks in jobs

Kea Tijdens & Stefano Visintin

January 2016

This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Programme for Research, Technological Development and Demonstration under Grant Agreement No 312691

Abstract

Do occupational titles refer to the same work activities, as assumed in occupational classifications? Up to now, no large-scale empirical testing of this assumption has been conducted. Using the task descriptions provided for all ISCO 4-digit occupations, the frequency of task implementation was tested using respondents in the multi-country, multilingual WageIndicator web survey on work and wages in 13 countries. The web survey targets individuals in the labour force. Depending on their self-selected occupation, the relevant task list was shown and respondents were asked to tick on a 5-point scale how often they performed each task. For 427 occupations (ISCO-08 4-digits) in total 3,237 occupation-specific tasks were available. Between November 2013 and August 2015 33,678 respondents had completed the tasks questions for their respective occupations. The results show that task measurement is feasible because it can generate sufficient observations to allow for analysis for a range of detailed, 4-digit occupations. Moreover, given that the WageIndicator web survey also holds data on wages, the median and average hourly wages (in EUR) could be computed for each task separately, showing that the average wages of tasks performed on a daily or weekly basis ranged between EUR 5 and 34. The data collection challenges future empirical testing of hypotheses concerning the variation in task frequencies and their related wage premiums within and across countries, across occupations' skill levels, across firm sizes, across regions and alike.

This report constitutes Milestone 21.3, for Work Package 21 of the InGRID project.

January 2016

© 2016, Amsterdam – InGRID, Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – project number 312691

General contact: inclusive.growth@kuleuven.be

p.a. InGRID

HIVA - Research Institute for Work and Society
Parkstraat 47 box 5300, 3000 LEUVEN, Belgium

For more information K.G.Tijdens@uva.nl;

Please refer to this publication as follows:

Tijdens, K., & de Visintin, S. (2016). *What do workers do? Measuring the intensity and market value of tasks in jobs*, Working paper, Leuven, InGRID project, M21.3.

Information may be quoted provided the source is stated accurately and clearly.

This publication is also available via <http://www.inclusivegrowth.be/project-output>

This publication is part of the InGRID project, this project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Programme for Research, Technical Development and Demonstration under Grant Agreement No 312691.

The information and views set out in this paper are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of life or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

Contents

Abstract	2
1. Introduction	5
2. Review of previous tasks measurements	7
2.1 Introduction	7
2.2 Occupations are not similar, findings from the EurOccupations project	7
2.3 How to explain the findings?	8
3. Collecting data to compare job content	11
3.1 Task data collected via the <i>WageIndicator</i> web survey	11
3.2 Data and methodology	13
4. Estimating the market value of tasks in the Netherlands	15
5. Conclusions	19
appendix 1 List of the 427 ISCO-08 occupations 4-digit	21
appendix 2 List of tasks by occupation	33
appendix 3 Number of respondents by occupation and country	137
appendix 4 Most Frequent answer 1 = never - 5 = daily by occupation & task and by country	159
appendix 5 Ratio of valid answers on total respondents identified in each occupation, by task and country	233
appendix 6 Estimated market value of tasks in the Netherlands (EUR)	307
appendix 7 Country abbreviations	341
Bibliography	343

1. Introduction

ILO's hierarchical occupational classification ISCO-08 defines a job as a bundle of tasks and duties performed by one person (ILO 2012; Hunter, 2014). Jobs with the same set of main tasks and duties are aggregated into 433 occupation units at the 4-digit level of the classification. Thus, an occupational title refers to the same work activities. It assumes also that across countries, similar occupations are coded similarly into the classification. With occupations as a core concept, the challenge arises whether occupations indeed have similar meanings across and within countries. Hence, do similar occupational titles refer to the same job content? Unfortunately, an empirical basis for this assumption is lacking. For researchers the tasks in occupations are a black box. In labour force surveys, as well as in many other socio-economic surveys, the classification of respondents' jobs into occupations is almost solely based on job titles, and only in ambiguous cases coders explore the job description.

This Working Paper explores an innovative method to measure how frequently jobholders carry out tasks associated with their occupation and how much these tasks are valued in the labour market. Questions such as *do the same occupations reflect the same work activities within and across countries?* are addressed by exploring the descriptive statistics of the measurement of occupation-specific tasks in a web survey in 13 countries. Furthermore we embark on an exercise which final aim is to provide the market value (in EUR) of the implementation of those tasks.

The paper is deliverable D21.1.2 'Develop methods to facilitate the testing of the comparability of the job content of occupational titles as well as the skill requirements for these occupations across EU Member States' of InGRID work package 21 'Innovative tools and protocols for working conditions'. It is the second WP 21 deliverable about occupational measurement and coding.

The paper builds on previous work related to the task frequency measurement by Tijdens, De Ruijter and De Ruijter (2011; 2012; 2014), and Fabo and Tijdens (2014). Analysis of the task data have been undertaken by Milhaylov and Tijdens (2014), and Visintin *et al* (2015). Note that this paper solely focusses on the measurement of task frequencies in jobs, using a web survey of jobholders. It does not include the measurement of skills needed to perform the tasks, although skills represent the capacity to perform the tasks. Yet, the measurement of tasks may provide further ideas how to use web surveys for the measurement of skills.

Section 2 provides a review of the measurement of tasks in occupations in surveys in Europe. Section 3 specifies how the tasks have been measured in the web survey used here. Section 4 proposes and implements a methodology that estimates the market value of tasks. Section 5 drafts some conclusions. Appendix 1 shows the list of the 427 ISCO-08 occupations at 4-digits, for which the tasks were measured. Appendix 2 lists all tasks of these occupations. Appendix 3 provides tables with the mean scores on the tasks. Appendix 4 shows the most frequent answer for each task in each country. Appendix 5 collects the data on valid responses, in particular it shows the percentage of valid responses for each task in each country. Appendix 6 presents the results of the task values estimation. Appendix 7 holds a list of country abbreviations.

2. Review of previous tasks measurements

2.1 Introduction

Do similar job titles refer to the same work activities within and across countries? This question can also be phrased differently. Does an Italian carpenter engage in the same activities as a carpenter from Germany, Slovakia or the Netherlands? The practical relevance of this question refers to European policies to increase labour mobility across borders. The EURES job portal is an effort of the European Public Employment Services to encourage job seekers to find vacancies across borders.¹ Currently ESCO, which is an abbreviation for the European Skills, Competences and Occupations taxonomy, is developed, aiming to create a multilingual framework of occupations, skills, competences and qualifications and to support EURES in the aim to find jobs for job seekers.² The well-known O*NET® occupational information system in the United States of America stands as an example for ESCO. O*NET has a long tradition of empirical investigations of the content of occupations.³ Across European countries, hardly cross-national studies have been undertaken to explore if occupational titles have the same meaning beyond semantic similarities and thus if they include the same work activities.

The scientific relevance of the above mentioned question refers to the growing interest in occupations as a core concept in a range of academic disciplines. Occupations have been explored for almost a century in I/O psychology (Morgeson & Dierdorff, 2011), and for half a century in the sociology of occupations (e.g. Larson, 1977). In labour economics, the studies on gender segregation by occupation and equal pay exists for several decades (e.g. Reskin, 1984).

Beyond the scientific relevance of tasks stands their practical importance. Jobs are essentially composed by different working activities that produce output, namely tasks. Accordingly, the added value of a job can be decomposed in the value added by the implementation of each single task within it. Therefore, the price at which the implementation of each task is paid represents a key information in the process of wage setting.

2.2 Occupations are not similar, findings from the EurOccupations project

One of the first European attempts to measure the job content of occupations on a large scale was taken in the EurOccupations project, which ran from 2006 - 2009.⁴ Its research objective was dealing with the (broad) question: ‘Are occupations similar regarding work activities?’ (see Tijdens, De Ruijter & De Ruijter, 2011; 2012; 2014). The project established research teams in eight countries and aimed to, first, build a database containing almost 1,500 of the most frequent 5-digit ISCO-08 occupations for the eight countries;⁵ second, to test the similarity of the job content across the eight countries for 160 occupations selected from the database. The selection was based on variation in skill level, in gender composition, in number of jobholders, and coverage of all industries.

1 See <https://ec.europa.eu/eures/public/homepage>

2 See <https://ec.europa.eu/esco/portal/home#modal-one>

3 See <https://www.onetonline.org/>

4 EurOccupations aimed at developing a detailed 8-country occupations database for comparative socio-economic research in the European Union. Funded by EU-FP6 (no 028987, 2006-09) with BEL, DEU, ESP, FRA, GBR, ITA, NLD, POL, coordinated by KG Tijdens <http://www.wageindicator.org/main/Wageindicatorfoundation/projects/euroccp>

5 The WageIndicator Foundation has used this database for its continuous, worldwide web survey, but added more occupations and more languages.

Using desk research, the project partners drafted and tested 10 task descriptions for the 160 occupations, thereby building on the work of the O*NET® and its approach of analysing work activities by means of job-specific descriptions.⁶ A multilingual web survey was designed and in 2007 and 2008 the partners recruited experts through their networks and invited them to complete the survey for the occupations they were knowledgeable about. These experts had to rate the frequency of each task of the occupation at stake on a 5 point rating scale, ranging from never to daily. In total 2,468 experts completed 2,950 questionnaires. For a number of occupations the teams could however not find a sufficient number of experts. Then it was decided to recruit jobholders via the Internet, using teasers calling for survey respondents working in a specific occupation. The teasers were posted on the frequently visited national WageIndicator websites on work and wages, resulting in another 1,661 ratings.⁷ Even with over 4,100 ratings, the EurOccupations study encountered quite a number of occupations with none or insufficient ratings, and when broken down by country, the problem grew worse.

Using interrater agreement statistics (rWG) a lack of agreement or no agreement at all was shown for 51% of the 160 occupations, a weak or moderate agreement was so for 38%, whereas for only 12% of the occupation displayed a strong agreement (Tijdens, De Ruijter & De Ruijter, 2014). Across all occupations, in Spain agreement was 80%, in Germany 58%, in the Netherlands 43%, and in Poland 48%. The data revealed that jobholder ratings did not differ from expert ratings. The overall conclusion from the EurOccupations project was that although assumed that occupations are similar across countries, to a large extent they were not. Hence, the main conclusion was that the within-occupation similarity of tasks was rather an idea than a fact.

2.3 How to explain the findings?

This raised the question how to explain the unexpected findings? Are occupations diverse across European countries, and does it therefore make no sense to aim for labour mobility on occupational basis? Are the methods and data sources critical for the results, and could a larger sample size per occupation or a larger number than the 160 occupations improve the measurements? If so and if stuck to expert ratings, how to cope with the large resources needed for recruiting more experts? Is the aggregation level of the occupations appropriate to distinguish between different jobs and to group jobholders performing similar activities? Recalling that the EurOccupations study tested the similarity of occupations at a 5-digit level, would a testing of 4-digit occupations change the results? One conclusion from the EurOccupations study stood firmly: surveying occupation-specific task frequencies by means of a web survey was a proper way to test task similarity within occupations, for the technical features as well as for its cost-effectiveness in relation to the volume of respondents to be reached.

In 2013 two projects allowed for a follow-up of the EurOccupations project, notably the InGRID infrastructure and the EDUWORKS project.⁸ The follow-up study aimed to collect task frequency information for a larger number of occupations, for 4-digit occupations, for a greater number of countries and specifically from a much larger number of respondents. The EurOccupations project showed that the method to invite experts to rate task frequencies was costly in terms of human resources and that the method to invite jobholders was far less so. The project also showed that a web survey was a proper method to ask jobholders about their tasks. Hence the follow-up study needed a large-scale, multi-country web survey addressing jobholders. For several reasons the multi-country, multilingual, continuous WageIndicator web survey was particularly suited. The survey's advanced technologies allowed for a routing from respondent's self-selected occupation to the related tasks list. Finally, the follow-up study was feasible because of the expertise of the first author as the scientific coordinator of this web survey.

⁶ See <http://www.onetonline.org/>

⁷ See www.wageindicator.org

⁸ See <https://inclusivgrowth.be/> and <http://eduworks-network.eu/pages/home>

A recent development in the economic academic discourse focusses on the task-based approach analysing the evolution of salaries (their polarisation) and the role played by technological change with this respect (e.g. Autor *et al.*, 2003), offshorability of jobs intended as the possibility of performing specific tasks abroad (Grossman & Rossi-Hansberg, 2008) or the transferability of skills across occupations (Gathmann & Schonberg, 2010). This approach mostly classifies occupations according to a measure of routine task intensity, aiming to investigate the impact of technology on routine and non-routine tasks. This approach differs from that of EurOccupations, because the latter primarily aims for an understanding of the division of labour within occupations.

3. Collecting data to compare job content

3.1 Task data collected via the *WageIndicator* web survey

The *WageIndicator* web survey is posted continuously at national *WageIndicator* websites (www.wageindicator.org). The first *WageIndicator* website started in the Netherlands in 2001, and *WageIndicator* is operational today in 85 countries, receiving millions of visitors (25 million in 2014). Web traffic is high due to search engine optimisation, web-marketing, media attention, word-of-mouth advertising, and social media activities. The websites provide job-related content, labour law and minimum wage information, VIP wages, and a free salary check providing users salary references on the basis of personal characteristics such as occupation, country and experience. Salary estimations are based on the web survey data. The websites are consulted by employees, self-employed, students, job seekers, and individuals with a job on the side to find information about wages or for their annual performance talks, job mobility decisions, occupational choices and alike. In return for free information web visitors are invited to complete a questionnaire with a lottery prize incentive. Between 1% and 5% of all visitors completes the survey. Approximately 70,000 questionnaires are filled each year.⁹ The multilingual questionnaire is comparable across countries and is held in the national languages. It is composed by questions about a wide range of work and wage related subjects, including socio-demographics (Tijdens *et al.*, 2010). In 2001, the survey started in the Netherlands, with other countries gradually joining from 2005 onwards.

Task descriptions are core to the task frequency measurement. The EurOccupations project team drafted task lists for 160 occupations, using desk research. In the follow-up study, an existing tasks list could be used. For its ISCO update, ILO drafted descriptions of tasks for all 433 occupational units at 4-digit ISCO-08 (ILO, 201; Hunter, 2014). For the follow-up study task lists for 427 of the 433 units have been prepared (see Appendix 1 for the list of occupations). For six so-called ‘not-elsewhere-classified occupations’ no task lists have been included. The number of tasks varies per occupation, but the large majority of occupations have seven to ten tasks and for the remaining occupations the number of tasks varies between 4 and 14. In total 3,237 occupation-specific tasks are in use for the 427 occupations, which is on average 7.58 tasks per occupation (see Appendix 2 for the list of all tasks). The *WageIndicator* team adapted ILO’s task descriptions for the web survey.

The task lists have been translated from English into six other languages: Spanish, Russian, French, Dutch, Portuguese, and Bahasa.¹⁰ The tasks could therefore be included in the *WageIndicator* web survey in 13 countries, namely Argentina, Australia, Belarus, Belgium, Brazil, Indonesia, Kazakhstan, Mexico, Netherlands, Russia, South Africa, Spain and the United Kingdom (see Appendix 7 for the list of country abbreviations). These countries have been selected because they represent different regions around the world and have adequate response rates to the web survey. The data collection started in November 2013 and was still continuing at the time of writing this paper

The follow-up study aimed to explore the task frequency ratings of jobholders who are asked to rate their own job. In the web survey, respondents are asked to self-select their occupation. For the

⁹ Completed questionnaires are those filled in by respondents who have provided information about at least their wage, gender, time of first job, occupation title and level of education. In 2014, there were approximately 240,000 completed and uncompleted questionnaires.

¹⁰ The tasks were not translated with the aim to serve the study, but were to be posted in the so-called Jobs&Salary pages of the national *WageIndicator* websites. Each national website has 433 Jobs&Salary pages with information about the occupation. These pages act as so-called landing pages for a wide range of search terms used in Search Engines. Luckily, the translations could also be used for the web survey.

survey question ‘What is your occupation’, the WageIndicator web survey employs a lookup database that consists of approximately 1,700 occupational titles, all coded according to ISCO-08. The selection of occupation is displayed to the respondent as visible on Figure 3.1. Each ISCO-08 4-digit occupational unit comprises of at least one, but mostly more than one occupational title. To navigate the lookup table, respondents can choose to use a tool for text string matching or a search tree (Tijdens, 2014). Depending on the selected occupation, the survey system identifies the relevant ISCO-08 4-digit occupational unit and shows the associated tasks list. Respondents are asked to tick how frequently they carry out each task on the basis of five answer categories: *never*, *yearly*, *monthly*, *weekly* and *daily*. The tasks are displayed to the respondent as visible on Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.1 Screenshot for choice of occupation: selection Chemical engineer

Your occupation

What is your current occupation?

Please select your occupation.

🔍

Agriculture, nature, animals, environment

Care, children, welfare, social work

→ **Cars, mechanics, technicians, engineers**

Cleaning, housekeeping, garbage, waste

Clerks, secretaries, post, telephone

Commercial, shop, buy and sale

Construction, fittings, housing

Education, research, training

Finance, banking, insurance

Food manufacturing

Guards, army, police

HRM, labour intermediary, organisation

Health care, paramedics, laboratory

Hospitality, tourism, leisure, sports

IT, automation, telecommunication

Industrial production, manufacture

Cars

Draughtsman

Electrical

→ **Engineer**

Engineering technician

Mechanic, electrician

Petrol station

Research, consultancy

Support services (internal)

Aerospace engineer

Aircraft engineer

Automotive engineer

Chemical engineer

Civil engineer

Dredging engineer

Electrical engineer (professional)

Electronics engineer

Engineering department manager

Environmental engineer

Health and safety engineer

Hydraulics engineer

Industrial engineer

Installation or repairs department manager

Logistics engineer

Marine engineer

Materials engineer

Mechanical engineer

« Previous
Next »

Source WageIndicator web survey: Paywizard.co.uk

Figure 3.2 Screenshot for the task set of the Chemical engineer

In your current job, how often do you carry out the following tasks?						
	Never	Yearly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily	Not applicable
Conducting research and advising on, and developing commercial-scale chemical processes to refine crude oil and other liquids or gases, and to produce substances and items such as petroleum derivatives, explosives, food and drink products, medicines, or synthetic materials	<input type="radio"/>					
Specifying chemical production methods, materials and quality standards and ensuring that they conform to specifications	<input type="radio"/>					
Establishing control standards and procedures to ensure safety and efficiency of chemical production operations and safety of workers operating equipment or working in close proximity to on-going chemical reactions	<input type="radio"/>					
Designing chemical plant equipment and devising processes for manufacturing chemicals and products	<input type="radio"/>					
Performing tests throughout stages of production to determine degree of control over variables, including temperature, density, specific gravity, and pressure	<input type="radio"/>					
Developing safety procedures to be employed	<input type="radio"/>					
Preparing estimates of production costs and production progress reports for management	<input type="radio"/>					
Performing laboratory studies of steps in manufacture of new products and testing proposed process in small scale operation such as a pilot plant	<input type="radio"/>					

Source WageIndicator web survey: Paywizard.co.uk

3.2 Data and methodology

Between November 2013 and August 2015 33,678 respondents had completed the tasks questionnaire for their respective occupations. Table 3.1 presents the number of observations per country. An observation is here defined as a questionnaire filled in by respondents who have provided valid information about at least three quarters of the tasks listed for their occupation. Appendix 3 provides a table with the number of observations per occupation per country. Observations in which the same frequency (straight-lining) was selected for all the tasks were considered untrustworthy and therefore excluded.

Table 3.1 Number of valid observations per country between November 2013 and August 2015

Country	Locale	Language	N
Argentina	es_AR	Spanish	1,783
Australia	en_AU	English	116
Belgium	nl_BE/fr_BE	Dutch/French	1,704
Brazil	pt_BR	Portuguese	1,892
Belarus	ru_BY	Russian	3,752
Indonesia	ba_ID	Bahasa	2,147
Kazakhstan	ru_KZ	Russian	3,158
Mexico	es_MX	Spanish	3,079
Netherlands	nl_NL	Dutch	9,729
Russian Federation	ru_RU	Russian	825
South Africa	en_ZA	English	2,935
Spain	es_ES	Spanish	1,516
United Kingdom	en_GB	English	1,042
Total			33,678

Source WageIndicator data NOV-2013-AUG-2015

This working paper details the descriptive statistics of the data collection in Appendix 3 through 5. Appendix 3 presents the total count of valid responses per occupation and country. The Netherlands is the country where most valid observations were collected (9,729) while the most common occupation in the dataset is *General office clerks* (ISCO code 4110, 1981 observations in total). Other most observations were noticed for the *Accounting associate professionals*, *Administrative and executive secretaries*, *Shop sales assistants*, and *Secretaries (general)*. Hardly any observations were noticed for the *Meteorologists*, *Dispensing opticians*, *Poultry producers*, *Riggers and cable splicers*, *Forestry labourers*, and other occupations. Appendix 4 shows the most frequent answer (where 1 = Never; 2 = Yearly; 3 = Monthly; 4 = Weekly; 5 = Daily) for each task in each country. For two thirds of these tasks the frequency varies from 1 to 5 across the 13 countries, pointing to substantial cross-country variation of occupational tasks. Appendix 5 collects the data on valid responses, in particular it shows the percentage of valid responses for each task in each country. It provides information on the drop out of workers once they are presented the tasks and answered at least to one.

4. Estimating the market value of tasks in the Netherlands

Jobs can be decomposed into the units of work activities that produce output, namely the task implemented in their completion and, consequently, the price at which the execution of a single task is paid becomes a fundamental information when setting wages in the labour market.

In this section we describe a methodology implemented to estimate the market value of tasks. The market value of a task is here intended as the (hourly) salary paid to perform that specific task. In short, it is estimated as the median of the (gross hourly) salary perceived by workers performing the task intensively (which means on daily or weekly basis).

Given the national scope of most labour markets, it is our belief that this exercise has to be performed at country level. Therefore, we confine the implementation of this approach to the Dutch labour market, but the same methodology can be replicated in all countries in the dataset. Approximately 7,000 respondents provided information about both, salary and the intensity by which they perform each task corresponding to their occupations in the Dutch section of the WageIndicator survey.

Outlier responses often affects self-reported wage data (see Acemoglu and Autor, 2011, among others). We rely on the following steps to filter noisy information. We first leave out dubious values (gross salaries below EUR 0.5 or above EUR 1,000 per hour), and subsequently focus on the 1st through 99th percentile of the resulting distribution. Approximately 6,800 wages responses are considered in this exercise.

We (arbitrary) set a threshold of 5 data points in order to be able to estimate the median salary value of a specific task. According to this rule of thumb, occupations for which we have less than 5 responses are excluded. So are all tasks performed on a daily or weekly basis by less than 5 workers. We ended up considering 231 (out of 412) occupations and 933 (out of 3,236) tasks. For each of these tasks we computed the median gross hourly salary of all those workers who reported performing the task intensively.

Table 4.1 Best and least valued tasks, median and average values in EUR

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Leading and managing the activities of research and development staff	122303	35.36	33.82
Consulting with engineering staff to evaluate interface between hardware and software	251203	33.84	32.50
Representing the organisation at official occasions and board meetings in negotiations at conventions seminars public hearings and forums	112009	33.68	35.90
Planning and directing daily operations	122306	33.20	32.85
Directing the selection and installation of ICT resources and the provision of user training	133003	33.20	29.68
Conducting research and improving or developing concepts instruments theories and operational methods related to chemistry	211301	32.86	35.59
Directing software programming and development of documentation	251206	32.71	32.13
Representing the enterprise or organisation in dealings with outside bodies	121108	32.70	36.42
Planning the overall research and development programme of an enterprise or organisation specifying goals and budgetary requirements	122302	32.33	31.28
Researching analysing and evaluating requirements for software applications and operating systems	251201	32.29	31.15
...
Washing cutting measuring and mixing foods for cooking	941102	5.93	6.72
Cleaning kitchens food preparation areas and service areas	941201	5.75	9.14
Noting what has been sold and collecting goods needed from the stockroom	933405	5.09	6.24
Receiving opening unpacking and inspecting for damage merchandise from manufacturer or distributor	933408	5.09	6.76
Directing customers to location of articles sought	933407	4.26	5.81
Removing goods with past due use-by dates	933403	4.12	6.06
Filling shelves with goods ensuring goods with the earliest use-by dates are at the front of shelves	933402	4.11	4.97
Maintaining shelf order by removing stock belonging in a different location	933404	4.11	5.72
Obtaining articles for customers from shelf or stockroom	933406	4.11	5.64
Placing goods neatly in bins and on racks and stacking bulky goods on floors	933401	3.61	5.86

Source WageIndicator data NOV-2013-AUG-2015, selection respondents in the Netherlands

A pull of the results is presented Table 4.1, where the best and least paid tasks are presented. The full outcome of the exercise is presented in Appendix 6. It can be observed how among the most valued tasks stand those concerning leadership and management of teams and firms (e.g. *Representing the organisation at official occasions and board meetings in negotiations at conventions seminars public hearings and forums* is paid EUR 34 per hour, *Planning and directing daily operations* 33). ICT and software development and maintenance are also well acknowledged in the market (e.g. *Consulting with engineering staff to evaluate interface between hardware and software* is paid EUR 34 per hour, *Directing the selection and installation of ICT resources and the provision of user training* 33). Research activities and their management is another group of activities with an elevated market value (e.g. by *Leading and managing the activities of research and development staff* one can earn EUR 35 per hour, *Conducting research and improving or developing concepts instruments theories and operational methods related to chemistry* pays 33). It can also be noticed how tasks belonging simultaneously to more than one of the groups mentioned are amongst the highest valued ones.

On the other end of the table the tasks are reported for which a low market value were estimated. All activities performed by shelf fillers are at the bottom of this ranking (e.g. *Obtaining articles for customers from shelf or stockroom* receives EUR 4 per hour). Low level food service and catering activities are also paid quite poorly (e.g. *Washing dishes and cooking utensils and putting them away* makes EUR 7 per

hour). Routinary administrative tasks form a more surprisingly (to a certain extent) group of poorly paid tasks (e.g. *Performing mail-handling duties in public post offices or privately owned delivery establishments* and *Arranging appointments and collecting payments* pay less than EUR 9 per each hour worked).

The added value of this exercise consists in presenting a simple methodology that is able to deal with one of the most relevant questions in labour market negotiation: what is the market value of the capability of executing a specific unit of work activity. It presents some clear limitations, the most relevant being the bias produced by the data availability. Less than 30% of the tasks identified are included in the exercise. However it is our belief that as the volume of data collected grows, this limitation will lose relevance. The estimation of the market value of the hour execution of specific work activities is however significant information to labour market stakeholders, e.g. workers, employers and employment services providers.

5. Conclusions

This paper challenges the empirical testing of the assumption underlying the ISCO occupational classification that jobs with the same set of main tasks and duties are aggregated into 433 occupation units at the 4-digit level of the classification. Using the task descriptions provided for all ISCO 4-digit occupations, the frequency of task implementation was tested for respondents in the WageIndicator web survey on work and wages. Depending on their occupation the relevant task list was shown.

This paper proves that such task measurement is feasible. Moreover, given that the WageIndicator web survey also holds data on wages, the median and average hourly wages (in EUR) could be computed for frequently performed tasks. The data challenges future empirical analyses of hypotheses concerning the variation in task frequencies and the related wages within and across countries, across the occupation's skill levels, across firm sizes, across regions and alike.

appendix 1 List of the 427 ISCO-08 occupations 4-digit

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
1111	Legislators
1112	Senior government officials
1113	Traditional chiefs and heads of village
1114	Senior officials of special-interest organisations
1120	Managing directors and chief executives
1211	Finance managers
1212	Human resource managers
1213	Policy and planning managers
1219	Business services and administration managers not elsewhere classified
1221	Sales and marketing managers
1222	Advertising and public relations managers
1223	Research and development managers
1311	Agricultural and forestry production managers
1312	Aquaculture and fisheries production managers
1321	Manufacturing managers
1322	Mining managers
1323	Construction managers
1324	Supply, distribution and related managers
1330	Information and communications technology service managers
1341	Child care services managers
1342	Health services managers
1343	Aged care services managers
1344	Social welfare managers
1345	Education managers
1346	Financial and insurance services branch managers
1349	Professional services managers not elsewhere classified
1411	Hotel managers
1412	Restaurant managers
1420	Retail and wholesale trade managers
1431	Sports, recreation and cultural centre managers
2111	Physicists and astronomers
2112	Meteorologists
2113	Chemists

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
2114	Geologists and geophysicists
2120	Mathematicians, actuaries and statisticians
2131	Biologists, botanists, zoologists and related professionals
2132	Farming, forestry and fisheries advisers
2133	Environmental protection professionals
2141	Industrial and production engineers
2142	Civil engineers
2143	Environmental engineers
2144	Mechanical engineers
2145	Chemical engineers
2146	Mining engineers, metallurgists and related professionals
2149	Engineering professionals not elsewhere classified
2151	Electrical engineers
2152	Electronics engineers
2153	Telecommunications engineers
2161	Building architects
2162	Landscape architects
2163	Product and garment designers
2164	Town and traffic planners
2165	Cartographers and surveyors
2166	Graphic and multimedia designers
2211	Generalist medical practitioners
2212	Specialist medical practitioners
2221	Nursing professionals
2222	Midwifery professionals
2230	Traditional and complementary medicine professionals
2240	Paramedical practitioners
2250	Veterinarians
2261	Dentists
2262	Pharmacists
2263	Environmental and occupational health and hygiene professionals
2264	Physiotherapists
2265	Dieticians and nutritionists
2266	Audiologists and speech therapists
2267	Optometrists and ophthalmic opticians
2269	Health professionals not elsewhere classified
2310	University and higher education teachers
2320	Vocational education teachers
2330	Secondary education teachers
2341	Primary school teachers
2342	Early childhood educators

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
2351	Education methods specialists
2352	Special needs teachers
2353	Other language teachers
2354	Other music teachers
2355	Other arts teachers
2356	Information technology trainers
2359	Teaching professionals not elsewhere classified
2411	Accountants
2412	Financial and investment advisers
2413	Financial analysts
2421	Management and organisation analysts
2422	Policy administration professionals
2423	Personnel and careers professionals
2424	Training and staff development professionals
2431	Advertising and marketing professionals
2432	Public relations professionals
2433	Technical and medical sales professionals (excluding ICT)
2434	Information and communications technology sales professionals
2511	Systems analysts
2512	Software developers
2513	Web and multimedia developers
2514	Applications programmers
2519	Software and applications developers and analysts not elsewhere classified
2521	Database designers and administrators
2522	Systems administrators
2523	Computer network professionals
2529	Database and network professionals not elsewhere classified
2611	Lawyers
2612	Judges
2619	Legal professionals not elsewhere classified
2621	Archivists and curators
2622	Librarians and related information professionals
2631	Economists
2632	Sociologists, anthropologists and related professionals
2633	Philosophers, historians and political scientists
2634	Psychologists
2635	Social work and counselling professionals
2636	Religious professionals
2641	Authors and related writers
2642	Journalists
2643	Translators, interpreters and other linguists

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
2651	Visual artists
2652	Musicians, singers and composers
2653	Dancers and choreographers
2654	Film, stage and related directors and producers
2655	Actors
2656	Announcers on radio, television and other media
2659	Creative and performing artists not elsewhere classified
3111	Chemical and physical science technicians
3112	Civil engineering technicians
3113	Electrical engineering technicians
3114	Electronics engineering technicians
3115	Mechanical engineering technicians
3116	Chemical engineering technicians
3117	Mining and metallurgical technicians
3118	Draughtspersons
3119	Physical and engineering science technicians not elsewhere classified
3121	Mining supervisors
3122	Manufacturing supervisors
3123	Construction supervisors
3131	Power production plant operators
3132	Incinerator and water treatment plant operators
3133	Chemical processing plant controllers
3134	Petroleum and natural gas refining plant operators
3135	Metal production process controllers
3141	Life science technicians (excluding medical)
3142	Agricultural technicians
3143	Forestry technicians
3151	Ships' engineers
3152	Ships' deck officers and pilots
3153	Aircraft pilots and related associate professionals
3154	Air traffic controllers
3155	Air traffic safety electronics technicians
3211	Medical imaging and therapeutic equipment technicians
3212	Medical and pathology laboratory technicians
3213	Pharmaceutical technicians and assistants
3214	Medical and dental prosthetic technicians
3221	Nursing associate professionals
3222	Midwifery associate professionals
3230	Traditional and complementary medicine associate professionals
3240	Veterinary technicians and assistants
3251	Dental assistants and therapists

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
3252	Medical records and health information technicians
3253	Community health workers
3254	Dispensing opticians
3255	Physiotherapy technicians and assistants
3256	Medical assistants
3257	Environmental and occupational health inspectors and associates
3258	Ambulance workers
3259	Health associate professionals not elsewhere classified
3311	Securities and finance dealers and brokers
3312	Credit and loans officers
3313	Accounting associate professionals
3314	Statistical, mathematical and related associate professionals
3315	Valuers and loss assessors
3321	Insurance representatives
3322	Commercial sales representatives
3323	Buyers
3324	Trade brokers
3331	Clearing and forwarding agents
3332	Conference and event planners
3333	Employment agents and contractors
3334	Real estate agents and property managers
3339	Business services agents not elsewhere classified
3341	Office supervisors
3342	Legal secretaries
3343	Administrative and executive secretaries
3344	Medical secretaries
3351	Customs and border inspectors
3352	Government tax and excise officials
3353	Government social benefits officials
3354	Government licensing officials
3355	Police inspectors and detectives
3359	Regulatory government associate professionals not elsewhere classified
3411	Legal and related associate professionals
3412	Social work associate professionals
3413	Religious associate professionals
3421	Athletes and sports players
3422	Sports coaches, instructors and officials
3423	Fitness and recreation instructors and program leaders
3431	Photographers
3432	Interior designers and decorators
3433	Gallery, museum and library technicians

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
3434	Chefs
3511	Information and communications technology operations technicians
3512	Information and communications technology user support technicians
3513	Computer network and systems technicians
3514	Web technicians
3521	Broadcasting and audio-visual technicians
3522	Telecommunications engineering technicians
4110	General office clerks
4120	Secretaries (general)
4131	Typists and word processing operators
4132	Data entry clerks
4211	Bank tellers and related clerks
4212	Bookmakers, croupiers and related gaming workers
4213	Pawnbrokers and money-lenders
4214	Debt-collectors and related workers
4221	Travel consultants and clerks
4222	Contact centre information clerks
4223	Telephone switchboard operators
4224	Hotel receptionists
4225	Enquiry clerks
4226	Receptionists (general)
4227	Survey and market research interviewers
4229	Client information workers not elsewhere classified
4311	Accounting and bookkeeping clerks
4312	Statistical, finance and insurance clerks
4313	Payroll clerks
4321	Stock clerks
4322	Production clerks
4323	Transport clerks
4411	Library clerks
4412	Mail carriers and sorting clerks
4413	Coding, proof-reading and related clerks
4414	Scribes and related workers
4415	Filing and copying clerks
4416	Personnel clerks
4419	Clerical support workers not elsewhere classified
5111	Travel attendants and travel stewards
5112	Transport conductors
5113	Travel guides
5120	Cooks
5131	Waiters

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
5132	Bartenders
5141	Hairdressers
5142	Beauticians and related workers
5151	Cleaning and housekeeping supervisors in offices, hotels and other establishments
5152	Domestic housekeepers
5153	Building caretakers
5161	Astrologers, fortune-tellers and related workers
5162	Companions and valets
5163	Undertakers and embalmers
5164	Pet groomers and animal care workers
5165	Driving instructors
5169	Personal services workers not elsewhere classified
5211	Stall and market salespersons
5212	Street food salespersons
5221	Shop keepers
5222	Shop supervisors
5223	Shop sales assistants
5230	Cashiers and ticket clerks
5241	Fashion and other models
5242	Sales demonstrators
5243	Door to door salespersons
5244	Contact centre salespersons
5245	Service station attendants
5246	Food service counter attendants
5311	Child care workers
5312	Teachers' aides
5321	Health care assistants
5322	Home-based personal care workers
5329	Personal care workers in health services not elsewhere classified
5411	Fire-fighters
5412	Police officers
5413	Prison guards
5414	Security guards
5419	Protective services workers not elsewhere classified
6111	Field crop and vegetable growers
6112	Tree and shrub crop growers
6113	Gardeners, horticultural and nursery growers
6114	Mixed crop growers
6121	Livestock and dairy producers
6122	Poultry producers
6123	Apiarists and sericulturists

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
6129	Animal producers not elsewhere classified
6130	Mixed crop and animal producers
6210	Forestry and related workers
6221	Aquaculture workers
6222	Inland and coastal waters fishery workers
6223	Deep-sea fishery workers
6224	Hunters and trappers
6310	Subsistence crop farmers
6320	Subsistence livestock farmers
6330	Subsistence mixed crop and livestock farmers
6340	Subsistence fishers, hunters, trappers and gatherers
7111	House builders
7112	Bricklayers and related workers
7113	Stonemasons, stone cutters, splitters and carvers
7114	Concrete placers, concrete finishers and related workers
7115	Carpenters and joiners
7119	Building frame and related trades workers not elsewhere classified
7121	Roofers
7122	Floor layers and tile setters
7123	Plasterers
7124	Insulation workers
7125	Glaziers
7126	Plumbers and pipe fitters
7127	Air conditioning and refrigeration mechanics
7131	Painters and related workers
7132	Spray painters and varnishers
7133	Building structure cleaners
7211	Metal moulders and coremakers
7212	Welders and flamecutters
7213	Sheet-metal workers
7214	Structural-metal preparers and erectors
7215	Riggers and cable splicers
7221	Blacksmiths, hammersmiths and forging press workers
7222	Toolmakers and related workers
7223	Metal working machine tool setters and operators
7224	Metal polishers, wheel grinders and tool sharpeners
7231	Motor vehicle mechanics and repairers
7232	Aircraft engine mechanics and repairers
7233	Agricultural and industrial machinery mechanics and repairers
7234	Bicycle and related repairers
7311	Precision-instrument makers and repairers

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
7312	Musical instrument makers and tuners
7313	Jewellery and precious-metal workers
7314	Potters and related workers
7315	Glass makers, cutters, grinders and finishers
7316	Sign writers, decorative painters, engravers and etchers
7317	Handicraft workers in wood, basketry and related materials
7318	Handicraft workers in textile, leather and related materials
7321	Pre-press technicians
7322	Printers
7323	Print finishing and binding workers
7411	Building and related electricians
7412	Electrical mechanics and fitters
7413	Electrical line installers and repairers
7421	Electronics mechanics and servicers
7422	Information and communications technology installers and servicers
7511	Butchers, fishmongers and related food preparers
7512	Bakers, pastry-cooks and confectionery makers
7513	Dairy-products makers
7514	Fruit, vegetable and related preservers
7515	Food and beverage tasters and graders
7516	Tobacco preparers and tobacco products makers
7521	Wood treaters
7522	Cabinet-makers and related workers
7523	Woodworking-machine tool setters and operators
7531	Tailors, dressmakers, furriers and hatters
7532	Garment and related pattern-makers and cutters
7533	Sewing, embroidery and related workers
7534	Upholsterers and related workers
7535	Pelt dressers, tanners and fellmongers
7536	Shoemakers and related workers
7541	Underwater divers
7542	Shotfirers and blasters
7543	Product graders and testers (excluding foods and beverages)
7544	Fumigators and other pest and weed controllers
7549	Craft and related workers not elsewhere classified
8111	Miners and quarriers
8112	Mineral and stone processing plant operators
8113	Well drillers and borers and related workers
8114	Cement, stone and other mineral products machine operators
8121	Metal processing plant operators
8122	Metal finishing, plating and coating machine operators

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
8131	Chemical products plant and machine operators
8132	Photographic products machine operators
8141	Rubber products machine operators
8142	Plastic products machine operators
8143	Paper products machine operators
8151	Fibre preparing, spinning and winding machine operators
8152	Weaving and knitting machine operators
8153	Sewing machine operators
8154	Bleaching, dyeing and fabric cleaning machine operators
8155	Fur and leather preparing machine operators
8156	Shoemaking and related machine operators
8157	Laundry machine operators
8159	Textile, fur and leather products machine operators not elsewhere classified
8160	Food and related products machine operators
8171	Pulp and papermaking plant operators
8172	Wood processing plant operators
8181	Glass and ceramics plant operators
8182	Steam engine and boiler operators
8183	Packing, bottling and labelling machine operators
8211	Mechanical machinery assemblers
8212	Electrical and electronic equipment assemblers
8219	Assemblers not elsewhere classified
8311	Locomotive engine drivers
8312	Railway brake, signal and switch operators
8321	Motorcycle drivers
8322	Car, taxi and van drivers
8331	Bus and tram drivers
8332	Heavy truck and lorry drivers
8341	Mobile farm and forestry plant operators
8342	Earthmoving and related plant operators
8343	Crane, hoist and related plant operators
8344	Lifting truck operators
8350	Ships' deck crews and related workers
9111	Domestic cleaners and helpers
9112	Cleaners and helpers in offices, hotels and other establishments
9121	Hand launderers and pressers
9122	Vehicle cleaners
9123	Window cleaners
9129	Other cleaning workers
9211	Crop farm labourers
9212	Livestock farm labourers

ISCO-08 code	ISCO-08 label
9213	Mixed crop and livestock farm labourers
9214	Garden and horticultural labourers
9215	Forestry labourers
9216	Fishery and aquaculture labourers
9311	Mining and quarrying labourers
9312	Civil engineering labourers
9313	Building construction labourers
9321	Hand packers
9329	Manufacturing labourers not elsewhere classified
9331	Hand and pedal vehicle drivers
9332	Drivers of animal-drawn vehicles and machinery
9333	Freight handlers
9334	Shelf fillers
9411	Fast food preparers
9412	Kitchen helpers
9510	Street and related service workers
9520	Street vendors (excluding food)
9611	Garbage and recycling collectors
9612	Refuse sorters
9613	Sweepers and related labourers
9621	Messengers, package deliverers and luggage porters
9622	Odd job persons
9623	Meter readers and vending-machine collectors
9624	Water and firewood collectors
9629	Elementary workers not elsewhere classified

appendix 2 List of tasks by occupation

Code	Task
111101 ¹¹	Presiding over or participating in the proceedings of legislative bodies and administrative councils of national, state, regional or local governments or legislative assemblies
111102	Determining, formulating, and directing policies of national, state, regional or local governments
111103	Making, ratifying, amending or repealing laws, public rules and regulations within a statutory or constitutional framework
111104	Serving on government administrative boards or official committees
111105	Investigating matters of concern to the public and promoting the interests of the constituencies which they represent
111106	Attending community functions and meetings to provide service to the community, understand public opinion and provide information on government plans
111107	Negotiating with other legislators and representatives of interest groups in order to reconcile differing interests, and to create policies and agreements
111108	As members of the government, directing senior administrators and officials of government departments and agencies in the interpretation and implementation of government policies
111201	Advising national, state, regional or local governments and legislators on policy matters
111202	Advising on the preparation of government budgets, laws and regulations, including amendments
111203	Establishing objectives for government departments or agencies in accordance with government legislation and policy
111204	Formulating or approving and evaluating programs and procedures for the implementation of government policies in conjunction or consultation with government
111205	Recommending, reviewing, evaluating and approving documents, briefs and reports submitted by middle managers and senior staff members
111206	Ensuring appropriate systems and procedures are developed and implemented to provide budgetary control
111207	Co-ordinating activities with other senior government managers and officials
111208	Making presentations to legislative and other government committees regarding policies programs or budgets
111209	Overseeing the interpretation and implementation of government policies and legislation by government departments and agencies
111301	Allocating the use of communal land and other resources among households in the community or village
111302	Collecting and distributing surplus production of the community or village
111303	Settling disputes between members of the community or village
111304	Disciplining members of the community or village for violation of rules and customs
111305	Performing ceremonial duties in connection with births, marriages, deaths, harvests and other important occasions
111306	Representing the community or village on local or regional councils
111307	Informing the community or village about government rules and regulations
111401	Determining and formulating the policies, rules and regulations of the organisation
111402	Planning, directing and coordinating the general functioning of the organisation

¹¹ Note: the first four digits of the code refer to the ISCO-08 code of the occupation, the last two digits are a follow-up number of the task.

Code	Task
111403	Reviewing the operations and results of the organisation and reporting to boards of directors and governing bodies, the organisation's membership and funding agencies
111404	Negotiating on behalf of the organisation, its members and relevant special-interest groups
111405	Promoting the interests of the organisation, its members and relevant special-interest groups before the legislature, government or general public
111406	Planning, organising and directing sections charged with implementing the organisation's policies, programmes, rules and regulations
111407	Ensuring appropriate systems and procedures are developed and implemented to provide budgetary control
111408	Monitoring and evaluating performance of the organisation or enterprise against established objectives and policies
111409	Representing the organisation at official occasions and board meetings, in negotiations, at conventions, public hearings and forums
112001	Planning, directing and coordinating the general functioning of an enterprise or organisation
112002	Reviewing the operations and results of the enterprise, or organisation and reporting to boards of directors and governing bodies
112003	Determining objectives, strategies, policies and programs for the enterprise or organisation
112004	Providing overall leadership and management to the enterprise or organisation
112005	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
112006	Authorising material, human and financial resources to implement organisational policies and programs
112007	Monitoring and evaluating performance of the organisation or enterprise against established objectives and policies
112008	Consulting with senior subordinate staff and reviewing recommendations and reports
112009	Representing the organisation at official occasions and board meetings, in negotiations, at conventions, seminars, public hearings and forums
112010	Selecting, or approving the selection of senior staff
112011	Ensuring the organisation complies with relevant legislation and regulations
121101	Planning, directing and coordinating the financial operations of an enterprise or organisation
121102	Assessing the financial situation of the enterprise or organisation, preparing budgets and overseeing financial operations
121103	Consulting with the chief executive and with managers of other departments or sections
121104	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
121105	Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures
121106	Planning and directing daily operations
121107	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
121108	Representing the enterprise or organisation in dealings with outside bodies
121201	Planning, directing and coordinating the personnel and industrial relations activities, policies and practices of an enterprise or organisation
121202	Planning and organizing procedures for recruitment, training, promotion, transfer and dismissal of staff,
121203	Planning and organizing negotiations and procedures for determination of wage structures and level and for consultation with workers on conditions of employment
121204	Overseeing safety, health and related programmes and activities
121205	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
121206	Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures
121207	Overseeing the development and implementation of management information systems
121208	Ensuring compliance with standards and legislation relating to employees rights, health and safety, equal opportunity and related concerns
121209	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff for the entire enterprise or organisation

Code	Task
121210	Consulting with senior management and with managers of other departments
121211	Representing the enterprise or organisation in dealings with outside bodies
121301	Developing, implementing and monitoring strategic plans, programs, policies, processes, systems and procedures to achieve goals, objectives and work standards
121302	Developing, directing, administering and participating in policy research and analysis
121303	Coordinating the implementation of policies and practices
121304	Establishing activity measures and measurements of accountability
121305	Planning and directing daily operations
121306	Leading and managing the activities of policy development and strategic planning staff
121307	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
121308	Representing the enterprise or organisation in negotiations, and at conventions, seminars, public hearings and forums
121901	Providing administrative, strategic planning and operational support, research and advice to senior management on matters such as the management of building facilities and administrative services
121902	Developing and managing the organisation's administrative and physical resources
121903	Developing and implementing administrative and procedural statements and guidelines for use by staff in the organisation
121904	Analysing complex resource management issues and initiatives that affect the organisation, and preparing associated reports, correspondence and submissions
121905	Providing information and support for the preparation of financial reports and budgets
121906	Leading, managing and developing administrative staff to ensure smooth business operations and the provision of accurate and timely information
121907	Representing the enterprise or organisation in negotiations, and at conventions, seminars, public hearings and forums
121908	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
121909	Planning and directing daily operations
121910	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
122101	Planning and organizing special sales and marketing programmes based on sales records and market assessments
122102	Determining price lists, discount and delivery terms, sales promotion budgets, sales methods, special incentives and campaigns
122103	Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures related to sales and marketing activities
122104	Leading and managing the activities of sales and marketing staff
122105	Planning and directing daily operations
122106	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
122107	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
122108	Representing the enterprise or organisation at sales and marketing conventions, trade exhibitions and other forums
122201	Planning, directing and coordinating the advertising and public relations activities of an enterprise or organisation
122202	Negotiating advertising contracts with clients or with newspapers, radio and television stations, sports and cultural organisations and advertising agencies
122203	Planning and managing information programmes to inform legislators, the mass media and the general public about the plans, accomplishments and points of view of the enterprise or organisation
122204	Leading and managing the activities of advertising and public relations staff
122205	Establishing and managing budgets and controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
122206	Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures

Code	Task
122207	Planning and directing daily operations
122208	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
122301	Planning, directing and coordinating research and development activities, in-house or commissioned from external research organisations, to develop new or improved technical processes, products, knowledge, or utilisation of materials
122302	Planning the overall research and development programme of an enterprise or organisation, specifying goals and budgetary requirements
122303	Leading and managing the activities of research and development staff
122304	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
122305	Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures
122306	Planning and directing daily operations
122307	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
122308	Representing the enterprise or organisation at conventions, seminars and conferences
131101	Monitoring agricultural and forestry market activity and planning production to meet contract requirements and market demand
131102	Establishing and managing budgets, monitoring production output and costs, recording information such as farm management practices, and preparing financial and operational reports
131103	Conferring with buyers to arrange for the sale of crops and livestock
131104	Contracting with farmers or independent owners for production of crops and livestock, or for management of production
131105	Planning the type, intensity and sequence of farm operations (eg. determining the best times for planting, spraying and harvesting)
131106	Analysing soil to determine types and quantities of fertilizer required for maximum production
131107	Purchasing machinery, equipment, and supplies such as tractors, seed, fertilizer, and chemicals
131108	Identifying and controlling agricultural and forest environmental toxins, weeds, pests and diseases
131109	Organizing farming operations such as maintaining buildings, water supply systems and equipment
131110	Directing and coordinating activities such as planting, irrigation, chemical application, harvesting, and grading
131111	Inspecting plantations and fields to determine maturity dates of crops, or to estimate potential crop damage from weather
131112	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of agricultural and forestry workers and contractors
131201	Monitoring aquaculture and fishery market activity and planning production and fishing activities to meet contract requirements and market demand
131202	Establishing and managing budgets, monitoring production output and costs, recording information such as fisheries management practices, and preparing financial and operational reports
131203	Conferring with buyers to arrange for the sale of produce and catches
131204	Contracting with fishing skippers or owners of vessels and aquaculture farms for fishing and aquaculture operations, or for management of production
131205	Conducting and organizing aquaculture or fishery stock examinations in order to identify diseases or parasites
131206	Devising and coordinating activities to improve fish hatching and growth rates, and to prevent disease in hatcheries
131207	Monitoring environments to maintain or improve conditions for aquatic life
131208	Directing and monitoring trapping and spawning of fish, egg incubation, and fry rearing, applying knowledge of management and fish culturing techniques
131209	Coordinating the selection and maintenance of brood stock
131210	Directing and monitoring the transfer of mature fish to lakes, ponds, streams, or commercial tanks
131211	Purchasing machinery, equipment, and supplies such as vessels and nets

Code	Task
131212	Organizing operations such as maintenance of ships, boats and equipment
131213	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of aquaculture or fishery workers and contractors
132101	Determining, implementing and monitoring production strategies, policies and plans
132102	Planning details of production activities in terms of output quality and quantity, cost, time available and labour requirements
132103	Controlling the operation of production plant and quality procedures through planning of maintenance, designation of operating hours and supply of parts and tools
132104	Establishing and managing budgets, monitoring production output and costs, and adjusting processes and resources to minimize costs
132105	Consulting with and informing other managers about production matters
132106	Overseeing the acquisition and installation of new plant and equipment
132107	Controlling the preparation of production records and reports
132108	Coordinating the implementation of occupational health and safety requirements
132109	Identifying business opportunities and determining products to be manufactured
132110	Researching and implementing regulatory and statutory requirements affecting manufacturing operations and the environment
132111	Overseeing the provision of quotes for the manufacture of specialized goods and establishing contracts with customers and suppliers
132112	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
132201	Conferring with other managers to set production quotas, plan extraction sites and develop policies for the removal of raw materials
132202	Evaluating efficiency of production sites to determine adequacy of personnel, equipment and technologies used, and make changes to work schedule or equipment when necessary
132203	Planning details of production activities in terms of output quality and quantity, cost, time available and labour requirements
132204	Controlling the operation of plant and quality procedures through planning of maintenance, designation of operating hours and supply of equipment
132205	Establishing and managing budgets, monitoring production output and costs, and adjusting processes and resources to minimize costs
132206	Overseeing the acquisition and installation of new plant and equipment
132207	Controlling the preparation of production records and reports
132208	Coordinating the implementation of health and safety requirements
132209	Researching and implementing regulatory and statutory requirements affecting mineral extraction operations and the environment
132210	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
132301	Interpreting architectural drawings and specifications
132302	Coordinating labour resources, and procurement and delivery of materials, plant and equipment
132303	Negotiating with building owners, property developers and subcontractors involved in the construction process to ensure projects are completed on time and within budget
132304	Preparing tenders and contract bids
132305	Operating and implementing coordinated work programs for sites
132306	Ensuring adherence to building legislation and standards of performance, quality, cost and safety
132307	Arranging submission of plans to local authorities
132308	Building under contract, or subcontracting specialized building services
132309	Arranging building inspections by relevant authorities
132310	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
132311	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff and subcontractors

Code	Task
132401	Determining, implementing and monitoring purchasing, storage and distribution strategies, policies and plans
132402	Preparing and implementing plans to maintain required stock levels at minimum cost
132403	Negotiating contracts with suppliers to meet quality, cost and delivery requirements
132404	Monitoring and reviewing storage and inventory systems to meet supply requirements and control stock levels
132405	Operating recording systems to track all movements of goods, and ensuring re-ordering and re-stocking at optimal times
132406	Liaising with other departments and customers concerning requirements for outward goods and associated forwarding transportation
132407	Overseeing the recording of purchase, storage and distribution transactions
132408	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
132409	Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures
132410	Planning and directing daily operations
132411	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
133001	Consulting with users, management, vendors, and technicians to assess computing needs and system requirements and specifying technology to meet those needs
133002	Formulating and directing information and communication technology (ICT) strategies, policies and plans
133003	Directing the selection and installation of ICT resources and the provision of user training
133004	Directing ICT operations, analysing workflow, establishing priorities, developing standards and setting deadlines
133005	Overseeing the security of ICT systems
133006	Assigning, reviewing, managing and leading the work of systems analysts, programmers, and other computer-related workers
133007	Evaluating the organisation's technology use and needs and recommending improvements, such as hardware and software upgrades
133008	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
133009	Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures
133010	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
133011	Representing the enterprise or organisation at ICT related conventions, seminars and conferences
134101	Developing and implementing programs to enhance the physical, social, emotional and intellectual development of young children
134102	Establishing and monitoring budgets and determining allocation of funds for staff, supplies, materials, equipment and maintenance
134103	Overseeing and coordinating the provision of care for children in before-school, after-school, day, and vacation care centres
134104	Directing and supervising child carers in providing care and supervision for young children
134105	Managing physical facilities and making sure all buildings and equipment are maintained to ensure the centre is a safe area for children, staff and visitors
134106	Reviewing and interpreting government codes, and developing procedures to meet codes (eg, concerning safety and security)
134107	Monitoring children's progress and conferring with parents or guardians
134108	Preparing and maintaining records and accounts for a child care centre
134109	Recruiting and evaluating staff and coordinating their professional development
134201	Providing overall direction and management for the service, facility, organisation or centre
134202	Directing, supervising and evaluating the work activities of medical, nursing, technical, clerical, service, maintenance, and other personnel

Code	Task
134203	Establishing objectives and evaluative or operational criteria for units they manage
134204	Directing or conducting recruitment, hiring and training of personnel
134205	Developing, implementing and monitoring procedures, policies and performance standards for medical, nursing, technical and administrative staff
134206	Monitoring the use of diagnostic services, inpatient beds, facilities, and staff to ensure effective use of resources and assess the need for additional staff, equipment, and services
134207	Controlling administrative operations such as budget planning, report preparation and expenditure on supplies, equipment and services
134208	Liaising with other health and welfare service providers, boards and funding bodies to coordinate the provision of services
134209	Advising government bodies about measures to improve health and welfare services and facilities
134210	Representing the organisation in negotiations, and at conventions, seminars, public hearings and forums
134301	Providing overall direction and management for the service, facility, organisation or centre
134302	Directing, supervising and evaluating the work activities of nursing, personal care, technical, clerical, service, maintenance, and other personnel
134303	Establishing objectives and evaluative or operational criteria for units they manage
134304	Directing or conducting recruitment, hiring and training of personnel
134305	Developing, implementing and monitoring procedures, policies and performance standards for nursing, personal care, technical, and administrative staff
134306	Coordinating and administering welfare programs and care services for the elderly
134307	Controlling administrative operations such as budget planning, report preparation, expenditure on supplies, equipment and services
134308	Liaising with other health and welfare providers, boards and funding bodies to coordinate the provision of services
134309	Advising government bodies about measures to improve health and welfare services and facilities
134310	Representing the organisation in negotiations, and at conventions, seminars, public hearings and forums
134401	Providing overall direction and management for the service, facility, organisation or centre
134402	Developing, implementing and monitoring procedures, policies and standards for staff
134403	Monitoring and evaluating resources devoted to the provision of welfare, housing, and other social services
134404	Controlling administrative operations such as budget planning, report preparation, expenditure on supplies, equipment and services
134405	Liaising with other welfare and health services providers, boards and funding bodies to discuss areas of health and welfare service cooperation and coordination
134406	Advising government bodies about measures to improve welfare services and facilities
134407	Representing the organisation in negotiations, and at conventions, seminars, public hearings and forums
134408	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
134409	Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures
134410	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
134411	Representing the organisation at conventions, seminars and conferences
134501	Determining educational programs based on frameworks established by education authorities and governing bodies
134502	Implementing systems and procedures to monitor school performance and student enrolments
134503	Directing administrative and clerical activities concerning student admissions and educational services
134504	Controlling administrative operations such as budget planning, report preparation, expenditure on supplies, equipment and services
134505	Providing leadership and guidance to teaching, academic and administrative staff as well as to students

Code	Task
134506	Evaluating the work of teachers and lecturers by visiting classrooms, observing teaching methods, reviewing instructional objectives and examining learning materials
134507	Promoting the educational program, and representing the service or institution in the wider community
134508	Supervising the maintenance of educational facilities
134509	Developing and enforcing a disciplinary code to create a safe and conducive environment for students and teachers
134510	Organizing and implementing methods of raising additional funds in conjunction with parent and community groups and sponsors
134511	Controlling selection, training and supervision of staff
134601	Planning, directing and coordinating the activities of staff in the branch
134602	Establishing and maintaining relationships with individual and business customers
134603	Providing advice and assistance to customers on their financial and insurance needs and with matters such as changes in law that may affect customers
134604	Examining, evaluating and processing loan and insurance applications
134605	Monitoring credit extension decisions
134606	Conducting financial investigations
134607	Overseeing the flow of cash and financial instruments, and the preparation of financial and regulatory reports
134608	Approving or rejecting, or coordinating the approval or rejection of, lines of credit commercial, real estate and personal loans
134609	Coordinating cooperation with other branches of the company
134610	Managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
134611	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
134901	Providing overall direction and management for the service, facility, organisation or centre
134902	Developing, implementing and monitoring procedures, policies and standards for staff
134903	Directing, supervising and evaluating the work activities of professional technical, clerical, service, maintenance, and other personnel
134904	Monitoring and evaluating resources devoted to the provision of services
134905	Controlling administrative operations such as budget planning, report preparation, expenditure on supplies, equipment and services
134906	Planning, directing and coordinating the provision of services
134907	Coordinating cooperation with other service provision agencies in the same or related fields
134908	Managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
134909	Overseeing the selection, training and performance of staff
141101	Directing and overseeing reservation, reception, room service and housekeeping activities
141102	Supervising security arrangements, and garden and property maintenance
141103	Planning and supervising bar, restaurant, function and conference activities
141104	Observing liquor, gaming, and other laws and regulations
141105	Assessing and reviewing customer satisfaction
141106	Overseeing accounting and purchasing activities
141107	Undertaking budgeting for the establishment
141108	Controlling selection, training and supervision of staff
141109	Ensuring compliance with occupational health and safety regulations
141110	Providing guests with local tourism information, and arranging tours and transportation
141201	Planning menus in consultation with chefs and cooks

Code	Task
141202	Planning and organizing special functions
141203	Arranging the purchasing and pricing of goods according to budget
141204	Maintaining records of stock levels and financial transactions
141205	Ensuring dining, kitchen and food storage facilities comply with health regulations and are clean, functional and of suitable appearance
141206	Conferring with customers to assess their satisfaction with meals and service
141207	Selecting, set staff work schedules, training and supervising waiting and kitchen staff
141208	Taking reservations, greeting guests and assisting in taking orders
141209	Negotiating arrangements with clients and suppliers
141210	Ensuring compliance with occupational health and safety regulations
142001	Determining product mix, stock levels and service standards
142002	Formulating and implementing purchasing and marketing policies, and setting prices
142003	Promoting and advertising the establishment's goods and services
142004	Maintaining records of stock levels and financial transactions
142005	Undertaking budgeting for the establishment
142006	Controlling selection, training and supervision of staff
142007	Ensuring compliance with occupational health and safety regulations
143101	Planning and organizing the range and mix of entertainment, attractions, cultural activities, and sports and fitness programmes to be offered by the centre
143102	Ensuring that facilities are kept clean and in good condition
143103	Keeping abreast of new trends and developments in the creative arts and arranging theatrical productions and performances by bands and orchestras
143104	Advising on the facilities available and promoting publicity in relation to events, shows and activities
143105	Checking and keeping custody of all cash receipts and making regular stock checks
143106	Establishing and managing budgets, controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources
143107	Planning and directing daily operations
143108	Controlling the selection, supervision and performance of staff
143109	Ensuring compliance with health and safety regulations
211101	Conducting research and improving or developing concepts, theories, instrumentation, software and operational methods related to physics and astronomy
211102	Conducting experiments, tests and analyses on the structure and properties of matter in fields such as mechanics, thermodynamics, electronics, communications, power generation and distribution, aerodynamics, optics and lasers, remote sensing, medicine, sonics, magnetism, and nuclear physics
211103	Evaluating results of investigations and experiments and expressing conclusions, mainly using mathematical techniques and models
211104	Applying principles, techniques and processes to develop or improve industrial, medical, military and other practical applications
211105	Ensuring the safe and effective delivery of radiation (ionising and non-ionising) to patients to achieve a diagnostic or therapeutic result as prescribed by a medical practitioner
211106	Ensuring the accurate measurement and characterisation of physical quantities used in medical applications
211107	Testing, commissioning and evaluating equipment used in applications such as imaging, medical treatment and dosimetry
211108	Advising and consulting with medical practitioners and other health care professionals in optimizing the balance between the beneficial and deleterious effects of radiation
211109	Observing, analysing and interpreting celestial phenomena and developing methods, numerical models and techniques to extend knowledge of fields such as navigation, satellite communication, space exploration, celestial bodies and cosmic radiation

Code	Task
211110	Developing, implementing and maintaining standards and protocols for the measurement of physical phenomena and for the use of nuclear technology in industrial and medical applications
211111	Preparing scholarly papers and reports
211201	Investigating direction and speed of air movements, pressures, temperatures, humidity, physical and chemical transformation of pollutants and other phenomena such as cloud formation and precipitation, electrical disturbances or solar radiation
211202	Studying data collected from meteorological stations, radar and satellite imagery and computer model output to plot and forecast weather conditions
211203	Preparing and reporting short-term or long-term weather maps, forecasts and warnings relating to atmospheric phenomena such as cyclones, storms and other hazards to life and property and disseminating information about atmospheric conditions through a variety of media including radio, television, print and the Internet
211204	Conducting experiments in fog dispersal, cloud seeding, rain enhancement and other types of weather modification programs
211205	Developing and testing mathematical computer models of weather and climate for experimental or operational use
211206	Participating in studies of the effect of weather on the environment
211207	Analysing the impact of industrial projects and human activity on the climate and quality of the air and work with the social science, engineering and economic communities to develop appropriate mitigation strategies
211208	Engaging in the design and development of new equipment and procedures for meteorological data collection, remote sensing, or for related applications
211209	Conducting research on and improving or developing concepts, theories and operational methods related to the composition, structure and dynamics of the atmosphere and preparing scientific papers and reports on the outcome of this research
211210	Preparing scholarly papers and reports
211301	Conducting research and improving or developing concepts, instruments, theories and operational methods related to chemistry
211302	Conducting experiments, tests and analyses to investigate chemical composition and energy and chemical changes in various natural or synthetic substances, materials and products
211303	Developing procedures for environmental control, quality control and various other procedures for manufacturers or users
211304	Conducting programs of sample and data collection and analysis to identify and quantify environmental toxicants
211305	Participating in interdisciplinary research and development projects working with chemical engineers, biologists, microbiologists, agronomists, geologists or other professionals
211306	Using micro-organisms to convert substances into new compounds
211307	Determining ways to strengthen or combine materials or develop new materials
211308	Reproducing and synthesizing naturally occurring substances and creating new artificial substances
211309	Preparing scholarly papers and reports
211401	Conducting research and improving or developing concepts, theories and operational methods related to geology and geophysics
211402	Studying composition and structure of the earth's crust, examining rocks, minerals, fossils and other materials, to determine processes affecting the development of the earth, trace evolution of past life, establish nature and chronology of geological formations and assess their commercial applications
211403	Interpreting research data and preparing geological reports, maps, charts and diagrams, reports and papers
211404	Applying geological knowledge to problems encountered in civil engineering projects such as the construction of dams, bridges, tunnels, and large buildings and land reclamation projects
211405	Using various remote sensing programs to investigate and measure seismic, gravitational, electrical, thermal, and magnetic forces affecting the earth
211406	Estimating weight, size and mass of the earth and composition and structure of its interior, and studying the nature, activity and predictability of volcanoes, glaciers and earthquakes

Code	Task
211407	Charting the earth's magnetic field and applying this and other collected data for broadcasting, navigation and other purposes
211408	Studying and measuring physical properties of seas and the atmosphere and their inter-relationship, such as the exchange of thermal energy
211409	Locating and determining the nature and extent of oil, gas and mineral deposits using seismological, gravimetric, magnetic, electrical or radiometric methods
211410	Identifying deposits of construction materials and determining their characteristics and suitability for use as concrete aggregates, road fill or for other applications
211411	Researching the movement, distribution and physical properties of ground and surface waters
211412	Advising in areas such as waste management, route and site selection and the restoration of contaminated sites
212001	Studying, improving and developing mathematical, actuarial and statistical theories and techniques
212002	Advising on or applying mathematical principles, models and techniques to a wide range of tasks in the fields of engineering, natural, social or life sciences
212003	Conducting logical analyses of management problems, especially in terms of input-output effectiveness, and formulating mathematical models of each problem usually for programming and solution by computer
212004	Applying mathematics, statistics, probability and risk theory to assess potential financial impacts of future events
212005	Planning and organizing surveys and other statistical collections, and designing questionnaires
212006	Evaluating, processing, analysing, and interpreting statistical data and preparing them for publication
212007	Advising on or applying various data collection methods and statistical methods and techniques, and determining reliability of findings, especially in such fields as business or medicine as well as in other areas of natural, social or life sciences
212008	Preparing scholarly papers and reports
212009	Supervising the work of mathematical, actuarial and statistical assistants and statistical clerks
213101	Undertaking research in laboratories and in the field to increase scientific knowledge of living organisms, to discover new information to test hypotheses to solve problems in areas such as the environment, agriculture and health and to develop new products, processes and techniques for pharmaceutical, agricultural and environmental use
213102	Designing and conducting experiments and tests
213103	Gathering human, animal, insect and plant specimens and data, and studying their origin, development, chemical and physical form, structure, composition, and life and reproductive processes
213104	Examining living organisms using a variety of specialised equipment, instruments, technologies and techniques such as electron microscopes, telemetry, global positioning systems, biotechnology, satellite imaging, genetic engineering, digital imaging analysis, polymerase chain reaction and computer modelling
213105	Identifying, classifying, recording and monitoring living organisms and maintaining databases
213106	Writing scientific papers and reports detailing research and any new findings which are then made available to the scientific community in scientific journals or at conferences for scrutiny and further debate
213107	Designing and carrying out environmental impact assessments to identify changes caused by natural or human factors
213108	Providing advice to governments, organisations and businesses in areas such as conservation, management of natural resources, the effects of climate change and pollution
213201	Collecting and analysing data and samples related to produce, feed, soil, water quality and other factors affecting farm, forest or fishery production
213202	Advising on techniques for improving the production of crops, livestock and fish, and alternative production options
213203	Advising on livestock and crop disease, control of pests and weeds, soil improvement, animal husbandry and feeding programs

Code	Task
213204	Studying the effects of cultivation techniques, soils, insects, diseases and fisheries practices on animal, crop, forestry and fisheries yield
213205	Studying fish migration, growth, feeding and spawning and devising methods of collecting, fertilizing, incubating and hatching fish eggs
213206	Researching into characteristics, use capability and productivity of soils and applying findings to development of improved agricultural, horticultural and forestry practices
213207	Developing procedures and techniques for solving agricultural problems and improving the efficiency of production
213208	Managing forest and fisheries resources to maximize their long-term commercial, recreational and environmental benefits
213209	Studying the propagation and culture of forest trees, methods for improving the growth of stock, and the effects of thinning on forest yields
213210	Investigating, planning and implementing management procedures to cope with the effects of fires, floods, droughts, soil erosion, pests and diseases
213211	Preparing scientific reports and conducting advisory information sessions and lectures for farming, forestry and fishing communities and other groups
213301	Conducting research, performing tests, collecting samples, performing field and laboratory analysis to identify sources of environmental problems and recommending ways to prevent, control and remediate the impact of environmental problems
213302	Assessing the likely impact that potential or proposed activities, projects and developments may have on the environment, and recommending whether such developments should proceed
213303	Developing and coordinating the implementation of environmental management systems to enable organisations to identify, monitor and control the impact of their activities, products and services on the environment
213304	Conducting audits to evaluate environmental impact of existing activities, processes, wastes, noises and substances
213305	Assessing an organisation's compliance with government and internal environmental regulations and guidelines, identifying violations and determining appropriate remedial action
213306	Providing technical advice and support services to organisations on how best to deal with environmental problems in order to reduce environmental damage and minimize financial loss
213307	Developing conservation plans
214101	Studying functional statements, organisational charts and project information to determine functions and responsibilities of workers and work units and to identify areas of duplication
214102	Establishing work measurement programs and analysing work samples to develop standards for labour utilisation
214103	Analysing workforce utilisation, facility layout, operational data and production schedules and costs to determine optimum worker and equipment efficiencies
214104	Developing specifications for manufacture, and determining materials, equipment, piping, material flows, capacities and layout of plant and systems
214105	Organising and managing project labour and the delivery of materials, plant and equipment
214106	Establishing standards and policies for installation, modification, quality control, testing, inspection and maintenance according to engineering principles and safety regulations
214107	Inspecting plant to improve and maintain performance
214108	Directing the maintenance of plant buildings and equipment, and coordinating the requirements for new designs, surveys and maintenance schedules
214109	Advising management on new production methods, techniques and equipment
214110	Liaising with materials buying, storing and controlling departments to ensure a steady flow of supplies
214201	Conducting research and developing new or improved theories and methods related to civil engineering
214202	Advising on and designing structures such as bridges, dams, docks, roads, airports, railways, canals, pipelines, waste-disposal and flood-control systems, and industrial and other large buildings

Code	Task
214203	Determining and specifying construction methods, materials and quality standards, and directing construction work
214204	Establishing control systems to ensure efficient functioning of structures as well as safety and environmental protection
214205	Organising and directing maintenance and repair of existing civil engineering structures
214206	Analysing the behaviour of soil and rock when placed under pressure by proposed structures and designing structural foundations
214207	Analysing the stability of structures and testing the behaviour and durability of materials used in their construction
214301	Conducting research, assessing and reporting on the environmental impact of existing and proposed construction, civil engineering and other activities
214302	Inspecting industrial and municipal facilities and programs to evaluate operational effectiveness and ensure compliance with environmental regulations
214303	Designing and overseeing the development of systems, processes and equipment for control, management, or remediation of water, air, or soil quality
214304	Providing environmental engineering assistance in network analysis, regulatory analysis, and planning or reviewing database development
214305	Obtaining, updating, and maintaining plans, permits, and standard operating procedures
214306	Providing engineering and technical support for environmental remediation and litigation projects, including remediation system design and determination of regulatory applicability
214307	Monitoring progress of environmental improvement programs
214308	Advising corporations and government agencies of procedures to follow in cleaning up contaminated sites to protect people and the environment
214309	Collaborating with environmental scientists, planners, hazardous waste technicians, engineers from other disciplines, and specialists in law and business to address environmental problems
214401	Advising on and designing machinery and tools for manufacturing, mining, construction, agricultural, and other industrial purposes
214402	Advising on and designing steam, internal combustion and other non-electric motors and engines used for propulsion of railway locomotives, road vehicles or aircraft, or for driving industrial or other machinery
214403	Advising on and designing: hulls, superstructures and propulsion systems of ships mechanical plant and equipment for the release, control and utilisation of energy heating, ventilation and refrigeration systems, steering gear, pumps, and other mechanical equipment
214404	Advising on and designing airframes, undercarriages and other equipment for aircraft as well as suspension systems, brakes, vehicle bodies and other components of road vehicles
214405	Advising on and designing non-electrical parts of apparatus or products such as word processors, computers, precision instruments, cameras and projectors
214406	Establishing control standards and procedures to ensure efficient functioning and safety of machines, machinery, tools, motors, engines, industrial plant, equipment, or systems
214407	Ensuring that equipment, operation and maintenance comply with design specifications and safety standards
214501	Conducting research and advising on, and developing commercial-scale chemical processes to refine crude oil and other liquids or gases, and to produce substances and items such as petroleum derivatives, explosives, food and drink products, medicines, or synthetic materials
214502	Specifying chemical production methods, materials and quality standards and ensuring that they conform to specifications
214503	Establishing control standards and procedures to ensure safety and efficiency of chemical production operations and safety of workers operating equipment or working in close proximity to on-going chemical reactions
214504	Designing chemical plant equipment and devising processes for manufacturing chemicals and products
214505	Performing tests throughout stages of production to determine degree of control over variables, including temperature, density, specific gravity, and pressure
214506	Developing safety procedures to be employed

Code	Task
214507	Preparing estimates of production costs and production progress reports for management
214508	Performing laboratory studies of steps in manufacture of new products and testing proposed process in small scale operation such as a pilot plant
214601	Determining the location and planning the extraction of coal, metallic ores, non-metallic minerals, and building materials, such as stone and gravel
214602	Determining most suitable methods of efficient mining and extraction, types of machinery to be used, planning layout and directing construction of shafts and tunnels
214603	Determining drilling site and devising methods of controlling the flow of water, oil or gas from wells
214604	Planning and directing storage, initial treatment and transportation of water, oil or gas
214605	Establishing safety standards and procedures and first-aid facilities, especially underground
214606	Conducting research, developing methods of extracting metals from their ores and advising on their application
214607	Investigating properties of metals and alloys, developing new alloys and advising on and supervising technical aspects of metal and alloy manufacture and processing
214608	Maintaining technical liaison and consultancy with other relevant specialists such as geologists and geophysicists
214609	Examining deposits or mines to evaluate profitability
214901	Applying knowledge of engineering to the design, development, and evaluation of biological and health systems and products, such as artificial organs, prostheses, and instrumentation
214902	Designing devices used in various medical procedures, imaging systems such as magnetic resonance imaging, and devices for automating insulin injections or controlling body functions
214903	Designing components of optical instruments such as lenses, microscopes, telescopes, lasers, optical disc systems and other equipment that utilize the properties of light
214904	Designing, testing, and coordinating the development of explosive ordnance material to meet military procurement specifications
214905	Designing and overseeing construction and operation of nuclear reactors and power plants and nuclear fuels reprocessing and reclamation systems
214906	Designing and developing nuclear equipment such as reactor cores, radiation shielding, and associated instrumentation and control mechanisms
214907	Assessing damage and providing calculations for marine salvage operations
214908	Studying and advising on engineering aspects of particular manufacturing processes, such as those related to glass, ceramics, textiles, leather products, wood, and printing
214909	Identifying potential hazards and introducing safety procedures and devices
215101	Advising on and designing power stations and systems which generate , transmit and distribute electrical power
215102	Supervising, controlling and monitoring the operation of electrical generation, transmission and distribution systems
215103	Advising on and designing systems for electrical motors, electrical traction and other equipment, or electrical domestic appliances
215104	Specifying electrical installation and application in industrial and other buildings and objects
215105	Establishing control standards and procedures to monitor performance and safety of electrical generating and distribution systems, motors and equipment
215106	Determining manufacturing methods for electrical systems, as well as maintenance and repair of existing electrical systems, motors and equipment
215201	Advising on and designing electronic devices or components, circuits, semi-conductors, and systems
215202	Specifying production or installation methods, materials and quality standards and directing production or installation work of electronic products and systems
215203	Establishing control standards and procedures to ensure efficient functioning and safety of electronic systems, motors and equipment
215204	Organising and directing maintenance and repair of existing electronic systems and equipment

Code	Task
215205	Designing electronic circuits and components for use in fields such as aerospace guidance and propulsion control, acoustics, or instruments and controls
215206	Researching and advising on radar, telemetry and remote control systems, microwaves and other electronic equipment
215207	Designing and developing signal processing algorithms and implementing these through appropriate choice of hardware and software
215208	Developing apparatus and procedures to test electronic components, circuits and systems
215301	Advising on and designing telecommunications devices or components, systems, equipment and distribution centres
215302	Specifying production or installation methods, materials, quality and safety standards and directing production or installation work of telecommunications products and systems
215303	Organizing and directing maintenance and repair of existing telecommunication systems, motors and equipment
215304	Researching and advising on telecommunications equipment
215305	Planning and designing communications networks based on wired, fibre optical and wireless communication media
215306	Designing and developing signal processing algorithms and implementing these through appropriate choice of hardware and software
215307	Designing telecommunications networks and radio and television distribution systems, including both cable and over the air
216101	Developing new or improved architectural theories and methods
216102	Inspecting sites and consulting clients, management and other stakeholders to determine type, style and size of proposed buildings and alterations to existing buildings
216103	Providing information regarding designs, materials and estimated building times
216104	Preparing project documentation, including sketches and scale drawings, and integrating structural, mechanical and aesthetic elements in final designs
216105	Writing specifications and contract documents for use by builders and calling tenders on behalf of clients
216106	Making necessary contacts to ensure feasibility of projects regarding style, cost, timing, and compliance with regulations
216107	Identifying and finding best solutions for problems regarding function and quality of interior environments of buildings and making necessary designs, drawings and plans
216108	Monitoring construction or rehabilitation work to ensure compliance with specifications and quality standards
216109	Maintaining technical liaison and consultancy with other relevant specialists
216201	Developing new or improved theories and methods in landscape architecture
216202	Inspecting sites and consulting clients, management and other stakeholders to determine type, style and size of proposed buildings, parks, roads and other open spaces
216203	Compiling and analysing site and community data about geographical and ecological features, landforms, soils, vegetation, site hydrology, visual characteristics and human-made structures, to formulate land use and development recommendations, and for preparing environmental impact statements
216204	Preparing reports, site plans, working drawings, specifications and cost estimates for land development, showing location and details of proposals, including ground modelling, structures, vegetation and access
216205	Writing specifications and contract documents for use by builders and civil engineering contractors and calling tenders on behalf of clients
216206	Making necessary contacts to ensure feasibility of projects regarding style, cost, timing, and compliance with regulations
216207	Identifying and finding best solutions for problems regarding function and quality of exterior environments and making necessary designs, drawings and plans
216208	Monitoring construction or rehabilitation work to ensure compliance with specifications and quality standards
216209	Maintaining technical liaison and consultancy with other relevant specialists

Code	Task
216301	Determining the objectives and constraints of the design brief by consulting with clients and stakeholders
216302	Formulating design concepts for clothing, textiles, industrial, commercial and consumer products, and jewellery
216303	Harmonizing aesthetic considerations with technical, functional, ecological and production requirements
216304	Preparing sketches, diagrams, illustrations, plans, samples and models to communicate design concepts
216305	Negotiating design solutions with clients, management, and sales and manufacturing staff
216306	Selecting, specifying and recommending functional and aesthetic materials, production methods and finishes for manufacture
216307	Detailing and documenting the selected design for production
216308	Preparing and commissioning prototypes and samples
216309	Supervising the preparation of patterns, programs and tooling, and the manufacturing process
216401	Planning layout and coordinating development of urban areas
216402	Compiling and analysing data on economic, legal, political, cultural, demographic, sociological, physical and environmental factors affecting land use
216403	Conferring with government authorities, communities and specialists in fields such as architecture, planning, social science the environment and the law
216404	Devising and recommending use and development of land, and presenting narrative and graphic plans, programs and designs to groups and individuals
216405	Advising governments, companies and communities on urban and regional planning issues and proposals
216406	Reviewing and evaluating environmental impact reports
216407	Planning layout and coordinating development of urban areas
216408	Planning and the development of land areas for parks, schools, institutions, airports, roadways and related projects, and for commercial, industrial and residential sites
216409	Planning and advising on routing and control of road traffic and public transportation systems for efficiency and safety
216501	Surveying, measuring and describing land surfaces, mines, underground surfaces, sea, river and lake beds
216502	Noting exact position of various features and recording survey data in digital form
216503	Making charts and maps to be used in determining navigable waters and channels and in planning construction of marine structures
216504	Planning and conducting aerial photographic surveys
216505	Designing, compiling and revising maps and charts using aerial and other photographs, satellite imagery, survey documents and data, existing maps and records, reports and statistics
216506	Undertaking research and development of surveying and photogrammetric measurement systems, cadastral systems and land information systems
216507	Studying and advising on technical, aesthetic and economic aspects of map production
216508	Maintaining technical liaison and consultancy with other relevant specialists
216601	Determining the objectives and constraints of the design brief by consulting with clients and stakeholders
216602	Undertaking research and analysing functional communication requirements
216603	Formulating design concepts for the subject to be communicated
216604	Preparing sketches, diagrams, illustrations and layouts to communicate design concepts
216605	Designing complex graphics and animation to satisfy functional, aesthetic and creative requirements of the design brief
216606	Creating two-dimensional and three-dimensional images depicting objects in motion or illustrating a process, using computer animation or modelling programs
216607	Negotiating design solutions with clients, management, sales and production staff
216608	Selecting, specifying or recommending functional and aesthetic materials and media for publication, delivery or display

Code	Task
216609	Detailing and documenting the selected design for production
216610	Supervising or carrying out production in the chosen media
221101	Conducting physical examinations of patients and interviewing them and their families to determine their health status
221102	Ordering laboratory tests, X-rays and other diagnostic procedures and analysing findings to determine the nature of disorders or illnesses
221103	Providing continuing medical care for patients including prescribing, administering, counselling on and monitoring curative treatments and preventive measures
221104	Performing surgery and other clinical procedures
221105	Advising individuals, families and communities on health, nutrition and lifestyle which aid prevention or treatment of disease and disorders
221106	Providing referrals to patients and families for specialized care in hospitals, rehabilitation centres or other types of health care centres
221107	Identifying, managing and providing referrals for complications before, during and after childbirth
221108	Recording patients' medical information and history and exchanging information with specialist practitioners and other health workers as required for continuing medical care
221109	Reporting births, deaths and notifiable diseases to government authorities to meet legal and professional requirements
221110	Conducting research in human health and medical services and disseminating the findings such as through scientific reports
221111	Planning and participating in programs designed to prevent the occurrence and spread of common diseases
221201	Conducting physical examinations of patients and interviewing them and their families to determine their health status
221202	Considering medical information provided by a referring doctor or other health care provider,
221203	Ordering specialized diagnostic tests to determine the nature of disorders or illnesses
221204	Prescribing, administering and monitoring patients' responses to treatments, medications, anaesthetics, psychotherapies, physical rehabilitation programmes and other preventive and curative measures
221205	Performing surgery of a general or specialized nature
221206	Managing complications before, during and after childbirth
221207	Recording patients' medical information and exchanging information with other health professionals to ensure the provision of comprehensive care
221208	Reporting births, deaths and notifiable diseases to government authorities to meet legal and professional requirements
221209	Providing information to patients and families and communities about preventive measures, treatment and care for specific ailments
221210	Performing autopsies to determine cause of death
221211	Conducting research into specific human disorders and illnesses and preventive or curative methods and disseminating the findings such as through scientific reports
221212	Planning and participating in programs designed to prevent the occurrence and spread of specific diseases
222101	Planning, providing and evaluating nursing care for patients according to the practice and standards of modern nursing
222102	Coordinating the care of patients in consultation with other health professionals and members of health teams
222103	Developing and implementing care plans for the biological, social, and psychological treatment of patients in collaboration with other health professionals
222104	Planning and providing personal care, treatments and therapies including administering medications, and monitoring responses to treatment or care plan
222105	Cleaning wounds and applying surgical dressings and bandages

Code	Task
222106	Monitoring pain and discomfort experienced by patients and alleviating pain using a variety of therapies, including the use of pain-killing drugs
222107	Planning and participating in health education programmes, health promotion and nurse education activities in clinical and community settings
222108	Answering questions from patients and families and providing information about prevention of ill-health, treatment and care
222109	Supervising and coordinating the work of other nursing, health and personal care workers
222110	Conducting research on nursing practices and procedures and disseminating findings such as through scientific papers and reports
222201	Planning, providing and evaluating care and support services for women and babies before, during and after pregnancy and childbirth according to the practice and standards of modern midwifery care
222202	Providing advice to women and families and conducting community education on health, nutrition, hygiene, exercise, birth and emergency plans, breastfeeding, infant care, family planning and contraception, lifestyle and other topics related to pregnancy and childbirth
222203	Assessing progress during pregnancy and childbirth, managing complications and recognising warning signs requiring referral to a medical doctor with specialized skills in obstetrics
222204	Monitoring the health status of newborns, managing complications and recognising warning signs requiring referral to a medical doctor with specialized skills in neonatology
222205	Monitoring pain and discomfort experienced by women during labour and delivery and alleviating pain using a variety of therapies, including the use of pain-killing drugs
222206	Reporting births to government authorities to meet legal and professional requirements
222207	Conducting research on midwifery practices and procedures and disseminating findings such as through scientific papers and reports
222208	Planning and conducting midwifery education activities in clinical and community settings
223001	Conducting physical examinations of patients and interviewing them and their families to determine their health status
223002	Developing and implementing treatment plans for physical, mental and psychosocial ailments using applications such as acupuncture, ayurvedic, homoeopathic and herbal medicine
223003	Evaluating and documenting patients' progress through treatment plans
223004	Providing health, nutrition and lifestyle advice to individuals, families and communities
223005	Prescribing and preparing traditional medicines, such as herbal, plant, mineral and animal extracts, to stimulate the body's capacity for self-healing
223006	Exchanging information about patients with other health care workers as needed to ensure continuing and comprehensive health care
223007	Conducting research into traditional and complementary medicines and treatments and disseminating findings such as through scientific papers and reports
224001	Conducting physical examinations of patients and interviewing them and their families to determine their health status
224002	Performing basic or more routine medical and surgical procedures, including prescribing and administering treatments, medications and other preventive or curative measures, especially for common diseases and disorders
224003	Administering or ordering diagnostic tests, such as x-ray, electrocardiogram, and laboratory tests
224004	Performing therapeutic procedures, such as injections, immunisations, suturing and wound care, and infection management
224005	Assisting medical doctors with complex surgical procedures
224006	Monitoring patients' progress and response to treatment, and identifying signs and symptoms requiring referral to medical doctors
224007	Advising patients and families on diet, exercise and other habits which aid prevention or treatment of disease and disorders
224008	Identifying and referring complex or unusual cases to medical doctors, hospitals or other places for specialized care

Code	Task
224009	Reporting births, deaths and notifiable diseases to government authorities to meet legal and professional requirements
224010	Recording patients' medical information
225001	Determining the presence and nature of abnormal conditions by physical examination, laboratory testing and through diagnostic imaging techniques including radiography and ultrasound
225002	Treating animals medically and surgically, and administering and prescribing drugs, analgesics, and general and local anaesthetics
225003	Performing surgery, dressing wounds and setting broken bones
225004	Rendering obstetric and dental services to animals
225005	Participating in programs designed to prevent the occurrence and spread of animal diseases
225006	Inoculating animals against, and testing for infectious diseases and notifying authorities of outbreaks of infectious animal diseases
225007	Performing autopsies to determine cause of death
225008	Advising clients on health, nutrition and feeding, hygiene, breeding and care of animals
225009	Providing euthanasia services for animals
226101	Diagnosing diseases, injuries, irregularities and malformations of teeth and associated structures in the mouth and jaw using a range of methods such as radiographs, salivary tests and medical histories
226102	Providing preventative oral health care such as periodontal treatments, fluoride applications and oral health promotion
226103	Administering anesthetics to limit the amount of pain experienced by patients during procedures
226104	Prescribing medication for relief of ongoing pain after procedures
226105	Providing restorative oral care such as implants, complex crown and bridge restorations, and orthodontics, and repairing damaged and decayed teeth
226106	Providing surgical treatments such as extraction of teeth, biopsy of tissue, and performing orthodontic treatment
226107	Measuring and taking impressions of patients' jaws and teeth in order to determine the shape and size of dental prostheses
226108	Designing , making, and fitting prosthodontic appliances such as space maintainers, bridges, and dentures, or writing fabrication instructions or prescriptions for dental prosthetic technicians
226109	Restoring oral function with removable and fixed oral prostheses
226110	Assisting in diagnosing general diseases having oral manifestations such as diabetes
226111	Educating patients and families on dental hygiene, nutrition and other measures to take care of oral health
226112	Supervising dental hygienists, dental assistants and other staff
226201	Receiving prescriptions for medicinal products from medical doctors and other health professionals, checking patients' medicine histories, and ensuring proper dosage and methods of administration and drug compatibility before dispensing
226202	Preparing or supervising the preparation and labelling of liquid medicines, ointments, powders, tablets and other medications to fill prescriptions
226203	Providing information and advice to prescribers and clients regarding drug interactions, incompatibility and contra-indications, side effects, dosage and proper medication storage

Code	Task
226204	Collaborating with other health care professionals to plan, monitor, review, and evaluate the quality and effectiveness of the medicine therapy of individual patients, and the effectiveness of particular drugs or therapies
226205	Maintaining prescription files and recording issue of narcotics, poisons and habit-forming drugs in accordance with legal and professional requirements
226206	Storing and preserving vaccines, serums and other drugs subject to deterioration
226207	Advising clients on and supplying non-prescription medicines and diagnostic and therapeutic aids for common conditions
226208	Supervising and coordinating the work of pharmacy technicians, pharmacy interns and pharmacy sales assistants
226209	Conducting research to develop and improve pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and related chemical products
226210	Conferring with chemists, engineering professionals and other professionals about manufacturing techniques and ingredients
226211	Testing and analysing drugs to determine their identity, purity and strength in relation to specified standards
226212	Evaluating labels, packaging and advertising of drug products
226213	Developing information and risks of particular drugs
226301	Developing, implementing and reviewing programs and policies to minimize potential environmental and occupational risks to health and safety
226302	Preparing and implementing plans and strategies for the safe, economic and suitable disposal of commercial, industrial, medical and household wastes
226303	Implementing prevention programs and strategies for communicable diseases, food safety, waste water treatment and disposal systems, recreation and domestic water quality, contaminated and hazardous substances
226304	Identifying, reporting and documenting hazards, and assessing and controlling risks in the environment and workplace and advising on compliance with relevant law and regulations
226305	Developing, implementing and monitoring programs to minimize workplace and environmental pollution involving chemical, physical and biological hazards
226306	Advising methods to prevent, eliminate, control, or reduce the exposure of workers, students, the public and the environment to radiological and other hazards
226307	Promoting ergonomic principles within the workplace such as matching furniture, equipment and work activities to the needs of employees
226308	Providing education, information, training, and advice to persons at all levels on aspects of occupational hygiene and environmental health
226309	Recording and investigating injuries and equipment damage, and reporting safety performance
226310	Coordinating arrangements for the compensation, rehabilitation and return to work of injured workers
226401	Administering muscle, nerve, joint and functional ability tests to identify and assess physical problems of patients
226402	Establishing treatment goals with patients and designing treatment programs to reduce physical pain, strengthen muscles, improve cardiothoracic, cardiovascular and respiratory functions, restore joint mobility, and improve balance and coordination

Code	Task
226403	Developing, implementing and monitoring programs and treatments using the therapeutic properties of exercise, heat, cold, massage, manipulation, hydrotherapy, electrotherapy, ultraviolet and infra-red light and ultrasound in the treatment of patients
226404	Instructing patients and their families in procedures to be continued outside clinical settings
226405	Recording information on patients' health status and responses to treatment in medical records-keeping systems, and sharing information with other health professionals as required to ensure continuing and comprehensive care
226406	Developing and implementing programmes for screening and prevention of common physical ailments and disorders
226407	Supervising the work of physiotherapy assistants and others
226501	Instructing individuals, families and communities on nutrition, the planning of diets and preparation of food to maximize health benefits and reduce potential risks to health
226502	Planning diets and menus, supervising the preparation and serving of meals, and monitoring food intake and quality to provide nutritional care in settings offering food services
226503	Compiling and assessing data relating to health and nutritional status of individuals, groups and communities based on nutritional values of food served or consumed
226504	Planning and conducting nutrition assessments, intervention programmes, and education and training to improve nutritional levels among individuals and communities
226505	Consulting with other health professionals and care providers to manage the dietary and nutritional needs of patients
226506	Developing and evaluating food and nutrition products to meet nutritional requirements
226507	Conducting research on nutrition and disseminating the findings at scientific conferences and in other settings
226601	Evaluating hearing, speech and language performance in patients to determine the nature of hearing and communication disorders
226602	Administering hearing or speech/language tests or other examinations using specialized diagnostic instruments and equipment, and interpreting test results alongside other medical, social and behavioural diagnostic data to determine appropriate courses of treatment
226603	Planning, directing and participating in counselling, screening, speech rehabilitation and other programs related to hearing and communication
226604	Prescribing hearing aids and other assistive devices according to patients' needs and instructing them in their use
226605	Planning and conducting treatment programs to manage physical disorders affecting speech and swallowing in patients such as stuttering and feeding disorders
226606	Counselling and guiding hearing and/or language-impaired individuals, their families, teachers and employers
226607	Referring patients and families to additional medical or educational services if needed
226701	Examining patients' eyes and conducting diagnostic tests to assess ocular health and determine the nature and extent of vision problems and abnormalities
226702	Testing visual function using specialized instruments and equipment for measuring visual acuity and refractive error, function of visual pathways, visual fields, eye movements, freedom of vision and intraocular pressure
226703	Detecting, diagnosing and managing eye disease, including prescribing medications for the treatment of eye disease

Code	Task
226704	Consulting with and referring patients to ophthalmologists or other health professionals if additional medical treatment is necessary
226705	Detecting and diagnosing eye movement disorders and defects of binocular function, and planning and managing treatment programs, including counselling patients in eye exercises to coordinate movement and focusing of eyes
226706	Prescribing corrective eyeglasses, contact lenses and other vision aids, and checking optical devices for performance, safety, comfort and lifestyle
226707	Advising on visual health matters such as contact lens care, vision care for the elderly, optics, visual ergonomics, and occupational and industrial eye safety
226901	Interviewing patients and conducting diagnostic tests to determine their health status and the nature of physical or mental disorders, illnesses or other health problems
226902	Developing and implementing treatment plans for injuries, illnesses and other physical and mental impairments
226903	Evaluating and documenting patients' progress through treatment plans, and referring patients and families to medical doctors or other health care providers for specialized, rehabilitative or other care services as needed
226904	Assessing functional limitations of clients resulting from illness, disability or other impairment, and providing therapy
226905	Recommending environmental adaptations in the home, leisure, work and school environments on an individual or group basis to enable them to perform their daily activities and occupations
226906	Planning and implementing therapeutic programs on an individual and group basis for improving and maintaining physical, cognitive, emotional and social functioning, including through the use of arts and crafts, dance and movement, music and other recreational activities
226907	Identifying and prescribing treatments for conditions affecting the foot, ankle and related structures of the leg due to illness, disease or other physical impairment, and prescribing corrective footwear and advising on foot care to manage foot ailments
226908	Performing minor surgical procedures such as on the foot and ankles
231001	Designing and modifying curricula and preparing courses of study in accordance with requirements
231002	Preparing and delivering lectures and conducting tutorials, seminars and laboratory experiments
231003	Stimulating discussion and independent thought among students
231004	Supervising, where appropriate, experimental and practical work undertaken by students
231005	Administering, evaluating and marking examination papers and tests
231006	Directing research of post-graduate students or other members of department
231007	Researching into and developing concepts, theories and operational methods for application in industrial and other fields
231008	Preparing scholarly books, papers or articles
231009	Participating in departmental and faculty meetings and in conferences and seminars
232001	Developing curricula and planning course content and methods of instruction
232002	Determining training needs of students or workers and liaising with individuals, industry and other education sectors to ensure provision of relevant education and training programs

Code	Task
232003	Presenting lectures and conducting discussions to increase students' knowledge and competence
232004	Instructing and monitoring students in the use of tools, equipment and materials and the prevention of injury and damage
232005	Observing and evaluating students' work to determine progress, provide feedback, and make suggestions for improvement
232006	Administering oral, written or performance tests to measure progress, evaluate training effectiveness and assess competency
232007	Preparing reports and maintaining records such as student grades, attendance rolls, and training activity details
232008	Supervising independent or group projects, field placements, laboratory work, or other training
232009	Providing individualized instruction and tutorial or remedial instruction
232010	Conducting on-the-job training sessions to teach and demonstrate principles, techniques, procedures, or methods of designated subjects
233001	Designing and modifying curricula and preparing educational courses of study in accordance with curriculum guidelines
233002	Establishing and enforcing rules for behaviour and procedures for maintaining order among students
233003	Preparing and giving lessons, discussions, and demonstrations in one or more subjects
233004	Establishing clear objectives for all lessons, units, and projects and communicating those objectives to students
233005	Preparing materials and classrooms for class activities
233006	Adapting teaching methods and instructional materials to meet students' varying needs and interests
233007	Observing and evaluating students' performance and behaviour
233008	Preparing, administering and marking tests, assignments and examinations to evaluate pupils' progress
233009	Preparing reports about pupils' work and conferring with other teachers and parents
233010	Participating in meetings concerning the school's educational or organisational policies
233011	Planning, organizing and participating in school activities such as excursions, sporting events and concerts
234101	Preparing daily and longer term lesson plans in accordance with curriculum guidelines
234102	Instructing children individually and in groups, using various teaching methods and materials (eg computers, books, games), adapting to children's varying needs
234103	Maintaining discipline and good working habits in the classroom
234104	Planning and conduct activities with the children such as sporting activities, concerts and excursions
234105	Assigning and grading class work and homework
234106	Preparing, administering, and grading tests and assignments to evaluate children's progress
234107	Observing and evaluating children's performance and behaviour
234108	Supervising children during classes and at other times in the school day, including the playground during breaks

Code	Task
234109	Participating in staff meetings and other sessions, and conferring with other teachers concerning educational issues
234110	Preparing for and attending parent meetings to discuss children's progress and problems
234201	Planning and organizing individual and group activities designed to facilitate the development of children's motor skills, cooperative and social skills, confidence and understanding
234202	Promoting language development through story-telling, role-play, songs, rhymes and informal conversations and discussions
234203	Leading children in activities that provide opportunities for creative expression through the media of art, dramatic play, music and physical fitness
234204	Observing children in order to evaluate progress and to detect signs of developmental, emotional or health related problems with parents
234205	Observing and assessing nutritional health, welfare and safety needs of children and identifying factors which may impede their progress
234206	Supervising children's activities to ensure safety and resolve conflicts
234207	Guiding and assisting children in the development of proper eating, dressing and toilet habits
234208	Discussing progress or problems of children with parents and other staff members and identifying appropriate actions and referrals to other services
234209	Establishing and maintaining collaborative relationships with other service providers working with young children
235101	Researching into current developments in curricula, teaching methods and other educational practices, and advising on necessary changes and possible improvements
235102	Evaluating and advising on contents of courses and methods of examination
235103	Researching into audio-visual and other teaching aids and advising on, planning and organising their introduction in educational establishments
235104	Documenting subjects and courses developed, and evaluating new courses
235105	Providing ongoing professional development, training and consultative services to teachers
235106	Organizing and conducting workshops and conferences to train teachers in new programs and methods
235107	Developing the structure, content and objectives of new educational courses and programs
235108	Visiting schools periodically and conferring with administrative and teaching staff on questions relating to curricula, teaching methods, equipment and other matters
235109	Visiting classrooms to observe teaching techniques and to evaluate teachers performance, and scholastic results obtained
235110	Preparing reports and making recommendations to educational authorities concerning possible changes and improvements in curricula, teaching methods, and other matters
235201	Assessing students' abilities and limitations with regard to intellectual, physical, social and emotional impairments, exceptional intellectual gifts, or other specific problems
235202	Designing or modifying curricula and preparing and delivering programmes, lessons and activities adapted to students' abilities and needs
235203	Giving instruction on an individual or group basis using special techniques or aids appropriate to students' needs
235204	Employing special educational strategies and techniques during instruction to improve the development of sensory- and perceptual-motor skills, language, cognition, and memory

Code	Task
235205	Establishing and enforcing rules for behaviour and policies and procedures to maintain order among students
235206	Teaching academic subjects, and practical and self-help skills to students with hearing, sight and other impairments
235207	Stimulating and developing students' confidence interests, abilities, manual skills and coordination
235208	Conferring with other staff members to plan and schedule lessons for special needs students
235209	Preparing and maintaining student data and other records and submitting reports
235210	Administering various forms of assessment and evaluating progress of each student
235211	Conferring with students, parents, head teacher and other relevant professionals involved in the students' care to develop individual educational plans designed to promote students' development
235301	Assessing the level of ability and the extent of language difficulties of students, and establishing students' needs and learning goals
235302	Planning, preparing and delivering lessons and workshops for groups and individuals with content and rate of progression adapted to students' abilities and needs
235303	Designing and producing teaching materials and adapting existing materials
235304	Assessing students' progress
235305	Assisting students in classroom settings where subjects are taught in a language other than the students' native language
235306	Providing assistance to other teachers by designing special teaching programs for students still learning the main language of instruction
235307	Assigning and correcting work, and preparing and grading exams
235308	Assessing, recording and reporting on students' progress
235401	Assessing the students' level of ability and determining needs and learning goals
235402	Planning, preparing and delivering programs of study, lessons and workshops for individual students and groups
235403	Preparing and presenting material on the theory and interpretation of music
235404	Instructing and demonstrating practical aspects of singing or of playing a particular instrument
235405	Teaching students to read and write musical notation
235406	Assigning exercises and teaching pieces of music relevant to students' level of ability, interests and talents
235407	Assessing students and offering advice, criticism and encouragement
235408	Revising curricula, course content, course materials and methods of instruction
235409	Preparing students for examinations, performances and assessments
235410	Arranging visits and tours to musical performances
235411	Organizing and assisting in auditions or performances of students' work
235501	Assessing the students' level of ability and determining learning needs
235502	Planning, preparing and delivering programs of study, lessons and workshops for individual students and groups
235503	Preparing and presenting material on the theory of the subject area being studied

Code	Task
235504	Instructing and demonstrating practical aspects of drama, dance, visual or other arts
235505	Assigning exercises and work relevant to students' level of ability, interests and talents
235506	Assessing students and offering advice, criticism and encouragement
235507	Revising curricula, course content, course materials and methods of instruction
235508	Preparing students for examinations, performances and assessments
235509	Arranging visits and tours to exhibitions and performances
235510	Organising and assisting in performances or exhibitions of students' work
235601	Identifying the information technology training needs and requirements of individual users and organisations
235602	Preparing and developing instructional training material and aids such as handbooks, visual aids, online tutorials, demonstration models, and supporting training reference documentation
235603	Designing, coordinating, scheduling and conducting training and development programs that can be delivered in the form of individual and group instruction, and facilitating workshops, meetings, demonstrations and conferences
235604	Monitoring and performing ongoing evaluation and assessment of training quality and effectiveness, and reviewing and modifying training objectives, methods and course deliverables
235605	Gathering, investigating and researching background materials to gain a full understanding of the subject matter and systems
235606	Keeping up-to-date with new product version releases, advances in software, and general information technology trends, writing end user products and materials such as user training, tutorial and instruction manuals, online help, and operating and maintenance instructions
235901	Assessing students' level of ability and determining learning needs
235902	Planning, preparing and delivering programs of study, lessons and workshops for individual students and groups
235903	Preparing and presenting material on the theory of the subject area being studied
235904	Instructing and demonstrating practical aspects of the subject area being studied
235905	Assigning exercises and work relevant to students' level of ability, interests and aptitude
235906	Assessing students and offering advice, criticism and encouragement
235907	Revising curricula, course content, course materials and methods of instruction
235908	Preparing students for examinations and assessments
235909	Counselling students regarding educational issues such as course and program selection, class scheduling, school adjustment, truancy, study habits, and career planning
235910	Counselling students to help them understand and overcome personal, social, or behavioural problems affecting their education
235911	Preparing students for later educational experiences by encouraging them to explore learning opportunities and to persevere with challenging tasks
241101	Advising on, planning and installing budgetary, accounts controlling and other accounting policies and systems
241102	Preparing and certifying financial statements for presentation to management, shareholders and statutory or other bodies

Code	Task
241103	Preparing tax returns, advising on taxation problems and contesting disputed claims before tax officials
241104	Preparing or reporting on profit forecasts and budgets
241105	Conducting financial investigations in such matters as suspected fraud, insolvency and bankruptcy
241106	Auditing accounts and bookkeeping records
241107	Conducting investigations and advising management on financial aspects of productivity, stockholdings, sales, new products, etc.
241108	Devising and controlling a system to determine unit cost of products and services
241201	Building and maintaining a client base
241202	Interviewing clients to determine financial status and objectives, risk tolerance and other information needed to develop financial plans and investment strategies
241203	Setting financial objectives, and developing and implementing strategies for achieving the financial objectives
241204	Arranging to buy and sell stocks and bonds for clients
241205	Monitoring investment performance, and reviewing and revising investment plans based on modified needs and changes in markets
241206	Recommending and arranging insurance cover for clients
241301	Analysing financial information to produce forecasts of business, industry, and economic conditions for use in making investment decisions
241302	Maintaining knowledge and staying abreast of developments in the fields of industrial technology, business, finance, and economic theory
241303	Interpreting data affecting investment programs, such as price, yield, stability, future trends in investment risks, and economic influences
241304	Monitoring economic, industrial, and corporate developments through analysis of information obtained from financial publications and services, investment banking firms, government agencies, trade publications, company sources, and personal interviews
241305	Recommending investments and investment timing to companies, investment firm staff, or the investing public
241306	Determining the prices at which securities should be syndicated and offered to the public
241307	Preparing plans of action for investment based on financial analyses
241308	Evaluating and comparing the relative quality of various securities in a given industry
241309	Presenting oral and written reports on general economic trends, individual corporations, and entire industries
242101	Assisting and encouraging the development of objectives, strategies and plans aimed at achieving customer satisfaction and the efficient use of organisations' resources
242102	Analysing and evaluating current systems and structures
242103	Discussing current systems with staff and observing systems at all levels of organisation
242104	Directing clients towards more efficient organisation and developing solutions to organisational problems
242105	Undertaking and reviewing work studies by analysing existing and proposed methods and procedures such as administrative and clerical procedures
242106	Recording and analysing organisations' work flow charts, records, reports, manuals and job descriptions

Code	Task
242107	Preparing and recommending proposals to revise methods and procedures, alter work flows, redefine job functions and resolve organisational problems
242108	Assisting in implementing approved recommendations, issuing revised instructions and procedure manuals, and drafting other documentation
242109	Reviewing operating procedures and advising of departures from procedures and standards
242201	Liaising and consulting with program administrators and other interested parties to identify policy needs
242202	Reviewing existing policies and legislation to identify anomalies and out-of-date provisions
242203	Researching social, economic and industrial trends, and client expectations of programs and services provided
242204	Formulating and analysing policy options, preparing briefing papers and recommendations for policy changes, and advising on preferred options
242205	Assessing impacts, financial implications, interactions with other programs and political and administrative feasibility of policies
242206	Conducting threat and risk assessments and developing responses
242207	Reviewing operations and programs to ensure consistency with policies of the organisation
242301	Advising on and performing personnel functions relating to employee recruitment, placement, training, promotion, compensation, and employee-management relations or other areas of personnel policy
242302	Studying and analysing jobs performed in an establishment by various means, including interviews with workers, supervisors and management, and writing detailed position, job or occupation descriptions from information obtained
242303	Preparing occupational information or working on occupational classification systems
242304	Advising and working on the foregoing and other aspects of job and occupation analyses in such fields as personnel administration, workforce research and planning, training, or occupational information and vocational guidance
242305	Studying and advising individuals on employment opportunities, career choices and further education or training that may be desirable
242401	Identifying training needs and requirements of individuals and organisations
242402	Setting human resource development objectives and evaluating learning outcomes
242403	Preparing and developing instructional training material and aids such as handbooks, visual aids, online tutorials, demonstration models, and supporting training reference documentation
242404	Designing, coordinating, scheduling and conducting training and development programs that can be delivered in the form of individual and group instruction, and facilitating workshops, meetings, demonstrations and conferences
242405	Liaising with external training providers to arrange delivery of specific training and development programs
242406	Promoting internal and external training and development, and evaluating these promotional activities
242407	Monitoring and performing ongoing evaluation and assessment of internal and external training quality and effectiveness, and reviewing and modifying training objectives, methods and course deliverables
242408	Gathering, investigating and researching background materials to gain an understanding of various subject matters and systems

Code	Task
243101	Planning, developing and organizing advertising policies and campaigns to support sales objectives
243102	Advising managers and clients on strategies and campaigns to reach target markets, creating consumer awareness and effectively promoting the attributes of goods and services
243103	Writing advertising copy and media scripts, and arranging television and film production and media placement
243104	Analysing data regarding consumer patterns and preferences
243105	Interpreting and predicting current and future consumer trends
243106	Researching potential demand and market characteristics for new goods and services and collecting and analysing data and other statistical information
243107	Supporting business growth and development through the preparation and execution of marketing objectives, policies and programs
243108	Commissioning and undertaking market research to identify market opportunities for new and existing goods and services
243109	Advising on all elements of marketing such as product mix, pricing, advertising and sales promotion, selling, and distribution channels
243201	Planning and organizing publicity campaigns and communication strategies
243202	Advising executives on the public relations implications of their policies, programs and practices preparing and controlling the issue of news and press releases
243203	Undertaking and commissioning public opinion research, analysing the findings and planning public relations and promotional campaigns
243204	Organizing special events, seminars, entertainment, competitions and social functions to promote goodwill and favourable publicity
243205	Representing organisations and arranging interviews with publicity media
243206	Attending business, social and other functions to promote the organisation
243207	Commissioning and obtaining photographs and other illustrative material
243208	Selecting, appraising and revising material submitted by publicity writers, photographers, illustrators and others to create favourable publicity
243301	Compiling lists of prospective client businesses using directories and other sources
243302	Acquiring and updating knowledge of employers' and competitors' goods and services, and market conditions
243303	Visiting regular and prospective client businesses to establish and act on selling opportunities
243304	Assessing clients' needs and resources and recommending appropriate goods or services
243305	Providing input to product design where goods or services must be tailored to suit clients' needs
243306	Developing reports and proposals as part of sales presentation to demonstrate benefits from use of good or service
243307	Estimating costs of installing and maintaining equipment
243308	Monitoring customers' changing needs and competitor activity, and reporting these developments to sales management
243309	Quoting and negotiating prices and credit terms, and preparing and administering sales contracts
243310	Arranging delivery of goods, installation of equipment and the provision of services

Code	Task
243311	Reporting to sales management on sales made and the marketability of goods and services
243312	Consulting with clients after sale to ensure satisfaction, resolve any problems and provide ongoing support
243401	Soliciting orders and selling goods to retail, industrial, wholesale and other establishments
243402	Selling technical equipment, supplies and related services to business establishments or individuals
243403	Discussing the needs of new and existing customers and providing specialised information about how particular equipment, supplies and services meet those needs
243404	Quoting and negotiating prices and credit terms, and completing contracts and recording orders
243405	Updating customer records and preparing sales reports
243406	Arranging delivery of goods, installation of equipment and the provision of services
243407	Reporting customers' reactions and requirements to manufacturers
251101	Consulting with users to formulate and document requirements and with management to ensure agreement on systems principles
251102	Identifying and analysing business processes, procedures and work practices
251103	Identifying and evaluating inefficiencies and recommending optimal business practices, and system functionality and behaviour
251104	Taking responsibility for deploying functional solutions, such as creating, adopting and implementing system test plans
251105	Developing functional specifications for use by systems developers
251106	Expanding or modifying systems to improve work flow or serve new purposes
251107	Coordinating and linking the computer systems within an organisation to increase compatibility
251201	Researching, analysing and evaluating requirements for software applications and operating systems
251202	Researching, designing, and developing computer software systems
251203	Consulting with engineering staff to evaluate interface between hardware and software
251204	Developing and directing software testing and validation procedures
251205	Modifying existing software to correct errors, to adapt it to new hardware or to upgrade interfaces and improve performance
251206	Directing software programming and development of documentation
251207	Assessing, developing, upgrading and documenting maintenance procedures for operating systems, communications environments and applications software
251208	Consulting with customers concerning maintenance of software systems
251301	Analysing, designing and developing Internet sites applying a mixture of artistry and creativity with software programming and scripting languages and interfacing with operating environments
251302	Designing and developing digital animations, imaging, presentations, games, audio and video clips, and Internet applications using multimedia software, tools and utilities, interactive graphics and programming languages
251303	Communicating with network specialists regarding web-related issues, such as security and hosting web sites, to control and enforce Internet and web server security, space allocation, user access, business continuity, web site backup and disaster recovery planning

Code	Task
251304	Designing, developing and integrating computer code with other specialised inputs, such as image files, audio files and scripting languages, to produce, maintain and support websites
251305	Assisting in analysing, specifying and developing Internet strategies, web-based methodologies and development plans
251401	Writing and maintaining program code outlined in instructions and specifications in accordance with quality accredited standards
251402	Revising, repairing or expanding existing programs to increase operating efficiency or adapt to new requirements
251403	Conducting trial runs of programs and software applications to confirm that they will produce the desired information
251404	Compiling and writing documentation of program development
251405	Identifying and communicating technical problems, processes and solutions
251901	Developing and documenting software testing plans
251902	Installing software and hardware and configuring operating system software in preparation for testing
251903	Verifying that programmes function according to user requirements and established guidelines
251904	Executing, analysing and documenting results of software application tests and information and telecommunication systems tests
251905	Developing and implementing software and information system testing policies, procedures and scripts
252101	Designing and developing database architecture, data structures, tables, dictionaries and naming conventions for information systems projects
252102	Designing, constructing, modifying, integrating, implementing and testing database management systems
252103	Conducting research and providing advice on the selection, application and implementation of database management tools
252104	Developing and implementing data administration policy, documentation, standards and models
252105	Developing policies and procedures for database access and usage and for the backup and recovery of data
252106	Performing the operational establishment and preventive maintenance of backups, recovery procedures, and enforcing security and integrity controls
252201	Maintaining and administering computer networks and related computing environments including computer hardware, systems software, applications software and all configurations
252202	Recommending changes to improve systems and network configurations, and determining hardware or software requirements related to such changes
252203	Diagnosing hardware and software problems
252204	Performing data backups and disaster recovery operations
252205	Operating master consoles to monitor the performance of computer systems and networks, and to coordinate computer network access and use
252301	Analysing, developing, interpreting and evaluating complex system design and architecture specifications, data models and diagrams in the development, configuration and integration of computer systems

Code	Task
252302	Researching, analysing, evaluating and monitoring network infrastructure to ensure networks are configured to operate at optimal performance
252303	Assessing and recommending improvements to network operations and integrated hardware, software, communications and operating systems
252304	Providing specialist skills in troubleshooting network problems and emergencies
252305	Installing, configuring, testing, maintaining and administering new and upgraded networks, software database applications, servers and workstations
252306	Preparing and maintaining procedures and documentation for network inventory, and recording diagnosis and resolution of network faults, enhancements and modifications to networks, and maintenance instructions
252307	Monitoring network traffic, and activity, capacity and usage to ensure continued integrity and optimal network performance
252901	Developing plans to safeguard computer files against accidental or unauthorized modification, destruction, or disclosure and to meet emergency data processing needs
252902	Training users and promoting security awareness to ensure system security and to improve server and network efficiency
252903	Conferring with users to discuss issues such as computer data access needs, security violations, and programming changes
252904	Monitoring current reports of computer viruses to determine when to update virus protection systems
252905	Modifying computer security files to incorporate new software, correct errors, or change individual access status
252906	Monitoring use of data files and regulate access to safeguard information in computer files
252907	Performing risk assessments and executing tests of data processing system to ensure functioning of data processing activities and security measures
252908	Encrypting data transmissions and erecting firewalls to conceal confidential information as it is being transmitted and to keep out tainted digital transfers
261101	Giving clients legal advice on a wide variety of subjects and undertaking legal business on clients' behalf
261102	Researching legal principles, statutes and previous court decisions related to specific cases
261103	Gathering evidence to formulate a defence or to initiate legal actions, by such means as interviewing clients and witnesses to ascertain the facts of a case
261104	Evaluate findings and develop strategies and arguments in preparation for presentation of cases
261105	Pleading clients' cases before courts of law, tribunals and administrative boards or instructing barristers to plead in higher courts of justice
261106	Accepting briefs and pleading in the higher court
261107	Acting as prosecutor on behalf of the government
261108	Negotiating settlements in matters which involve legal disputes
261109	Drafting legislation and preparing government regulations based on existing laws
261110	Drawing up legal documents such as contracts, real estate transactions and wills and preparing statements of legal opinions
261201	Presiding over trials and hearings
261202	Interpreting and enforcing rules of procedure and making rulings regarding the admissibility of evidence

Code	Task
261203	Determining the rights and obligations of the parties involved, and, in cases tried by jury
261204	Instructing the jury on points of law that are applicable to the case
261205	Weighing and considering evidence in non-jury trials and deciding legal guilt or innocence or degree of liability of the accused or defendant
261206	Passing sentence on persons convicted in criminal cases, determining damages or other appropriate remedy in civil cases and issuing court orders
261207	Researching legal issues and writing opinions on the issues
261901	Giving advice on legal aspects of various personal, business and administrative problems
261902	Drawing up legal documents and contracts
261903	Arranging property transfers
261904	Determining, by inquest, the causes of any death not obviously due to natural causes
262101	Evaluating and preserving records for administrative, historical, legal, evidential and other purposes
262102	Directing or carrying out the preparation of indexes, bibliographies, microfilm copies and other reference aids to the collected material and making them available to users
262103	Researching the origin, distribution and use of materials and objects of cultural and historical interest
262104	Organizing, developing and maintaining collections of artistic, cultural, scientific or historically significant items
262105	Directing or undertaking classification and cataloguing of museum and art gallery collections and organizing exhibitions
262106	Researching into, appraising, and developing, organizing and preserving historically significant and valuable documents such as government papers, private papers, photographs, maps, manuscripts, audio-visual materials
262107	Preparing scholarly papers and reports
262108	Planning and implementing the computerized management of archives and electronic records
262109	Organizing exhibitions at museums and art galleries, publicizing exhibits and arranging special displays for general, specialized or educational interest
262110	Appraising and acquiring archival materials to build and develop an archival collection for research purposes
262201	Organizing, developing and maintaining a systematic collection of books, periodicals and other printed, audio-visually and digitally recorded material
262202	Selecting and recommending acquisitions of books and other printed or audio-visually and digitally recorded material
262203	Organizing, classifying and cataloguing library material
262204	Managing library borrowing and inter-library loan facilities and information networks
262205	Retrieving material and providing information to business and other users based on the collection itself or on library and information-network systems
262206	Conducting research and analysing or modifying library and information services in accordance with changes in users' needs
262207	Devising and implementing schemes and conceptual models for the storage, organisation, classification and retrieval of information
262208	Preparing scholarly papers and reports

Code	Task
262209	Performing manual, on-line and interactive media reference searches, making interlibrary loans and performing other functions to assist users in accessing library materials
263101	Forecasting changes in the economic environment for short-term budgeting, long-term planning and investment evaluation
263102	Formulating recommendations, policies and plans for the economy, corporate strategies and investment, and undertaking feasibility studies for projects
263103	Monitoring economic data to assess the effectiveness, and advise on the appropriateness, of monetary and fiscal policies
263104	Forecasting production and consumption of specific products and services based on records of past production and consumption and general economic and industry-specific conditions
263105	Preparing forecasts of income and expenditure, interest rates and exchange rates
263106	Analysing factors that determine labour force participation, employment, wages, unemployment and other labour market outcomes
263107	Applying mathematical formulae and statistical techniques to test economic theories and devise solutions to economic problems
263108	Compiling, analysing and interpreting economic data using economic theory and a variety of statistical and other techniques
263109	Evaluating the outcome of political decisions concerning public economy and finances economic policy and possible courses of action in the light of past, present and projected economic factors and trends
263110	Preparing scholarly papers and reports
263111	Examining problems related to the economic activities of individual companies
263112	Conducting research on market conditions in local, regional or national areas to set sales and pricing levels for goods and services, to assess market potential and future trends and to develop business strategies
263201	Conducting research on the origin, development, structure, social patterns, organisations and inter- relationships of human society
263202	Tracing the origin and evolution of humanity through the study of changing characteristics and cultural and social institutions
263203	Tracing the development of humanity through the material remains of its past, such as dwellings, temples, tools, pottery, coins, weapons, or sculpture
263204	Studying physical and climatic aspects of areas and regions, and correlating these findings with economic, social and cultural activities
263205	Developing theories, models and methods to interpret and describe social phenomena
263206	Evaluating the outcome of political decisions concerning social policy
263207	Analysing and evaluating social data
263208	Advising on the practical application of findings in the formulation of economic and social policies for population groups and regions, and for the development of markets
263209	Preparing scholarly papers and reports
263301	Researching, mostly by reasoning, into the general causes, principles and meanings of the world, human actions, experience and existence, and interpreting and developing philosophical concepts and theories
263302	Consulting and comparing primary sources, such as original or contemporary records of past events, and secondary sources such as archaeological or anthropological findings

Code	Task
263303	Extracting relevant material, checking its authenticity, and researching into and describing the history of a particular period, country or region, or a particular facet - for example economic, social or political - of its history
263304	Conducting research in such fields as political philosophy, or past and present theory and practice of political systems, institutions or behaviour
263305	Observing contemporary political institutions and opinions, collecting data on them from various sources, including interviews with government and political party officials and other relevant persons
263306	Developing theories, models and methods to interpret and describe the nature of human experience and historical and political events and behaviour
263307	Presenting findings and conclusions for publication or use by government, political parties or other organisations and interested persons
263308	Preparing scholarly papers and reports
263401	Planning and carrying out tests to measure mental, physical and other characteristics such as intelligence, abilities, aptitudes, potentialities, etc., interpreting and evaluating results, and providing advice
263402	Analysing the effect of heredity, social, occupational and other factors on individual thought and behaviour
263403	Conducting counselling or therapeutic interviews with individuals and groups, and providing follow-up services
263404	Maintaining required contacts, such as those with family members, educational authorities or employers, and recommending possible solutions to, and treatment of, problems
263405	Developing theories, models and methods to interpret and describe social phenomena
263406	Preparing scholarly papers and reports
263407	Formulating achievement, diagnostic and predictive tests for use by teachers in planning methods and content of instruction
263408	Conducting surveys and research studies on job design, work groups, morale, motivation, supervision and management
263501	Interviewing clients individually, in families, or in groups, to assess their situation and problems and determine the types of services required
263502	Analysing the client's situation and presenting alternative approaches to resolving problems
263503	Compiling case records or reports for courts and other legal proceedings
263504	Providing counselling, therapy and mediation services and facilitating group sessions to assist clients to develop skills and insights needed to deal with and resolve their social and personal problems
263505	Planning and implementing programs of assistance for clients including crisis intervention and referral to agencies that provide financial assistance, legal aid, housing, medical treatment and other services
263506	Investigating cases of abuse or neglect and taking action to protect children and other at risk persons
263507	Working with offenders during and after sentence, to help them to integrate into the community and to change attitudes and behaviour in order to reduce further offending
263508	Providing advice to prison governors and to probation and parole review boards that help determine whether, and under what conditions, an offender should be incarcerated, released from prison or undergo alternative correctional measures
263509	Acting as advocates for client groups in the community and lobbying for solutions to problems affecting them
263510	Developing prevention and intervention programs to meet community needs
263511	Maintaining contact with other social service agencies, educational institutions and health care providers involved with clients to provide information and obtain feedback on clients' overall situation and progress
263601	Perpetuating sacred traditions, practices and beliefs

Code	Task
263602	Conducting religious services, rites and ceremonies
263603	Undertaking various administrative and social duties, including participating in committees and meetings of religious organisations
263604	Providing spiritual and moral guidance in accordance with the religion professed
263605	Propagating religious doctrines in own country or abroad
263606	Preparing religious sermons and preachings
263607	Developing and directing study courses and religious education programmes
263608	Counselling individuals regarding interpersonal, health, financial, and religious problems
263609	Scheduling and participating in special events such as camps, conferences, seminars, and retreats
264101	Conceiving, writing and editing novels, plays, scripts, poetry and other material for publication or presentation
264102	Conducting research to establish factual content and to obtain other necessary information
264103	Writing scripts and continuities and preparing programmes for stage, film, radio and television productions
264104	Analysing material, such as specifications, notes and drawings, and writing manuals, user guides and other documents to explain clearly and concisely the installation, operation and maintenance of software, electronic, mechanical and other equipment
264105	Writing brochures, handbooks and similar technical publications
264106	Selecting material for publication, checking style, grammar and accuracy of content, arranging for any necessary revisions and checks of proof copies before printing
264201	Collecting local, national and international news through interviews, investigation and observation, attending public events, seeking out records, reviewing written work, attending film and stage performances
264202	Collecting, reporting and commenting on news and current affairs for publication in newspapers and periodicals, or for broadcasting by radio, television or webcast media
264203	Receiving, analysing and verifying news and other copy for accuracy
264204	Interviewing politicians and other public figures at press conferences and on other occasions, including individual interviews recorded for radio, television or webcast media
264205	Researching and reporting on developments in specialized fields such as medicine, science and technology
264206	Writing editorials and commentaries on topics of current interest to stimulate public interest by expressing the views of a publication or broadcasting station
264207	Writing critical reviews of literary, musical and other artistic works based on knowledge, judgement and experience for newspapers, television, radio and other media
264208	Selecting material for publication, checking style, grammar, accuracy and legality of content and arranging for any necessary revisions
264209	Liaising with production staff in checking final proof copies immediately prior to printing
264210	Selecting, assembling and preparing publicity material about business or other organisations for issue through press, radio, television and other media
264301	Studying relationships between ancient parent languages and modern language groups, tracing the origin and evolution of words, grammar and language forms, and presenting findings
264302	Advising on or preparing language classification systems, grammars, dictionaries and similar materials
264303	Translating from one language into another and ensuring that the correct meaning of the original is retained, that legal, technical or scientific works are correctly rendered, and that the phraseology and terminology of the spirit and style of literary works are conveyed as far as possible
264304	Developing methods for the use of computers and other instruments to improve productivity and quality of translation
264305	Interpreting simultaneously from a spoken or a signed language into another spoken or signed language , in particular at conferences, meetings and similar occasions, and ensuring that the correct meaning and the spirit of the original are transmitted
264306	Revising and correcting translated material
265101	Conceiving and developing ideas, designs and styles for paintings, drawings and sculptures

Code	Task
265102	Arranging objects, positioning models, and selecting landscapes and other visual forms according to chosen subject matter
265103	Selecting artistic media, method and materials
265104	Creating representational or abstract three-dimensional or relief forms by shaping, carving and working and combining materials such as wood, stone, clay, metal, ice or paper
265105	Creating representational or abstract drawings and paintings using pencils, ink, chalk, oil paints, water colours or through the application of other techniques
265106	Creating drawings and engraving or etching them on metal, wood, or other materials
265107	Creating cartoons to depict persons and events, often in caricature
265108	Restoring damaged, soiled and faded paintings and other art objects
265201	Creating melodic, harmonic and rhythmic structures to express ideas and emotions in musical form
265202	Translating ideas and concepts into standard musical signs and symbols for reproduction and performance
265203	Adapting or arranging music for particular instrumental or vocal groups, instruments or occasions
265204	Conducting instrumental or vocal groups
265205	Selecting music for performances and assigning instrumental parts to musicians
265206	Playing one or more musical instruments as a soloist or as a member of an orchestra or a musical group
265207	Singing as soloists or members of vocal groups or other bands
265208	Practising and rehearsing to maintain a high standard of performance
265301	Conceiving and creating dances, which often convey a story, theme, idea or mood, by a pattern of steps, movements and gestures
265302	Performing dances as a soloist, with a partner or as a member of a dancing group before live audiences or for film, television or other visual media
265303	Training ,exercising and attending dance classes to maintain the required levels of ability and fitness
265304	Directing and participating in rehearsals to practice dance steps and techniques required for a performance
265305	Auditioning for dance roles or for memberships in dance companies
265306	Coordinating the music with the music directors
265401	Choosing writers, studying scripts to determine artistic interpretation, and instructing actors on acting methods
265402	Directing all aspects of dramatic productions on stage, television, radio or in motion pictures, including choice of actors, and final decisions concerning costumes, set designs, sound or lighting effects
265403	Planning, organizing and controlling the various stages and scheduling involved in the production of presentations, motion pictures, television shows and radio programs
265404	Engaging and supervising all technical personnel, and determining the treatment, scope and scheduling of production
265405	Maintaining production archives and negotiating royalties
265406	Creating, planning, writing scripts for recording, videotaping and editing programs
265407	Supervising the positioning of scenery, props and lighting and sound equipment
265501	Learning lines and cues and playing parts in dramatic productions on stage, commercials, television, radio or in motion pictures
265502	Assuming characters created by a playwright or author and communicating this to an audience
265503	Telling stories or reading literary works aloud to educate or entertain listeners
265504	Attending auditions and casting calls in order to audition for roles
265505	Preparing for performances through rehearsals under the instruction and guidance of production directors
265506	Reading scripts and undertaking research to gain understanding of parts, themes and characteristics
265507	Acting parts and portraying roles as developed in rehearsals in film, television, radio and stage productions
265601	Reading news bulletins and making other announcements on radio or television

Code	Task
265602	Introducing performing artists or persons being interviewed, and making related announcements on radio, television, or in theatres, night-clubs and other establishments
265603	Interviewing persons in public, especially on radio and television
265604	Studying background information in order to prepare for programs or interviews
265605	Commenting on music and other matters , such as weather or traffic conditions
265901	Performing amusing antics and telling funny stories
265902	Performing tricks of illusion and sleight of hand, and feats of hypnotism
265903	Performing difficult and spectacular acrobatics, and gymnastic or juggling feats
265904	Training and performing with animals
311101	Collecting samples and preparing materials and equipment for experiments, tests and analyses
311102	Carrying out routine laboratory tests and performing a variety of technical support functions to assist chemical and physical scientists in research, development, analysis and testing
311103	Controlling the quality and quantity of laboratory supplies by testing samples and monitoring usage and preparing detailed estimates of quantities and costs of materials and labour required for projects, according to the specifications given
311104	Setting up, operating, and maintaining laboratory instruments and equipment, monitoring experiments, making observations, and calculating and recording results
311105	Preparing materials for experimentation such as freezing and slicing specimens and mixing chemicals
311106	Collecting and testing earth and water samples, recording observations and analysing data in support of geologists or geophysicists
311201	Performing or assisting with field and laboratory tests of soils and construction materials
311202	Providing technical assistance connected with the construction of buildings and other structures, and with surveys or the preparation of survey reports
311203	Ensuring compliance with design specifications, relevant legislation and regulations, and maintenance of desired standards of materials and work
311204	Applying technical knowledge of building and civil engineering principles and practices in order to identify and solve problems arising
311205	Advising on the installation of fire detectors and sprinkler systems and the use of materials in the construction of buildings and means of transportation to reduce risk of fire and extent of damage and danger if fire occurs
311206	Organizing maintenance and repairs
311207	Inspecting buildings and structures during and after construction to ensure that they comply with building, grading, zoning and safety laws and approved plans, specifications and standards, as well as with other rules concerning quality and safety of buildings
311301	Providing technical assistance in research on and development of electrical equipment and facilities, or testing prototypes
311302	Designing and preparing blueprints of electrical installations and circuitry according to the specifications given
311303	Preparing detailed estimates of quantities and costs of materials and labour required for manufacture and installation according to the specifications given
311304	Monitoring technical aspects of the manufacture, installation, utilisation, maintenance and repair of electrical systems and equipment to ensure satisfactory performance and compliance with specifications and regulations
311305	Planning installation methods, checking completed installation for safety and controls or undertaking the initial running of the new electrical equipment or systems
311306	Assembling, installing, testing, calibrating, modifying and repairing electrical equipment and installations to conform with regulations and safety requirements
311401	Providing technical assistance in research and development of electronic equipment, or testing prototypes

Code	Task
311402	Designing and preparing blueprints of electronic circuitry according to the specifications given
311403	Preparing detailed estimates of quantities and costs of materials and labour required for the manufacture and installation of electronic equipment, according to the specifications given
311404	Monitoring technical aspects of the manufacture, utilisation, maintenance and repair of electronic equipment to ensure satisfactory performance and ensure compliance with specifications and regulations
311405	Assisting in the design, development, installation, operation and maintenance of electronic systems
311406	Planning installation methods, checking completed installation for safety and controls or undertaking the initial running of the new electronic equipment or system
311407	Conducting tests of electronic systems, collecting and analysing data, and assembling circuitry in support of electronics engineers
311501	Providing technical assistance in research on and development of machines and mechanical installations, facilities and components, or testing prototypes
311502	Designing and preparing layouts of machines and mechanical installations, facilities and components according to the specifications given
311504	Monitoring technical aspects of manufacture, utilisation, maintenance and repair of machines and mechanical installations, facilities and components to ensure satisfactory performance and compliance with specifications and regulations
311505	Developing and monitoring the implementation of safety standards and procedures for marine survey work in relation to ships' hulls, equipment and cargoes
311506	Assembling and installing new and modified mechanical assemblies, components, machine tools and controls, and hydraulic power systems
311507	Conducting tests of mechanical systems, collecting and analysing data, and assembling and installing mechanical constructions in support of mechanical engineers
311508	Ensuring that mechanical engineering designs and finished work are within specifications, regulations and contract provisions
311601	Assisting in research on and development of industrial chemical processes, plant and equipment, or testing prototypes
311602	Designing and preparing layouts of chemical plants according to the specifications given
311603	Preparing detailed estimates of quantities and costs of materials and labour required for manufacture and installation according to the specifications given
311604	Monitoring technical aspects of the construction, installation, operation, maintenance and repair of chemical plants to ensure satisfactory performance and compliance with specifications and regulations
311605	Conducting chemical and physical laboratory tests to assist scientists and engineers in making qualitative and quantitative analyses of solids, liquids, and gaseous materials
311701	Providing technical assistance in research on and development of processes to determine the properties of metals and new alloys
311702	Providing technical assistance in geological and topographical surveys, and in the design and layout of oil, natural gas and mineral ore extraction and transportation systems, and processing and refining plants for minerals and metals
311703	Preparing detailed estimates of quantities and costs of materials and labour required for mineral, oil and natural gas exploration, extraction, processing and transport projects

Code	Task
311704	Monitoring technical, regulatory and safety aspects of the construction, installation, operation, maintenance and repair of mineral ore, oil and natural gas exploration, extraction, transport and storage installations and of mineral processing plants
311705	Helping plan and design mines, mine shafts, tunnels and underground first-aid facilities
311706	Collecting and preparing rock, mineral and metal samples, performing laboratory tests to determine properties, analysing and reporting test results and maintaining testing equipment
311707	Using microscopes, electromagnetic irradiation machines, spectrometers, spectrographs, densitometers and tension testing machines
311708	Assisting scientists in the use of electrical, sonic, or nuclear measuring instruments in both laboratory and production activities to obtain data indicating potential sources of metallic ore, gas, or petroleum
311801	Preparing and revising working drawings from sketches and specifications from engineers and designers for the manufacture, installation and erection of machinery and equipment or for the construction, modification, maintenance and repair of buildings, dams, bridges, roads and other architectural and civil engineering projects
311802	Operating computer-aided design and drafting equipment to create, modify and generate hard-copy and digital representations of working drawings
311803	Operating digitising table or similar equipment to transfer hard-copy representation of working drawings, maps and other curves to digital form
311804	Preparing and revising illustrations for reference works, brochures and technical manuals dealing with the assembly, installation, operation, maintenance and repair of machinery and other equipment and goods
311805	Copying drawings and paintings onto stone or metal plates for printing
311806	Preparing wiring diagrams, circuit board assembly diagrams, and layout drawings used for manufacture, installation, and repair of electrical equipment in factories, power plants, and buildings
311807	Creating detailed working diagrams of machinery and mechanical devices, including dimensions, fastening methods, and other engineering information
311808	Arranging for completed drawings to be reproduced for use as working drawings
311901	Collecting data and providing technical assistance regarding efficient, safe and economic utilisation of personnel, material and equipment, methods of work and sequence of operations and supervision of their implementation and efficient layout of plant or establishment
311902	Aiding in the identification of potential hazards and introducing safety procedures and devices
311903	Modifying and testing equipment and devices used in the prevention, control, and remediation of environmental pollution, site remediation, and land reclamation
311904	Assisting in the development of environmental pollution remediation devices under the direction of an engineer
311905	Assisting engineers in testing and designing robotics equipment
312101	Directly supervising and coordinating the activities of workers who extract minerals and other natural deposits from the earth, operate underground conveyances or heavy equipment in surface mines and quarries
312102	Establishing methods to meet work schedules and recommending measures to mining managers to improve productivity
312103	Working with managerial and technical personnel, other departments and contractors to resolve operational problems and coordinate activities

Code	Task
312104	Providing reports and other information to mining managers about all aspects of mining or quarrying operations
312105	Determining staffing and material needs for the mine or quarry
312201	Co-ordinating and supervising the activities of process control technicians, machine operators, assemblers, and other manufacturing labourers
312202	Organizing and planning the daily work with regard to plans, economy, staff and environment
312203	Preparing cost estimates, records and reports
312204	Identifying and reporting shortage of staff or components
312205	Ensuring safety of workers
312206	Instructing and training new staff
312301	Reading specifications to determine construction requirements and planning procedures
312302	Organizing and coordinating the material and human resources required to complete jobs
312303	Examining and inspecting work progress
312304	Examining equipment and construction sites to ensure that health and safety requirements are met
312305	Supervising construction sites and coordinating work with other construction projects
312306	Supervising the activities of building trades workers, labourers and other construction workers
313101	Operating, monitoring and inspecting various types of energy generating power plants
313102	Operating and controlling power generating systems and equipment including boilers, turbines, generators, condensers, and reactors in hydro, thermal, coal, oil, natural gas, and nuclear power plants to generate and distribute electrical power
313103	Controlling start-up and shut-down of power plant equipment, controlling switching operations, regulating water levels and communicating with systems operators to regulate and coordinate transmission loads, frequency and line voltages
313104	Taking readings from charts, meters and gauges at established intervals, troubleshooting and performing corrective action as necessary
313105	Completing and maintaining station records, logs and reports, and communicating with other plant personnel to assess equipment operating status
313106	Cleaning and maintaining equipment such as generators, boilers, turbines, pumps, and compressors in order to prevent equipment failure or deterioration
313201	Operating and monitoring computerized control systems, machinery and related equipment in wastewater treatment, sewage treatment, and liquid waste plants to regulate flow, treatment and disposal of sewage and wastes, and in water filtration and treatment plants to regulate the treatment and distribution of water for human consumption and for later disposal into natural water systems
313202	Controlling the operation of multiple-hearth incinerator furnaces and related equipment to burn sludge and solid waste
313203	Inspecting equipment and monitoring operating conditions, meters, filters, chlorinators, and gauges in central control room to determine load requirements, to verify that flows, pressures, and temperatures are within specification, and to detect malfunctions
313204	Monitoring and adjusting controls of auxiliary equipment, such as exhaust emissions, scrubbers, and incinerator heat recovery units

Code	Task
313205	Collecting and testing water and sewage samples for chemical and bacterial content, using test equipment and colour analysis standards
313206	Analysing test results to make adjustments to plant equipment and systems to disinfect and deodorize water and other liquids
313207	Performing security and safety checks in plant and on grounds
313208	Completing and maintaining plant logs and reports
313301	Operating electronic or computerized control panel from a central control room to monitor and optimize physical and chemical processes for several processing units
313302	Adjusting equipment, valves, pumps, controls and process equipment
313304	Controlling process start-up and shut-down, troubleshooting and monitoring outside process equipment
313305	Verifying equipment for malfunctions, carrying out routine operating tests and arranging for maintenance
313306	Analysing sample products, performing tests, recording data and writing production logs
313401	Operating electronic or computerized control panel from a central control room to monitor and optimize physical and chemical processes for several processing units
313402	Adjusting equipment, valves, pumps, controls and process equipment
313403	Controlling process start-up and shut-down, troubleshooting and monitoring outside process equipment
313404	Verifying equipment for malfunctions, testing well pipes for leaks and fractures and arranging for maintenance
313405	Analysing sample products, performing tests, recording data and writing production logs
313501	Co-ordinating and monitoring the operation of a particular aspect of metal processing production through control panels, computer terminals or other control systems, usually from a central control room
313502	Operating multi-function central process control machinery to grind, separate, filter, melt, roast, refine or otherwise process metals
313503	Observing computer printouts, video monitors and gauges to verify specified processing conditions and to make necessary adjustments
313504	Co-ordinating and supervising production crew such as machine and process operators, assistants and helpers
313505	Starting up and shutting down production systems in cases of emergency or as required by schedule
313506	Providing and organising training for members of production crew
313507	Maintaining shift log of production and other data and preparing production and other reports
314101	Assisting in designing, setting up and conducting experiments
314102	Setting up, calibrating, operating and maintaining laboratory instruments and equipment
314103	Collecting and preparing specimens and samples, chemical solutions and slides and growing cultures for use in experiments
314104	Performing routine field and laboratory tests
314105	Monitoring experiments to ensure adherence to correct laboratory quality control procedures and health and safety guidelines
314106	Making observations of tests, and analysing, calculating, recording and reporting test results using appropriate scientific methods

Code	Task
314107	Preserving, classifying and cataloguing specimens and samples
314108	Keeping detailed logs of worked performed
314109	Using computers to develop models and analyse data
314110	Using complex and high-powered equipment to perform work
314111	Participating in the research, development and manufacture of products and processes
314112	Ordering and stocking laboratory supplies
314113	Maintaining relevant databases
314201	Preparing materials and equipment for experiments, tests and analyses
314202	Collecting and preparing specimens such as soils, plant or animal cells, tissues or parts of organs for experiments, tests and analyses
314203	Assisting with and performing experiments, tests and analyses applying methods and techniques such as microscopy, histochemistry, chromatography, electrophoresis and spectroscopy
314204	Identifying pathogenic micro-organisms, insects, parasites, fungi and weeds harmful to crops and livestock, and assisting in devising methods of control
314205	Analysing produce to set and maintain standards of quality
314206	Conducting or supervising operational programs such as fish hatchery, greenhouse and livestock production
314207	Analysing samples of seeds for quality, purity and germination rating
314208	Collecting data and estimating quantities and costs of materials and labour required for projects
314209	Organizing maintenance and repairs of research equipment
314301	Conducting forest inventories, surveys and field measurements following accepted scientific and operational procedures
314302	Assisting in and performing technical functions in the preparation of forest management and harvest plans using photogrammetric and mapping techniques and computerized information systems
314303	Assisting in planning and supervision of construction of access routes and forest roads
314304	Supervising and performing technical functions in silvicultural operations involving site preparation, planting, and tending of tree crops
314305	Coordinating activities such as timber scaling, forest fire suppression, disease or insect control or pre-commercial thinning of forest stands
314306	Supervising and performing technical functions in forest harvesting operations
314307	Ensuring adherence to regulations and policies concerning environmental protection, resource utilisation, fire safety and accident prevention
314308	Supervising forest tree nursery operations
314309	Providing technical support to forestry research programs in areas such as tree improvement, seed orchard operations, insect and disease surveys or experimental forestry and forest engineering
314310	Preparing forest cultivation and cutting plans
315101	Controlling and participating in the operation, maintenance and repair of mechanical, electrical and electronic equipment and machinery on board ship
315102	Ordering fuel and other engine-room stores and maintaining record of operations
315103	Performing technical supervision of the installation, maintenance and repair of ship's machinery and equipment to ensure compliance with specifications and regulations
315104	Inspecting and conducting maintenance and emergency repairs to engines, machinery and auxiliary equipment
315105	Standing engine room watch, monitoring and noting performance of engines, machinery and auxiliary equipment
315201	
315202	Controlling and participating in deck and bridge-watch activities

Code	Task
315203	Navigating vessels into and out of ports and through channels, straits and other waters where special knowledge is required
315204	Ensuring safe loading and unloading of cargo and observance of safety regulations and procedures by crew and passengers
315205	Performing technical supervision of maintenance and repair of ship to ensure compliance with specifications and regulations
315206	Applying knowledge of principles and practices relating to ship's operation and navigation in order to identify and solve problems arising
315207	Ordering ship's stores and recruiting crew as required and maintaining record of operations
315208	Transmitting and receiving routine and emergency information with shore stations and other ships
315301	Flying and navigating aircraft in accordance with established control and operating procedures
315302	Preparing and submitting flight plan or examining standard flight plan
315303	Controlling the operation of mechanical, electrical and electronic equipment and ensuring that all instruments and controls work properly
315304	Applying knowledge of principles and practices of flying in order to identify and solve problems arising
315305	Examining maintenance records and conducting inspections to ensure that the aircraft is mechanically sound, maintenance has been performed and that all equipment is operational
315306	Signing necessary certificates and maintaining official records of flight
315307	Obtaining briefings and clearances before flights and maintaining contact with air traffic or flight control during flight
315401	Directing and controlling aircraft approaching and leaving airport and their movement on the ground
315403	Directing and controlling aircraft operating in designated airspace sector
315402	Examining and approving flight plans
315404	Informing flight crew and operations staff about weather conditions, flight, operational facilities, plans and air traffic
315403	Applying knowledge of principles and practices of air traffic control in order to identify and solve problems arising
315404	Initiating and organizing emergency, search and rescue services and procedures
315405	Directing all aircraft and service vehicles on or near airport runways
315406	Maintaining radio and telephone contact with adjacent control towers, terminal control units and other control centres, and coordinating the movement of aircraft into adjoining areas
315501	Carrying out technical duties related to the development of electronic and computerized air navigation systems and equipment, and testing prototypes
315502	Providing technical help in the design and layout of specific interface circuitry of air navigation and aircraft detection tracking systems
315503	(contributing) to the preparation of cost estimates and technical and training specifications for air traffic control and safety equipment
315504	Providing or assisting with the technical supervision of construction, installation and operation of ground-based air navigation equipment and its maintenance and repair to ensure that standards are met
315505	Applying the knowledge and skills of air traffic safety engineering principles and practices in order to identify and solve problems arising
315506	Developing, modifying and debugging system software
315507	Modifying existing ground-based air navigation systems and equipment to adapt them to new air traffic control procedures, in order to improve capability, reliability and integrity, or to facilitate air traffic control procedures and airspace designation
315508	Controlling, monitoring and certifying navigation and surveillance air traffic management equipment and calibrating the ground-based air navigation system to ensure maximum accuracy and safety of flight, take-off and landing operations
315509	Providing technical training and supervising other workers

Code	Task
321101	Operating or overseeing operation of radiologic, ultrasound and magnetic imaging equipment to produce images of the body for diagnostic purposes
321102	Explaining procedures, observing and positioning patients, and using protection devices to ensure safety and comfort during examination, scan, or treatment
321103	Position imaging or treatment equipment, monitoring video displays, and adjusting settings and controls according to technical specifications
321104	Reviewing and evaluating developed x-rays, video tape, or computer generated information to determine if images are satisfactory for diagnostic purposes and recording results
321105	Monitoring patients' conditions and reactions, reporting abnormal signs to a medical practitioner
321106	Measuring and recording radiation dosage or radiopharmaceuticals received and used for patients, following prescription issued by a medical practitioner
321107	Administering, detecting and mapping radiopharmaceuticals or radiation in patients' bodies, using radioisotope, camera or other equipment for diagnosing and treating diseases
321108	Recording and disposing of radioactive materials and storing radiopharmaceuticals, following radiation safety procedures
321201	Conducting chemical analysis of body fluids, including blood, urine, and spinal fluid, to determine presence of normal and abnormal components
321202	Operating, calibrating and maintaining equipment used in quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as spectrophotometers, calorimeters, flame photometers, and computer-controlled analysers
321203	Entering data from analysis of laboratory tests and clinical results into records-keeping systems and reporting results to medical practitioners and other health professionals
321204	Analysing samples of biological material for chemical content or reaction
321205	Setting up, cleaning, and maintaining laboratory equipment
321206	Analysing laboratory findings to check the accuracy of the results
321207	Establishing and monitoring programs to ensure the accuracy of laboratory results and developing, standardizing, evaluating, and modifying procedures, techniques and tests used in the analysis of specimens
321208	Obtaining specimens, cultivating, isolating and identifying microorganisms for analysis
321209	Examining cells stained with dye to locate abnormalities
321210	Inoculating fertilized eggs, broths, or other bacteriological media with organisms
321301	Preparing medications and other pharmaceutical compounds under the guidance of a pharmacist or other health professional
321302	Dispensing medicines and drugs to clients and giving written and oral instructions on their use, as prescribed by medical doctors, veterinarians or other health professionals
321303	Maintaining proper storage and security conditions for drugs
321305	Filling and labelling containers with prescribed medications
321306	Assisting clients by answering questions, locating items or referring them to a pharmacist
321307	Pricing and filing prescriptions that have been filled, establish and maintain patient records, including lists of medications taken by individual patients
321308	Ordering, labelling, and counting stock of medications, chemicals, and supplies, and entering inventory data into records-keeping systems
321309	Cleaning and preparing equipment and containers used to prepare and dispense medicines and pharmaceutical compounds
321401	Examining, interviewing, and measuring patients in order to determine their appliance needs, and to identify factors that could affect appliance fit
321402	Conferring with medical and dental practitioners in order to formulate specifications and prescriptions for devices and appliances
321403	Interpreting prescriptions or specifications to determine the type of product or device to be fabricated, and the materials and tools that will be required

Code	Task
321404	Making or receiving casts or impressions of patients' torsos, limbs, mouths or teeth for use as fabrication patterns
321405	Designing and making orthotic and prosthetic devices using materials such as thermoplastic and thermosetting materials, metal alloys and leather, and hand and power tools
321406	Fitting appliances and devices onto patients, testing and evaluating them, and making adjustments for proper fit, function, and comfort
321407	Repairing, modifying, and maintaining medical and dental prosthetic and supportive devices, according to specifications
321408	Bending, forming, and shaping fabric or material so that it conforms to prescribed contours
321409	Fabricating full and partial dentures and constructing mouth guards, crowns, metal clasps, inlays, bridgework and other aids
321410	Instructing patients in the use and care of prosthetic or orthotic devices
322101	Providing nursing and personal care and treatment and health advice to patients as per care plans established by health professionals
322102	Administering medications and other treatments to patients, monitoring patients' condition and responses to treatment, and referring patients and their families to a health professional for specialised care as needed
322103	Cleaning wounds and applying surgical dressings
322104	Updating information on patients' condition and treatments received in records-keeping systems
322105	Assisting in planning and managing the care of individual patients
322106	Assisting in giving first-aid treatment in emergencies
322201	Providing advice to women, families and communities on health, nutrition, hygiene, exercise, birth and emergency plans, breastfeeding, infant care, family planning and contraception, lifestyle and other topics related to pregnancy and childbirth
322202	Assessing progress during pregnancy and childbirth, and recognizing signs and symptoms requiring referral to a health professional
322203	Providing delivery care, usually only in the absence of identified potential complications, or assisting medical doctors or midwifery professionals with delivery care
322204	Providing care and support to women and newborns following childbirth, monitoring their health status, and identifying signs and symptoms requiring referral to a health professional
323001	Examining patients and interviewing them and their families to determine their health status and the nature of physical or mental disorders or illnesses or other ailments
323002	Recommending and providing care and treatment for illnesses and other ailments using traditional techniques and medicaments, such as physical manipulation and exercises, blood-letting using natural vessels, and preparations using herbs and other plants, insects and animal extracts
323003	Providing care and treatment for physical injuries such as setting and healing fractured and dislocated bones using traditional methods of physical manipulation and herbal therapies
323004	Advising individuals, families and the community on health, nutrition, hygiene, lifestyle and other issues to maintain or improve health and well-being
323005	Referring patients to, and exchanging information with, other health care providers to ensure comprehensive and continuing care
324001	Advising communities and individuals on the treatment of animals and their diseases and injuries
324002	Conducting examinations of animals to make diagnoses or refer more difficult cases to veterinarians when needed
324003	Treating ill or injured animals, especially for common diseases and disorders
324004	Cleaning and sterilising examination tables and instruments and preparing materials used in the examination and treatment of animals
324005	Carrying out technical tasks connected with artificial insemination of animals
324006	Getting animals ready for examination or treatment and restraining or holding them during treatment
324007	Assisting veterinarians to administer anaesthetics and oxygen during treatment
324008	Placing animals in cages for recovery from operations and monitoring their condition

Code	Task
324009	Producing radiographs, collecting samples, and performing other laboratory tests to assist in diagnosis of animal health problems
324010	Performing routine animal dental procedures and assisting veterinarians with animal dentistry
325101	Advising communities and individuals on dental hygiene, diet and other preventive measures to reduce potential risks to oral health
325102	Conducting visual and physical examinations of patients' mouths, teeth and related structures to assess oral health status
325103	Identifying cases of patients with poor oral health or oral disease requiring referral to a dentist or other health professional
325104	Assisting dentists during complex dental procedures
325105	Providing fluoride treatments, cleaning and removing deposits from teeth, preparing cavities and placing fillings, administering local anaesthesia, and performing other types of basic or routine clinical dental procedures
325106	Preparing, cleaning and sterilizing dental instruments, equipment and materials used in the examination and treatment of patients
325107	Getting patients ready for examination or treatment including explaining procedures and correct positioning
325108	Taking impressions of the mouth and dental radiographs to support diagnosis and fitting of dental prosthetics
325201	Planning, developing, maintaining and operating a variety of health record indexes and storage and retrieval systems to classify and analyse information
325202	Transcribing, compiling and processing patient medical records, admission and discharge documents, and other medical reports into records-keeping systems to provide data for patient monitoring and referral, epidemiological monitoring, research, billing, cost control and care improvement
325203	Reviewing records for completeness, accuracy and compliance with regulations
325204	Translating narrative descriptions and numeric information from medical records and other documents on health services delivery into codes associated with standard classification systems
325205	Protecting the security of medical records to ensure that confidentiality is maintained and releasing information to authorized persons and agencies in accordance with regulations
325206	Supervising clerical and administrative workers involved in the maintenance of medical records
325301	Providing information to families and communities on a range of health issues including nutrition, hygiene, infant and child care, immunisations, family planning, risk factors and prevention of common infectious diseases, poisoning prevention, first aid for treatment of simple and common ailments, substance abuse, domestic violence, and other topics
325302	Visiting families in their homes to provide information on the health, social and other services available and support them in gaining access to these services
325303	Visiting families who do not usually access medical establishments to monitor on a regular basis certain conditions, such as progress with pregnancy, child growth and development, and environmental sanitation
325304	Distributing to households medical supplies for the prevention and treatment of diseases such as malaria, pneumonia and diarrhoeal diseases, and instructing family and community members in the use of these products
325305	Conducting outreach efforts to groups who do not usually access medical establishments with information and basic medical supplies for prevention and management of certain health conditions for which they are most at risk, such as HIV/AIDS and other communicable diseases
325306	Collecting data from households and communities who do not usually access medical establishments for purposes of patient monitoring and referral and reporting to meet health regulations
325401	Examining and taking facial and eye measurements of clients for fitting of eyeglasses and other optical devices
325402	Providing advice to clients with selection and maintenance of eyeglasses and frames, types of contact lenses and other optical devices to improve performance, safety, comfort and lifestyle
325403	Interpreting optical prescriptions and preparing work order for optical laboratory for grinding and mounting of lenses in frames, preparation of contact lenses and other required work
325404	Verifying exactness of finished optical appliances and devices to the original prescription and fit of clients

Code	Task
325501	Administering manual treatments such as massage therapy or pressure point therapy
325502	Administering electrical modality treatments, ultrasound, and other specialized techniques and equipment, including infra-red lamps, wet compresses, and herbal and mineral therapies
325503	Instructing, motivating, safeguarding and assisting patients as they practice physical exercises, relaxation techniques and functional activities
325504	Conferring with physiotherapists or other health care providers to evaluate patient information for planning, modifying, and coordinating treatment
325505	Monitoring and recording patients' progress during treatments, including measuring their range-of-joint motion and vital signs
325506	Fitting patients for orthopedic braces, prostheses, and other physical supportive devices such as crutches, and instructing patients in the use of such devices
325601	Interviewing patients and their families to obtain information on their health status and medical history
325602	Assisting medical doctors and other health professionals to examine and treat patients, including measuring and recording vital signs, administering medications, and performing routine clinical procedures such as giving injections and removing sutures
325603	Getting patients ready for examination and treatment, including explaining procedures and showing them to examination rooms
325604	Preparing and handling medical instruments and supplies, sterilizing instruments and disposing of contaminated supplies in accordance with safety procedures
325605	Collecting blood, tissue or other specimens, and preparing them for laboratory testing
325606	Providing information to patients and families on health care topics including medications prescribed by a medical doctor or other health professional
325607	Providing prescription and drug refill information to pharmacies
325608	Maintaining cleanliness of patient waiting and examination rooms
325609	Recording information on patients' medical history, diagnostic testing and treatment procedures and results, and other relevant information in medical records-keeping systems
325610	Scheduling appointments with patients, and preparing documentation required for billing, reporting and insurance purposes
325701	Advising employers' and workers' representatives on the implementation of government and other rules and regulations concerning occupational safety and the working environment
325702	Inspecting places of work to ensure that the working environment, machinery and equipment conform to government and other rules, regulations and standards related to sanitation and/or occupational and environmental health and safety
325703	Giving advice on environmental sanitary problems and techniques
325704	Inspecting places of work and, by interviews, observations and other means, obtaining information about work practices and accidents to determine compliance with safety rules and regulations
325705	Inspecting areas of production, processing, transport, handling, storage and sale of products to ensure conformity with government and other rules, regulations and standards
325706	Advising enterprises and the general public on the implementation of government and other rules and regulations concerning hygiene, sanitation, purity and grading of primary products, food, drugs, cosmetics and similar goods
325707	Inspecting establishments to ensure that they conform to government and other rules and regulations concerning emission of pollutants and disposal of dangerous wastes
325708	Initiating action to maintain or improve hygiene and prevent pollution of water, air, food or soil
325709	Promoting preventive and corrective measures such as control of disease carrying organisms and of harmful substances in the air, hygienic food handling, proper disposal of waste and cleaning of public places
325710	Estimating quantities and costs of materials and labour required for health, safety and sanitation remediation projects
325801	Assessing health status of persons involved in accidents, natural disasters and other emergency situations, and determining needs for immediate and specialized medical assistance

Code	Task
325802	Performing medical procedures and administering drugs and other therapies according to protocol for emergency treatment, including resuscitating and defibrillating patients and operating life-support equipment
325803	Monitoring changes in health status of patients during transport to and from medical, rehabilitation and other health care facilities
325804	Providing information and training to community groups and essential service workers in first aid for initial care of an illness or injury
325805	Attending and/or patrolling large-scale public gatherings and other events where health emergencies are more likely to occur
325806	Recording information on patients' conditions and treatments provided in medical records-keeping systems
325901	Interviewing and examining patients to obtain information on their health status and the nature and extent of injury, illness or other physical or mental health problem
325902	Administering therapeutic care and treatment to patients, including the manual and physical chiropractic and osteopathic techniques
325903	Monitoring patients' progress through treatment plans, and identifying signs and symptoms requiring referral to a medical doctor or other health professional
325904	Recording information on patients' health status and responses to treatment in medical records-keeping systems
325905	Sharing information with other health care providers when required to ensure continuing and comprehensive care
331101	Obtaining information about the financial circumstances of customers and companies
331102	Analysing market trends for securities, bonds, stocks and other financial instruments, including foreign exchange
331103	Informing prospective customers about market conditions and prospects
331104	Advising on and participating in the negotiation of terms for loans, and organisation and placement of stocks and bonds in the financial market to raise capital for customers
331105	Recording and transmitting buy and sell orders for securities, stocks, bonds or other financial instruments and for foreign exchange for future or immediate delivery
331201	Interviewing applicants for personal, mortgage, student and business loans
331202	Researching and evaluating loan applicant's financial status, references, credit and ability to repay the loan
331203	Submitting credit and loan applications to management with recommendations for approval or rejection
331204	Approving or rejecting loan applications within authorized limits ensuring that credit standards of the institution are respected
331205	Completing credit and loan documentation
331301	Maintaining complete records of all financial transactions of an undertaking according to general bookkeeping principles, with guidance from accountants
331302	Verifying accuracy of documents and records relating to payments, receipts and other financial transactions
331303	Preparing financial statements and reports for specified periods
331304	Applying bookkeeping principles and practices in order to identify and solve problems arising in the course of their work
331305	Using standard computer software packages to perform accounting and related calculations
331306	Supervising the work of accounts and bookkeeping clerks
331401	Assisting in planning and performing statistical, mathematical, actuarial, and related calculations
331402	Preparing detailed estimates of quantities and costs of materials and labour required for statistical census and survey operations
331403	Performing technical tasks connected with establishing, maintaining and using registers and sampling frames for census and survey operations
331404	Performing technical tasks connected with data collection and quality control operations in censuses and surveys

Code	Task
331405	Using standard computer software packages to perform mathematical, actuarial, and statistical accounting and related calculations
331406	Preparing statistical, mathematical, actuarial, accounting and other results for presentation in graphical or tabular form
331407	Applying statistical, mathematical, actuarial, accounting and related principles and practices in order to identify and solve problems arising in the course of their work
331408	Supervising the work of statistical clerks
331501	Determining the quality or value of raw materials, real estate, industrial equipment, personal and household effects, works of art, gems and other objects
331502	Assessing the extent of damage or loss and liabilities of insurance companies and underwriters for losses covered by insurance policies
331503	Obtaining records of sales and value of similar items or property
331504	Inspecting items or property to evaluate condition, size, and construction
331505	Preparing reports of value, outlining the estimation factors and methods used
332101	Obtaining information about customers' circumstances necessary to determine appropriate type of insurance and conditions
332102	Negotiating with customers to determine type and degree of risk for which insurance is required
332103	Explaining details of insurance and conditions, risk coverage premiums and benefits to customers
332104	Assisting clients to determine the type and level of coverage required, calculating premiums and establishing method of payment
332105	Negotiating and placing reinsurance contracts
332106	Advising on, negotiating terms for and placing insurance contracts for large or special types of projects, installations or risks
332201	Soliciting orders and selling goods to retail, industrial, wholesale and other establishments
332202	Selling equipment, supplies and related services to business establishments or individuals
332203	Obtaining and updating knowledge of market conditions and of employer's and competitors' goods and services
332204	Providing prospective customers with information about the characteristics and functions of the products and equipment for sale, and demonstrating its use or qualities
332205	Quoting prices and credit terms, recording orders and arranging deliveries
332206	Reporting customers' reactions and requirements to suppliers and manufacturers
332207	Following up clients to ensure satisfaction with products purchased
332301	Determining or negotiating contract terms and conditions, awarding supplier contracts or recommending contract awards for the purchase of equipment, raw materials products, services and the purchasing of merchandise for resale
332302	Obtaining information about requirements and stock and developing specifications for quantity and quality to be purchased, costs, delivery dates and other contract conditions
332303	Purchasing general and specialized equipment, materials or business services for use or for further processing by their establishment
332304	Inviting tenders, consulting with suppliers and reviewing quotations
332305	Purchasing merchandise for resale by retail or wholesale establishments
332306	Studying market reports, trade periodicals and sales promotion materials and visiting trade shows, showrooms, factories and product design events
332307	Selecting the merchandise or products that best fit the establishment's requirements
332308	Negotiating with suppliers on prices, discounts, credit terms and transportation arrangements
332309	Overseeing distribution of merchandise to outlets and maintaining adequate stock levels
332310	Establishing delivery schedules, monitoring progress and contacting clients and suppliers to resolve problems

Code	Task
332401	Establishing contact between buyers and sellers of commodities
332402	Discussing buying or selling requirements of clients and giving advice accordingly
332403	Buying and selling cargo space on ships
332404	Negotiating purchase or sale of commodities and commodity futures
332405	Finding cargo and/or storage space for commodities and negotiating freight, shipping and storage charges
332406	Monitoring and analysing market trends and other factors affecting the supply and demand for commodities and shipping services
333101	Carrying out customs clearing procedures for exports or imports
333102	Ensuring that insurance is in order
333103	Ensuring that export/import licences and other formalities are in order
333104	Signing and issuing bills of lading
333105	Checking import/export documentation to determine cargo contents, and classifying goods into different fee or tariff groups, using a tariff coding system
333201	Promoting conferences, conventions and trade shows to potential customers
333202	Responding to inquiries concerning services provided and costs for room and equipment hire, catering and related services
333203	Discuss with clients their needs and outlining package options to meet these needs
333204	Arranging and coordinating services, such as, conference facilities, catering, signage, displays, audio-visual and computer equipment, accommodation, transport and social events, for participants, logistical arrangements for presenters
333205	Organizing registration of participants
333206	Negotiating the type and costs of services to be provided within budget
333207	Overseeing work by contractors and reporting on variations to work orders
333301	Matching jobseekers with vacancies
333302	Finding workers for vacant posts against a commission from the employer or worker
333303	Discussing with enterprises/organisations the needed skills and other characteristics of the workers to be employed or contracted
333304	Finding workers with appropriate skills, and undertaking the necessary formalities according to national or international regulations and requirements
333305	Ensuring that the employment contracts meet legal requirements and signing them
333306	Advising on training schemes
333401	Obtaining information about properties to be sold or leased, the circumstances of their owner and the needs of prospective buyers or tenants
333402	Showing properties to be sold or leased to prospective buyers or tenants and explaining terms of sale or conditions of rent or lease
333403	Facilitating negotiations with tenants and owners on rents and fees
333404	Drawing up leasing and sale agreements and estimating costs
333405	Arranging signing of lease agreements and transfer of property rights
333406	Collecting rent and bond monies on behalf of owner and inspecting properties before, during and after tenancies
333407	Ensuring the availability of workers to perform maintenance of the properties
333901	Obtaining information about services to be sold and needs of prospective buyers
333902	Negotiating contracts on behalf of seller or buyer and explaining terms of sale and payment to client
333903	Signing agreements on behalf of seller or buyer and ensuring that the contract is honoured
333904	Making sure that the business service purchased is made available to the buyer in the agreed format at the agreed time

Code	Task
333905	Selling by auction various kinds of property, cars, livestock, art, jewellery and other objects
334101	Coordinating, assigning and reviewing the work of clerks engaged in word processing, record keeping and filing, operating telephones and switchboards, data entry, desktop publishing and other activities involving general office and administrative skills
334102	Establishing work schedules and procedures and co-coordinating activities with other work units or departments
334103	Resolving work-related problems and preparing and submitting progress and other reports
334104	Training and instructing employees in job duties, safety procedures and company policies, or arranging for training to be provided
334105	Evaluating employees' job performance and conformance to regulations, and recommending appropriate personnel action
334106	Assisting in recruitment, interviewing, and selection of employees
334201	Preparing and processing legal documents and papers, such as deeds, wills, affidavits and briefs
334202	Reviewing and proofreading documents and correspondence to ensure compliance with legal procedures
334203	Mailing, faxing, or arranging for delivery of legal correspondence to clients, witnesses, and court officials
334204	Organizing and maintaining documents, case files and law libraries
334205	Screening requests for meetings, scheduling and organizing meetings
334206	Assisting in the preparation of budgets, monitoring of expenditures, drafting of contracts and purchasing or acquisition orders
334207	Supervising the work of office support workers
334301	Drafting administrative correspondence and minutes
334302	Obtaining, proposing and monitoring deadlines and follow-up dates
334303	Screening requests for meetings, scheduling and organizing meetings and travel arrangements
334304	Assisting in the preparation of budgets, monitoring of expenditures, drafting of contracts and purchasing or acquisition orders
334305	Liaising with other staff about a range of matters relating to the organisation's operations
334306	Writing and answering business or technical letters and other similar correspondence
334307	Preparing verbatim reports of proceedings in legislative assemblies, courts of law or other places using shorthand or specialized office equipment
334308	Supervising the work of clerical support workers
334401	Scheduling and confirming medical appointments and communicating messages for medical staff and patients
334402	Compiling, recording and reviewing medical charts, reports, documents and correspondence
334403	Interviewing patients to complete forms, documents and case histories
334404	Completing insurance and other claims forms
334405	Maintaining medical files and records and technical library
334406	Preparing financial statements and billing procedures
334407	Assisting in the preparation of budgets, drafting of contracts and purchasing or acquisition orders
334408	Supervising the work of office support workers and other office staff
335101	Patrolling national borders and coastal waters to stop persons from illegally entering or leaving the country and from illegally importing or exporting currency or goods
335102	Checking travel documents of persons crossing national borders to ensure that they have the necessary authorisations and certificates
335103	Inspecting the luggage of persons crossing national borders to ensure that it conforms to government rules and regulations concerning import or export of goods and currencies

Code	Task
335104	Examining transport documents and freight of vehicles crossing national borders to ensure conformity with government rules and regulations concerning goods in transit and the import and export of goods, and to verify that necessary payments have been made
335105	Detaining persons and seizing prohibited and undeclared goods found to be in violation of immigration and customs laws
335106	Co-ordinating and co-operating with other agencies involved in law enforcement, deportation and prosecution
335107	Performing related administrative tasks to record findings, transactions, violations and determinations
335108	When necessary, testifying in a court of law about the circumstances and results of investigations carried out
335201	Advising organisations, enterprises and the public on government laws, rules and regulations concerning the determination and payment of taxes, duties and other government fees, and on the public's rights and obligations
335202	Examining tax returns, bills of sale and other relevant documents to determine type and amount of taxes, duties and other types of fees to be paid
335203	Investigating filed tax returns and accounting records, systems and internal controls of organisations to ensure compliance with taxation laws and regulations
335204	Performing related administrative tasks to document findings, maintain records and report on actions taken for cases
335301	Advising individuals and organisations on government laws, rules and regulations concerning government benefit programs and the determination and disbursement of payments or referral to services, as well as on the public's rights and obligations
335302	Examining applications and other relevant documents to determine type and amount of benefit which individuals are eligible to receive
335303	Assessing documentation and interviewing benefit recipients to ensure eligibility for continuing benefits or services
335304	Performing related administrative tasks to maintain client records and prepare reports on determinations regarding eligibility, referral decisions, termination of benefits and abuse or fraud
335401	Advising individuals on government laws and regulations concerning the type of licence required and the conditions attached to such licences, and on the public's rights and obligations
335402	Examining applications and relevant documents and determining whether a licence can be granted and the conditions which should be attached
335403	Examining applications and approving the issue of passports
335404	Performing related administrative tasks to process applications, document activities, evaluations and determinations, and to prepare correspondence to inform applicants of licensing decisions
335405	Administering and scoring tests required to license applicants
335501	Establishing contacts and sources of information about crimes planned or committed, in order to prevent crimes or identify suspected offenders
335502	Obtaining and verifying evidence by examining crime and accident scenes for clues and physical evidence, interviewing witnesses and suspects and analysing documents and computer files
335503	Analysing evidence in order to solve crimes, identify criminal activity and gather information for court cases
335504	Establishing contacts and sources of information not readily available or apparent concerning establishments or the circumstances and behaviour of persons, usually with the aim of preventing a crime
335505	Making arrests
335506	Testifying in courts of law or reporting to superiors about circumstances and results of investigations
335901	Examining places of business to ensure the use of correct weights and measures in trade
335902	Monitoring price regulations to assess appropriateness of costs for goods and services to protect consumer interests
335903	Monitoring wage regulations to ensure appropriate levels of pay for work performed and to assess compliance with employment standards legislation
335904	Performing related investigative and administrative tasks to record findings, document compliance problems or inappropriate business practices and to prepare reports and correspondence

Code	Task
341101	Documenting court proceedings and judgements
341102	Serving statements of claims, summons, warrants, subpoenas and other court orders
341103	Maintaining order in court and hearing rooms
341104	Preparing legal documents including trial briefs, pleadings, appeals, wills and contracts and preparing papers summarising legal positions, or setting out conditions of loans or insurance
341105	Investigating facts, assembling evidence and researching relevant statutes, decisions and other legal documents to prepare cases
341106	Advising clients on legal matters
341107	Examining documentation such as mortgages, liens, judgements, easements, contracts and maps in order to verify properties' legal descriptions and ownership
341108	Preparing documents relating to transfer of real estate, stocks or other matters requiring formal registration
341201	Collecting information relevant to clients' needs and assessing their relevant skills, strengths and deficits
341202	Helping persons with disabilities or the elderly to obtain services and to improve their ability to function in society
341203	Assisting clients to identify options and develop plans of action while providing necessary support
341204	Assisting clients to identify and access community resources including legal, medical and financial assistance, housing, employment, transportation, assistance with moves, day care and other referral services
341205	Counselling clients living in group homes and half-way houses, supervising their activities and assisting in pre-release and release planning
341206	Participating in the selection and admission of clients to appropriate programs
341207	Providing crisis intervention and emergency shelter services
341208	Implementing life skills workshops, substance abuse treatment programs, behaviour management programs, youth services programs and other community and social service programs under the supervision of social work or health care professionals
341209	Assisting in evaluating the effectiveness of interventions and programs by monitoring and reporting on clients' progress
341210	Maintaining contact with other social service agencies, schools and health care providers involved to provide information and obtain feedback on clients' overall situation and progress
341301	Undertaking religious works
341302	Preaching and propagating the teachings of a particular religious faith
341303	Assisting at services of public worship and religious rites
341304	Providing religious education, spiritual guidance and moral support to individuals and communities
341305	Administering and participating in programs to provide food, clothing and shelter to those in need
341306	Advising communities and individuals on proper behaviour and faith to preserve or improve well-being
342101	Participating in competitive sporting events
342102	Participating in regular practice and training sessions and undertaking private training to maintain the required standard of fitness and skill
342103	Maintaining a high degree of expertise in a particular sport
342105	Deciding on strategies in consultation with coaches
342106	Assessing other competitors and conditions at venues
342107	Competing in sporting events
342108	Adhering to the rules and regulations associated with a specific sport
342201	Identifying strengths and weaknesses of athletes or teams
342202	Planning, developing and implementing training and practice sessions
342203	Developing, planning and co-ordinating competitive schedules and programs
342204	Motivating and preparing athletes or teams for competitive events or games

Code	Task
342205	Formulating competitive strategy, developing game plans and directing athletes and players during games or athletic events
342206	Analysing and evaluating athletes' or teams' performances and modifying training programs
342207	Monitoring and analysing technique and performance, and determining how future improvements can be made
342208	Officiating at sporting events or athletic competitions to maintain standards of play and to ensure that game rules and safety regulations are observed
342209	Recording lapsed time and keeping scores during events or competitions
342210	Judging the performance of competitors, awarding points, imposing penalties for infractions and determining results
342211	Compiling scores and other athletic records
342301	Planning and carrying out recreational and fitness activities
342302	Monitoring recreational, sports or fitness activities to ensure safety and provide emergency or first aid assistance when required
342303	Evaluating and monitoring clients' abilities and fitness and recommending activities
342304	Demonstrating and teaching body movements, concepts and skills used in fitness routines and recreational activities
342305	Instructing in the use of equipment
342306	Explaining and enforcing safety procedures, rules and regulations
343101	Taking photographs for advertising, or other commercial, industrial or scientific purposes and to illustrate stories and articles in newspapers, magazines and other publications
343102	Taking portrait photographs of persons and groups of persons
343103	Studying requirements of a particular assignment and decide on type of camera, film, lighting and background accessories to be used
343104	Determining picture composition, making technical adjustments to equipment and photograph subject
343105	Operating scanners to transfer photographic images to computers
343106	Operating computers to manipulate photographic images
343107	Adapting existing photographic images to create new digitized images to be included in multimedia products
343108	Using airbrush, computer or other techniques to create the desired visual effect
343201	Determining the objectives and constraints of the design brief by consulting with clients and stakeholders
343202	Researching and analysing spatial, functional, efficiency, safety and aesthetic requirements
343203	Formulating design concepts for the interiors of buildings
343204	Preparing sketches, diagrams, illustrations and plans to communicate design concepts
343205	Negotiating design solutions with clients, management, suppliers and construction staff
343206	Selecting, specifying and recommending functional and aesthetic materials, furniture and products for interiors
343207	Detailing and documenting selected design for construction
343208	Coordinating the construction and the decoration of interiors
343209	Designing and painting stage scenery
343210	Designing and decorating show windows and other display areas to promote products and services
343301	Mounting and preparing objects for display
343302	Designing and arranging exhibit furnishings, display cases and display areas
343303	Assisting in setting up lighting and display equipment
343304	Receiving, shipping, packing and unpacking exhibits
343305	Ordering new library materials and maintaining library records and circulation systems

Code	Task
343306	Cataloguing printed and recorded material
343307	Entering data into databases and editing computer records
343308	Operating audio-visual and reprographic equipment
343309	Searching and verifying bibliographic data
343401	Planning and developing recipes and menus, estimating food and labour costs, and ordering food supplies
343402	Monitoring quality of dishes at all stages of preparation and presentation
343403	Discussing food preparation issues with managers, dieticians, kitchen and waiting staff
343404	Supervising and coordinating the activities of cooks and other workers engaged in food preparation
343405	Inspecting supplies, equipment, and work areas to ensure conformance to established standards
343406	Determining how food should be presented, and creating decorative food displays
343407	Instructing cooks and other workers in the preparation, cooking, garnishing, and presentation of food
343408	Participating in the recruitment of kitchen staff and monitoring their performance
343409	Preparing, seasoning and cooking speciality foods and complex dishes
343410	Explaining and enforcing hygiene and food safety regulations
351101	Operating and controlling peripheral and related computer equipment
351102	Entering commands, using computer terminal, and activating controls on computer and peripheral equipment to integrate and operate equipment
351103	Monitoring systems for equipment failure or errors in performance
351104	Notifying supervisor or maintenance technician of equipment malfunctions
351105	Responding to program error messages by finding and correcting problems, referring the problem to other staff or terminating the program
351106	Reading job set-up instructions to determine equipment to be used, order of use, material such as disks and paper to be loaded, and control settings
351107	Retrieving, separating and sorting program output as needed, and sending data to specified users
351108	Loading peripheral equipment, such as printers, with selected materials for operating runs, or oversee such loading by peripheral equipment operators
351201	Answering user inquiries regarding software or hardware operation to resolve problems
351202	Entering commands and observing system functioning to detect errors
351203	Installing and performing minor repairs to hardware, software, or peripheral equipment, following design or installation specifications
351204	Overseeing the daily performance of communications and computer systems
351205	Setting up equipment for employee use, performing or ensuring proper installation of cables, operating systems, or appropriate software
351206	Maintaining records of daily data communication transactions, problems and remedial actions taken, or installation activities
351207	Reproducing technical problems encountered by users
351208	Consulting user guides, technical manuals and other documents to research and implement solutions
351301	Operating, maintaining and troubleshooting network systems
351302	Operating and maintaining data communications systems other than networks
351303	Assisting users with network and data communications problems
351304	Installing computer hardware, network software, operating system software and applications software
351305	Performing start up and close down as well as backup and disaster recovery operations for computer networks
351401	Installing, monitoring and supporting the reliability and usability of Internet and Intranet websites or web server hardware or software

Code	Task
351402	Developing and maintaining documentation, policies and instructions, recording operational procedures and system logs
351403	Developing, coordinating, implementing and monitoring security measures
351404	Analysing and making recommendations to enhance performance, including upgrading and acquiring new systems
351405	Liaising with, and providing guidance to, clients and users
351406	Modifying web pages
351407	Performing web server backup and recovery operations
352101	Controlling equipment to record sound
352102	Controlling equipment to edit and mix image and sound recordings to ensure satisfactory quality and to create special image and sound effects
352103	Applying knowledge of principles and practices of image and sound recording and editing in order to identify and solve problems
352104	Controlling transmitting and broadcast systems and satellite systems for radio and television programmes
352105	Controlling radio communications systems, satellite services, and multiplex systems on land, sea or in aircraft
352106	Applying knowledge of principles and practices of broadcasting, telecommunications terminals and transmissions systems, in order to identify and solve problems
352107	Making emergency repairs to equipment
352201	Providing technical assistance connected with research and the development of telecommunications equipment, or testing prototypes
352202	Studying technical material such as blue prints and sketches to determine the method of work to be adopted
352203	Preparing detailed estimates of costs of materials and labour required for the manufacture and installation of telecommunications equipment, according to the specifications given
352204	Providing technical supervision of the manufacture, utilisation, maintenance and repair of telecommunications systems to ensure satisfactory performance and compliance with specifications and regulations
352205	Applying technical knowledge of telecommunications engineering principles and practices in order to identify and solve problems arising in the course of their work
411001	Recording, preparing, sorting, classifying and filing information
411002	Sorting, opening and sending mail
411003	Photocopying and faxing documents
411004	Preparing reports and correspondence of a routine nature
411005	Recording issue of equipment to staff
411006	Responding to telephone or electronic enquiries or forwarding to appropriate person
411007	Checking figures, preparing invoices and recording details of financial transactions made
411008	Transcribing information onto computers, and proofreading and correcting copy
412001	Checking, formatting and transcribing correspondence, minutes and reports from dictation, electronic documents or written drafts to conform to office standards, using typewriter, personal computer or other word processing equipment
412002	Using various computer software packages including spreadsheets to provide administrative support
412003	Dealing with incoming or outgoing mail
412004	Scanning, recording and distributing mail, correspondence and documents
412005	Screening requests for meetings or appointments and helping to organize meetings
412006	Screening and recording leave and other staff-members' entitlements
412007	Organizing and supervising filing systems
412008	Dealing with routine correspondence on their own initiative

Code	Task
413101	Typing written material from rough drafts, corrected copies, voice recordings, or shorthand using a computer, word processor or typewriter
413102	Checking completed work for proper spelling, grammar, punctuation and formatting
413103	Gathering and arranging the material to be typed, following instructions
413104	Filing and storing completed documents on computer hard drive or disk, or maintain a computer filing
413105	Taking dictation and recording other matter in shorthand
413106	Reproducing the spoken word, environmental sounds and song lyrics as captions for cinema and television
413107	Transcribing information recorded in shorthand and on sound recording equipment
413201	Receiving and registering invoices, forms, records and other documents for data capture
413202	Entering numerical data, codes and text from source material into computer-compatible storage
413203	Verifying accuracy and completeness of data and correcting entered data, if needed
413204	Operating bookkeeping and calculating machines
413205	Importing and exporting data between different database systems and softwares
421101	Process customer cash deposits and withdrawals, cheques, transfers, bills, credit card payments, money orders, certified cheques and other related banking transactions
421102	Crediting and debiting clients' accounts
421103	Paying bills and making money transfers on clients' behalf
421104	Receiving mail, selling postage stamps and conducting other post office counter business such as bill payments, money transfers and related business
421105	Changing money from one currency to another, as requested by clients
421106	Making records of all transactions and reconciling them with cash balance
421201	Determining risks to decide odds and to hedge or refuse bets
421202	Preparing and issuing lists of approximate odds
421203	Distributing cards, rolling dice or spinning a roulette wheel
421204	Explaining and interpreting operating rules of a gambling establishment
421205	Announcing winning numbers, paying winners and collecting payments from losers
421301	Evaluating articles offered as pledges, calculating interest, and lending money
421302	Returning articles when the loan is paid or, in the event of non-payment, selling pledged articles
421303	Lending money as personal loans against success of future harvest and other similar undertakings
421304	Collecting loans when the pledge involved the success of future harvest and other similar undertakings
421305	Keeping a record of items received and money distributed and received
421401	Tracing and locating debtors
421402	Telephoning, visiting, or writing to customers to collect money or arrange for later payments
421403	Preparing reports including amounts collected and maintain records and files related to collection work
421404	Recommending legal action or discontinuation of service when payment cannot be otherwise obtained
421405	Asking for and collecting charity payments
422101	Obtaining information about the availability, cost and convenience of different types of transport and accommodation, ascertaining customer's requirements and advising them on travel arrangements
422102	Preparing itineraries
422103	Making and confirming reservations
422104	Issuing tickets and vouchers
422105	Helping customers in obtaining necessary travel documents such as visas
422106	Preparing bills and receiving payments

Code	Task
422107	Organizing group tours for business or vacation travel and selling them
422201	Dealing with incoming calls and messages from clients, whether to answer queries, handle calls for service or sort out complaints
422202	Identifying requirements and entering events into a computer system
422203	Dispatching tasks to other units, when relevant
422204	Invoicing or handling payments, where necessary
422205	Sending letters, information sheets and other documents to clients
422206	Advising clients of additional products or services
422301	Operating switchboards and consoles to connect, hold, transfer, and disconnect telephone calls
422302	Making connections for outgoing calls
422303	Dealing with telephone inquiries and recording messages
422304	Forwarding messages to staff or clients
422305	Investigating operating system problems and informing repair services
422401	Maintaining an inventory of rooms available for occupancy, reservations and room assignments
422402	Registering arriving guests, assigning rooms verifying customer's credit and issuing room keys
422403	Providing information regarding hotel services and services available in the community
422404	Providing information about availability of accommodation and making room reservations
422405	Responding to guests' requests for housekeeping and maintenance services as well as complaints
422406	Contacting housekeeping or maintenance services when guests report problems
422407	Compiling and checking guest accounts for charges using computerized or manual systems
422408	Receiving and forwarding messages in person or using telephone or telephone switchboard
422409	Reviewing statements of charges to departing guests and receiving payment
422501	Answering inquiries about goods, services, and policy and providing information about their availability, location, price and related issues
422502	Responding to enquiries about problems and providing advice, information and assistance
422503	Recording information about enquiries and complaints
422504	Referring complex enquiries to team leaders or expert advisers
422505	Issuing relevant forms, information kits and brochures to interested parties
422601	Receiving and welcoming visitors, guests or clients
422602	Making appointments for clients
422603	Dealing with telephone requests for information or appointments
422604	Supplying information pamphlets, brochures or forms
422701	Contacting individuals by telephone or in person and explaining the purpose of the interview
422702	Asking questions following the outlines of questionnaires and surveys
422703	Recording responses on paper or entering responses directly into a computer database through computer-assisted interviewing systems
422704	Identifying and resolving inconsistencies in responses
422705	Providing feedback to survey sponsors concerning problems in obtaining valid data
422901	Interviewing patients to obtain and process information required to provide hospital services
422902	Interviewing applicants for public assistance to gather information pertinent to their application
422903	Verifying the accuracy of information provided
422904	Initiating procedures to grant, modify, deny or terminate assistance
422905	Providing information and answering questions concerning benefits and claims procedures

Code	Task
422906	Referring patient or applicant to other organisations if they are ineligible for services
431101	Checking figures, postings, and documents for correct entry, mathematical accuracy, and proper codes
431102	Operating computers programmed with accounting software to record, store, and analyse information
431103	Classifying, recording, and summarizing numerical and financial data to compile and keep financial records, using journals and ledgers or computers
431104	Calculating, preparing, and issuing bills, invoices, account statements, and other financial statements according to established procedures
431105	Compiling statistical, financial, accounting or auditing reports and tables pertaining to such matters as cash receipts, expenditures, accounts payable and receivable, and profits and losses
431201	Processing insurance enrolments, cancellations, claims transactions, policy changes and payments
431202	Obtaining and compiling statistical or actuarial data based on routine or special sources of information
431203	Calculating totals, averages, percentages and other details and presenting them in the required tabular form
431204	Preparing financial documents, and calculating interest or brokerage charges and stamp duties payable
431205	Maintaining records of bonds, shares and other securities bought or sold on behalf of clients or employer
431301	Maintaining records of employee attendance, leave and overtime to calculate pay and benefit entitlements, using manual or computerized systems
431302	Preparing and verifying statements of earnings for employees, indicating gross and net salaries and deductions such as taxes, union dues, garnishments and insurance and pension plans
431303	Preparing employee payments and benefit payments by cheque or electronic transfer
431304	Reviewing time sheets, work charts, wage computation, and other information to detect and reconcile payroll discrepancies
431305	Verifying attendance, hours worked, and pay adjustments, and posting information onto designated records
432101	Arranging and controlling receipt and dispatch of goods and keeping relevant records
432102	Maintaining stock records, verifying issue of goods, estimating needs and making requisitions of new stocks
432103	Receiving, storing and issuing tools, spare parts, or various equipment and maintaining relevant records
432104	Weighing goods received, issued, produced, or dispatched and maintaining relevant records
432105	Compiling inventories of furniture and other items received for storage
432201	Computing quantities, qualities and types of materials required by production programme
432202	Preparing production requirements schedules, ensuring that materials are available when needed, and keeping relevant records
432203	Preparing or assisting in the preparation of production operation schedules on the basis of customers' orders and production capacity and performance
432204	Verifying stocks, arranging deliveries and investigating delays
432205	Recording and coordinating the flow of work and materials
432301	Keeping records of operational aspects and coordinating the timing of passenger and freight transport
432302	Directing train routings within a division or zone of a railway system and keeping related records
432303	Directing, controlling and keeping records of freight handling at a railway yard
432304	Coordinating and keeping records of operational activities concerning road transport, such as allocation and scheduling of vehicles and drivers, loading and unloading of vehicles and storage of goods in transit
432305	Coordinating and keeping records of operational activities concerning air transport, such as compiling passenger lists and freight manifests
432306	Preparing reports for management
441101	Issuing and receiving library books and other materials
441102	Reshelving books and other library materials
441103	Performing clerical activities such as manual and electronic filing, word processing and occasional typing
441104	Maintaining journal subscriptions

Code	Task
441105	Assisting library users in accessing basic library materials and making interlibrary loans
441106	Maintaining library records relating to the acquisition, issue and return of books and other
441201	Performing mail-handling duties in public post offices or privately owned delivery establishments
441202	Sorting and delivering mail to private houses and businesses
441203	Providing delivery confirmation records when requested by the client
441204	Sorting and keeping simple records of incoming and outgoing correspondence and dispatching outgoing mail in various establishments
441301	Converting information into codes and classifying information by codes for data-processing purposes
441302	Comparing proofs of texts and related material prepared for printing with original material, correcting errors and marking texts for printer according to the established rules
441303	Sorting forms and marking them with identification numbers
441304	Sorting documents for filing or to collate sets of pages
441305	Addressing circulars and envelopes by hand
441401	Reading letters and other written matter to persons who are unable to read or write and providing necessary interpretation and information
441402	Writing letters and completing forms on behalf of others
441403	Offering advice to individuals and interpreting and helping with the completion of government and other official forms
441501	Sorting or classifying materials according to guidelines such as content, purpose, user criteria, or chronological, alphabetical, or numerical order
441502	Filing material in drawers, cabinets and storage boxes
441503	Locating and remove materials from files when requested
441504	Keeping records of materials filed and removed
441505	Photocopying, scanning or faxing documents
441601	Updating information on, employment history, salaries, performance evaluations, qualifications and training and leave taken and accumulated
441602	Initiating records for newly appointed workers and checking records for completeness
441603	Processing applications for employment and promotions and advising applicants of results
441604	Receiving and answering inquiries about employment entitlements and conditions
441605	Sending out job applications and announcements of job openings and job examinations
441606	Maintaining and updating manual and computerized filing and registration systems, and compiling and preparing reports and documents relating to personnel activities
441607	Storing and retrieving personnel records and files on request
441901	Receiving customers' orders for classified advertising, writing and editing copy, calculating advertising rates and billing customers
441902	Writing business and government correspondence such as replies to requests for information and assistance, damage claims, credit and billing enquiries and service complaints
441903	Assisting in the preparation of periodicals, advertisements, catalogues, directories and other material for publication
441904	Reading newspapers, magazines, press releases and other publications to locate and file articles of interest to staff and clients
511101	Greeting passengers entering aircraft or ships, checking tickets or boarding passes, and directing them to their seats or berths
511102	Announcing, explaining and demonstrating safety and emergency procedures, such as the use of oxygen masks, seat belts, and life jackets
511103	Assembling and serving pre-prepared meals and beverages
511104	Selling duty-free and other goods

Code	Task
511105	Taking care of general needs and comfort of passengers, answering inquiries, and keeping cabins clean and tidy
511106	Directing and assisting passengers and following prescribed procedures in the event of an emergency, such as evacuating a plane following an emergency landing
511107	Verifying that first aid kits and other emergency equipment are in working order
511108	Administering first aid to passengers in distress
511109	Attending pre-flight briefings concerning weather, altitudes, routes, emergency procedures, crew coordination, lengths of flights, food and beverage services offered, and numbers of passengers
511110	Preparing passengers and aircraft for take-off and landing
511111	Determining special assistance needs of passengers such as small children, the elderly, or disabled persons
511201	Collecting and issuing tickets, passes or fares, and checking the validity of tickets issued previously
511202	Attending to sleeping-cars and their occupants on passenger trains
511203	Providing assistance with boarding, seating and luggage as required, especially to elderly, sick, or injured people
511204	Opening and closing doors for passengers
511205	Performing equipment safety checks prior to departure
511206	Signalling to drivers to stop or proceed
511207	Greeting passengers boarding transport vehicles, and announcing routes and stops
511208	Ensuring that safety regulations are respected
511209	Responding to passengers requests and complaints and providing information about stops and connections
511210	Taking appropriate action in case of emergencies or accidents
511301	Escorting and guiding tourists on cruises and sightseeing tours
511302	Escorting visitors through places of interest such as museums, exhibitions, theme parks, factories and other industrial establishments
511303	Describing and providing information on points of interest and exhibits and responding to questions
511304	Conducting educational activities for school children
511305	Monitoring visitors' activities to ensure compliance with establishment or tour regulations and safety practices
511306	Greeting and registering visitors and tour participants, and issuing any required identification badges or safety devices
511307	Distributing brochures, showing audio-visual presentations, and explaining procedures and operations at tour sites
511308	Providing for physical safety of groups, and performing activities such as providing first aid and directing emergency evacuations
511309	Resolving any problems with tour itineraries, service, or accommodation
512001	Planning meals, preparing and cooking foodstuffs
512002	Planning, supervising and coordinating the work of kitchen helpers
512003	Checking the quality of food
512004	Weighing, measuring and mixing ingredients according to recipes and personal judgement
512005	Regulating the temperature of ovens, grills, roasters and other cooking equipment, inspecting and cleaning the kitchen, kitchen equipment, serving areas, to ensure safe and sanitary food handling practices
512006	Operating large volume cooking equipment such as grills, deep-fat fryers, or griddles
513101	Setting tables with clean linen, cutlery, crockery and glassware
513102	Greeting customers and presenting them with menus and beverage lists
513103	Advising on food and beverage choices
513104	Taking orders for food and drinks and passing order to kitchen or bar staff

Code	Task
513105	Serving food and beverages to clients at tables
513106	Clearing tables and returning dishes and cutlery to kitchen
513107	Presenting bills, accepting payment and operating point of sales machines and cash registers
513201	Taking beverage orders from serving staff or directly from patrons
513202	Preparing and serving alcoholic and non-alcoholic drinks at a bar
513203	Washing used glassware, cleaning and maintaining bar service areas, tea and coffee-making areas and equipment such as espresso machines
513204	Collecting payment for sales, operating cash registers and balancing cash receipts
513205	Tapping kegs and attaching supply lines
513206	Assisting in keeping bar properly stocked and arranging bottles and glasses
513207	Checking identification of customers to verify age requirements for purchase of alcohol
513208	Taking steps to limit problems related to excessive drinking such as persuading customers to stop drinking, declining further service and ordering transportation
513209	Mixing ingredients to prepare cocktails and other drinks
513210	Serving snacks or other food items to customers at the bar
514101	Cutting, washing, tinting and waving hair
514102	Shaving or trimming beards and moustaches
514103	Giving scalp treatment
514104	Fitting wigs according to customers' requirements
514105	Providing advice on hair care, beauty products and hairstyles
514106	Styling hair into dreadlocks and braids and adding hair extensions
514107	Arranging appointments and collecting payments
514108	Cleaning work areas and sanitizing instruments
514201	Cleaning and applying creams, lotions and related products to face and parts of body
514202	Giving facial and body massage
514203	Applying make-up to clients of a beauty parlour or to actors and other performers
514204	Cleaning, shaping and polishing finger- and toe-nails and treating minor ailments of the human foot such as corns, calluses or deformed toe-nails
514205	Attending to clients taking baths and administering elementary massage
514206	Using waxing, sugaring and depilation techniques to remove unwanted bodily hair
514207	Advising clients on diet and exercise to assist in weight loss and slimming
514208	Arranging appointments and collecting payments
515101	Engaging, training, discharging, organizing and supervising helpers, cleaners and other housekeeping staff
515102	Purchasing or controlling the purchase of supplies
515103	Controlling storage and issue of supplies
515104	Supervising general welfare and conduct of housekeeping staff in institutions
515105	Sweeping or vacuum-cleaning, washing and polishing floors, furniture and other fixtures
515106	Making beds, cleaning bathrooms, supplying towels, soap and related items
515107	Cleaning kitchens and generally helping with kitchen work, including dishwashing
515108	Restocking minibars and replenishing items such as drinking glasses and writing equipment
515201	Supervising workers employed in households as domestic staff
515202	Purchasing or controlling the purchase of supplies
515203	Controlling storage and issue of supplies

Code	Task
515204	Assisting in cases of minor injury or illness by performing tasks such as taking temperature, giving medicine, putting on bandages
515205	Sweeping or vacuum-cleaning, washing and polishing floors, furniture and other fixtures
515206	Making beds, cleaning bathrooms, supplying towels, soap and related items
515207	Taking care of household pets and plants, receiving visitors, answering telephones, delivering messages and shopping for groceries
515208	Preparing and cooking meals, setting and clearing tables and serving food and beverages
515209	Cleaning kitchens and generally helping with kitchen work, including dishwashing
515301	Supervising the work of cleaning, housekeeping and building maintenance staff and contractors
515302	Participating in cleaning, simple repairs and maintenance of building interiors
515303	Regulating conduct of tenants and visitors in such matters as noise abatement or misuse of property
515305	Providing small services to absent tenants such as accepting deliveries on their behalf or providing requested information to callers
515306	Notifying management and owners of buildings of the need for major repairs
515307	Patrolling buildings to ensure security is maintained
515308	Filling out registration forms and providing tenants with copies of rules
516101	Casting horoscopes of individuals at birth or later to recount past and forecast future events and conditions of their lives
516102	Interpreting characteristics of clients' palms, samples of playing cards, position of tea leaves or coffee remnants in a cup, shapes and patterns of bones of dead animals, etc.
516103	Forecasting future events on the basis of these interpretations
516104	Determining auspicious times for various human activities such as inaugurations, marriages, journeys and religious and other ceremonies
516105	Giving warnings and advice on possible courses of action
516106	Advising individuals on precautions to be taken to avoid evil influences
516201	Providing companionship to employer by accompanying him/her to various places, reading, conversing and participating in activities such as sports
516202	Assisting in entertaining visitors in employer's home
516203	Keeping wardrobe and personal effects of the employer in good order
516301	Making arrangements for, and conducting, funerals, cremations and burials
516302	Embalming human bodies to retard or arrest the process of decay
516303	Conforming to health and sanitation and ensuring that legal requirements concerning embalming are met
516304	Incising and closing incisions on various parts of the body and reshaping or reconstructing disfigured or maimed bodies when necessary
516305	Dressing bodies and placing them in caskets
516306	Conducting interviews to arrange for preparation of obituary notices, to assist with the selection of caskets or urns, and to determine the location and time of burials or cremations
516401	Bathing and feeding animals
516402	Leading or carrying animals to treatment room and holding them during treatment
516403	Cleaning and sterilising veterinary surgical instruments
516404	Labelling drugs, chemicals and other pharmaceutical preparations and replenishing stock
516405	Sterilising bottles, beakers and other equipment
516406	Cleaning, organizing, and disinfecting animal quarters such as pens, stables, cages, and yards, and animal equipment such as saddles and bridles
516407	Collecting and recording animal information such as weight, size, physical condition, treatments received, medications given, and food intake

Code	Task
516408	Training animals to develop and maintain desired animal behaviour for competition, entertainment, obedience, security, riding and other activities
516409	Grooming animals by performing tasks such as washing, brushing, clipping, and trimming coats, cutting nails and cleaning ears
516501	Instructing students under actual driving conditions, and explaining and demonstrating the operation of brakes, clutch, gear selection, automatic transmission, signals and lights
516502	Teaching road traffic regulations
516503	Teaching road craft and road safety
516504	Advising students when they are ready to undergo driving examination
516505	Advising on and teaching advanced driving techniques required for emergency situations
516506	Illustrating and explaining handling and mechanical operation of motor vehicles and driving techniques using blackboard diagrams and audio-visual aids
516901	Accompanying clients to restaurants and other outings
516902	Acting as a dancing partner
516903	Welcoming clients to a night-club and ensuring that they are entertained well
521101	Obtaining permission to set up a stand at a particular place in streets, markets or other open spaces
521102	Determining product mix, stock and price levels for goods to be sold
521103	Buying or contracting a regular supply of goods to be sold from wholesale suppliers or directly from producers
521104	Erecting and dismantling stalls and stands, transporting, storing, loading and unloading goods for sale
521105	Demonstrating and selling goods and accepting payment
521106	Stacking and displaying goods for sale, and wrapping and packing goods sold
521107	Keeping accounts and maintaining a record of stock levels
521201	Obtaining permission or a licence, where required, to sell food and drinks on the street or in a public place
521202	Obtaining food and drinks for sale
521203	Preparing, either beforehand or on the spot, food and drinks for sale
521204	Loading and unloading, pushing, pedalling or carrying hand-cart, truck, tray or basket to bring food and drinks to the desired place in the street, or to public places such as stations or cinemas
521205	Displaying and selling food and drinks and accepting payment
522101	Determining product mix, stock and price levels for goods to be sold
522102	Purchasing and ordering goods for sale from markets, wholesalers and other suppliers
522103	Budgeting and maintaining records of stock levels and financial transactions
522104	Determining prices and displaying goods for sale
522105	Selling goods to customers and advising them on product use
522106	Examining returned goods and deciding on appropriate action
522107	Taking inventory of goods in stock
522201	Planning and preparing work schedules and assigning staff to specific duties
522202	Instructing staff on sales procedures, including how to handle difficult or complex cases
522203	Ensuring that customers receive prompt service
522204	Participating in and providing advice to managers on interviewing, hiring, training, evaluating, promoting and dismissing staff, and resolving staff grievances
522205	Examining returned goods and deciding on appropriate action
522206	Taking inventory of goods for sale and ordering new stock
522207	Ensuring that goods and services are correctly priced and displayed
522208	Ensuring that safety procedures are enforced

Code	Task
522301	Determining customer requirements and advising on product range, price, delivery, warranties and product use and care
522302	Demonstrating and explaining to customers the establishment's goods and services
522303	Selling goods and services, accepting payment by a variety of payment methods, preparing sales invoices and recording sales using cash registers
522304	Assisting with the ongoing management of stock such as product inventories and participating in stock takes
522305	Stacking and displaying goods for sale, and wrapping and packing goods sold
523001	Receiving and verifying payment by cash, cheque, credit card or automatic debit in stores, ticket offices, or similar establishments
523002	Giving change and issuing receipts
523003	Issuing tickets for attendance at sporting and cultural events
523004	Counting and recording money received or paid out and balancing against cash register sales records
523005	Receiving incoming cash, checking it against sales slips and other documents, and preparing it for deposit at bank
523006	Operating cash register to calculate total to be paid from or to clients
523007	Scanning, weighing and recording prices of goods
523008	Wrapping and placing merchandise in bags
524101	Dressing in sample apparel of new or current styles or of type wanted by customer
524102	Walking, turning and posing to demonstrate style and characteristics of garments, fashion accessories and other merchandise to best advantage
524103	Posing as subject for sculpture, painting and other types of visual art
524104	Posing for still photography for magazines and other advertising media
524105	Posing for television, video and cinema commercials and other productions
524201	Setting up displays and demonstrating articles for sale to inform customers about their characteristics and mode of use, as well as to stimulate buying interest
524202	Answering questions and offering advice on the use of goods
524203	Selling goods or directing customers to sales staff
524204	Taking orders and making arrangements for payment and delivery of goods
524205	Offering sample goods and distributing catalogues and advertising material
524301	Giving details of various goods or services and of terms of sale by visiting clients and potential clients door to door
524302	Demonstrating or describing goods or services on offer
524303	Recording orders and transactions and placing orders received with suppliers
524304	Preparing invoices and sales contracts and accepting payment
524305	Distributing letters, information sheets and other documents to clients
524306	Compiling lists of prospective clients and calling on them to obtain new business
524307	Travelling between sales areas and clients and transporting samples or goods for sale
524401	Promoting goods and services by telephone or electronic mail, following scripts and working from lists of contacts
524402	Creating interest in goods and services, and seeking a sale or agreement to see sales representatives
524403	Arranging processing and despatch of goods and services, information kits and brochures to customers
524404	Arranging appointments for sales representatives
524405	Recording notes for follow-up action and updating marketing databases to reflect changes to the status of each customer
524406	Reporting competitor activities and issues raised by contacts for attention by managers

Code	Task
524407	Maintaining statistics of calls made and successes achieved
524408	Submitting periodic reports on telemarketing activities and results
524501	Filling fuel tanks and containers to level specified by customer
524502	Checking and replenishing air pressure in vehicle tyres, and oil and other vehicle fluid levels
524503	Washing vehicle windscreens and windows
524504	Performing minor repair work to vehicles such as replacing tyres, light bulbs and windscreen wiper blades
524505	Maintaining and operating automatic car wash facilities
524506	Collecting payments from customers for purchases
524507	Cleaning petrol pumps and surrounding driveway, shop and facilities
524508	Undertaking stock control and preparing reports on fuel, oil, accessories and other items sold
524601	Serving food to customers at counters
524602	Ascertaining the products desired by the customer, assisting customer in making a choice and taking orders
524603	Cleaning, peeling, slicing and trimming foodstuffs using manual and electric appliances
524604	Preparing simple food items and reheating prepared meals
524605	Portioning and wrapping food or placing it directly on plates for service to patrons
524606	Packaging take-away food
524607	Stocking refrigerators, salad and buffet bars and keeping records of the quantities of food used
524608	Receiving payment for food items purchased
531101	Assisting children to wash, dress and feed themselves
531102	Taking children to and from school or outdoors for recreation
531103	Playing games with children, or entertaining them by reading or storytelling
531104	Assisting in the preparation of materials and equipment for children's education and recreational activities
531105	Managing children's behaviour and guiding their social development
531106	Disciplining children and recommending or initiating other measures to control behaviour, such as caring for own clothing and picking up toys and books
531107	Observing and monitoring children's play activities
531108	Keeping records on individual children, including daily observations and information about activities, meals served, and medications administered
531201	Demonstrating, supervising and participating in activities that enhance the physical, social, emotional and intellectual development of children in schools and preschools
531202	Preparing indoor and outdoor areas for learning and recreational activities
531203	Assisting children with intellectual, physical, behavioural and other learning difficulties with their studies
531204	Assisting children individually to learn social skills
531205	Assisting with preparing teaching materials, and copying and collating written and printed material
531206	Operating audio-visual equipment, computers and other teaching aides
531207	Distributing and collecting lesson material
532101	Providing care, support and treatment to patients and residents of medical, rehabilitative and residential care facilities as per treatment plans established by medical, nursing and other health professionals
532102	Assisting patients with personal and therapeutic care needs such as personal hygiene, feeding, dressing, physical mobility and exercise, communication, taking oral medications and changing dressings
532103	Positioning, lifting and turning patients and transporting them in wheelchairs or on movable beds
532104	Maintaining patients' environmental hygiene standards, such as cleaning patient rooms and changing bed-linen
532105	Providing massage and other non-pharmacological pain relief measures, such as during pregnancy and labour

Code	Task
532106	Observing patients' condition, responses and behaviour and reporting changes to a health professional
532201	Assisting clients with personal and therapeutic care needs such as personal hygiene, feeding, dressing, physical mobility and exercise, communication, taking oral medications and changing dressings, usually as per care plans established by a health professional
532202	Maintaining records of client care, changes in condition and responses to care and treatment, and reporting concerns or providing referrals to a health or social services professional
532203	Positioning and lifting clients with physical mobility challenges, and helping transport them in wheelchairs and motor vehicles
532204	Providing clients and families with emotional support and information and advice on topics such as nutrition, hygiene, exercise, caring for infants, or adapting to disability or illness
532205	Maintaining clients' environmental hygiene standards, such as changing bed linen, washing clothes and dishes, and cleaning living quarters
532206	Providing psychological support to clients such as through conversation or reading aloud
532207	Planning, purchasing, preparing, or serving meals to meet nutritional requirements or prescribed diets
532208	Providing support to parents and care for newborns during the postpartum period
532209	Scheduling and accompanying clients for appointments with medical doctors and other health professionals or performing other errands
532901	Cleaning and sterilizing surgical, dental and pharmaceutical instruments, bottles, beakers and other equipment
532902	Labelling drugs, chemicals and other pharmaceutical preparations and replenishing stock on shelves
532903	Lifting, turning, and moving patients and transporting them in wheelchairs or on moveable beds
532904	Preparing patients for examination or treatment
532905	Setting up instrument trays, preparing materials, and assisting dentists or radiographers during procedures
532906	Exposing diagnostic x-rays
541101	Responding to fire alarms and other calls for assistance, such as automobile and industrial accidents, bomb threats and other emergencies
541102	Controlling and extinguishing fires using manual and power equipment and firefighting chemicals
541103	Fighting special types of fires and using special equipment in industrial establishments
541104	Rescuing people from burning buildings and accident sites and those trapped in dangerous situations
541105	Preventing or limiting the spread of dangerous substances in case of fires or accidents
541106	Informing the public about fire prevention
541201	Patrolling a specific area to maintain public order, respond to emergencies, protect people and property and enforce laws and regulations
541202	Identifying, pursuing and arresting suspects and perpetrators of criminal acts
541203	Directing traffic and assuming authority in the event of accidents
541204	Providing emergency assistance to victims of accidents, crimes and natural disasters
541301	Searching arriving prisoners, putting their valuables in safekeeping, escorting prisoners to their cells
541302	Making periodic inspection tours of cells and inspecting and maintaining the security of locks, doors and gates
541303	Supervising prisoners at work, meals, or during recreation periods
541304	Observing the conduct and behaviour of prisoners to prevent disturbances and escapes
541305	Patrolling prison areas to prevent escape
541306	Assisting with the implementation of rehabilitation programs
541307	Escorting prisoners in transit and during temporary leaves
541401	Patrolling premises and checking doors, windows and gates to prevent and detect signs of unauthorised entry

Code	Task
541402	Controlling access to establishments, monitoring and authorizing the entrance or departure of employees and visitors, checking identification and issuing security passes
541403	Circulating among visitors, patrons, or employees to preserve order, protect property from theft or vandalism and enforce the regulations of the establishment
541404	Responding to alarms, investigating disturbances and contacting superiors, police or fire-fighters as appropriate
541405	Performing security checks of passengers and luggage at airports
541406	Picking up and ensuring the safe delivery of cash and valuables to banks, automated teller machines and retail establishments
541901	Patrolling beaches and swimming pools to prevent accidents and to rescue bathers from drowning
541902	Monitoring traffic flow to locate safe gaps through which pedestrians can cross streets
541903	Patrolling an assigned area to enforce parking regulations
541904	Directing traffic
611101	Monitoring market activity and conditions, determining types and quantities of crops to be grown, and planning and coordinating production accordingly
611102	Preparing soil by hand or machine, and spreading fertilizers and manure
611103	Selecting and sowing seeds, and planting seedlings
611104	Maintaining crops by cultivating soil, by transplanting, pruning or thinning plants, and by setting up and operating irrigation equipment
611105	Controlling weeds, pests and diseases, by applying herbicides and pesticides
611106	Harvesting crops and destroying diseased or superfluous crops
611107	Inspecting, cleaning, grading, packaging, storing and loading crops for sale or delivery to market
611108	Tending working animals and maintaining farm buildings, structures, equipment and water supply systems
611109	Storing and carrying out some processing of produce
611110	Promoting and marketing products, arranging the sale, purchase and transportation of produce and supplies and maintaining and evaluating records of farm activities and transactions
611111	Training and supervising workers in crop production, maintenance duties, and health and safety precautions and hiring and discharging workers and contractors
611201	Monitoring market activity and conditions, determining types and quantities of crops to be grown, and planning and coordinating production accordingly
611202	Preparing soil by hand or machine, and spreading fertilizers and manure
611203	Selecting and sowing seeds, and planting seedlings
611204	Maintaining crops by cultivating soil, by transplanting, pruning or thinning trees and shrubs, and by setting up and operating irrigation equipment
611205	Controlling weeds, pests and diseases, by applying herbicides and pesticides
611206	Tending trees or bushes, collecting sap and harvesting crops
611207	Inspecting, cleaning, grading, packaging, storing and loading crops for sale or delivery to market
611208	Tending working animals and maintaining farm buildings, structures, equipment and water supply systems
611209	Storing and carrying out some processing of produce
611210	Promoting and marketing products, arranging the sale, purchase and transportation of produce and supplies and maintaining and evaluating records of farm activities and transactions
611211	Training and supervising workers in crop production, maintenance duties, and health and safety precautions and hiring and discharging workers and contractors
611301	Monitoring market activity and conditions determining kinds and amounts of vegetables, horticultural and nursery products to be grown and planning and coordinating production accordingly
611302	Preparing land by conditioning soil, levelling ground and installing and operating irrigation and drainage systems

Code	Task
611303	Planting trees, hedges, garden plants, grass
611304	Pruning and trimming trees, shrubs and hedges, installing plant supports and protection, and rolling, mowing, aerating and edging lawns
611305	Constructing features and facilities within gardens, such as paths or paved areas, walls, rockeries, garden beds ponds and water features, sheds and fences
611306	Checking the health of plants and trees, identifying and treating weeds, pests and diseases, and applying mulch and fertilizers
611307	Producing saplings, bulbs and seeds and raising plants from seeds or cuttings
611308	Harvesting crops, inspecting, cleaning, grading, packaging, storing and loading products for sale or delivery to market
611309	Maintaining buildings, greenhouses and other structures, equipment and water supply systems
611310	Storing and carrying out some processing of produce
611311	Promoting and marketing products, arranging the sale, purchase and transportation of produce and supplies and maintaining and evaluating records of activities and transactions
611312	Training and supervising workers in production, maintenance duties, and health and safety precautions and hiring and discharging workers and contractors
611401	Monitoring market activity and conditions, determining types and quantities of crops to be grown, and planning and coordinating production accordingly
611402	Preparing soil by hand or machine, and spreading fertilizers and manure
611403	Selecting and sowing seeds, and planting seedlings
611404	Maintaining crops by cultivating soil, by transplanting, pruning or thinning crops trees and shrubs, and by setting up and operating irrigation equipment
611405	Growing flowers and vegetables by intensive cultivation
611406	Producing saplings, bulbs and seeds
611407	Harvesting crops, inspecting, cleaning, grading, packaging, storing and loading products for sale or delivery to market
611408	Tending working animals and maintaining farm buildings, structures, equipment and water supply systems
611409	Storing and carrying out some processing of produce
611410	Promoting and marketing products, arranging the sale, purchase and transportation of produce and supplies and maintaining and evaluating records of activities and transactions
611411	Training and supervising workers in production, maintenance duties, and health and safety precautions and hiring and discharging workers and contractors
612101	Monitoring market activity and conditions, determining kinds and amounts of stock to produce, planning and coordinating production accordingly
612102	Cultivating pastures and providing and monitoring fodder and water supplies to maintain appropriate nutritional levels and condition of livestock
612103	Monitoring and examining animals to detect illness, injury, or disease, and to check physical condition such as rate of weight gain
612104	Grooming , marking, clipping, trimming, drenching and/or castrating animals and shearing coats to collect hair or wool
612105	Herding livestock to pastures for grazing or to scales, sheds, vehicles, or other enclosures
612106	Milking animals by hand or using milking machines
612107	Mixing feed, additives, and medicines in prescribed portions and distributing or hand-feeding to animals for consumption
612108	Performing duties related to livestock reproduction, such as breeding, artificial insemination, and helping with animal births
612109	Maintaining and cleaning farm buildings, machinery, equipment, and structures
612110	Slaughtering and skinning animals and preparing them for market
612111	Storing and carrying out some processing of animal and dairy produce

Code	Task
612112	Promoting and marketing products, arranging the sale, purchase and transportation of livestock, produce and supplies and maintaining and evaluating records of farm activities and transactions
612113	Training and supervising workers in animal care procedures, maintenance duties, and health and safety precautions and hiring and discharging workers and contractors
612201	Monitoring market activity, planning and coordinating production accordingly, maintaining and evaluating records of farming activities
612202	Growing and purchasing feed and other supplies needed to maintain appropriate nutritional levels and condition of poultry
612203	Monitoring and examining poultry to detect illness, injury, or disease, and to check physical condition, such as rate of weight gain, and removing weak, ill and dead poultry from flock
612204	Mixing feed and feed additives and filling feed and water containers
612205	Vaccinating poultry via drinking water, injection, or dusting of air
612206	Collecting and storing eggs and packaging them for sale delivery to market
612207	Determining sex of chicks and facilitating breeding, artificial insemination, and hatching of eggs
612208	Renting or investing in and maintaining and cleaning farm buildings, machinery, equipment, and structures
612209	Slaughtering and dressing poultry for sale or delivery to market
612210	Storing and carrying out some processing of produce
612211	Arranging the sale, purchase and transportation stock, produce and supplies
612212	Training and supervising workers in poultry production procedures, maintenance duties, and health and safety precautions, and hiring and discharging workers and contractors
612301	Monitoring market activity and conditions, determining kinds and amounts of insect products to produce, planning and coordinating production accordingly
612302	Purchasing insects and growing or purchasing feed and other supplies
612303	Breeding, raising and tending insects and collecting their products
612304	Renting or investing in and maintaining and cleaning buildings, machinery, equipment , and structures
612305	Storing and carrying out some processing of produce
612306	Arranging the sale, purchase and transportation of stock, produce and supplies and maintaining and evaluating records of farming activities
612307	Training and supervising workers in production procedures, maintenance duties, and health and safety precautions, and hiring and discharging workers and contractors
612901	Monitoring market activity and conditions, determining kinds and amounts of products to produce, planning and coordinating production accordingly
612902	Raising, feeding and tending animals
612903	Killing and skinning animals, and preparing animals or animal products for market
612904	Monitoring and examining animals to detect illness, injury, or disease, and to check physical condition such as rate of weight gain
612905	Performing duties related to animal reproduction, such as breeding, artificial insemination, and helping with animal births
612906	Renting or investing in and maintaining and cleaning buildings, machinery, equipment , and structures
612907	Slaughtering and skinning animals and preparing them for market
612908	Storing and carrying out some processing of produce
612909	Promoting and marketing products, arranging the sale, purchase and transportation of stock, produce and supplies and maintaining and evaluating records of activities and transactions
612910	Training and supervising workers in animal care procedures, maintenance duties, and health and safety precautions
613001	Monitoring market activity and conditions, determining kinds and amounts of crops to be grown and animals to be raised, and planning and coordinating production accordingly
613002	Purchasing seeds, fertilizer, and other supplies

Code	Task
613003	Performing operations such as land preparation, sowing, planting, cultivating and harvesting crops
613004	Producing or buying fodder and other food supplies
613005	Breeding, raising and tending animals
613006	Killing and skinning animals, and preparing animals or animal products for market
613007	Renting or investing in and maintaining and cleaning farm buildings, machinery, equipment, and structures
613008	Storing and carrying out some processing of produce
613009	Promoting and marketing products, arranging the sale, purchase and transportation of livestock, produce and supplies and maintaining and evaluating records of farm activities and transactions
613010	Training and supervising workers in animal care procedures, maintenance duties, and health and safety precautions and hiring and discharging workers and contractors
621001	Assessing sites for reforestation, selecting seedlings and planting trees using manual planting tools and caring for forest stands
621002	Locating trees to be felled and estimating volume of timber
621003	Operating chainsaw and other power saws to thin young forest stands, trim, top and fell trees and saw them into logs
621004	Shaping rough wooden products from logs at felling site
621005	Stacking logs and loading them in chutes or floating them down rivers
621006	Keeping watch to detect forest fires, participating in fire fighting operations, completing fire fighting reports and maintaining fire fighting equipment
621007	Controlling weeds and undergrowth in regenerating forest stands using manual tools and chemicals
621008	Operating and maintaining a skidder, bulldozer or other prime mover to pull a variety of scarification or site preparation equipment over areas to be regenerated
621009	Collecting seed cones, pruning trees, assisting in planting surveys and marking trees for subsequent operations
621010	Training and supervising other workers in forestry procedures, including forestry labourers and plant operators
622101	Breeding, raising and cultivating fish, mussels, oysters and other forms of aquatic life as cash crops or for release into freshwater or saltwater
622102	Collecting and recording growth, production, and environmental data
622103	Conducting and supervising stock examinations in order to identify diseases or parasites
622104	Monitoring environments to ensure maintenance of optimum conditions for aquatic life
622105	Directing and monitoring trapping and spawning of fish, egg incubation, and fry rearing, applying knowledge of management and fish culturing techniques
622106	Cleaning, freezing, icing or salting catch on- or offshore and preparing fish and other products for shipment
622107	Maintaining buildings, tanks, machinery, boats and other equipment
622108	Delivering or marketing products
622109	Renting or investing in buildings, equipment and machinery and purchasing food and other supplies
622110	Supervising and training aquaculture and fish hatchery support workers
622201	Preparing and repairing nets and other fishing gear and equipment
622202	Selecting area for fishing, plotting courses and computing navigational positions using compass, charts and other aids
622203	Operating fishing vessels to, from and at fishing grounds
622204	Baiting, setting, operating and hauling in fishing gear by hand or using hoisting equipment
622205	Gathering various forms of aquatic life from shores and shallow waters
622206	Maintaining engine fishing gear and other on-board equipment
622207	Keeping records of transactions, fishing activities, weather and sea conditions and estimating costs and budgets

Code	Task
622208	Sorting, and storing catch in holds with salt and ice
622209	Removing catches from fishing equipment, measuring them to ensure compliance with legal size and returning undesirable or illegal catches to the water
622210	Direct fishing operations, and supervising fishing crew members
622301	Preparing and repairing nets and other fishing gear and equipment
622302	Commanding fishing vessels to from and at deep-sea fishing grounds
622303	Determining areas for fishing, plotting courses and computing navigational positions using compass, charts, tables and other aids
622304	Steering vessels and operating electronic fishing aids
622305	Directing fishing operations and supervising crew activities
622306	Recording fishing progress, activities, weather and sea conditions on ship's log
622307	Baiting, setting and hauling in fishing gear
622308	Cleaning, freezing, icing or salting catch on- or offshore
622309	Selecting and training vessel crews
622401	Setting traps to catch mammals, birds or reptiles
622402	Killing trapped or free mammals, birds or reptiles with firearms or other weapons
622403	Skinning and otherwise treating killed mammals, birds or reptiles to obtain desired products for sale or delivery
622404	Delivering or selling trapped live mammals, birds or reptiles
622405	Repairing and maintaining equipment
631001	Preparing the soil, sowing, planting, tending and harvesting field crops
631002	Growing vegetables, fruit and other tree and shrub crops
631003	Fetching water and gathering firewood
631004	Building and maintaining houses and other shelters
631005	Making tools, clothes and utensils for use by the household
631006	Selling some products at local markets
632001	Cultivating pastures, or managing grazing lands, and monitoring feed and water supplies needed to maintain condition of livestock
632002	Monitoring and examining animals to detect illness, injury, or disease, and to check physical condition
632003	Grooming and marking animals and shearing coats to collect hair or wool
632004	Herding or leading livestock to pastures, grazing land and water supplies
632005	Raising, tending, feeding and milking animals or draining blood from them
632006	Breeding animals and helping with animal births
632007	Slaughtering and skinning animals and preparing them and their products for consumption or sale
632008	Carrying out some processing of animal products
632009	Building and maintaining houses and other shelters
632010	Making tools, clothes and utensils for use by the household
632011	Fetching water and gathering firewood
632012	Buying, bartering and selling animals and some products
633001	Preparing the soil, sowing, planting, tending and harvesting field crops
633002	Growing vegetables, fruit and other tree and shrub crops
633003	Gathering wild fruits, medicinal plants
633004	Breeding, tending and feeding mammals and poultry mainly to obtain meat, eggs, milk, hair, skin or other products

Code	Task
633005	Fetching water and gathering firewood
633006	Storing produce for later use and carrying out some processing of produce
633007	Building and maintaining houses and other shelters
633008	Making tools, clothes and utensils for use by the household
633009	Selling some products at local markets
634001	Gathering wild fruits, roots, medicinal and other plants
634002	Hunting or trapping animals mainly to obtain meat, milk, hair, skin or other products
634003	Fetching water and gathering firewood
634004	Catching fish and gathering other forms of aquatic life
634005	Storing or carrying out some processing of their produce
634006	Building and maintaining houses and other shelters
634007	Making tools, clothes and utensils for use by the household
634008	Selling some products at local markets
711101	Preparing ground for erecting building or other structures
711102	Erecting structures to support roof, and building and covering walls with appropriate materials
711103	Fixing rafters to roof and covering with roofing material
711104	Levelling floor to make it smooth and serviceable
711105	Maintaining and repairing existing structures
711106	Arranging for specialized work such as bricklaying, painting, plumbing and electrical wiring to be done by subcontractors
711107	Coordinating and supervising the activities of subcontractors, labourers and other workers
711201	Laying stone, brick and similar building blocks to construct or repair walls, partitions, fireplaces and other structures such as smokestacks, furnaces, converters, kilns and ovens, piers and abutments
711202	Laying footpaths, kerbs and pavements
711203	Laying bricks or other masonry to build patios, garden walls and other decorative installations
711301	Driving wedges into quarried stone to break it into slabs or blocks
711302	Selecting and grading slabs and blocks of granite, marble, and other stone
711303	Cutting, shaping and finishing building and monumental stone such as granite or marble by using hand or hand-powered tools
711304	Making patterns and marking shapes on stone for subsequent sawing, planing, drilling and other dressing and cutting operations
711305	Cutting and carving characters, figures or designs on stone blocks used for monuments or memorials
711306	Setting stone in the erection of monuments and memorials
711307	Repairing and replacing stonework on old buildings, churches and monuments
711401	Constructing and repairing reinforced concrete floors, walls, tanks, silos and other concrete structures
711402	Making shuttering or assembling prefabricated forms for moulding concrete
711403	Cementing openings in walls or casings for wells
711404	Finishing and smoothing surfaces of concrete structures
711405	Applying a durable, smooth surfacing composed of cement, sand pigment and marble particles to floors, known as a terrazzo finish
711501	Making, altering and repairing structural and other woodwork at a work-bench and on a construction site
711502	Constructing, erecting and installing heavy-framed wooden structures on building sites
711503	Fitting, assembling and altering internal and external fixtures of buildings, such as walls, doors, door and window frames, facings and panelling

Code	Task
711504	Making, repairing and fitting scenic equipment for theatrical performances, motion picture or television productions
711505	Constructing, assembling, altering and repairing wooden fixtures and fittings in train coaches, aircraft, ships, boats, floats, and other vehicles
711901	Climbing and performing miscellaneous construction and building maintenance work on tall structures such as towers, chimneys and spires
711902	Erecting temporary metal or wooden scaffolding on building sites
711903	Demolishing buildings and other structures
712101	Studying drawings, specifications and construction sites to determine materials required
712102	Covering frameworks with slate and pre-fabricated tiles on pitched roofs
712103	Laying a waterproof shield and fixing metallic or synthetic materials to a building's frame
712104	Sizing and cutting roofing materials to fit around edges corners and protuberances such as chimney
712105	Using natural materials such as thatching to provide roof coverings
712106	Creating temporary structures such as scaffolding and ladders
712201	Preparing floor areas for covering with a variety of materials
712202	Assembling carpet, tiles or other materials and laying them on floors according to design and other specifications
712203	Preparing wall areas for covering with tiles or other materials for decorative or other purposes such as acoustic insulation
712204	Setting tiles and constructing and laying mosaic panels to walls, floors and other surfaces
712301	Applying one or more coats of plaster to interior walls and ceilings of buildings to produce finished surface
712302	Measuring, marking and installing ornamental plaster panels, and casting and trimming ornamental plaster cornices
712303	Applying protective and decorative covering of cement, plaster and similar materials to exterior building surfaces
712304	Making and installing decorative plaster fixtures of fibrous plaster
712401	Cutting insulation material by size and shape
712402	Applying slabs and sheets of insulating or sound-absorbing materials to walls, floors and ceilings of buildings
712403	Blow and pack insulating or sound-absorbing materials into cavities between walls, floors and ceilings of buildings with power-driven machines
712404	Examining plans, specifications and work sites to determine the type, quality and quantity of insulation material required
712405	Applying insulating materials to exposed surfaces of equipment such as boilers, pipes and tanks
712406	Insulating refrigeration and air-conditioning equipment
712501	Selecting the type of glass to be used, cutting to right size and shape and installing in windows, doors, showers and partitions of buildings
712502	Installing glass and mirrors in skylights, display cases, interior walls and ceilings
712503	Installing or replacing windscreens in vehicles or boats
712504	Creating decorative glass features such as glass walls, staircases, balustrades and stained-glass windows
712601	Measuring, cutting, threading, bending, jointing, assembling, installing, maintaining and repairing pipes, fittings and fixtures of drainage, heating, water supply and sewerage systems
712602	Installing gas appliances, dishwashers and water heaters, sinks and toilets using hand and power tools
712603	Laying clay, concrete or cast-iron pipes in ditches to form sewers, drains or water mains, or for other purposes
712604	Inspecting, examining and testing installed systems and pipes, using pressure gauge, hydrostatic testing, observation or other methods

Code	Task
712701	Interpreting blueprints, drawings or other specifications
712702	Assembling, installing and repairing components for air conditioning and refrigeration systems
712703	Connecting piping and equipment by bolting, riveting, or welding
712704	Testing systems, diagnosing faults and performing routine maintenance or servicing
713101	Cleaning and preparing walls and other surfaces of buildings for painting or wallpapering
713102	Selecting and preparing paints to required colours by mixing pigments and additives
713103	Applying or spraying paint, varnish, and similar materials to surfaces, fixtures and fittings of buildings
713104	Measuring and hanging wallpaper or other fabrics on interior walls and ceilings
713105	Applying paints, varnishes and stains to surfaces using brushes, rollers and sprays
713201	Preparing surfaces to be coated using a variety of methods to remove grease, dirt and rust
713202	Painting cars, buses, trucks and other vehicles, and applying varnish and other protective coatings
713203	Applying paint as well as protective coatings of enamel or varnish on metal, wooden and other manufactured products, usually with a hand-spraying device
713301	Cleaning exterior surfaces of stone, brick, metal or similar materials by means of chemicals, or a jet of steam or sand applied under high pressure
713302	Removing soot from flues, chimneys and connecting pipes
713303	Removing asbestos, mould and fire damaged surfaces from buildings
721101	Making moulds by hand or using auxiliary machines on a bench for small metal castings, on the foundry floor, or in a pit for large castings
721102	Making cores for use in metal moulds
721103	Cleaning and smoothing moulds, core boxes, and repairing surface imperfections
721104	Moving and positioning work pieces such as mould sections, patterns, and bottom boards, using cranes, or signalling others to move work pieces
721105	Positioning patterns inside mould sections and clamping sections together
721106	Cutting spouts, runner holes and sprue holes into moulds
721107	Lifting upper mould sections from lower sections and remove moulded patterns
721201	Welding metal parts using gas flame, or an electric arc, thermite compound or other methods
721202	Operating resistance-welding machines
721203	Using blowtorch to make and repair lead linings, pipes, floors and other lead fixtures
721204	Brazing metal parts together
721205	Cutting metal pieces using gas flame or an electric arc
721206	Joining metal parts by hand soldering
721207	Monitoring the fitting, burning, and welding processes to avoid overheating of parts or warping, shrinking, distortion, or expansion of material
721208	Examining work pieces for defects and measuring work pieces with straight edges or templates to ensure conformance with specifications
721301	Marking sheet metal for cutting and shaping
721302	Making and repairing household utensils and other articles in tin, copper and light alloys, or ornamental articles
721303	Making and repairing boilers, tanks, vats and similar containers
721304	Installing and repairing sheet-metal parts of vehicles and aircraft
721305	Converting blueprints into shop drawings to be followed in the construction and assembly of sheet metal products
721306	Determining project requirements, including scope, assembly sequences, and required methods and materials, according to blueprints, drawings, and written or verbal instructions

Code	Task
721307	Inspecting product quality and installation to ensure conformance to specifications
721401	Marking metal framework as a guide when drilling, cutting, and shaping them for use in buildings, ships and other structures
721402	Drilling, cutting and shaping structural steel in a workshop
721403	Erecting steel framework for buildings, bridges and other constructions
721404	Assembling and erecting the framework and other metal parts of ships' structures
721405	Shaping and fitting structural-steel plates of ships under construction or repair
721406	Riveting structural-metal members by hand, machine or pneumatic riveter
721501	Estimating the size, shape and weight of objects to be moved and deciding on the type of equipment to move them
721502	Installing and repairing cables, ropes, wires, pulleys and other tackle
721503	Joining, repairing and fitting attachments to wires, ropes and cables
721504	Working as member of crew erecting and repairing derricks for drilling water, gas- and oil-wells
721505	Lifting and mounting scenery, lighting and other equipment in theatres and on film sets
721506	Installing and maintaining communication towers, aerial cableways, funicular railways, ski lifts and similar infrastructure
722101	Heating metal in forge furnace and manufacturing and repairing articles by drawing, bending, cutting, hammering metal on an anvil, punching, shearing, joining and hardening or tempering
722102	Cutting, hammering metal on an anvil, punching, shearing, joining and hardening or tempering
722103	Shaping heated metal into forgings on power hammer equipped with open dies
722104	Operating closed-die drop hammer
722105	Operating a power-press machine equipped with closed dies
722106	Drawing wire
722107	Reading work orders or blueprints to determine specified tolerances and sequences of operations for machine setup
722108	Measuring and inspecting machine parts to ensure conformance to product specifications
722201	Reading and interpreting engineering drawings and specifications of tools, dies, prototypes or models
722202	Preparing templates and sketches, and determining work processes
722203	Visualizing and computing dimensions, sizes, shapes, and tolerances of assemblies, based on specifications
722204	Positioning, securing and measuring metal stock or castings to lay out for machining
722205	Setting up, operating and maintaining conventional and computer numerically controlled machine tools to cut, turn, mill, plane, drill, bore, grind or otherwise shape workpieces to prescribed dimensions and finish
722206	Fitting and assembling parts to make and repair jigs, fixtures and gauges
722207	Repairing and modifying sports guns and other small arms
722208	Making, fitting, assembling, repairing and installing lock parts and locks
722209	Making and repairing metal patterns for foundry moulds
722210	Laying out lines and reference points on metal stock to guide other workers who cut, turn, mill, grind or otherwise shape metal
722211	Verifying dimensions, alignments, and clearances of finished parts for conformance to specifications, using precision measuring instruments and testing completed items for proper operation
722301	Setting one or more types of machine tool for production of metal articles in standardised series
722302	Operating and monitoring metalworking machines, such as lathes, milling, planing, boring, drilling, grinding or honing machines, including multi-purpose numerically controlled machines
722303	Performing similar tasks when machining plastics and other metal substitutes
722304	Observing machine operations to detect work piece defects or machine malfunctions, adjusting machines as necessary

Code	Task
722305	Inspecting work pieces for defects, and measuring work pieces to determine accuracy of machine operation, using rules, templates, or other measuring instruments
722306	Changing worn machine accessories, such as cutting tools and brushes, using hand tools
722401	Operating fixed or portable buffing and polishing machines
722402	Sharpening cutting tools and instruments using grinding wheels or mechanically operated grinding machines
722403	Repairing, adjusting and sharpening saw blades and metal teeth of cylinders in textile carding machines
722404	Dressing grinding wheels, according to specifications
722405	Monitoring machine operations to determine whether adjustments are necessary, stop machines when problems occur
722406	Inspecting, feeling, and measuring work pieces to ensure that surfaces and dimensions meet specifications
722407	Selecting and mounting grinding wheels on machines, according to specifications, using hand tools and applying knowledge of abrasives and grinding procedures
723101	Detecting and diagnosing faults in engines and parts
723102	Fitting, examining, testing and servicing motor vehicle and motorcycle engines
723103	Replacing engine components or complete engines
723104	Fitting, examining, adjusting, dismantling, rebuilding and replacing defective parts of motor vehicles
723105	Installing or adjusting motors and brakes, and adjusting steering or other parts of motor vehicles
723106	Installing, adjusting, servicing and replacing mechatronics components of motor vehicles
723107	Performing scheduled maintenance services, such as oil changes, lubrications and engine tune-ups, to achieve smoother running of vehicles and ensure compliance with pollution regulations
723108	Reassembling engines and parts after being repaired
723201	Fitting, examining, testing and servicing aircraft engines
723202	Replacing engine components or complete engines
723203	Examining and inspecting airframes and aircraft components, including landing gear, hydraulic systems, and deicers to detect wear, cracks, breaks, leaks, or other problems
723204	Maintaining, repairing, overhauling, modifying and testing the aircraft's structure and mechanical and hydraulic systems
723205	Reading and interpreting manuals, service bulletins, and other specifications to determine the feasibility and method of repairing or replacing malfunctioning or damaged components
723206	Maintaining, repairing, and rebuilding aircraft structures, functional components, and parts such as wings and fuselage, rigging, hydraulic units, oxygen systems, fuel systems, electrical systems, gaskets, and seals
723207	Inspecting completed work to certify that maintenance meets standards and the aircraft is ready for operation
723208	Maintaining repair logs, documenting all preventive and corrective aircraft maintenance
723209	Installing and testing electrical and electronic components, assemblies, and systems in aircraft
723210	Connecting components to assemblies such as radio systems, instruments, magnetos, inverters, and in-flight refuelling systems
723301	Fitting, installing, examining, servicing and repairing engines, machinery and mechanical equipment
723302	Greasing stationary engines and machinery
723303	Inspecting and testing new machinery and mechanical equipment for conformity with standards and specifications
723304	Disassembling machinery and equipment to remove parts and make repairs
723305	Examining parts for defects such as breakage and excessive wear
723306	Operating newly repaired machinery and equipment to verify the adequacy of repairs
723307	Recording repairs and maintenance performed
723401	Examining, servicing and repairing bicycles and other non-motorized transport equipment

Code	Task
723402	Cleaning and lubricating bearings and other moving parts
723403	Replacing and repairing components and accessories, such as brakes, driving chain mechanism, wheels, handle bars etc.
723404	Changing tyres and controlling air pressure
723405	Spray painting frames
723406	Assembling new bicycles, wheelchairs and similar non-motorized equipment
731101	Repairing, cleaning, and adjusting mechanisms of timing instruments, such as watches and clocks
731102	Adjusting timing regulators, using calipers, watch-rate recorders, and tweezers
731103	Cleaning, rinsing, and drying timepiece parts, using solutions and ultrasonic or mechanical watch-cleaning machines
731104	Testing timepiece accuracy and performance, using meters and other electronic instruments
731105	Testing accuracy of meters, gauges, indicators, or other recording or controlling instruments to locate defective components and for conformance to standards
731106	Calibrating instruments or scales, using hand tools, computer, or electronic devices
731107	Inspecting components, connections, and drive mechanisms to detect defects
731108	Assembling instruments and devices, such as barometers, control valves, gyroscopes, hygrometers, speedometers, tachometers, and thermostats
731109	Testing, calibrating, and adjusting electronic, mercurial, aneroid, and other types of meteorological instruments for compliance with printed specifications and schematic diagrams, using voltmeters, oscilloscopes, and other test instruments
731110	Adjusting and repairing masts, supporting structures, clearance lights, control panels, control cabling and wiring, and other electrical and mechanical devices
731111	Repairing and setting optical instruments such as microscopes, telescopes, theodolites, sextants
731112	Checking whether assembled units conform to specifications and ensuring stipulated performance and sensitivity by standard tests
731201	Fabricating and assembling musical instruments and instrument parts of wood, metal, leather and other materials
731202	Repairing or replacing musical instrument parts and components, such as strings, bridges, felts, and keys, using hand and power tools
731203	Playing and inspecting instruments to evaluate their sound quality and to locate any defects
731204	Adjusting string tensions to achieve proper tone or pitch of stringed instruments
731205	Adjusting lips, reeds, or toe hole of organ pipes, using hand tools, to regulate airflow and loudness of sound
731206	Tuning and servicing pipe organs by adjusting organ pipes to conform with pitch of tuning fork and adjusting other pipes with reference to tuned pipes
731207	Installing new drumheads in percussion instruments
731208	Tuning accordions by aurally comparing pitch of reeds with master reeds and filing reeds to obtain standard pitch
731209	Aligning pads and keys on reed or wind instruments
731210	Tuning percussion instruments to required pitch by tightening or loosening cords holding leather pieces fixed atop or at both ends of instrument
731211	Assembling and installing new pipe organs and pianos in buildings
731301	Casting jewellery and other non-ferrous metal articles by hand
731302	Creating new jewellery designs and modifying existing designs, using computers as necessary
731303	Cutting designs in moulds to be used in the fabrication of metal and jewellery products
731304	Altering existing jewellery mountings in order to reposition jewels or to adjust mountings
731305	Repairing, reshaping and restyling old jewellery or precious metal ware following designs or instructions

Code	Task
731306	Making complete jewellery articles such as rings, necklaces, bangles, brooches and bracelets from materials such as gold, silver, platinum, and precious or semiprecious stones
731307	Examining gem surfaces and internal structures, using polariscopes, refractometers, microscopes, and other optical instruments, to differentiate between stones, to identify rare specimens, or to detect flaws, defects, or peculiarities affecting gem values
731308	Cutting and polishing gems and setting them in jewellery articles
731309	Engraving or embossing letters, designs or decorative lines on jewellery and precious metal ware
731310	Grinding, drilling and finishing jewel bearings for use in precision instruments such as compasses and chronometers
731311	Examining assembled or finished products to ensure conformance to specifications, using magnifying glasses or precision measuring instruments
731401	Making articles of pottery and porcelain
731402	Making clay or plaster moulds
731403	Reading technical drawings to know customer's requirements
731404	Forming articles on potter's wheel by pressing thumbs into centres of revolving clay to form hollows, and press on the inside and outside of emerging clay cylinders with hands and fingers, gradually raising and shaping
731405	Adjusting wheel speeds according to the feel of the clay as pieces enlarge and walls become thinner
731406	Operating jigger machines to form ceramic ware, such as bowls, cups, plates, and saucers
731407	Adjusting and setting controls of pug mill that mixes, extrudes, cuts, and deposits clay charges in or over moulds as specified
731408	Smoothing surfaces of finished pieces, using rubber scrapers and wet sponges
731409	Forming abrasive wheels by moulding and pressing an abrasive mixture by hand or by machine
731410	Examining finished ware for defects, verifying accuracy of shapes and sizes of objects, using callipers and templates
731411	Preparing work for sale or exhibition, and maintaining relationships with retail, pottery, art, and resource networks
731501	Heating glass to pliable stage, using gas flames or ovens, and rotating glass to heat it uniformly
731502	Blowing and bending glass tubing into specified shapes to form scientific apparatus like flasks, retorts, pipettes
731503	Grinding and polishing glass objects or parts to correct defects or to prepare surfaces for further finishing and smoothing and polishing rough edges, using belt sander or polishing wheels
731504	Examining glass stock and finished products and marking or discarding items with defects such as spots, stains, scars, snags, chips, scratches, or unacceptable shapes or finishes
731505	Reading work orders to determine dimensions, cutting locations, and quantities to cut
731506	Observing gauges, computer printouts and video monitors to verify specified processing conditions and make adjustments as necessary
731507	Positioning pattern or drawing on glass, measuring dimensions, and marking cutting lines, using glass cutting tools and cutting glass along marked outlines or around pattern
731508	Setting up, operating and adjusting computerized or robotic glass cutting equipment
731509	Inspecting, weighing, and measuring products to verify conformance to specifications, using instruments such as micrometers, callipers, magnifiers, and rulers
731510	Regulating oven temperatures according to glass types to be processed
731511	Transferring pattern for individual stained glass parts from full size drawing to pattern paper, using stylus to trace drawings
731512	Spraying silver solution on glass to provide mirrored surface, using spray gun
731513	Laying out, cutting and grinding optical and other glass to specified dimensions, weight for moulding into lens blanks and for use as watch crystals
731601	Painting decorative free-hand designs on objects, such as pottery, glass, (cigarette) cases, lampshades

Code	Task
731602	Transferring from paper decorative or ornamental designs on articles
731603	Integrating and developing visual elements, such as line, space, mass, colour, and perspective, in order to produce desired effects such as the illustration of ideas, emotions, or moods
731604	Laying out and painting in one or more languages letters, figures, monograms and designs to make signs
731605	Sketching or tracing design or lettering onto work piece or pattern material to prepare pattern or stencil
731606	Designing pattern or lettering to paint work pieces, such as signs, glassware, pottery, or zinc plates
731607	Using software and routing equipment to produce 3D carved images for application onto larger signage as well as engraved and inlaid signs
731608	Designing and producing normal flat cut lettering, lettering that is shadowed or lettering that is ready cut for application
731609	Writing, painting, or printing signs or show cards used for display or other purposes
731610	Cutting out letters and signs for display purposes from wallboard or cardboard, by hand or machines, such as electrically powered jigsaw or bandsaw
731611	Examining sketches, diagrams, samples, blueprints, or photographs to decide how designs are to be etched, cut, or engraved onto work pieces
731612	Measuring and computing dimensions of lettering, designs, or patterns to be engraved
731613	Engraving and printing patterns, ornamental designs, etchings, trademarks, figures or lettering onto flat or curved surfaces of a wide variety of metal, glass, plastic, or ceramic items
731614	Etching decorative designs, calibration markings and other figures on glass articles
731701	Preparing wood, straw, rattan, reeds, stone, shells, or similar materials
731702	Carving floral and artistic designs on wooden surfaces for decorative purposes
731703	Painting free hand decorative designs on glass and pottery or porcelain ware
731704	Carving, assembling, weaving, painting and decorating various articles for personal or household use such as salad bowls, serving-spoons, cutting-boards, trays, vases, jugs, baskets, straw hats, straw mats and similar objects
731705	Carving, assembling, weaving and painting various decorative articles such as statues and other sculptures, chess pieces, jewellery, and similar objects
731706	Making wicker furniture from rattan, reeds, rushes, willow branches and similar materials
731707	Making various kinds of baskets by interlacing osier, rattan, reeds, rushes or similar materials
731708	Forming bottom of basket by interlacing strips of rattan, wood veneer or other material with framework of rods of material such as willow
731709	Inserting rods around edge of bottom between woven sections of bottom and bending them upright to serve as framework for sides
731710	Selecting and preparing brush materials, such as bristles, nylon, fibres and wire, and setting them in brush base
731711	Fastening brush base to broom handles
731801	Spinning and dyeing with natural dyestuffs, wool, cotton and other fibres
731802	Lace-making and weaving, knitting, or embroidering various garments and articles for household use
731803	Preparing and dyeing hides with natural dyestuffs and making traditional footwear or handbags, belts and other accessories
731804	Spinning and winding yarn by hand
731805	Drawing warp threads into loom by hand
731806	Weaving plain or figured cloth, tapestry, lace, carpet or other fabrics on hand looms
731807	Making carpets by using a knotting technique
731808	Knitting garments and other articles on hand-operated machine or by hand
731809	Crocheting or making braid by hand
731810	Making nets by hand

Code	Task
731811	Grading and classifying natural textile fibres
731812	Washing wool fibres
731813	Cleaning and fluffing textile fibres
731814	Forming fibres into sliver, combing them, combining sliver into sliver laps
732101	Operating graphic cameras and other photographic equipment to reproduce camera-ready copy onto films, plates and digital output devices
732102	Using computer applications to generate images, text, layouts and impositions for print and other visual media displays
732103	Operating plate making equipment to reproduce images from film to printing plates, digital output devices and presses
732104	Operating computer screen-based equipment for scanning, colour separation, colour correction, masking, creative design, combining, imposing, retouching, and other processes used to transfer copy to film and produce film for plate, digital output and cylinder productions
732105	Carrying out digital and chemical proofing from digital systems, and negative and positive films
732106	Evaluating printed proofs, checking and correcting them for quality
732107	Preparing and exposing carbon tissue for laying on cylinders by transfer method, and developing images
732201	Setting, adjusting and monitoring substrate-feed mechanisms, delivery mechanisms, inking systems and other printing machine functions
732202	Mixing ink and solvents to standard, and regulating paper and ink supply during print runs
732203	Monitoring, evaluating and determining press to check print quality standards against proofs and detect malfunctions
732204	Producing a variety of printed products using relief, lithographic, flexographic and gravure printing presses, and in-line finishing systems
732205	Preparing plates, blankets and impression cylinders on small offset lithographic printing presses
732206	Loading paper into feeding mechanisms
732207	Monitoring machine operations and quality of printing
732208	Maintaining, adjusting, repairing and cleaning machines
732209	Producing digital print images, and transferring and outputting images
732301	Setting up and supervising the operation of automatic binding and finishing equipment
732302	Binding books full and half, and repairing bindings
732303	Folding, collating and sewing signatures by machine and hand
732304	Operating paper guillotines for pre-press and post-press paper cutting and trimming, and programming electronically operated units
732305	Operating systems to insert printed material into newspapers, magazines and envelopes
732306	Embellishing printed products automatically and manually
732307	Operating photographic and electronic reproduction devices
741101	Installing, maintaining and repairing electrical wiring systems and related equipment in various buildings such as schools, hospitals, commercial establishments, residential buildings and other structures
741102	Examining blueprints, wiring diagrams and specifications to determine sequences and methods of operation
741103	Planning layout and installation of electrical wiring, equipment and fixtures, based on job specifications and relevant standards
741104	Inspecting electrical systems, equipment, and components to identify hazards, defects, and the need for adjustment or repair
741105	Selecting, cutting and connecting wire and cable to terminals and connectors
741106	Measuring and laying out installation reference points
741107	Positioning and installing electrical switchboards
741108	Testing continuity of circuit

Code	Task
741201	Fitting, adjusting and repairing various kinds of electrical machinery and motors, generators, switchgear and control apparatus, instruments, or electrical parts of elevators and related equipment
741202	Fitting, adjusting and repairing electrical parts in domestic appliances, industrial machines and other appliances
741203	Inspecting and testing manufactured electrical products
741204	Installing, testing, connecting, commissioning, maintaining and modifying electrical equipment, wiring and control systems
741205	Designing, installing, maintaining, servicing and repairing electric and hydraulic passenger and freight lifts, escalators, moving walkways and other lift equipment
741206	Connecting electrical systems to power supply
741207	Replacing and repairing defective parts
741301	Installing and repairing overhead and underground electrical power and electrical traction lines
741302	Making joints in overhead and underground cables
741303	Adhering to safety practices and procedures, such as checking equipment regularly and erecting barriers around work areas
741304	Opening switches or attaching grounding devices to remove electrical hazards from disturbed or fallen lines or to facilitate repairs
741305	Climbing poles or using truck-mounted buckets to access equipment
741306	Identifying defective sectionalizing devices, circuit breakers, fuses, voltage regulators, transformers, switches, relays, or wiring, using wiring diagrams and electrical-testing instruments
742101	Examining and testing machines, instruments, components, other equipment and control systems to identify faults
742102	Adjusting, repairing, and replacing worn and defective parts and wiring, and maintaining machines, equipment and instruments
742103	Reassembling, test operating and adjusting equipment
742104	Installing electronic instruments and control systems
742105	Coordinating work with that of engineers, technicians, and other maintenance personnel
742106	Interpreting test data to diagnose malfunctions and systemic performance problems
742107	Installing, adjusting, repairing or replacing electrical and electronic components, assemblies, and systems using hand tools, power tools, or soldering irons
742108	Connecting components to assemblies such as radio systems, instruments, magnetos, inverters, and in-flight refuelling systems
742109	Keeping records of maintenance and repair work
742201	Maintaining, troubleshooting, testing and repairing computers, data transmission equipment and computer peripherals
742202	Fitting and adjusting computer hardware
742203	Installing, maintaining, repairing, and diagnosing malfunctions of microwave, telemetry, multiplexing, satellite and other radio and electromagnetic wave communications systems
742204	Providing technical advice and information, and monitoring the performance of complex telecommunications networks and equipment
742205	Installing and repairing cabling for computer, radio, telephone and television transmission
742206	Joining telecommunications and data cables and sealing sheathes
742207	Installing, maintaining and repairing antennae used in communications
751101	Slaughtering animals
751102	Flaying and trimming carcasses
751103	Boning, cutting and dressing meat and fish for sale or further processing
751104	Preparing ingredients and making sausages and similar products using chopping, mixing and shaping machines

Code	Task
751105	Curing meat, fish and other foods
751106	Operating smokehouses or ovens to smoke meat, fish and other foodstuffs
751107	Cooking or in other ways preparing meat, fish and related food items for sale
751108	Selling meat or fish to customers, including wrapping, weighing and labelling products, and receiving payment
751201	Making bread, cakes, biscuits, pastries, pies and other flour products
751202	Making handmade confectionery from mixtures of sugar, chocolate and other ingredients using hand tools and some machines
751203	Combining measured ingredients in bowls of mixing, blending, or cooking machinery
751204	Checking the quality of raw materials to ensure that standards and specifications are met
751205	Applying glazes, icings, or other toppings to baked goods, using spatulas or brushes
751206	Checking the cleanliness of equipment and operation of premises before production runs to ensure compliance with occupational health and safety regulations
751207	Monitoring oven temperatures and product appearance
751208	Coordinating the forming, loading, baking, unloading, de-panning and cooling of batches of bread, rolls, pastry and confectionary products
751301	Boiling or pasteurizing milk to achieve specified butter fat content
751302	Separating cream from milk and churning cream into butter
751303	Dumping measured amounts of starter and other ingredients into milk
751304	Curdling milk, heating curd until it reaches desired firmness, draining curd and placing cheese into moulds to press it into shape
751305	Salting cheese and piercing or smearing cheese with cultured wash to develop mould growth
751306	Placing and turning cheese blocks on shelves to cure cheese
751307	Monitoring product quality before packaging by inspecting, taking samples and adjusting treatment conditions when necessary
751308	Recording amounts of ingredients used, test results, and time cycles
751401	Extracting juices from various fruits
751402	Extracting oils from oil-bearing seeds, nuts or fruits
751403	Cooking, salting or drying fruit, vegetables and related foods
751404	Mixing and adding ingredients such as pectin, sugar, spices and vinegar to assist preservation and enhance texture, appearance and flavour
751405	Transferring preserved foods to sterile jars, bottles or other containers
751501	Inspecting, testing, tasting and smelling agricultural products, food and beverages at various stages of processing
751502	Determining quality, acceptability to consumer tastes and approximate value of products and grading them into appropriate classes
751503	Discarding inferior products
751504	Recording the grade and/or identification numbers on tags, receiving, or sales sheets
751505	Weighing and measuring products
751601	Grading cured tobacco leaves by type, quality and locality where grown
751602	Mixing tobacco leaves according to formula to obtain a blend of distinct flavour
751603	Tending vacuum container which moistens tobacco for further processing
751604	Removing midribs and stalks from tobacco leaves and shredding tobacco
751605	Making cigars, cigarettes, snuff and other tobacco products by hand or with simple machines
752101	Operating and tending kilns, treating tanks and other equipment to dry lumber, prepare and season wood and other wood products, and to treat chemically and impregnate wood products with preservatives

Code	Task
752102	Monitoring equipment operation, gauges, and panel lights in order to detect deviations from standards and to ensure that processes are operating according to specifications
752103	Assisting in maintaining processing equipment and machines as required
752104	Cleaning, lubricating and adjusting equipment
752105	Transporting materials and products to and from work areas, manually or using carts, hand trucks, or hoists
752106	Completing and maintaining production reports
752201	Operating woodworking machines, such as power saws, jointers, mortisers and shapers, and using hand tools to cut, shape and form parts and components
752202	Studying plans, verifying dimensions of articles to be made, or preparing specifications and checking the quality and fit of pieces in order to ensure adherence to specifications
752203	Trimming joints and fitting parts and subassemblies together to form complete units using glue and clamps, and reinforcing joints using nails, screws or other fasteners
752204	Making, restyling and repairing various wooden articles, such as cabinets, furniture, vehicles, scale models, sports equipment and other parts or products
752205	Decorating furniture and fixtures by inlaying wood, applying veneer and carving designs
752206	Finishing surfaces of wooden articles or furniture
752301	Setting-up, programming, operating and monitoring several types of woodworking machines for sawing, shaping, boring, drilling, planing, pressing, turning, sanding or carving to fabricate or repair wooden parts for furniture, fixtures and other wooden products
752302	Operating preset special-purpose woodworking machines to fabricate wooden products such as coat hangers, mop handles, clothes pins and other products
752303	Selecting knives, saws, blades, cutter heads, cams, bits or belts according to workpiece, machine functions and product specifications
752304	Installing and adjusting blades, cutter heads, bits or belts, using hand tools
752305	Setting and adjusting various kinds of woodworking machines for operation by others
752306	Reading and interpreting specifications or following verbal instructions
753101	Making overcoats, suits, skirts, shirts, blouses, lingerie, corsetry, hats, wigs and similar garments often to clients' individual requirements
753102	Selecting textile fabrics, leather or fur pelts matching the desired size, colour, texture, and quality of the garment, cutting to shape them to garment pattern and arranging them on pattern according to the design
753103	Making garment style changes, such as tapering trouser legs, narrowing lapels, and adding or removing padding
753104	Selecting and modifying commercial patterns to customers and clothing manufacturer's specifications and fit
753105	Fitting, altering and repairing tailored clothing, dresses, coats and other garments according to customers' requests
753106	Making and caring for costumes used in theatrical, television and motion picture productions
753107	Folding, twisting, and draping material, such as satin or silk, or sewing ribbon or cloth in the form of artificial flowers or bows around crown and brim to shape and decorate hats
753108	Sewing, and fastening together materials and hair strands to make wigs
753109	Blending shades of hair to give natural appearance to wigs and arranging woven hair in specified position and sewing hair together to form hairpiece
753110	Making, altering, restyling and repairing fur garments and other fur articles
753111	Reclaiming furs or skins from old coats, gluing fabric to interior of fur coats and trimming fur garments
753201	Creating a master pattern for each size within a range of garment sizes, using charts, drafting instruments, computers, and/or grading devices
753202	Creating the blueprint or pattern pieces for a particular apparel design with the aid of a computer
753203	Calculating dimensions of patterns according to sizes, considering stretching of material

Code	Task
753204	Drawing details on outlined parts to indicate where parts are to be joined, as well as the positions of pleats, pockets and buttonholes, decorative stitching on shoe parts or eyelets on canvas products, using computers or drafting instruments
753205	Positioning templates or measuring materials to locate specified points of cuts or to obtain maximum yields and mark fabric accordingly
753206	Laying out master pattern on fabric and cutting sample pattern
753207	Testing patterns by making and fitting sample garments
753208	Placing patterns on top of layers of fabric and cutting fabric following patterns, using electric or manual knives, cutters or computer numerically controlled cutting devices
753209	Cutting fabric or fur pelts to make parts for garments and other fur articles
753210	Trimming excess material or cutting threads off finished products, such as cutting loose ends of a finished product
753211	Positioning leather on cutting bed of machine, maximizing usage according to skin grain, skin flaws and skin stretch
753212	Performing patternmaking, marking and cutting tasks in the manufacture of other products such as soft furnishings and canvas goods
753301	Repairing defective or damaged portion of cloth or garment by hand, using matching thread and needle
753302	Removing stitches from garments to be altered, using rippers or razor blades
753303	Selecting thread to match colour and shade of cloth to be darned
753304	Patching holes, sewing tears and ripped seams
753305	Pulling knots to the wrong sides of garments, using hooks
753306	Trimming ends with scissors to make mended portion look uniform with pattern of cloth
753307	Sewing ornamental designs by hand over stamped, printed or stencilled patterns on fabric using needle and coloured thread
753308	Embroidering ornamental designs on cloth by hand or machine using needle and coloured threads
753309	Softening leather or shoe material with water to prepare it for sewing
753310	Sewing or gluing decorative trimmings to articles, such as hats, caps, or millinery
753311	Hand sewing umbrella covers to frames, tacking cover to ribs along seams and sewing corners to tip of rib and sewing ties to outside of cover to hold umbrella when folded
753312	Fabricating and assembling thick cloth, canvas and like materials into sails, awning, tarpaulins and tents
753401	Discussing upholstery fabric, colour, and style with customers and providing cost estimate for upholstering furniture or other items
753402	Making upholstery patterns from sketches, customer descriptions or blueprints
753403	Laying out, measuring and cutting upholstery materials following patterns, templates, sketches, or design specifications
753404	Installing, arranging and securing springs, padding and covering material to furniture frames
753405	Sewing upholstery materials by hand to seam cushions and joining sections of covering materials
753406	Sewing rips or tears in material by hand
753407	Tacking, gluing or sewing ornamental trims, buckles, braids, buttons and other accessories to covers or frames on upholstered items
753408	Laying out, cutting, fabricating and installing upholstery in aircrafts, motor vehicles, railway cars, boats and ships
753409	Repairing raw hide covering of artificial limbs
753410	Renovating antique furniture using a variety of tools including ripping chisels, magnetic hammers and long needles
753411	Collaborating with interior designers to decorate rooms and coordinate furnishing fabrics
753412	Making quilts, cushions and mattresses

Code	Task
753501	Sorting and grading pelts, hides and skins according to colour, shading, size and density
753502	Scraping particles of flesh, fat, or protective tissue from skins or pelts to clean and soften them
753503	Removing hair from skin or hides soaked in lime water
753504	Preparing hides by curing them with salt
753505	Removing long, coarse hair from pelts and trimming underlying hair to even length
753506	Tanning and dressing pelts to improve lustre and beauty or restore natural appearance of pelts
753507	Preparing bark liquor for treating hides or skins
753508	Treating hides and skins in tanning solution to convert them into leather
753509	Tinting or dyeing furs to enhance natural shades of fur
753510	Removing wrinkles and setting grains on wet hide or skin
753511	Dressing and applying dyes and stains to leather
753512	Stretching and smoothing dressed pelts
753513	Seasoning leather by applying chemical solution or oil evenly on surface by hand brush and allowing it to dry in open air
753601	Making, modifying and repairing standard footwear to meet individual requirements
753602	Making, modifying and repairing orthopaedic or therapeutic footwear according to doctors' prescriptions, or modifying existing footwear for people with foot problems and special needs
753603	Repairing belts, luggage, purses and similar products
753604	Taking plaster casts of deformed legs or foot to prepare drawings
753605	Preparing inserts, heel pads, and lifts from casts of customers' feet
753606	Studying drawings and other specifications to make footwear according to customer's needs
753607	Studying work orders and/or shoe part tags to obtain information about workloads, specifications, and the types of materials to be used
753608	Checking the texture, colour, and strength of leather to ensure that it is adequate for a particular purpose
753609	Cutting out, shaping and padding parts for making leather articles
753610	Sewing rips or patching holes to repair articles, such as purses, belts, shoes, and luggage
753611	Removing and examining shoes, shoe parts, and designs to verify conformance to specifications such as proper embedding of stitches in channels
753612	Attaching accessories or ornamentation to decorate or protect products
753613	Making and repairing articles such as saddles and harnesses for animals, luggage, handbags, briefcases, leather bags, belts and other accessories
754101	Taking safety precautions, such as monitoring dive lengths and depths, and registering with authorities before diving expeditions begin
754102	Checking and maintaining diving equipment such as helmets, masks, air tanks, diving suits, harnesses and gauges
754103	Descending into water with the aid of diver helpers, using scuba gear or diving suits
754104	Working under water to lay and repair bridges, piers and harbour-wall foundations
754105	Inspecting for suspected damage and making minor repairs to ships' hulls and underwater installations
754106	Reporting on condition of wrecked ships
754107	Removing underwater obstructions
754108	Drilling holes for underwater blasting
754109	Performing various underwater tasks connected with salvage work or recovering dead bodies
754110	Communicating with workers on the surface while underwater, using signal lines or telephones
754111	Obtaining information about diving tasks and environmental conditions

Code	Task
754201	Ensuring workplace safety and explosives handling, storage and transport procedures and regulations are followed
754202	Planning and giving instructions for the lay out, depth and diameter of blast holes
754203	Checking depth and cleanliness of blast holes
754204	Determining quantity and type of explosives to be used
754205	Loading explosives into blast holes
754206	Assembling, or directing other workers to assemble, primer charges using detonators and explosive cartridges, and attaching electrical wires, fuses and detonating cords to primers
754207	Connecting wires, fuses and detonator cords into series, testing electrical circuits and repairing malfunctions, and connecting series to blasting machines
754208	Covering charges, filling blast holes with rock dust, sand and other materials, and tamping material to compact charges
754209	Ensuring all explosives are detonated, and reporting and attending to misfires
754210	Declaring blast areas safe after detonation of explosives
754211	Compiling and maintaining records about usage of explosives in compliance with laws and regulations
754301	Inspecting and testing products, parts and materials for conformity with specifications and standards
754302	Grading and classifying natural textile fibres for spinning and winding
754303	Discarding or rejecting products, materials, and equipment not meeting specifications
754304	Analysing and interpreting blueprints, data, manuals, and other materials to determine specifications, inspection and testing procedures
754305	Notifying supervisors and other personnel of production problems, and assisting in identifying and correcting these problems
754306	Recording inspection or test data, such as weights, temperatures, grades, or moisture content, and quantities inspected or graded
754307	Marking items with details such as grade and acceptance or rejection status
754308	Measuring dimensions of products using instruments such as rulers, calipers, gauges, or micrometers
754309	Analysing test data and making computations as necessary to determine test results
754401	Operating and monitoring equipment for spraying pests and weeds
754402	Mixing chemicals according to instructions
754403	Covering areas to specified depths with pesticides, applying knowledge of weather conditions, droplet sizes, elevation-to-distance ratios, and obstructions
754404	Spraying or releasing chemical solutions or toxic gases and setting traps to kill pests and vermin, such as mice, termites, and roaches
754405	Lifting, pushing, and swinging nozzles, hoses, and tubes in order to direct spray over designated areas
754406	Filling sprayer tanks with water and chemicals
754407	Cleaning and servicing machinery to ensure operating efficiency
754901	Heating, moulding and pressing optical glass to make lens blanks
754902	Grinding and polishing lens blanks
811101	Positioning, operating and monitoring the performance of a variety of underground and surface mining equipment including continuous mining, cutting and channelling plant
811102	Setting up and operating drilling equipment in underground and surface mines and quarries
811103	Operating machinery and using tools to remove loosened rock, ore, coal and other deposits
811104	Preparing, fitting and installing supports in underground workings
811105	Operating machinery to open new shafts, drives, air vents and rises
811106	Operating auxiliary plant such as pumps to expel air, water and mud
811107	Performing minor maintenance and repairs and lubricating and cleaning plant, machines and tools

Code	Task
811108	Completing records detailing operations completed during shifts
811109	Collecting mineral samples for laboratory analysis
811201	Setting up and operating stationary plant and machinery which grind, crush, cut, saw and slice rocks, minerals and stones according to the specifications for the job
811202	Positioning blocks and slabs of stone onto machines for sawing, cutting and further working
811203	Monitoring and maintaining the flow of unprocessed rocks, minerals and stones from conveyors into machines
811204	Operating washing, separating, leaching, precipitating, filtering, extracting and combining equipment to remove waste material and recover minerals
811205	Combining mineral ores with solvents to facilitate further processing
811206	Separating metal and mineral concentrates from ore and alluvial deposits by thickening, flotation, gravity separation, filtration, and or magnetic and electrostatic separation
811207	Observing meters, gauges and control panels, and adjusting valves and controls to ensure the safe and efficient operation of equipment, and detecting malfunctions, and assisting with plant and machinery maintenance and repair
811208	Examining processed materials visually or with hands to ensure compliance with established standards and job specifications, and collect samples for testing in laboratories
811209	Recording information about processing completed during shifts, such as quantities, types and dimensions of materials produced
811210	Sorting, stacking and moving processed minerals and stone for packaging, further processing or shipping
811301	Dismantling, moving and assembling drilling rigs and auxiliary equipment
811302	Assembling and dismantling pipes, casings and drill heads, and replacing dysfunctional equipment
811303	Operating controls to lower and raise drill pipes and casings in and out of wells, regulate pressure in the well and control the speed of tools
811304	Preparing drilling fluid and checking the operation of pumps to ensure adequate circulation of fluid in drill pipe and well
811305	Monitoring gauges and other indicators and listening to equipment to detect malfunctions and unusual well conditions, and determining the need to change drilling or equipment
811306	Maintaining, adjusting, repairing and cleaning drilling rigs, hoisting and other machinery
811307	Maintaining records of drilling and servicing operations
811308	Operating machines and tools to extract dust, cuttings and lost and broken drilling equipment from holes and wells
811309	Closing and sealing wells no longer in use
811310	Supervise and train crew members
811401	Operating extrusion, moulding, mixing, pumping, compacting, grinding and cutting machinery to manufacture and finish precast concrete and stone products
811402	Operating plant to produce cement, lime and clinker, including loading and unloading ingredients and operating continuous feed equipment such as pumps and conveyors
811403	Operating plant and machines which weigh and mix sand, gravel, cement, water and other ingredients to make concrete
811404	Operating plant and machinery which assemble and fill moulds with concrete and artificial stone mixtures, remove castings from moulds and finish surfaces of precast products
811405	Cutting, grinding, drilling, sandblasting and polishing concrete products and stone blocks, slabs and products to the specifications for the job
811406	Checking production plans and specifications to determine and select materials, ingredients, procedures, components, settings and adjustments for extrusion, moulding, mixing and compacting machines
811407	Monitoring plant and machines during operation by observing temperature and pressure gauges, and adjusting controls and reporting malfunctions as necessary
811408	Collecting and examining samples of mixtures and finished products for conformity to specifications and adjusting machine settings accordingly

Code	Task
811409	Checking and maintaining production records, including information about quantities, dimensions and types of materials and goods produced
811410	Arranging and assisting with plant and machinery maintenance and repair
812101	Setting up, preparing and adjusting mineral ore and metal processing machinery to carry out one step in the overall mineral ore or metal processing operation
812102	Operating single-function machinery to grind, separate, filter, mix, treat, cast, roll, refine or otherwise process metals and mineral ores
812103	Observing gauges, meters, computer printouts, video monitors and products to ensure correct operation of machine and verify specified processing conditions
812104	Adjusting equipment, valves, pumps, controls and process equipment
812105	Controlling the preparation, measuring and feeding of raw materials and processing agents into plant
812106	Controlling process start-up and shut-down, troubleshooting and monitoring outside process equipment
812107	Verifying equipment for malfunctions, carrying out routine operating tests and arranging for maintenance
812108	Analysing sample products, performing tests, recording data and writing production logs
812201	Operating and monitoring equipment which cleans metal articles in preparation for galvanising, enamelling or similar processes
812202	Operating and monitoring electroplating equipment
812203	Operating and monitoring hot-dip equipment used to coat iron and steel products
812204	Operating and monitoring machines which coat wire with non ferrous metal
812205	Operating and monitoring equipment used to spray molten metal or other substances on metal products to provide a protective or decorative coating or to build up worn or damaged surfaces
812206	Operating and monitoring equipment used to impart a rust-resistant finish to metal articles by treating them with chemicals and heating them
812207	Checking proper thickness of plating using micrometers, callipers or other devices, recording data and writing production logs
812208	Preparing and mixing metalizing solutions according to formulas or specifications
813101	Setting up, starting, controlling, adjusting and stopping machines and plant
813102	Monitoring reaction processes and transfers of products in conformance with safety procedures
813103	Monitoring meters, gauges and electronic instrumentation on one or more chemical or formulation units, such as mixers, kettles, blenders, dryers, tableting, encapsulation, granulation and coating machines
813104	Measuring, weighing and loading chemical ingredients following formulation cards
813105	Taking samples and performing routine chemical and physical tests of products and recording production data
813106	Cleaning and performing minor repairs to machines and plant
813201	Operating and monitoring equipment which makes photographic film and paper
813202	Operating, monitoring and testing photographic processing and printing equipment, and maintaining operational standards
813203	Preparing exposed film for different processing batches in dark rooms and dark chambers
813204	Inspecting images, films, prints and adjusting settings on print-making equipment to produce required colour, brightness, contrast, number, size and type of prints
813205	Adjusting settings and running automatic developing equipment
813206	Operating equipment to transfer film to video tape or other electronic media
813207	Performing photographic processing related tasks
813208	Operating automatic equipment (in retail establishments) to develop colour negatives, prints and slides
814101	Operating and monitoring machines which knead, mix and blend rubber and rubber compounds for further processing

Code	Task
814102	Operating and monitoring machines which produce sheets of rubber or rubberised fabric by a rolling process
814103	Operating and monitoring machines which extrude compounded rubber or shape vulcanised rubber by moulding
814104	Operating and monitoring machines which build up tires on a form, vulcanise tires and mould or rebuild used tires
814105	Examining outputs for defects and conformity to specifications
814106	Locating defects and repairing worn and faulty tyres by vulcanising or other processes
814201	Operating and monitoring machines which knead and blend compounds to obtain plastic materials
814202	Operating and monitoring machines which shape plastic materials by moulding, extrusion, blowing, cutting and other means
814203	Operating and monitoring machines which laminate plastics and plastic impregnated materials or produce fibreglass
814204	Encasing uncoated wire, cord, cable and optic fibre in plastic
814205	Examining outputs for defects and conformity to specifications
814206	Recycling waste plastic materials
814207	Making artificial eyes and contact lens discs, spectacle frames and plastic parts of orthopaedic appliances
814301	Operating and monitoring machines which glue paper to cardboard, cut it to the required length or cut and crease cardboard or paperboard to form box blanks
814302	Operating and monitoring pressing machines which form drinking cups or other containers from paper, paperboard or cardboard
814303	Operating and monitoring machines which cut, fold and glue paper to make envelopes and paper bags, or bags from other similar materials
815101	Operating and monitoring machines for tearing rags into fibre
815102	Operating and monitoring machines for cleaning and turning woollen yarn waste into fluffed wool
815103	Operating and monitoring machines which combine textile fibres into uniform blends
815104	Operating and monitoring machines which clean and fluff textile fibres, transform them into sliver, or into ribbon
815105	Operating machines for combining several slivers into one of same weight and thickness as the original
815106	Operating and monitoring machines which spin thread and yarn, wind two or more threads onto bobbin, twist two or more strands of yarn or thread into single strands of yarn to increase strength, smoothness and/or uniformity of yarn, or wind yarn or thread from one package to another
815107	Operating and monitoring spinning frame that draws out and twists sliver into yarn
815108	Operating and monitoring machines for drawing slivers received from drawing machine into loosely twisted strands
815109	Stiffening and finishing cloth and yarn by mixing ingredients such as starch, tallow, resins, soaps and water and boiling mixture for specified time
815110	Treating textiles with chemicals to make them water resistant
815111	Cleaning rollers and cylinders of carding machines to remove wool waste
815112	Operating and resurfacing metal drawing rolls of various spinning, combing and lapping machines with new rubber or leather covers
815201	Setting up and operating batteries of automatic, link-type knitting machines to knit garments of specified pattern and design
815202	Threading yarn, thread, and fabric through guides, needles, and rollers of machines for weaving, knitting, or other processing
815203	Tending automatic looms that simultaneously weave pile yarn, filling yarn, and warp yarn material to produce carpets and rugs with various coloured designs
815204	Operating and monitoring loom on which yarn or twist is intersected and knotted at regular intervals to form mesh

Code	Task
815205	Operating and monitoring large automatic multi-needle machines to embroider material or to sew lengths of several layers of material to make yard goods, quilts or mattress coverings
815206	Tending circular knitting machines that knit seamless hose
815207	Operating and monitoring knitting machines to knit hosiery to shape of foot and leg
815208	Operating and monitoring machine for knitting heel and toes of socks into ribs or tops cut from circular fabric
815209	Operating and monitoring machine which seams openings in toes of socks
815210	Operating and monitoring crocheter machine to knit lace, trimming etc. of desired pattern or design
815211	Examining looms to determine causes of loom stoppage
815212	Repairing or replacing worn or defective needles and other components
815213	Cleaning, oiling, and lubricating machines, using air hoses, cleaning solutions, rags, oil cans, and/or grease guns
815301	Operating or tending sewing machines to perform garment sewing operations, such as joining, reinforcing, seaming or decorating garments or garment parts
815302	Attaching buttons, hooks, zippers, fasteners, or other accessories to fabric
815303	Tending semiautomatic sewing machines with multiple-sewing heads controlled by pattern chain that embroiders various designs on garments
815304	Operating machines to automatically join, reinforce, or decorate material or articles
815305	Operating fur sewing machines to join fur pelt strips to required size and shape and join pelts into garment sections
815306	Operating stitching machines to sew leather parts together for leather garments, handbags, gloves
815307	Monitoring machine operation to detect problems such as defective stitching, breaks in thread, or machine malfunctions
815308	Performing equipment maintenance tasks such as replacing needles
815401	Starting and controlling machines and equipment to bleach, dye, or otherwise process and finish fabric, yarn, thread, and/or other textile goods
815402	Tending machines that shrink woven or knitted cloth to predetermined size or strengthen the weave
815403	Tending a variety of automatic machines that comb and polish furs
815404	Operating and monitoring machines that treat silk to give it body and weight
815405	Operating and monitoring machines that impregnate textiles to render them waterproof
815406	Dyeing articles to change or restore their colours
815407	Operating and monitoring machines that stretch, or impart lustre, or other type of finish to textiles
815408	Tending and regulating equipment that fumigates and removes foreign matter from furs
815409	Operating machines that comb, dry and polish furs, clean, sterilize and fluff feathers and blankets
815410	Keying in processing instructions to program electronic equipment
815411	Observing display screens, control panels, equipment, and cloth entering or exiting processes to determine if equipment is operating correctly
815412	Cleaning machine filters and lubricating equipment
815501	Operating and monitoring machines which remove flesh and fat from hides or pelts to clean and soften them prior to processing
815502	Operating and monitoring machines which remove long coarse hair from fur pelts, trim hair to even length and dye, stretch and smooth dressed pelts
815503	Operating and monitoring machines to remove epidermis hair roots, pigment cells and lime salts from skin
815504	Operating and monitoring machines to reduce thickness of hide or skin to uniform size
815505	Operating and monitoring machines to polish or roughen hides or skins to specified finish
815506	Operating and monitoring machines which separate residual wool from skins, or flesh and hair from hides

Code	Task
815507	Operating and monitoring machines in which hides are split edgeways
815508	Operating and monitoring machines which treat hides and skins in solutions to convert them into leather
815509	Treating surface of leather with oil and operating glazing machine to give glossy finish to leather
815510	Operating and monitoring machines which apply dyes and stains to leather
815511	Maintaining and repairing machinery
815601	Operating and monitoring machines which mark patterns and cut shoe parts
815602	Operating and monitoring machines which sew shoe parts together, edge, polish, or apply ornaments and perform finishing tasks
815603	Operating and monitoring machines which produce luggage, handbags, belts and other accessories, as well as other items such as saddles, collars or harnesses
815701	Sorting articles for cleaning according to the type colour, fabric and cleaning treatment required
815702	Placing sorted articles into receptacles and onto conveyor belts for moving to repair and cleaning areas
815703	Checking and removing stains from garments, and replacing buttons and making minor repairs
815704	Loading and unloading washing machines, driers and extractors
815705	Adding cleaning agents and starches to articles
815706	Smoothing articles and guiding them through cleaning and pressing machines
815707	Stopping and starting machines to untangle, straighten and remove articles
815708	Placing articles on shelves and hanging articles for delivery and collection
815709	Packaging articles and preparing orders for despatch
815901	Operating and monitoring machines which form and make hats out of textiles, fur or leather
815902	Operating and monitoring machines which make miscellaneous articles such as braids or other trimmings
815903	Operating and monitoring machines that fold cloth into measured length
815904	Operating and monitoring machines that wind thread, twine, or yarn into balls preparatory to shipping or further processing
815905	Operating and monitoring machines to measure size of pieces of leather
816001	Operating and monitoring machinery used to restrain, stun, slaughter animals and trim carcasses into standard meat and fish cuts
816002	Setting, operating and attending machinery and ovens to mix, bake and otherwise prepare bread and flour confectionery products
816003	Operating machinery to crush, mix, malt, cook and ferment grains and fruits to produce beer, wines, malt liquors, vinegar, yeast and related products
816004	Attending equipment to make jam, toffee, cheese, processed cheese, margarine, syrup, ice, pasta, ice-cream, sausages, chocolate, maize starch, edible fats and dextrin
816005	Operating equipment to cool, heat, dry, roast, blanch, pasteurize, smoke, sterilize, freeze, evaporate and concentrate foodstuffs and liquids used in food processing
816006	Mixing, pulping, grinding, blending and separating foodstuffs and liquids with appropriate equipment
816007	Processing tobacco leaves by machine to make cigarettes, cigars, pipe and other tobacco products
817101	Co-ordinating and monitoring from automated panel boards in control rooms the operation of screening equipment, washing equipment, digesters, mixing tanks and other equipment of wood, scrap, recyclable paper and other cellulose materials
817102	Operating and monitoring screening equipment, bleaching equipment, digesters, mixing tanks, washers and other machinery to carry out one or more cellulose processing steps
817103	Controlling start-up and shut-down of process machinery and equipment, and observing panel indicators, gauges, level indicators and other instruments to detect malfunctions and ensure process steps are carried out according to specifications
817104	Analysing instrument readings and production test samples and making adjustments to pulp production process and equipment as required

Code	Task
817105	Completing and maintaining production reports
817201	Examining logs and rough lumber to determine size, condition, quality and other characteristics to decide on best lumber cuts, or operating automated equipment conveying logs through laser scanners which determine the most productive and profitable cutting patterns
817202	Operating and monitoring log in-feed and conveyor systems
817203	Operating and monitoring automated lumber mill equipment from control rooms or equipment consoles of head saws, resaws and multiblade saws to saw logs, cants, slabs or wings and remove rough edges from sawn timber into dressed lumber of various sizes, and saw or split shingles and shakes
817204	Operating and monitoring plywood core-laying machines and hot-plate plywood presses and machines which cut veneer
817205	Cleaning and lubricating sawmill equipment
818101	Operating and monitoring glass-making furnaces to make glass by melting and fusing pre-mixed ingredients
818102	Tending hot- or cold-end spray equipment used to coat glassware with surface hardener
818103	Operating and maintaining machines that press or blow molten glass in moulds to form or shape containers, such as bottles, jars and drinking glasses
818104	Operating hand press to mould glass into required shape
818105	Operating drawing kiln to process molten glass into continuous sheet of flat glass
818106	Operating and monitoring floating-glass production plant
818107	Operating and maintaining finishing machines to grind, drill, sand, bevel, decorate, wash or polish glass or glass products
818108	Setting and operating press machines to mould ceramic articles from moist clay
818109	Operating machines to mix clay with water to knead it into a suitable plastic condition or semi-liquid form for making ceramic products
818110	Operating and monitoring kilns which bake pottery, porcelain ware, bricks and tiles
818111	Operating and monitoring machines for making glaze or abrasives
818112	Operating and monitoring machines which extrude molten glass to form fibreglass filaments
818113	Observing finished products to identify splits, cracks, breaks, colour and other imperfections
818201	Operating, cleaning, lubricating and monitoring steam engines, boilers and auxiliary equipment such as pumps, compressors and air-conditioning equipment to supply and maintain steam and power for buildings, marine vessels or pneumatic tools
818202	Analysing and recording instrument readings, troubleshooting and performing minor repairs to prevent equipment or system failure
818203	Monitoring and inspecting performance of equipment for efficient operation and ensuring boiler water, chemical, and fuel levels are maintained at required levels
818204	Firing coal furnaces by hand or with stokers and gas- or oil-fed boilers, using automatic gas feeds or oil pumps
818205	Testing boiler water quality or arrange for testing, adjusting and taking necessary corrective action, such as adding chemicals to prevent corrosion and harmful deposits
818206	Monitoring ship's engine, machinery and equipment indicators, recording variables and reporting abnormalities to ship engineer officer on watch
818207	Operating and maintaining off-loading liquid pumps and valves
818301	Operating and monitoring machines that weigh, wrap, seal and pack various products
818302	Operating and monitoring machines that fill and seal tubes, bottles, cans, boxes, bags and other containers with products, such as food, beverages, paints, oils and lotions
818303	Operating and monitoring machines that, by gluing or other methods, label products, packages and various containers
821101	Assembling and installing prefabricated parts or components to form subassemblies, mechanical machinery, engines and finished motor vehicles

Code	Task
821102	Reviewing work orders, specifications, diagrams and drawings to determine materials needed and assembly instructions
821103	Recording production and operational data on specified forms
821104	Inspecting and testing completed components and assemblies
821105	Rejecting faulty assemblies and components
821201	Assembling component parts and electrical and electronic systems and positioning, aligning and fastening units to assemblies, sub-assemblies, or frames using hand or power tools, soldering and micro-welding equipment
821202	Reviewing work orders, specifications, diagrams and drawings to determine materials needed and assembly instructions
821203	Recording production and operational data on specified forms
821204	Operating wire-coiling machines to wind wire coils used in electrical equipment and components such as registers, transformers, armature wires, electric motors and generators
821205	Inspecting and testing completed components and assemblies, wiring installations and circuits and rejecting faulty assembly components
821901	Assembling component parts and positioning, aligning and fastening units to assemblies, sub-assemblies, or frames using hand or power tools, soldering and micro-welding equipment
821902	Reviewing work orders, specifications, diagrams and drawings to determine materials needed and assembly instructions
821903	Recording production and operational data on specified forms
821904	Inspecting and testing components and completed assemblies
821905	Rejecting faulty products
831101	Driving or assisting in driving a steam, electric or diesel-electric locomotive engine
831102	Driving an underground or elevated passenger train
831103	Driving a locomotive to haul carriages underground or on the surface of a mine or quarry
831104	Watching for track hazards, observing signals and indicator gauges
831105	Operating communications systems to communicate with train crews and traffic controllers to ensure safe operation and scheduling of trains
831201	Taking charge of and safeguarding freight train during run
831202	Controlling flow of railway traffic over section of line by operating signals and switches from control panel or signal box
831203	Switching and coupling rolling stock in railway yards and sidings in accordance with orders about loading, unloading and make-up of trains
831204	Making up trains for hauling by locomotive or cable and directing their movement along haulage ways in a mine or quarry
831205	Checking train systems and equipment such as air conditioning and heating systems, brakes and brake hoses prior to train run
832101	Driving and tending motor cycle or motorised tricycle to transport materials, goods and passengers
832102	Observing traffic rules and signals
832103	Cleaning and washing vehicle as well as performing maintenance and minor repairs
832104	Keeping a record of journeys
832105	Delivering messages
832201	Driving and tending vans, cars or taxis to transport passengers
832202	Driving and tending cars, vans or small trucks to deliver mail or goods
832203	Assisting passengers with handling of luggage
832204	Collecting fares, payments for deliveries, or documents certifying deliveries

Code	Task
832205	Operating telecommunications equipment to report location and availability and follow directions of control centre
832206	Determining most appropriate route
832207	Assisting physically challenged passengers
832208	Operating equipment to facilitate the loading and unloading of physically challenged passengers
833101	Driving and tending motor bus, trolley bus or motor coach to transport local or long-distance passengers, mail or goods
833102	Driving and tending street tramcar transporting passengers
833103	Opening and closing doors before or after passengers board or alight
833104	Assisting passengers with luggage
833105	Controlling lighting, heating and ventilation on buses and trams
833106	Observing traffic to ensure safe progress
833107	Collecting fares or verifying passenger has necessary ticket
833201	Driving and tending a heavy motor vehicle, such as a lorry with or without trailer, to transport goods, liquids or heavy materials over short or long distances
833202	Determining the most appropriate routes
833203	Ensuring goods are stowed and securely covered, to prevent loss and damage
833204	Assisting with or carrying out loading or unloading operations, using various lifting or tipping devices
833205	Carrying out minor maintenance to vehicles, and arranging major maintenance and repairs
833206	Estimating weights to comply with load limitations, and ensuring the safe distribution of weights
834101	Driving and tending tractor-drawn or self-propelled special-purpose farm machinery to plough land and sow, fertilize, cultivate and harvest crops
834102	Driving and tending tractor-drawn or self-propelled special-purpose forestry machinery to clear land, plant, harvest and carry trees and timber or perform other forestry operations
834103	Preparing and positioning plant for operation
834104	Adjusting speed, height and depth of implements
834105	Operating plant to hold, lift and cut trees
834106	Operating attachments to lift, swing, release and sort trees and logs, and operating chipping machines and log splitting machines
834107	Feeding felled trees into processors to strip limbs and cut into logs and loading logs onto stockpiles and into trucks
834108	Servicing machinery and performing minor repairs
834201	Operating and monitoring excavating machinery equipped with moveable shovel, grab-bucket or dragline bucket, to excavate and move earth, rock, sand, gravel or similar materials
834202	Operating and monitoring machinery for digging trenches for sewers, drainage, water, oil, gas or similar pipelines
834203	Operating and monitoring machinery equipped with concave steel blade to move, distribute and level earth, sand, snow and other materials
834204	Operating and monitoring equipment to remove sand, gravel and mud from bottom of body of water
834205	Operating and monitoring machines for hammering wooden, concrete or steel piles into ground
834206	Operating and monitoring power roller to compact and smooth layers of materials in making roads, pavements and similar work
834207	Operating and monitoring machines which spread and smooth concrete or bituminous or tar preparations to construct roadways, roads or similar surfaces
834301	Operating and monitoring stationary or mobile cranes to lift, move, position or place equipment and materials

Code	Task
834302	Operating and monitoring equipment for hoisting, lowering or raising workers and materials on construction sites or in mines
834303	Operating and monitoring ski-lifts and similar equipment
834304	Operating and monitoring machinery used to haul ferry or barge with goods, passengers and vehicles across short stretches of water
834305	Operating and monitoring machinery to open and close bridges
834306	Operating and monitoring cranes equipped with dredging attachments to dredge waterways and other areas
834307	Operating cranes mounted on boats or barges to lift, move and place equipment and materials
834401	Operating and monitoring lifting-truck and similar equipment to load and unload, transport, lift and stack goods and pallets in terminals, harbours, ware-houses, factories and other establishments
834402	Positioning lifting devices under, over, or around loaded pallets, skids and boxes, and securing material or products for transport to designated areas
834403	Inspecting equipment to identify wear and damage
834404	Performing routine maintenance on vehicles and equipment
834405	Keeping records of work undertaken and breakdowns of vehicles
835001	Standing look-out watches at sea and when entering or leaving harbour or other narrow waters
835002	Steering ship according to instructions
835003	Handling ropes and wires, and operating mooring equipment
835004	Maintaining and, in some cases, operating ship's equipment, cargo gear, rigging, life-saving and fire- fighting appliances
835005	Performing deck and hull cleaning, scraping, painting and other maintenance duties as required
835006	Breaking out, rigging and stowing cargo-handling gear, stationary rigging and running gear
911101	Sweeping, vacuum-cleaning, polishing and washing floors and furniture, or washing windows and other fixtures
911102	Washing, ironing and mending linen and other textiles
911103	Washing dishes
911104	Helping with preparation, cooking and serving of meals and refreshments
911105	Purchasing food and various other household supplies
911106	Cleaning, disinfecting and deodorising kitchens, bathrooms and toilets
911107	Cleaning windows and other glass surfaces
911201	Sweeping or vacuum-cleaning, washing and polishing floors, furniture and other fixtures in buildings, coaches, buses, trams, trains and aircraft
911202	Making beds, cleaning bathrooms, supplying towels, soap and related items
911203	Cleaning kitchens and generally helping with kitchen work, including dishwashing
911204	Picking up rubbish, emptying garbage containers and taking contents to waste areas to removal
912101	Laundering and pressing linen, clothing, fabrics and similar articles by hand in a laundry or other establishment
912102	Cleaning, by hand and with chemical solutions, clothing, fabrics, leather goods and similar articles, in a dry-cleaning or other establishment
912103	Replacing buttons and making minor repairs
912104	Placing articles on shelves and hanging articles for delivery and collection
912201	Cleaning, washing and polishing cars and other vehicles, by hand or using hand-held power tools
912202	Vacuuming vehicle interiors and dry cleaning carpets and upholstery
912203	Applying cleaning agents to remove stains from vehicle exteriors and interiors
912204	Washing tyres and wheel arches and blackening tyres

Code	Task
912205	Washing and polishing vehicle windows
912206	Emptying and cleaning compartments in vehicles
912301	Washing windows or other glass surfaces with water or various solutions, drying and polishing them
912302	Using ladders, swinging scaffolds, bosun's chairs, hydraulic bucket trucks and other equipment to reach and clean windows in multi - storey buildings
912303	Selecting appropriate cleaning or polishing implement
912901	Cleaning carpets and upholstered furniture using cleaning machines and their attachments
912902	Selecting and applying cleaning agents to remove stains from carpets
912903	Cleaning stone walls, metal surfaces and fascias using high pressure water cleaners and solvents
912904	Applying chemicals and high pressure cleaning methods to remove micro-organisms from water and filtration systems and using wet vacuums and other deposits from swimming pools, cooling tower components and drains suction equipment to remove scale and accumulated dirt
921101	Digging and shovelling to clear ditches or for other purposes
921102	Loading and unloading supplies, produce and other materials
921103	Raking, pitching and stacking straw, hay and similar material
921104	Watering, thinning, and weeding crops by hand or using hand tools
921105	Picking fruit, nuts, vegetables and other crops
921106	Planting and harvesting field crops, such as rice, by hand
921107	Grading, sorting, bunching and packing produce into containers
921108	Performing minor repairs on fixtures, buildings and fences
921201	Digging and shovelling to clear ditches or for other purposes
921202	Loading and unloading supplies, produce and other materials
921203	Feeding, watering, and cleaning animals and keeping their quarters clean
921204	Monitoring livestock and reporting on their condition
921205	Assisting with maintaining the health and welfare of livestock
921206	Assisting with herding, droving and separating livestock for milking, shearing, transportation or slaughter and between pastures
921207	Collecting eggs and placing in incubators
921208	Raking, pitching, stacking and storing hay, straw and other types of animal feed and bedding
921209	Grading, sorting, packing produce into containers
921210	Performing minor repairs on fixtures, buildings and fences
921301	Digging and shovelling to clear ditches or for other purposes
921302	Loading and unloading supplies, produce and other materials
921303	Raking, pitching and stacking straw, hay and similar material
921304	Watering, thinning, and weeding crops by hand or using hand tools
921305	Picking fruit, nuts, vegetables and other crops and collecting eggs
921306	Planting and harvesting field crops, such as rice, by hand
921307	Feeding, watering, and cleaning animals and keeping their quarters clean
921308	Monitoring livestock, reporting on their condition
921309	Assisting with herding, droving and separating livestock for milking, shearing, transportation or slaughter and between pastures
921310	Grading, sorting, bunching and packing produce into containers
921311	Performing minor repairs on fixtures, buildings and fences
921401	Loading, unloading and moving supplies, produce and equipment

Code	Task
921402	Preparing garden sites and plots using hand tools and simple machines
921403	Assisting with planting and transplanting flowers, shrubs, trees and lawns
921404	Maintaining gardens by watering, weeding and mowing lawns
921405	Cleaning gardens and removing rubbish
921406	Assisting with propagating, planting and potting seeds, bulbs and cuttings
921407	Tending plants by hand watering and weeding
921408	Harvesting and packaging plants for sale and transport
921409	Performing minor repairs on fixtures, buildings and fences
921501	Digging holes for tree planting
921502	Stacking and loading logs and timber
921503	Clearing undergrowth in forest stands and thinning young plantations
921504	Maintaining look-out for fires in forests
921505	Removing major branches and tree tops, trimming branches and sawing trunks into logs
921506	Operating and maintaining manual machine saws to fell trees and cut felled trees and branches into logs
921507	Collecting seeds, and planting seedlings
921508	Performing minor repairs and maintenance of forest roads, buildings, facilities, and equipment
921601	Cleaning the sea-bed and feeding fish and molluscs that are being cultivated
921602	Gathering seaweed, sea mosses, clams and other molluscs
921603	Preparing nets, lines and other fishing tackle and other deck equipment
921604	Operating fishing gear to catch fish and other marine life
921605	Cleaning, sorting and packing fish and seafood in ice and salt and stowing catch in hold
921606	Cleaning deck surfaces and fish hold
921607	Handling mooring lines during docking
931101	Assisting miners and quarriers in maintaining machinery, equipment, and mine and quarry installations
931102	Assembling and dismantling mining equipment
931103	Removing tunnel supports from disused workings in mines and quarries
931104	Removing dangerous projections from mine and quarry workings
931105	Removing waste and serviceable materials and equipment from work areas after extraction activities have been completed
931106	Cleaning machinery, equipment, tools, roadways and haulage tracks
931107	Sorting, loading, unloading, stacking and storing tools, materials and supplies used by other mine workers
931201	Digging and filling holes and trenches using hand held tools
931202	Shovelling and spreading gravel and related materials
931203	Trimming and cutting rocks and concrete and bitumen surfaces using jack-hammers
931204	Loading and unloading construction materials, excavated material and equipment and transporting them around construction sites using wheelbarrows and hand trucks
931205	Cleaning work sites and removing obstructions
931301	Cleaning used building bricks and doing other simple work on demolition sites
931302	Mixing, pouring and spreading materials such as concrete, plaster and mortar
931303	Digging and filling holes and trenches using hand held tools
931304	Spreading sand, soil, gravel and similar materials
931305	Loading and unloading construction materials, excavated material and equipment and transporting them around construction sites using wheelbarrows, hods and hand trucks

Code	Task
931306	Cleaning work sites and removing obstructions
932101	Weighing, wrapping, sealing and packing material and various products by hand
932102	Filling bottles, cans, boxes, bags and other containers by hand
932103	Labelling products, packages and various containers by hand
932901	Conveying goods, material, equipment, etc. to work area, removing finished pieces
932902	Loading and unloading vehicles, trucks and trolleys
932903	Clearing machine blockages, cleaning machinery, equipment and tools
932904	Carrying out manual sorting of products or components
933101	Loading or unloading goods, or assisting passengers in getting on or off a vehicle
933102	Moving vehicle in the desired direction with due regard to other traffic and traffic regulations
933103	Inspecting vehicle components to identify wear and damage
933104	Maintaining vehicle, making minor repairs and installing replacement parts
933105	Collecting fares or charges
933201	Harnessing animals and hitching them to vehicles or machinery
933202	Loading or unloading goods, or assisting passengers in getting on or off a vehicle
933203	Driving animals in the desired direction with due regard to other traffic and traffic regulations
933204	Collecting fares or charges
933205	Driving animals to haul wagons in mines or quarries
933206	Driving animals hitched to farm or other machinery
933207	Driving working elephants
933208	Maintaining vehicle or machinery, making minor repairs and installing replacement parts
933209	Grooming and feeding animals
933301	Packing office or household furniture, machines, appliances and related goods to be transported from one place to another
933302	Carrying goods to be loaded on or unloaded from vans, trucks, wagons, ships, or aircraft
933303	Loading and unloading grain, coal, sand and similar goods by placing them on conveyor-belts, in pipes, etc.
933304	Connecting hoses between main shore installation pipes and tanks of barges, tankers and other ships to load and unload petroleum, liquefied gases and other liquids
933305	Carrying and stacking goods in warehouses and similar establishments
933306	Sorting cargo prior to loading and unloading
933401	Placing goods neatly in bins and on racks, and stacking bulky goods on floors
933402	Filling shelves with goods ensuring goods with the earliest use-by dates are at the front of shelves
933403	Removing goods with past due use-by dates
933404	Maintaining shelf order by removing stock belonging in a different location
933405	Noting what has been sold and collecting goods needed from the stockroom
933406	Obtaining articles for customers from shelf or stockroom
933407	Directing customers to location of articles sought
933408	Receiving, opening, unpacking, and inspecting for damage merchandise from manufacturer or distributor
941101	Preparing simple or pre-prepared foods and beverages such as sandwiches, hamburgers, pizzas, fish and chips, salads, and coffee
941102	Washing, cutting, measuring and mixing foods for cooking
941103	Operating large-volume single-process cooking equipment such as grills, deep-fat fryers or griddles
941104	Re-heating pre-prepared food

Code	Task
941105	Cleaning food preparation areas, cooking surfaces and utensils
941106	Taking and serving food and beverage orders in eating places that specialize in fast service and carry-out food
941107	Ordering and taking delivery of fast food ingredients
941108	Maintaining sanitation, health, and safety standards in work areas
941109	Operating large-volume cooking equipment such as grills, deep-fat fryers, or griddles
941110	Verifying that prepared food meets requirements for quality and quantity
941201	Cleaning kitchens, food preparation areas and service areas
941202	Assisting cooks and chefs in preparation of food by washing, peeling, chopping, cutting up measuring and mixing ingredients
941203	Assembling dishes for service
941204	Unpacking, checking, weighing and storing supplies in refrigerators, cupboards and other storage areas
941205	Washing dishes and cooking utensils and putting them away
941206	Checking, transferring, weighing and storing supplies in refrigerators, cupboards and other storage areas
941207	Preparing, cooking, toasting and heating simple food items
951001	Obtaining the materials necessary to perform services
951002	Approaching people on the street to offer services
951003	Cleaning and polishing shoes
951004	Cleaning and polishing car windows
951005	Running errands
951006	Assisting drivers to find a parking place and ensuring car is not damaged during driver's absence
951007	Handing out leaflets and free newspapers
951008	Receiving immediate payment
952001	Buying or receiving items for sale, or making simple items
952002	Loading and unloading basket, tray, push-cart, bicycle, or other vehicle, to transport goods to the designated spots
952003	Displaying goods or calling out to attract customer's attention
952004	Approaching potential customers on street and offering goods for sale
952005	Receiving immediate payment
961101	Collecting rubbish and recyclable materials and locating it into bins and garbage and recycling trucks
961102	Riding on or in garbage and recycling trucks
961103	Lifting garbage bins and emptying contents into trucks and larger containers
961104	Unloading garbage and recycling trucks
961201	Searching through refuse and collecting items for recycling from dump sites, domestic, commercial and industrial premises or from public places such as streets
961202	Sorting cardboard, paper, glass, plastic, aluminium or other recyclable materials
961203	Placing recyclable items and materials in designated compartments and containers for storage or transportation
961204	Identifying and setting aside items of furniture, equipment, machinery, or components that are suitable for repair or re-use

Code	Task
961205	Transporting recyclable items by hand or using non-motorized vehicles
961206	Selling recyclable or reusable materials
961301	Sweeping streets, parks, airports, stations and similar public places
961302	Shovelling snow
961303	Beating dust out of carpets by using a carpet-beater
961304	Cleaning rubbish, leaves and snow from driveways and grounds
962101	Delivering messages, packages and other items within an establishment or between establishments, or elsewhere
962102	Performing the duties of a post-runner
962103	Delivering various goods to and from enterprises, shops, households and other places
962104	Carrying and delivering luggage at hotels, stations, airports, and elsewhere
962105	Receiving and marking baggage by completing attaching claim checks
962106	Planning and following the most efficient route
962107	Sorting items to be delivered according to the delivery route
962201	Repairing broken windows, screens, doors, fences, barbecues, picnic tables, shelves, cupboards and other items
962202	Replacing defective items such as light bulbs
962203	Repairing and painting interior and exterior surfaces such as walls, ceilings and fences
962204	Adjusting doors and windows
962205	Replacing tap washers
962206	Putting up handrails and grab rails
962207	Unloading coal or wood and putting it into cellars of private households or establishments
962301	Filling storage areas of vending machines and collecting money from their containers
962302	Collecting money from parking meters and similar coin-boxes
962303	Reading electricity, gas or water meters and recording consumption
962304	Keeping records of merchandise distributed and money collected
962305	Proceeding along established routes to take readings of meter dials
962306	Verifying readings in cases where consumption appears to be abnormal, and record possible fluctuations
962307	Inspecting meters for unauthorized connections, defects, and damage such as broken seals
962401	Cutting and collecting wood from forests for sale in market or as fuel or for own consumption
962402	Visiting forests or fields to pick pieces of dried wood from ground and arranging them in heaps
962403	Cutting decayed branches and trunks of trees using axe and hand saw
962404	Tying collected wood into small faggots and carrying them or transporting them on a cart to the market for sale or to village or household for use
962405	Drawing water from wells, rivers or ponds etc. for domestic use
962406	Collecting water in leather bags, buckets or other containers from taps, rivers, ponds or wells and delivering the water to work sites, the houses of clients or to own household for drinking, cleaning of drains or storage in tanks
962901	Selling and collecting admission tickets, tags and passes from patrons at entertainment events
962902	Examining tickets or passes to verify authenticity, using criteria such as colour and date issued
962903	Guiding patrons to exits or providing other instructions or assistance in case of emergency
962904	Directing patrons to restroom and telephones

Code	Task
962905	Directing vehicle drivers to parking spaces
962906	Patrolling parking areas in order to prevent vehicle damage and vehicle property thefts
962907	Calculating parking charges, and collecting fees from customers
962908	Assigning dressing room facilities, locker space, or clothing containers to patrons of athletic or bathing establishments

appendix 3 Number of respondents by occupation and country

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Legislators	1111	1	0	0	0	1	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	8
Senior government officials	1112	1	0	0	4	8	4	8	2	3	0	3	1	1	35
Senior officials of special interest organisations	1114	0	0	3	2	1	3	3	4	3	2	5	0	0	26
Managing directors and chief executives	1120	41	3	30	22	44	41	29	41	105	6	69	36	24	491
Finance managers	1211	25	0	9	28	11	38	28	20	34	8	60	18	12	291
Human resource managers	1212	31	1	15	26	9	73	30	48	36	9	49	11	10	348
Policy and planning managers	1213	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	6
Business services and administration managers not elsewhere classified	1219	42	10	19	21	36	28	41	81	95	7	113	32	35	560
Sales and marketing managers	1221	23	1	20	26	64	37	66	36	89	18	47	29	26	482
Advertising and public relations managers	1222	3	1	4	0	11	8	13	18	16	4	14	4	4	100
Research and development managers	1223	4	0	10	7	5	12	5	13	24	3	11	5	3	102
Agricultural and forestry production managers	1311	3	0	0	1	2	5	1	1	0	1	3	0	1	18
Aquaculture and fisheries production managers	1312	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
Manufacturing managers	1321	2	0	2	3	7	0	4	2	6	2	4	2	2	36

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Mining managers	1322	1	0	0	1	0	11	4	5	10	0	3	2	0	37
Construction managers	1323	4	1	2	5	2	1	0	4	11	0	8	3	1	42
Supply, distribution and related managers	1324	12	1	15	14	8	17	10	19	38	5	27	11	11	188
Information and communications technology service managers	1330	12	0	12	6	4	2	4	10	41	2	23	10	10	136
Child care services managers	1341	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	5	0	3	0	2	14
Health services managers	1342	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	4	0	0	1	1	11
Aged care services managers	1343	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	0	1	8
Social welfare managers	1344	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	2	6	0	2	0	1	14
Education managers	1345	1	0	1	3	2	6	3	5	13	2	2	1	4	43
Financial and insurance services branch managers	1346	4	1	3	7	3	8	7	2	5	4	8	5	5	62
Professional services managers not elsewhere classified	1349	1	0	1	2	3	0	9	0	4	4	0	1	1	26
Hotel managers	1411	5	1	2	2	0	8	1	6	9	2	9	1	4	50
Restaurant managers	1412	2	0	3	0	4	3	6	7	35	1	16	8	2	87
Retail and wholesale trade managers	1420	6	2	10	20	18	16	21	9	36	1	17	6	11	173
Sports, recreation and cultural centre managers	1431	2	0	1	0	3	0	2	5	13	0	3	1	0	30
Physicists and astronomers	2111	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	1	7
Meteorologists	2112	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Chemists	2113	2	0	3	3	3	6	2	31	9	1	2	11	1	74
Geologists and geophysicists	2114	3	0	0	5	1	7	20	6	2	4	2	1	1	52
Mathematicians, actuaries and statisticians	2120	3	1	1	2	0	1	3	13	10	0	6	3	4	47

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Biologists, botanists, zoologists and related professionals	2131	1	0	3	0	2	0	1	5	4	0	0	1	0	17
Farming, forestry and fisheries advisers	2132	3	0	2	3	10	3	4	9	13	0	8	3	1	59
Environmental protection professionals	2133	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	0	14	2	7	0	0	28
Industrial and production engineers	2141	15	2	13	10	96	24	63	70	27	15	27	37	2	401
Civil engineers	2142	4	0	12	12	33	14	17	24	16	3	16	11	3	165
Environmental engineers	2143	1	0	0	4	3	0	8	4	1	1	2	2	1	27
Mechanical engineers	2144	14	1	9	13	9	4	7	38	14	4	32	17	9	171
Chemical engineers	2145	5	0	4	1	2	0	1	20	9	2	5	6	0	55
Mining engineers, metallurgists and related professionals	2146	0	0	0	1	11	1	8	3	2	1	2	1	0	30
Engineering professionals not elsewhere classified	2149	2	0	4	2	14	0	11	15	11	1	0	4	1	65
Electrical engineers	2151	9	1	5	9	8	0	20	13	8	6	7	7	3	96
Electronics engineers	2152	15	0	6	7	15	0	4	26	7	5	6	6	6	103
Telecommunications engineers	2153	7	0	2	1	10	2	31	27	2	6	6	20	1	115
Building architects	2161	19	1	5	2	14	21	0	58	17	2	8	4	0	151
Landscape architects	2162	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	6	5	0	0	0	0	13
Product and garment designers	2163	6	0	8	5	8	8	3	12	17	1	2	8	2	80
Town and traffic planners	2164	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	1	0	2	7
Cartographers and surveyors	2165	1	0	2	0	4	1	3	2	3	0	1	1	0	18
Graphic and multimedia designers	2166	36	1	17	9	12	20	10	49	101	7	38	17	21	338
Generalist medical practitioners	2211	3	0	1	1	6	2	8	17	1	2	2	4	0	47

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Specialist medical practitioners	2212	6	0	1	3	40	0	30	15	13	9	5	0	2	124
Nursing professionals	2221	15	0	45	7	46	16	20	23	113	10	7	8	4	314
Midwifery professionals	2222	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	5
Traditional and complementary medicine professionals	2230	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Paramedical practitioners	2240	1	0	1	0	9	3	5	1	22	0	2	0	0	44
Veterinarians	2250	1	0	2	0	22	0	2	7	10	0	1	2	1	48
Dentists	2261	0	0	0	2	7	1	0	7	0	3	1	0	0	21
Pharmacists	2262	0	0	4	3	5	5	1	5	5	3	4	2	0	37
Environmental and occupational health and hygiene professionals	2263	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	1	3	0	13	1	2	23
Physiotherapists	2264	2	0	4	2	1	1	1	12	36	1	1	6	1	68
Dietitians and nutritionists	2265	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	7	7	0	0	0	0	16
Audiologists and speech therapists	2266	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	1	6	0	1	0	0	12
Optometrists and ophthalmic opticians	2267	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	3	20	0	0	1	0	27
Health professionals not elsewhere classified	2269	3	0	2	0	4	2	2	1	17	0	4	3	2	40
University and higher education teachers	2310	14	2	14	11	68	18	91	94	73	21	29	34	12	481
Vocational education teachers	2320	0	1	1	0	19	3	34	14	46	8	7	1	3	137
Secondary education teachers	2330	15	0	2	5	142	14	187	25	42	15	13	11	5	476
Primary school teachers	2341	6	0	7	12	26	11	43	26	47	0	9	5	2	194
Early childhood educators	2342	2	1	2	2	7	2	2	5	1	0	7	0	0	31
Education methods specialists	2351	3	0	2	8	5	8	20	15	15	3	12	1	1	93
Special needs teachers	2352	2	0	4	3	14	10	16	8	14	1	1	0	0	73

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Other language teachers	2353	0	0	0	5	2	1	7	9	18	2	3	5	2	54
Other music teachers	2354	1	1	0	2	7	1	7	4	2	3	0	2	0	30
Other arts teachers	2355	1	0	0	0	10	1	4	0	9	1	0	1	0	27
Information technology trainers	2356	2	0	2	2	1	2	6	4	6	3	1	3	3	35
Teaching professionals not elsewhere classified	2359	2	1	1	4	16	1	9	13	26	2	16	1	8	100
Accountants	2411	31	4	14	1	54	58	37	61	64	7	89	25	30	475
Financial and investment advisers	2412	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	7	16	0	6	0	1	34
Financial analysts	2413	9	0	7	19	4	5	14	18	11	2	8	10	6	113
Management and organisation analysts	2421	9	2	6	12	0	8	5	15	20	0	13	8	5	103
Policy administration professionals	2422	1	0	7	2	0	3	3	8	38	2	4	0	9	77
Personnel and careers professionals	2423	14	1	23	25	49	70	55	32	120	5	62	9	14	479
Training and staff development professionals	2424	6	0	2	8	1	14	5	10	6	0	10	2	5	69
Advertising and marketing professionals	2431	21	1	11	21	74	17	44	81	160	14	73	44	36	597
Public relations professionals	2432	1	0	1	0	4	2	7	4	3	1	6	3	2	34
Technical and medical sales professionals (excluding ICT)	2433	2	0	4	5	17	6	1	12	24	1	4	10	1	87
Information and communications technology sales professionals	2434	0	0	5	0	2	0	4	0	12	0	4	4	5	36
Systems analysts	2511	47	1	36	32	13	10	12	30	140	7	52	67	18	465
Software developers	2512	7	0	12	2	25	1	16	26	19	18	15	30	21	192
Web and multimedia developers	2513	6	1	9	3	11	4	11	13	27	4	10	11	2	112
Applications programmers	2514	25	0	29	2	10	21	11	30	53	4	19	40	2	246

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Software and applications developers and analysts not elsewhere classified	2519	12	0	13	8	16	11	7	8	84	10	48	11	12	240
Database designers and administrators	2521	8	0	3	4	5	19	8	17	15	5	10	8	9	111
Systems administrators	2522	10	0	2	4	12	4	18	16	28	8	12	8	2	124
Computer network professionals	2523	5	0	5	2	0	3	3	12	43	3	10	3	4	93
Database and network professionals not elsewhere classified	2529	6	0	6	2	9	10	11	9	29	6	10	5	3	106
Lawyers	2611	8	0	1	6	9	0	14	28	10	9	4	13	0	102
Judges	2612	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	2
Legal professionals not elsewhere classified	2619	10	0	16	3	58	18	55	37	77	14	19	14	4	325
Archivists and curators	2621	1	0	1	2	2	1	0	2	2	0	3	0	1	15
Librarians and related information professionals	2622	2	0	0	4	17	2	9	3	3	2	1	0	3	46
Economists	2631	2	0	0	6	81	0	35	7	9	6	2	5	0	153
Sociologists, anthropologists and related professionals	2632	1	0	5	5	5	4	7	16	13	2	12	4	9	83
Philosophers, historians and political scientists	2633	1	0	1	0	2	0	2	3	1	0	1	0	1	12
Psychologists	2634	2	0	7	6	8	1	3	39	20	3	3	5	0	97
Social work and counselling professionals	2635	1	1	12	3	2	4	4	7	95	3	7	4	6	149
Religious professionals	2636	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	4	0	0	8
Authors and related writers	2641	1	0	2	0	4	1	0	4	13	0	9	1	2	37
Journalists	2642	20	2	12	21	17	20	16	34	48	10	46	5	7	258
Translators, interpreters and other linguists	2643	4	1	3	5	20	6	40	9	10	7	2	2	1	110
Visual artists	2651	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	6

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Musicians, singers and composers	2652	2	0	1	0	10	1	1	3	3	2	1	1	0	25
Dancers and choreographers	2653	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	7
Film, stage and related directors and producers	2654	5	0	4	0	5	2	1	7	9	0	3	2	0	38
Actors	2655	0	1	0	0	6	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	10
Announcers on radio, television and other media	2656	1	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	6
Creative and performing artists not elsewhere classified	2659	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Chemical and physical science technicians	3111	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	5
Civil engineering technicians	3112	4	0	2	8	13	13	11	3	21	1	22	2	2	102
Electrical engineering technicians	3113	9	0	20	12	3	8	4	1	31	1	4	1	3	97
Electronics engineering technicians	3114	8	1	5	1	4	6	1	5	3	1	7	2	3	47
Mechanical engineering technicians	3115	5	0	10	7	8	5	5	1	62	0	10	2	1	116
Chemical engineering technicians	3116	2	0	3	0	3	0	2	2	11	2	1	2	2	30
Mining and metallurgical technicians	3117	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	5	1	0	0	1	14
Draughts-persons	3118	4	4	39	29	47	20	49	7	97	11	26	7	7	347
Physical and engineering science technicians not elsewhere classified	3119	1	0	12	2	2	2	1	2	33	1	6	4	2	68
Mining supervisors	3121	0	0	0	2	14	6	6	0	0	4	4	0	0	36
Manufacturing supervisors	3122	9	1	5	5	2	16	3	16	10	1	8	9	1	86
Construction supervisors	3123	11	1	23	1	22	31	17	30	143	1	17	3	8	308

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Power production plant operators	3131	0	0	3	1	2	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	10
Incinerator and water treatment plant operators	3132	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	6
Chemical processing plant controllers	3133	0	0	5	0	4	1	1	0	22	0	0	3	2	38
Petroleum and natural gas refining plant operators	3134	1	0	2	0	1	0	4	2	7	1	1	0	0	19
Metal production process controllers	3135	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	0	1	1	1	0	0	9
Life science technicians (excluding medical)	3141	2	0	12	6	3	3	3	8	14	0	5	2	0	58
Agricultural technicians	3142	0	0	1	2	3	3	1	3	3	2	2	4	1	25
Forestry technicians	3143	1	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	8
Ships' engineers	3151	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	4
Ships' deck officers and pilots	3152	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	1	10	0	0	1	0	15
Aircraft pilots and related associate professionals	3153	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	1	9
Air traffic controllers	3154	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	1	0	1	6
Air traffic safety electronics technicians	3155	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2
Medical imaging and therapeutic equipment technicians	3211	0	0	3	0	3	1	2	1	8	0	2	0	1	21
Medical and pathology laboratory technicians	3212	1	1	11	1	3	2	3	3	17	0	2	0	0	44
Pharmaceutical technicians and assistants	3213	2	0	6	4	5	4	1	3	9	0	1	2	1	38
Medical and dental prosthetic technicians	3214	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	8	0	0	0	0	13

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Nursing associate professionals	3221	1	0	6	12	1	1	7	10	48	4	6	2	0	98
Midwifery associate professionals	3222	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Veterinary technicians and assistants	3240	2	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	24	1	1	1	0	34
Dental assistants and therapists	3251	2	0	9	3	3	0	0	0	29	0	2	5	0	53
Medical records and health information technicians	3252	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	8	1	0	0	0	13
Community health workers	3253	0	0	0	0	5	0	6	0	1	1	1	1	4	19
Dispensing opticians	3254	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Physiotherapy technicians and assistants	3255	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	8
Medical assistants	3256	1	0	1	2	15	1	5	1	53	1	1	1	1	83
Environmental and occupational health inspectors and associates	3257	7	0	4	2	5	10	4	13	23	0	9	4	1	82
Health associate professionals not elsewhere classified	3259	3	0	1	6	7	1	7	2	50	2	0	2	1	82
Securities and finance dealers and brokers	3311	0	0	0	0	1	3	4	1	1	0	2	1	0	13
Credit and loans officers	3312	3	0	2	3	4	18	5	9	5	0	5	1	1	56
Accounting associate professionals	3313	27	0	58	36	238	10	323	34	240	43	109	6	9	1,133
Statistical, mathematical and related associate professionals	3314	1	0	1	0	0	1	2	2	5	0	2	1	0	15
Valuers and loss assessors	3315	1	1	1	1	1	4	6	1	13	2	8	2	2	43
Insurance representatives	3321	3	0	5	1	5	5	8	0	13	2	10	2	3	57
Commercial sales representatives	3322	41	3	38	20	44	26	48	61	162	3	57	30	14	547

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Buyers	3323	18	0	22	31	13	8	18	26	79	5	30	14	5	269
Trade brokers	3324	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	0	1	6	3	17
Clearing and forwarding agents	3331	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	7
Conference and event planners	3332	3	1	1	2	5	2	1	5	16	1	12	3	1	53
Employment agents and contractors	3333	0	0	3	2	7	12	7	3	63	5	3	1	4	110
Real estate agents and property managers	3334	2	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	15	1	2	0	4	28
Business services agents not elsewhere classified	3339	1	0	2	4	1	13	2	4	5	2	4	2	3	43
Office supervisors	3341	18	1	2	6	9	29	15	23	30	5	10	2	1	151
Legal secretaries	3342	3	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	33	1	9	1	2	62
Administrative and executive secretaries	3343	37	6	30	75	41	52	54	36	162	12	208	16	54	783
Medical secretaries	3344	16	1	18	5	3	2	2	5	11	0	10	0	3	76
Customs and border inspectors	3351	0	0	0	0	6	1	3	2	3	0	0	0	1	16
Government tax and excise officials	3352	3	0	0	5	2	4	2	3	5	1	2	2	0	29
Government social benefits officials	3353	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	2	7	0	0	0	0	14
Government licensing officials	3354	1	0	1	1	2	2	4	0	8	2	1	0	0	22
Police inspectors and detectives	3355	0	0	2	0	6	0	2	2	13	1	4	1	0	31
Regulatory government associate professionals not elsewhere classified	3359	3	0	4	3	3	6	5	2	5	0	1	1	1	34
Police inspectors and detectives	3411	9	0	0	11	7	6	8	17	20	4	18	2	5	107
Social work associate professionals	3412	2	0	7	6	15	4	10	6	17	12	1	3	5	88

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Religious associate professionals	3413	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	4
Athletes and sports players	3421	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Sports coaches, instructors and officials	3422	2	1	0	1	7	0	9	6	15	0	3	3	0	47
Fitness and recreation instructors and program leaders	3423	1	0	2	1	5	1	2	3	60	1	1	1	0	78
Photographers	3431	1	0	3	4	4	4	2	8	7	0	5	3	1	42
Interior designers and decorators	3432	3	0	8	7	9	0	6	5	12	1	6	6	1	64
Gallery, museum and library technicians	3433	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	6
Chefs	3434	7	0	5	2	0	2	0	4	31	0	3	3	5	62
Information and communications technology operations technicians	3511	0	2	0	6	5	7	5	2	15	4	10	2	0	58
Information and communications technology user support technicians	3512	39	3	14	24	21	20	35	62	121	15	58	39	22	473
Computer network and systems technicians	3513	2	0	5	4	22	24	27	4	19	13	13	19	6	158
Web technicians	3514	0	0	1	2	3	13	1	1	43	0	0	1	0	65
Broadcasting and audio-visual technicians	3521	1	0	3	3	4	3	5	7	19	1	7	3	2	58
Telecommunications engineering technicians	3522	5	0	3	4	4	15	13	3	8	2	8	5	5	75
General office clerks	4110	81	6	90	90	151	262	125	196	737	44	107	52	40	1,981
Secretaries (general)	4120	77	0	40	60	38	18	21	88	167	4	53	30	9	605
Typists and word processing operators	4131	1	0	0	3	5	6	2	2	3	1	5	1	1	30
Data entry clerks	4132	2	0	0	1	4	1	3	0	4	0	4	0	1	20

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Bank tellers and related clerks	4211	3	1	6	3	7	8	6	11	21	0	12	3	1	82
Bookmakers, croupiers and related gaming workers	4212	1	0	0	0	8	0	4	0	6	1	0	3	0	23
Pawnbrokers and money-lenders	4213	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	6
Debt-collectors and related workers	4214	8	0	2	2	15	5	19	3	22	1	9	3	1	90
Travel consultants and clerks	4221	5	0	4	3	18	9	11	6	21	3	21	5	4	110
Contact centre information clerks	4222	8	1	4	13	16	8	13	18	106	1	32	14	23	257
Telephone switchboard operators	4223	8	0	1	10	0	2	3	1	13	0	6	2	0	46
Hotel receptionists	4224	4	0	1	15	4	0	9	4	9	0	2	2	1	51
Enquiry clerks	4225	1	0	0	3	1	0	0	5	1	0	1	1	0	13
Receptionists (general)	4226	30	4	11	78	14	15	11	20	122	2	66	10	9	392
Survey and market research interviewers	4227	1	0	1	2	1	1	4	2	3	2	3	2	2	24
Client information workers not elsewhere classified	4229	0	0	1	5	1	5	2	1	7	1	0	0	8	31
Accounting and bookkeeping clerks	4311	69	0	19	39	57	8	47	87	40	4	37	38	16	461
Statistical, finance and insurance clerks	4312	26	1	18	30	25	47	32	30	191	3	57	18	9	487
Payroll clerks	4313	1	0	0	1	19	0	8	10	8	2	8	1	3	61
Stock clerks	4321	10	1	24	48	33	35	35	10	141	3	38	9	14	401
Production clerks	4322	9	1	4	5	12	3	8	10	24	1	8	5	2	92
Transport clerks	4323	2	0	5	7	2	7	6	6	40	0	5	0	5	85
Library clerks	4411	0	0	1	0	7	6	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	19
Mail carriers and sorting clerks	4412	2	0	4	3	5	0	2	0	24	1	1	1	2	45
Coding, proof-reading and related clerks	4413	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	3

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Scribes and related workers	4414	0	0	0	2	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	7
Filing and copying clerks	4415	5	0	16	0	1	1	8	4	2	1	1	1	1	41
Personnel clerks	4416	30	0	19	49	21	47	29	61	77	7	12	9	6	367
Clerical support workers not elsewhere classified	4419	25	2	18	30	17	1	26	41	72	3	24	13	2	274
Travel attendants and travel stewards	5111	0	0	0	2	6	1	3	2	9	0	1	0	0	24
Transport conductors	5112	0	0	0	3	1	1	2	3	4	0	0	0	0	14
Travel guides	5113	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	2	5	1	0	1	0	13
Cooks	5120	8	0	4	10	14	5	5	8	103	3	4	8	4	176
Waiters	5131	9	0	6	6	4	1	1	0	85	0	1	0	4	117
Bartenders	5132	6	0	6	0	3	0	2	1	37	0	7	11	1	74
Hairdressers	5141	2	1	3	1	14	1	4	0	24	0	0	0	4	54
Beauticians and related workers	5142	0	0	4	1	5	2	2	1	14	1	4	2	3	39
Cleaning and housekeeping supervisors in offices, hotels and other establishments	5151	9	0	0	4	3	1	1	6	42	1	1	9	2	79
Domestic housekeepers	5152	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	3	0	0	9
Building caretakers	5153	2	0	1	5	3	5	5	0	15	0	0	3	0	39
Undertakers and embalmers	5163	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	5	0	0	1	0	10
Pet groomers and animal care workers	5164	2	1	1	0	16	0	1	1	16	0	1	1	0	40
Driving instructors	5165	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3
Personal services workers not elsewhere classified	5169	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	2	8
Stall and market salespersons	5211	0	0	0	5	4	0	4	1	3	0	1	0	0	18
Street food salespersons	5212	0	0	1	0	1	0	3	2	0	2	0	0	0	9
Shop keepers	5221	19	0	8	20	11	17	13	9	63	0	6	3	2	171
Shop supervisors	5222	9	0	9	8	23	5	20	26	76	0	3	5	9	193

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Shop sales assistants	5223	13	2	39	40	92	16	39	15	349	24	11	17	19	676
Cashiers and ticket clerks	5230	12	2	4	22	21	4	9	10	99	1	4	3	1	192
Sales demonstrators	5242	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	6
Door to door salespersons	5243	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	4
Contact centre salespersons	5244	6	0	5	5	2	0	2	1	40	1	11	4	4	81
Service station attendants	5245	0	0	1	3	1	0	1	0	8	0	3	0	0	17
Food service counter attendants	5246	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	7	0	2	0	1	14
Sales workers not elsewhere classified	5249	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Child care workers	5311	19	0	7	6	7	1	8	11	58	3	7	3	6	136
Teachers' aides	5312	0	0	1	2	41	0	11	2	34	2	0	1	3	97
Health care assistants	5321	2	0	23	7	4	1	2	2	145	4	1	11	9	211
Home-based personal care workers	5322	6	0	6	1	0	0	0	1	48	0	3	9	8	82
Personal care workers in health services not elsewhere classified	5329	0	0	0	1	5	0	3	2	7	3	1	1	2	25
Fire-fighters	5411	0	0	1	0	4	0	2	0	7	2	0	1	0	17
Police officers	5412	3	1	1	1	5	0	3	3	7	2	5	1	0	32
Prison guards	5413	0	0	3	2	2	0	0	0	10	0	1	1	1	20
Security guards	5414	11	1	6	24	29	35	15	13	66	8	11	9	10	238
Protective services workers not elsewhere classified	5419	1	0	0	1	1	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	11
Field crop and vegetable growers	6111	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	11	1	0	0	0	16
Tree and shrub crop growers	6112	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	2	1	0	6
Gardeners, horticultural and nursery growers	6113	2	0	6	1	4	0	0	2	80	2	2	0	4	103
Mixed crop growers	6114	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	5
Livestock and dairy producers	6121	2	0	0	0	8	2	0	1	8	0	2	2	0	25

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Poultry producers	6122	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Animal producers not elsewhere classified	6129	1	0	0	1	6	0	1	0	10	0	0	0	0	19
Mixed crop and animal producers	6130	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	4
Forestry and related workers	6210	0	1	4	0	17	3	1	1	7	3	2	0	0	39
Aquaculture workers	6221	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	6
Inland and coastal waters fishery workers	6222	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Deep-sea fishery workers	6223	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	2
Subsistence crop farmers	6310	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Subsistence livestock farmers	6320	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Subsistence mixed crop and livestock farmers	6330	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
House builders	7111	0	0	0	1	8	0	3	3	5	2	2	0	0	24
Bricklayers and related workers	7112	2	0	4	2	9	0	3	1	20	0	1	1	0	43
Stonemasons, stone cutters, splitters and carvers	7113	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
Concrete placers, concrete finishers and related workers	7114	0	0	0	1	11	1	0	0	6	1	0	2	0	22
Carpenters and joiners	7115	3	1	4	1	17	0	3	0	56	2	2	2	1	92
Building frame and related trades workers not elsewhere classified	7119	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	10	19	0	2	2	0	38
Roofers	7121	0	0	1	0	5	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	10
Floor layers and tile setters	7122	0	0	0	0	4	0	1	0	4	0	1	0	0	10
Plasterers	7123	0	0	0	0	12	0	3	0	2	1	0	0	0	18
Insulation workers	7124	0	0	1	0	3	0	1	0	3	0	0	2	0	10
Glaziers	7125	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	7

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Plumbers and pipe fitters	7126	0	0	4	0	11	1	5	1	15	2	1	1	0	41
Air conditioning and refrigeration mechanics	7127	1	1	0	4	1	2	0	2	12	0	0	3	0	26
Painters and related workers	7131	1	0	5	1	24	0	6	1	32	2	1	3	1	77
Spray painters and varnishers	7132	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	1	9
Building structure cleaners	7133	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	0	1	0	0	5
Metal moulders and coremakers	7211	0	0	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	9
Welders and flamecutters	7212	1	1	5	1	29	2	14	0	37	2	1	2	1	96
Sheet-metal workers	7213	0	0	3	2	5	4	3	1	27	1	1	0	0	47
Structural-metal preparers and erectors	7214	0	0	0	1	5	1	3	0	4	0	0	0	0	14
Riggers and cable splicers	7215	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Blacksmiths, hammersmiths and forging press workers	7221	2	0	0	1	3	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	10
Toolmakers and related workers	7222	1	0	0	3	9	0	1	2	8	1	0	0	1	26
Metal working machine tool setters and operators	7223	1	0	2	5	14	3	4	2	11	1	1	1	1	46
Metal polishers, wheel grinders and tool sharpeners	7224	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
Motor vehicle mechanics and repairers	7231	6	0	15	14	21	5	20	5	102	8	5	5	3	209
Aircraft engine mechanics and repairers	7232	0	0	0	1	1	5	0	0	6	0	3	1	1	18
Agricultural and industrial machinery mechanics and repairers	7233	1	0	10	8	25	13	22	6	81	5	6	7	3	187
Bicycle and related repairers	7234	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	17

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Precision-instrument makers and repairers	7311	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	4
Musical instrument makers and tuners	7312	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2
Jewellery and precious-metal workers	7313	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	7
Potters and related workers	7314	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Glass makers, cutters, grinders and finishers	7315	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
Sign writers, decorative painters, engravers and etchers	7316	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Handicraft workers in wood, basketry and related materials	7317	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	3
Handicraft workers in textile, leather and related materials	7318	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Pre-press technicians	7321	1	0	3	2	2	6	1	1	17	1	5	0	0	39
Printers	7322	2	0	2	2	12	9	5	3	11	1	4	0	2	53
Print finishing and binding workers	7323	0	0	1	3	0	2	3	0	7	1	0	1	0	18
Building and related electricians	7411	3	0	10	10	15	5	9	2	29	5	4	5	3	100
Electrical mechanics and fitters	7412	3	1	3	2	38	8	24	4	91	12	8	6	4	204
Electrical line installers and repairers	7413	2	0	2	1	12	2	5	3	14	3	8	1	1	54
Electronics mechanics and servicers	7421	0	0	2	2	2	2	0	1	5	0	0	1	0	15
Information and communications technology installers and servicers	7422	9	0	1	3	6	7	7	3	10	6	4	2	0	58
Butchers, fishmongers and related food preparers	7511	1	0	7	2	9	2	3	1	20	0	2	2	2	51

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Bakers, pastry-cooks and confectionery makers	7512	4	0	6	12	20	5	4	7	31	1	5	4	1	100
Dairy-products makers	7513	0	0	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Fruit, vegetable and related preservers	7514	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	3
Food and beverage tasters and graders	7515	3	0	0	4	6	4	1	4	3	1	6	1	1	34
Wood treaters	7521	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	8
Cabinet-makers and related workers	7522	0	1	2	2	5	0	1	1	7	0	1	1	0	21
Woodworking-machine tool setters and operators	7523	0	0	0	3	8	2	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	17
Tailors, dressmakers, furriers and hatters	7531	1	0	0	0	8	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Garment and related pattern-makers and cutters	7532	1	0	0	3	11	1	2	0	0	0	3	1	0	22
Sewing, embroidery and related workers	7533	3	1	0	5	6	0	3	1	4	0	0	0	0	23
Upholsterers and related workers	7534	3	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	9	0	0	2	0	17
Pelt dressers, tanners and fellmongers	7535	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
Shoemakers and related workers	7536	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	0	7
Underwater divers	7541	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
Product graders and testers (excluding foods and beverages)	7543	5	0	4	8	13	20	7	20	29	2	5	6	6	125
Fumigators and other pest and weed controllers	7544	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	4
Miners and quarriers	8111	0	0	0	0	5	1	8	0	0	3	0	0	0	17
Mineral and stone processing plant operators	8112	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	1	0	0	5

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Well drillers and borers and related workers	8113	1	0	1	2	2	3	6	0	4	0	0	0	0	19
Cement, stone and other mineral products machine operators	8114	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Metal processing plant operators	8121	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	6
Metal finishing, plating and coating machine operators	8122	0	0	0	3	3	1	2	0	0	2	1	1	0	13
Chemical products plant and machine operators	8131	1	0	2	2	1	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	9
Rubber products machine operators	8141	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	4	0	1	0	0	9
Plastic products machine operators	8142	3	0	0	7	11	5	1	3	6	1	0	1	0	38
Paper products machine operators	8143	1	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Fibre preparing, spinning and winding machine operators	8151	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2
Weaving and knitting machine operators	8152	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	5
Sewing machine operators	8153	3	0	0	4	12	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	23
Bleaching, dyeing and fabric cleaning machine operators	8154	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Shoemaking and related machine operators	8156	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
Laundry machine operators	8157	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	3

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Textile, fur and leather products machine operators not elsewhere classified	8159	0	0	0	2	2	1	0	1	3	0	1	1	0	11
Food and related products machine operators	8160	0	0	4	2	8	6	2	2	11	2	2	2	1	42
Pulp and papermaking plant operators	8171	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	5
Wood processing plant operators	8172	1	0	2	1	1	2	0	2	6	0	1	0	3	19
Glass and ceramics plant operators	8181	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	5
Steam engine and boiler operators	8182	2	0	0	1	3	4	2	1	1	3	0	0	0	17
Packing, bottling and labelling machine operators	8183	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Stationary plant and machine operators not elsewhere classified	8189	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Mechanical machinery assemblers	8211	1	0	1	0	1	2	1	0	4	0	0	0	0	10
Electrical and electronic equipment assemblers	8212	1	0	0	1	7	1	5	1	10	0	1	2	4	33
Assemblers not elsewhere classified	8219	0	0	0	2	10	2	1	1	16	1	1	0	1	35
Locomotive engine drivers	8311	0	0	1	0	1	1	4	0	3	0	1	0	0	11
Railway brake, signal and switch operators	8312	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	0	7
Motorcycle drivers	8321	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Car, taxi and van drivers	8322	5	1	9	11	25	11	14	1	61	0	1	10	6	155
Bus and tram drivers	8331	1	0	2	7	7	0	2	0	20	3	1	3	0	46

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Heavy truck and lorry drivers	8332	1	1	10	7	32	5	11	4	67	1	1	8	2	150
Mobile farm and forestry plant operators	8341	0	0	2	1	9	0	1	0	10	0	1	0	0	24
Earthmoving and related plant operators	8342	1	1	2	2	0	2	1	0	18	0	2	1	0	30
Crane, hoist and related plant operators	8343	0	0	2	2	3	0	0	2	12	1	0	1	0	23
Lifting truck operators	8344	1	0	0	5	1	4	0	0	18	0	1	3	2	35
Ships' deck crews and related workers	8350	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	16	1	0	0	0	18
Domestic cleaners and helpers	9111	21	0	14	11	0	0	5	2	86	0	24	1	2	166
Cleaners and helpers in offices, hotels and other establishments	9112	9	0	7	8	21	5	7	8	59	6	4	10	1	145
Hand launderers and pressers	9121	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	5
Vehicle cleaners	9122	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	5
Window cleaners	9123	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	3
Other cleaning workers	9129	6	0	1	9	11	1	2	2	10	0	1	1	2	46
Crop farm labourers	9211	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	7	0	2	0	0	14
Livestock farm labourers	9212	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	6	0	0	0	0	8
Mixed crop and livestock farm labourers	9213	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	12
Garden and horticultural labourers	9214	1	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	8	0	2	0	0	15
Forestry labourers	9215	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Mining and quarrying labourers	9311	1	0	0	1	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	8
Civil engineering labourers	9312	0	0	0	0	3	1	2	0	5	1	0	2	0	14
Building construction labourers	9313	1	0	2	3	15	4	3	3	8	0	2	2	1	44

Occupation description	ISCO-08 code (4-digits)	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IDN	KAZ	MEX	NLD	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR	Total
Hand packers	9321	0	0	2	0	0	1	1	1	4	0	0	1	0	10
Manufacturing labourers not elsewhere classified	9329	1	0	0	5	3	1	0	0	16	1	0	0	1	28
Freight handlers	9333	11	1	9	3	12	18	8	1	88	3	4	3	5	166
Shelf fillers	9334	3	0	1	11	2	1	1	0	55	0	0	1	1	76
Fast food preparers	9411	2	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	21	1	0	0	1	28
Kitchen helpers	9412	2	0	2	3	2	0	1	0	50	1	1	6	0	68
Street vendors (excluding food)	9520	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
Garbage and recycling collectors	9611	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	7
Refuse sorters	9612	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	5
Sweepers and related labourers	9613	0	0	0	1	13	1	3	1	2	1	0	1	0	23
Messengers, package deliverers and luggage porters	9621	3	0	0	0	1	2	2	2	12	0	1	3	0	26
Odd job persons	9622	0	0	1	0	7	1	0	0	13	3	2	1	0	28
Meter readers and vending-machine collectors	9623	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	5	0	1	1	0	11
Elementary workers not elsewhere classified	9629	0	0	1	2	2	0	0	2	4	0	0	1	1	13
Total		1,783	1,16	1,704	1,892	3,752	2,147	3,158	3,079	9,729	825	2,935	1,516	1,042	33,678

appendix 4 Most Frequent answer 1 = never - 5 = daily by occupation & task and by country

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
111101	5	NA	NA	NA	5	2	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
111102	1	NA	NA	NA	5	2	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
111103	1	NA	NA	NA	5	2	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
111104	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	3	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
111105	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	3	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
111106	1	NA	NA	NA	4	3	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
111107	4	NA	NA	NA	4	3	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
111108	3	NA	NA	NA	4	2	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
111201	3	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	3	3	2
111202	3	NA	NA	1	2	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	2
111203	4	NA	NA	2	1	1	1	1	1	NA	3	2	2
111204	4	NA	NA	2	1	1	1	3	1	NA	1	2	2
111205	4	NA	NA	5	2	1	1	3	1	NA	3	3	4
111206	4	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	3	1	NA	1	1	3
111207	4	NA	NA	5	1	2	1	3	1	NA	3	4	4
111208	4	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	2	1	3
111209	4	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	3	5	NA	1	1	3
111401	NA	NA	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	5	NA	NA
111402	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	NA	NA
111403	NA	NA	1	3	3	1	4	1	1	2	1	NA	NA
111404	NA	NA	1	2	3	1	5	3	1	1	1	NA	NA
111405	NA	NA	3	3	1	1	1	4	4	1	4	NA	NA
111406	NA	NA	3	2	1	1	1	4	3	2	5	NA	NA
111407	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	5	NA	NA
111408	NA	NA	1	1	2	1	4	3	2	2	5	NA	NA
111409	NA	NA	3	2	2	1	4	4	3	1	3	NA	NA
112001	5	5	5	2	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
112002	3	4	1	3	3	1	3	4	3	3	5	3	4
112003	2	4	2	2	3	1	3	3	3	2	2	2	4
112004	5	4	1	3	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5	5
112005	5	5	2	3	1	1	3	3	3	3	5	5	5
112006	5	4	1	1	1	1	1	5	3	1	5	5	5
112007	3	5	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	3
112008	4	4	3	3	3	4	4	5	4	4	5	5	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
112009	1	2	1	1	1	1	3	3	1	3	1	3	3
112010	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
112011	5	5	1	3	5	1	5	5	5	2	5	5	5
121101	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5
121102	5	NA	3	5	3	5	3	5	3	5	3	3	5
121103	4	NA	4	4	3	3	5	5	4	5	3	4	5
121104	3	NA	3	3	3	5	3	5	3	3	3	4	5
121105	5	NA	3	3	1	5	5	5	3	3	4	5	5
121106	5	NA	5	5	3	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5
121107	5	NA	1	3	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	1
121108	5	NA	1	3	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	3	1
121201	5	5	3	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	2
121202	3	5	3	5	5	3	5	5	3	5	5	5	1
121203	3	5	2	2	3	2	5	2	3	3	2	2	1
121204	5	5	2	2	2	3	3	4	3	1	3	1	1
121205	3	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1
121206	5	5	3	4	3	3	5	5	5	3	5	3	5
121207	5	5	1	1	1	5	1	5	3	1	3	1	4
121208	5	5	5	5	4	3	5	5	3	5	5	5	5
121209	3	5	5	3	3	3	5	3	3	5	5	5	3
121210	5	5	5	4	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	4
121211	1	5	3	3	1	3	3	3	3	5	3	3	1
121301	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	1	NA	NA	NA	4	4	NA	NA
121302	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	NA	5	2	NA	NA
121303	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	5	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA
121304	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	3	2	NA	NA
121305	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	5	NA	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA
121306	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	5	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA
121307	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA
121308	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	4	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA
121901	5	5	3	3	1	1	5	5	1	3	5	5	5
121902	5	4	4	5	5	1	5	5	3	4	5	5	5
121903	5	4	3	3	1	5	2	1	3	2	3	3	3
121904	4	3	2	3	3	4	3	4	3	3	3	5	1
121905	5	3	1	3	3	1	3	3	2	3	3	3	3
121906	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	3	5	5	5
121907	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
121908	5	5	2	5	1	1	1	5	3	3	1	4	1
121909	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	3	5	5	5
121910	5	5	4	5	1	2	1	5	3	3	3	1	1
122101	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	3
122102	3	2	5	2	5	3	3	3	3	5	3	4	3

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
122103	4	5	3	3	1	3	1	3	3	3	5	4	3
122104	3	5	5	5	1	5	1	4	5	1	5	4	5
122105	4	5	5	5	1	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5
122106	4	3	1	5	1	3	1	3	3	1	3	3	3
122107	1	4	1	3	1	3	1	5	3	1	5	3	1
122108	2	3	2	2	1	3	1	2	2	1	2	3	2
122201	1	5	5	NA	1	1	5	5	5	4	4	5	1
122202	1	1	3	NA	5	1	5	3	3	5	1	4	3
122203	1	4	2	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
122204	1	5	5	NA	1	1	4	5	5	1	5	5	1
122205	4	4	1	NA	1	1	3	3	2	3	1	1	4
122206	5	4	2	NA	5	2	4	3	5	1	5	4	5
122207	5	5	5	NA	1	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5
122208	4	5	1	NA	1	5	1	5	3	5	1	5	1
122301	4	NA	5	4	1	5	3	5	5	5	5	4	1
122302	1	NA	1	3	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	4	1
122303	4	NA	5	5	1	4	1	1	5	1	5	5	3
122304	1	NA	1	3	1	1	3	3	3	3	1	2	1
122305	1	NA	1	5	5	3	1	3	3	4	5	2	5
122306	5	NA	5	5	1	5	1	5	4	5	5	5	5
122307	1	NA	1	5	5	1	1	3	3	3	1	2	1
122308	1	NA	3	1	2	1	3	3	2	1	2	2	4
131101	2	NA	NA	3	1	3	2	5	NA	5	1	NA	2
131102	4	NA	NA	3	4	3	3	3	NA	5	2	NA	2
131103	1	NA	NA	3	1	1	2	5	NA	5	1	NA	1
131104	3	NA	NA	NA	4	1	NA	1	NA	5	1	NA	1
131105	4	NA	NA	NA	1	1	2	3	NA	3	1	NA	5
131106	2	NA	NA	2	1	1	2	2	NA	4	2	NA	4
131107	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	2	2	NA	4	2	NA	3
131108	3	NA	NA	2	1	1	2	2	NA	5	1	NA	5
131109	4	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	2
131110	5	NA	NA	5	3	1	2	3	NA	NA	1	NA	4
131111	4	NA	NA	4	4	1	2	3	NA	NA	1	NA	5
131112	3	NA	NA	2	2	1	2	3	NA	NA	3	NA	3
131201	NA	2	NA	NA									
131202	NA	1	NA	NA									
131203	NA	1	NA	NA									
131204	NA	2	NA	NA									
131205	NA	1	NA	NA									
131206	NA	2	NA	NA									
131207	NA	1	NA	NA									
131208	NA	1	NA	NA									

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
131209	NA	1	NA	NA									
131210	NA	1	NA	NA									
131211	NA	1	NA	NA									
131212	NA	1	NA	NA									
131213	NA	5	NA	NA									
132101	5	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	4	5	3	4	5	5
132102	3	NA	4	5	5	NA	2	3	3	3	4	5	5
132103	5	NA	2	5	5	NA	3	2	5	3	5	5	5
132104	4	NA	4	3	5	NA	5	3	3	3	4	1	5
132105	3	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	4	4	5	4	5	5
132106	2	NA	1	2	4	NA	2	3	2	2	1	2	3
132107	3	NA	1	5	5	NA	3	4	4	3	5	5	4
132108	1	NA	1	4	5	NA	5	2	2	4	2	1	2
132109	3	NA	3	2	5	NA	1	1	2	1	5	1	1
132110	2	NA	1	3	5	NA	1	1	2	2	1	5	4
132111	3	NA	1	1	5	NA	3	1	2	1	1	1	1
132112	1	NA	3	2	5	NA	3	3	3	4	5	3	4
132201	2	NA	NA	5	NA	1	4	2	1	NA	1	3	NA
132202	2	NA	NA	4	NA	4	1	2	1	NA	5	4	NA
132203	2	NA	NA	5	NA	3	1	3	1	NA	5	5	NA
132204	2	NA	NA	4	NA	5	1	3	1	NA	5	5	NA
132205	3	NA	NA	3	NA	3	1	3	4	NA	1	2	NA
132206	2	NA	NA	2	NA	3	1	5	1	NA	1	4	NA
132207	3	NA	NA	3	NA	5	3	5	5	NA	5	4	NA
132208	2	NA	NA	3	NA	1	1	4	1	NA	5	3	NA
132209	3	NA	NA	4	NA	1	1	5	1	NA	5	3	NA
132210	2	NA	NA	2	NA	3	3	3	1	NA	5	2	NA
132301	5	5	4	1	5	5	NA	5	4	NA	5	5	4
132302	5	5	1	1	5	5	NA	4	5	NA	5	5	4
132303	5	5	2	5	3	4	NA	4	3	NA	5	1	4
132304	3	5	4	1	1	4	NA	1	4	NA	1	5	4
132305	5	5	3	1	4	4	NA	4	1	NA	5	5	4
132306	5	5	2	5	5	4	NA	4	4	NA	5	5	4
132307	1	5	1	1	1	4	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA
132308	5	5	1	5	5	4	NA	4	4	NA	1	1	3
132309	1	4	1	5	1	4	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA
132310	5	5	3	1	1	4	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	5
132311	5	2	2	5	5	4	NA	4	4	NA	5	5	4
132401	5	5	1	5	1	1	1	5	4	3	5	5	5
132402	4	5	1	5	1	1	1	4	1	1	4	5	1
132403	2	2	1	1	3	1	1	2	3	1	3	1	1
132404	4	5	1	3	4	5	1	4	3	3	5	5	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
132405	3	5	5	1	5	5	3	4	3	5	5	5	4
132406	5	5	5	1	3	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5
132407	5	5	5	1	1	5	1	5	1	1	5	5	4
132408	3	5	1	1	1	3	1	4	3	1	1	5	1
132409	4	3	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	4	5	5	5
132410	5	5	5	5	4	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5
132411	2	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	3
133001	4	NA	5	5	4	2	1	4	5	1	5	5	5
133002	3	NA	4	5	3	1	1	2	3	1	5	4	4
133003	5	NA	3	5	3	2	1	3	3	1	5	5	3
133004	4	NA	5	5	4	3	2	3	5	1	5	4	5
133005	1	NA	3	5	3	4	3	3	3	1	5	2	4
133006	1	NA	5	5	5	4	1	5	5	4	5	5	5
133007	3	NA	3	5	3	1	2	3	3	1	3	3	4
133008	2	NA	3	1	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	4
133009	5	NA	3	3	3	2	2	3	4	2	3	3	4
133010	2	NA	2	2	3	2	1	2	2	1	3	4	3
133011	2	NA	2	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	2	2	2
134101	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	4	NA	5	NA	3
134102	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	3	NA	3	NA	1
134103	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	4	NA	3	NA	4
134104	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5
134105	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	3	NA	5	NA	3
134106	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	3	NA	2	NA	3
134107	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	4	NA	3	NA	3
134108	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	4	NA	5	NA	4
134109	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	3	NA	2	NA	1
134201	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	5	3	5	NA	NA	3	5
134202	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	2	3	5	NA	NA	3	5
134203	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	5	3	5	NA	NA	1	5
134204	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	4	2	3	4	NA	NA	2	2
134205	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	5	3	4	NA	NA	2	4
134206	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	4	3	3	1	NA	NA	3	1
134207	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	2	3	4	NA	NA	1	5
134208	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	3	2	3	4	NA	NA	1	5
134209	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	2	2	1	4	NA	NA	1	3
134210	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	5	2	1	1	NA	NA	1	2
134301	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	5
134302	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5
134303	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	5
134304	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	3
134305	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	1	NA	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
134306	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	4
134307	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	5	NA	4
134308	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	4
134309	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	2
134310	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	2
134401	NA	NA	4	3	NA	NA	NA	2	5	NA	4	NA	5
134402	NA	NA	3	2	NA	NA	NA	3	2	NA	3	NA	5
134403	NA	NA	3	3	NA	NA	NA	4	3	NA	4	NA	5
134404	NA	NA	2	3	NA	NA	NA	2	1	NA	4	NA	1
134405	NA	NA	4	2	NA	NA	NA	3	3	NA	1	NA	5
134406	NA	NA	3	2	NA	NA	NA	2	2	NA	2	NA	1
134407	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	2	NA	2	NA	3
134408	NA	NA	2	3	NA	NA	NA	2	2	NA	2	NA	1
134409	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	2	3	NA	4	NA	1
134410	NA	NA	3	3	NA	NA	NA	2	3	NA	4	NA	5
134411	NA	NA	3	2	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	2	NA	2
134501	2	NA	4	1	1	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	1
134502	4	NA	4	1	4	2	5	1	3	2	2	4	5
134503	4	NA	4	2	4	3	1	5	4	2	2	4	4
134504	3	NA	4	1	4	5	1	5	4	2	3	4	4
134505	5	NA	4	5	4	3	5	5	5	5	3	4	5
134506	5	NA	3	1	4	5	4	4	3	4	2	3	4
134507	5	NA	3	2	3	1	1	5	3	3	2	3	5
134508	4	NA	4	1	1	5	1	2	3	3	2	3	4
134509	5	NA	4	1	2	3	3	2	2	3	2	4	5
134510	4	NA	4	1	2	1	3	1	2	2	2	3	2
134511	5	NA	4	1	1	3	1	3	3	2	2	3	3
134601	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	1
134602	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	1	5	5	5	1
134603	2	5	1	5	3	1	4	5	5	4	1	5	1
134604	5	1	5	5	4	5	2	5	5	1	5	5	1
134605	1	1	5	5	3	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134606	1	5	5	5	1	5	2	1	4	1	1	1	1
134607	1	3	5	5	5	5	5	1	1	4	1	1	1
134608	1	4	5	5	2	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134609	5	5	1	3	1	2	3	1	1	1	5	5	5
134610	5	3	5	3	2	5	2	5	3	3	5	5	4
134611	5	5	4	5	4	3	5	3	3	1	5	5	1
134901	5	NA	5	1	1	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	4
134902	5	NA	1	1	1	NA	5	NA	3	1	NA	2	2
134903	5	NA	4	3	5	NA	1	NA	4	1	NA	2	3
134904	5	NA	4	2	5	NA	2	NA	2	1	NA	3	4

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
134905	1	NA	5	2	1	NA	2	NA	1	1	NA	3	4
134906	5	NA	5	3	5	NA	2	NA	2	1	NA	4	4
134907	5	NA	1	3	3	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	5
134908	3	NA	5	3	1	NA	1	NA	2	1	NA	2	4
134909	5	NA	3	1	1	NA	2	NA	2	1	NA	1	3
141101	5	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5
141102	4	5	1	4	NA	1	4	1	4	5	5	3	4
141103	5	4	5	4	NA	5	4	4	5	1	5	3	5
141104	5	1	1	1	NA	1	4	5	5	5	1	3	5
141105	5	5	5	4	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
141106	5	5	5	4	NA	1	4	4	5	5	5	5	5
141107	5	4	3	4	NA	5	4	4	4	5	3	5	2
141108	1	5	5	4	NA	3	4	3	4	3	5	5	4
141109	5	5	4	4	NA	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	4
141110	4	5	5	4	NA	5	5	5	5	4	5	1	4
141201	4	NA	3	NA	3	1	3	3	1	3	5	5	1
141202	1	NA	1	NA	5	1	4	3	1	4	5	3	3
141203	5	NA	4	NA	5	1	4	5	4	4	5	3	3
141204	3	NA	5	NA	5	1	3	5	4	4	5	5	3
141205	4	NA	4	NA	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	3
141206	5	NA	4	NA	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5
141207	3	NA	3	NA	5	1	5	4	5	4	5	4	4
141208	5	NA	4	NA	1	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	2
141209	5	NA	3	NA	1	5	4	5	1	4	5	5	1
141210	5	NA	4	NA	3	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	4
142001	5	5	5	5	4	1	5	5	4	5	5	3	5
142002	1	4	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	3	5	3	1
142003	5	3	1	1	5	5	3	5	1	3	5	5	5
142004	1	4	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5
142005	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	5	1	1	1	4
142006	1	5	2	1	1	3	3	1	5	2	5	1	5
142007	1	5	3	1	1	1	1	1	5	2	5	1	5
143101	1	NA	5	NA	2	NA	1	3	3	NA	1	2	NA
143102	4	NA	4	NA	5	NA	1	5	5	NA	4	5	NA
143103	1	NA	4	NA	2	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	2	NA
143104	1	NA	4	NA	3	NA	3	4	1	NA	1	3	NA
143105	3	NA	5	NA	3	NA	1	5	4	NA	3	5	NA
143106	4	NA	5	NA	5	NA	3	4	3	NA	3	5	NA
143107	4	NA	5	NA	2	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	5	NA
143108	5	NA	4	NA	5	NA	2	1	5	NA	5	5	NA
143109	2	NA	4	NA	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	1	5	NA
211101	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	5	1	NA	2	NA	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
211102	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	5	4	NA	3	NA	5
211103	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	4	4	NA	2	NA	5
211104	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	4	1	NA	4	NA	5
211105	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
211106	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
211107	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	3	1	NA	1	NA	5
211108	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
211109	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
211110	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	1	1	NA	4	NA	NA
211111	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	3	2	NA	1	NA	5
211201	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211202	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211203	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211204	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211205	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211206	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211208	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211209	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211210	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211301	1	NA	1	4	1	2	2	5	5	5	1	1	3
211302	5	NA	1	5	1	4	1	1	5	5	4	1	5
211303	1	NA	3	3	1	3	1	3	4	3	3	1	5
211304	1	NA	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	5	2	1	1
211305	1	NA	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	4
211306	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
211307	1	NA	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
211308	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
211309	4	NA	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	5	2	1	2
211401	1	NA	NA	4	2	5	1	4	1	1	3	1	2
211402	1	NA	NA	5	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	2	3
211403	2	NA	NA	1	4	4	5	5	4	3	1	4	3
211404	5	NA	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3
211405	1	NA	NA	1	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1
211406	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4
211407	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
211408	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
211409	1	NA	NA	1	2	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
211410	1	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1
211411	1	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	1	4	1	1	2	1
211412	1	NA	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
212001	5	1	1	4	NA	4	2	3	5	NA	1	5	2

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
212002	5	2	5	3	NA	5	2	1	1	NA	5	5	5
212003	1	1	4	3	NA	5	2	1	4	NA	5	5	5
212004	2	1	4	4	NA	5	1	1	4	NA	5	5	4
212005	1	5	1	2	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	3	1	4
212006	5	5	4	4	NA	NA	5	5	1	NA	1	1	5
212007	1	5	4	4	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	1	5	5
212008	1	2	1	2	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	1	1	1
212009	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	4	1	2	NA	5	2	3
213101	3	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	5	NA
213102	2	NA	3	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	5	NA
213103	1	NA	2	NA	1	NA	1	5	4	NA	NA	1	NA
213104	1	NA	3	NA	5	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	5	NA
213105	1	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA
213106	2	NA	2	NA	1	NA	1	1	4	NA	NA	2	NA
213107	2	NA	1	NA	1	NA	2	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA
213108	2	NA	1	NA	1	NA	2	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA
213201	1	NA	1	2	1	1	3	3	1	NA	5	4	2
213202	2	NA	1	4	3	1	1	3	1	NA	5	1	1
213203	4	NA	4	1	1	1	3	1	3	NA	1	3	1
213204	3	NA	3	1	5	1	4	2	1	NA	5	1	1
213205	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
213206	1	NA	1	1	1	1	4	4	1	NA	5	1	1
213207	3	NA	2	3	4	1	1	5	3	NA	5	3	1
213208	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
213209	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
213210	1	NA	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
213211	1	NA	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	3	1
213301	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	1	NA	3	2	3	NA	NA
213302	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	2	1	NA	4	1	5	NA	NA
213303	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA
213304	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	2	NA	1	2	2	NA	NA
213305	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	3	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA
213306	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	3	NA	3	1	3	NA	NA
213307	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	3	NA	1	2	1	NA	NA
214101	2	2	1	1	2	3	2	1	3	2	1	1	1
214102	1	2	1	1	1	3	1	5	1	1	1	3	1
214103	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	3
214104	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1
214105	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	4	5	1
214106	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	3	1	1
214107	5	2	1	4	5	1	5	5	1	1	1	1	1
214108	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
214109	2	3	1	4	3	1	1	3	1	2	3	3	1
214110	5	1	4	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1
214201	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1
214202	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	5	5	1
214203	3	NA	1	5	5	2	3	5	1	1	5	3	1
214204	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	1
214205	4	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	3	1
214206	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
214207	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	4
214301	4	NA	NA	1	2	NA	3	1	1	1	1	4	4
214302	4	NA	NA	3	2	NA	3	1	2	3	3	1	3
214303	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	4	2	5	3	1	3	1
214304	4	NA	NA	3	2	NA	5	5	1	2	5	3	1
214305	3	NA	NA	4	2	NA	1	3	1	3	3	4	1
214306	4	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	5	1	2	3	3	1
214307	5	NA	NA	1	2	NA	5	3	4	2	3	4	1
214308	4	NA	NA	1	2	NA	5	1	3	1	1	5	1
214309	3	NA	NA	1	2	NA	5	5	3	3	3	5	1
214401	1	2	3	1	1	4	1	1	4	2	5	1	4
214402	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1
214403	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	1	1	1
214404	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
214405	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1
214406	3	3	3	1	1	1	3	4	3	1	3	2	1
214407	5	3	3	5	2	5	5	5	4	3	5	3	5
214501	3	NA	1	2	3	NA	2	1	1	1	1	1	NA
214502	5	NA	1	4	3	NA	1	5	1	3	3	2	NA
214503	4	NA	2	4	5	NA	1	1	2	1	5	3	NA
214504	1	NA	1	2	1	NA	5	1	1	1	2	5	NA
214505	1	NA	3	5	5	NA	1	1	4	4	3	1	NA
214506	1	NA	1	2	1	NA	1	1	2	1	3	1	NA
214507	1	NA	3	4	1	NA	1	1	3	1	4	2	NA
214508	1	NA	1	2	5	NA	5	1	1	1	3	1	NA
214601	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	NA
214602	NA	NA	NA	1	1	3	2	1	1	3	1	4	NA
214603	NA	NA	NA	1	1	2	1	1	2	NA	1	4	NA
214604	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	4	NA	1	1	NA
214605	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	3	2	1	NA	1	4	NA
214606	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	4	1	NA	1	1	NA
214607	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	3	NA	1	1	NA
214608	NA	NA	NA	1	5	2	5	3	1	NA	1	1	NA
214609	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	2	2	1	NA	1	1	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
214901	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1
214902	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1
214903	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1
214904	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1
214905	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	4	2
214906	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1
214907	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1
214908	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1
214909	3	NA	4	4	1	NA	5	1	3	5	NA	5	1
215101	1	3	1	4	1	NA	1	1	1	2	1	1	2
215102	1	4	1	1	5	NA	5	1	1	5	1	1	1
215103	1	3	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	3	1	1	4
215104	3	3	1	1	1	NA	1	4	2	1	1	1	3
215105	1	3	3	5	1	NA	1	5	1	3	1	1	3
215106	1	5	1	1	5	NA	1	1	1	3	1	2	5
215201	1	NA	1	1	2	NA	1	3	5	5	1	5	4
215202	4	NA	1	1	1	NA	3	5	3	4	5	1	1
215203	3	NA	4	1	1	NA	1	5	3	2	1	1	2
215204	3	NA	1	1	5	NA	3	5	1	3	3	1	3
215205	1	NA	1	3	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
215206	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
215207	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
215208	1	NA	1	3	1	NA	1	3	3	1	1	4	2
215301	1	NA	2	2	1	3	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
215302	1	NA	2	5	1	3	1	1	1	1	3	1	3
215303	1	NA	3	5	1	2	5	5	1	5	5	1	3
215304	4	NA	3	5	1	2	3	5	4	5	1	5	4
215305	4	NA	3	5	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1
215306	1	NA	1	5	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
215307	3	NA	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
216101	1	2	2	1	1	2	NA	1	2	1	2	1	NA
216102	1	3	3	3	1	1	NA	1	4	2	4	1	NA
216103	4	3	4	2	1	3	NA	4	5	3	5	3	NA
216104	5	3	5	4	5	3	NA	5	5	4	5	5	NA
216105	1	3	1	5	1	3	NA	1	1	1	5	4	NA
216106	1	3	4	1	1	1	NA	1	4	1	5	1	NA
216107	5	3	2	4	5	3	NA	5	5	1	5	5	NA
216108	4	2	2	5	1	4	NA	5	3	1	5	4	NA
216109	4	3	4	4	5	1	NA	4	5	1	5	5	NA
216201	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	3	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
216202	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	1	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
216203	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
216204	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	3	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
216205	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	3	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
216206	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
216207	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	2	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
216208	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	2	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
216209	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	2	NA	3	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
216301	1	NA	1	1	1	3	2	4	4	4	1	5	3
216302	4	NA	1	4	5	4	5	1	5	4	3	5	4
216303	1	NA	4	5	1	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	4
216304	1	NA	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	4
216305	5	NA	3	5	5	4	5	5	3	3	5	5	4
216306	5	NA	5	4	1	4	5	5	5	3	5	5	4
216307	5	NA	1	5	5	4	5	5	5	3	5	5	4
216308	4	NA	1	5	1	5	5	5	1	3	3	3	4
216309	4	NA	1	4	1	5	5	5	1	3	4	1	4
216401	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	1	5	NA	3	NA	1
216402	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	3	NA	4	NA	1
216403	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	1	4	NA	5	NA	3
216404	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	5	4	NA	3	NA	1
216405	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	1	3	NA	4	NA	1
216406	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	1	1	NA	4	NA	3
216407	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	5	5	NA	3	NA	1
216408	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	1	5	NA	4	NA	1
216409	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	1	1	NA	5	NA	1
216501	5	NA	3	NA	1	5	2	3	1	NA	5	1	NA
216502	3	NA	4	NA	3	5	2	5	5	NA	5	4	NA
216503	1	NA	1	NA	1	2	1	2	1	NA	1	1	NA
216504	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	NA
216505	1	NA	3	NA	1	NA	1	3	1	NA	5	1	NA
216506	1	NA	3	NA	1	3	1	2	1	NA	5	1	NA
216507	1	NA	1	NA	1	2	1	3	1	NA	2	1	NA
216508	1	NA	4	NA	1	3	2	1	3	NA	5	1	NA
216601	5	5	1	4	1	1	5	1	3	1	5	1	4
216602	1	5	1	3	4	1	1	4	1	1	5	1	4
216603	5	5	4	1	5	4	5	5	3	4	5	5	5
216604	5	4	5	3	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5
216605	1	3	1	1	4	5	1	5	1	1	5	5	1
216606	1	3	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	5	1
216607	5	4	4	1	5	1	5	5	1	4	5	4	1
216608	1	5	4	1	5	3	1	4	3	3	3	4	4
216609	5	3	4	1	5	5	5	5	4	3	5	4	4
216610	5	4	1	1	1	4	5	5	5	3	5	5	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
221101	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA
221102	1	NA	5	4	5	1	5	5	4	5	5	5	NA
221103	1	NA	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA
221104	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	3	5	5	4	1	NA
221105	5	NA	4	1	5	5	5	5	4	5	1	5	NA
221106	5	NA	4	4	5	5	5	5	3	3	5	5	NA
221107	1	NA	1	5	1	1	5	5	1	1	1	1	NA
221108	1	NA	5	1	5	3	5	5	4	5	5	1	NA
221109	1	NA	1	4	3	1	3	1	2	1	3	5	NA
221110	1	NA	3	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA
221111	5	NA	1	2	3	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	NA
221201	5	NA	2	1	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5
221202	5	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	5	4	5	5	NA	5
221203	5	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	NA	4
221204	5	NA	4	1	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	NA	4
221205	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	5	1	NA	5
221206	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1
221207	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	NA	4
221208	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	5	NA	3
221209	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	5	5	4	5	5	NA	5
221210	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1
221211	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1
221212	1	NA	5	1	1	NA	5	2	1	1	1	NA	1
222101	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5
222102	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5
222103	5	NA	1	5	1	5	1	5	5	1	1	1	4
222104	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
222105	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	1
222106	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5
222107	1	NA	2	5	3	5	5	5	2	1	1	1	3
222108	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
222109	5	NA	1	5	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	1
222110	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3
222201	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
222202	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
222203	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
222204	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
222205	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
222206	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
222207	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
222208	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA
223001	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
223002	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
223003	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
223004	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
223005	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
223006	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
223007	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
224001	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	5	5	1	NA	1	NA	NA
224002	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	5	1	NA	3	NA	NA
224003	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	4	1	NA	1	NA	NA
224004	5	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	4	NA	NA
224005	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
224006	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	1	3	1	NA	1	NA	NA
224007	5	NA	5	NA	3	5	5	5	5	NA	1	NA	NA
224008	5	NA	4	NA	1	5	1	3	1	NA	4	NA	NA
224009	1	NA	4	NA	2	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
224010	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	1	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
225001	2	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	4	1	4
225002	4	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	5	5	NA	4	4	5
225003	1	NA	3	NA	3	NA	1	1	4	NA	3	1	5
225004	1	NA	2	NA	5	NA	1	1	4	NA	3	1	4
225005	5	NA	1	NA	5	NA	3	5	2	NA	4	4	5
225006	5	NA	1	NA	5	NA	3	1	5	NA	4	1	2
225007	5	NA	1	NA	5	NA	3	1	2	NA	3	3	3
225008	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	4	4	5
225009	1	NA	2	NA	1	NA	1	1	4	NA	3	1	5
226101	NA	NA	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA
226102	NA	NA	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA
226103	NA	NA	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA
226104	NA	NA	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA
226105	NA	NA	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	NA	1	2	NA	NA
226106	NA	NA	NA	1	1	5	NA	4	NA	1	5	NA	NA
226107	NA	NA	NA	3	1	5	NA	4	NA	1	2	NA	NA
226108	NA	NA	NA	1	1	3	NA	4	NA	1	2	NA	NA
226109	NA	NA	NA	1	1	3	NA	4	NA	1	3	NA	NA
226110	NA	NA	NA	1	1	4	NA	5	NA	3	5	NA	NA
226111	NA	NA	NA	4	5	3	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA
226112	NA	NA	NA	4	3	4	NA	1	NA	5	5	NA	NA
226201	NA	NA	1	1	5	5	2	5	5	4	1	2	NA
226202	NA	NA	5	5	1	5	2	1	5	1	1	1	NA
226203	NA	NA	1	1	1	2	3	5	5	1	1	4	NA
226204	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	2	1	5	4	1	4	NA
226205	NA	NA	1	1	1	5	5	5	5	1	5	4	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
226206	NA	NA	1	5	5	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	NA
226207	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	2	5	5	5	1	1	NA
226208	NA	NA	1	5	5	1	NA	1	5	5	1	1	NA
226209	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA
226210	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	5	1	NA
226211	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	NA
226212	NA	NA	1	1	5	5	3	1	1	5	5	1	NA
226213	NA	NA	1	5	1	5	2	1	1	1	1	1	NA
226301	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	2	NA	5	2	NA	5	3	4
226302	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	2	NA	3	1	NA	5	1	3
226303	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	2	NA	1	1	NA	5	1	1
226304	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	3	NA	5	1	NA	5	4	4
226305	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	3	NA	4	1	NA	4	1	3
226306	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	3	NA	5	2	NA	5	4	1
226307	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	2	NA	5	2	NA	1	3	3
226308	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	2	NA	5	2	NA	5	3	3
226309	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	3	NA	5	2	NA	3	3	4
226310	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	3	NA	3	1	NA	3	1	3
226401	1	NA	3	1	5	5	4	1	5	5	5	5	1
226402	3	NA	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4
226403	1	NA	1	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	1
226404	3	NA	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	1
226405	3	NA	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	5	3	1
226406	1	NA	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	1	3	3	1
226407	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1
226501	5	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
226502	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
226503	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
226504	5	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
226505	5	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
226506	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
226507	3	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
226601	NA	NA	4	1	5	NA	NA	5	4	NA	5	NA	NA
226602	NA	NA	4	1	5	NA	NA	5	4	NA	5	NA	NA
226603	NA	NA	1	1	3	NA	NA	5	3	NA	5	NA	NA
226604	NA	NA	4	1	1	NA	NA	2	1	NA	4	NA	NA
226605	NA	NA	5	3	1	NA	NA	3	1	NA	4	NA	NA
226606	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	4	5	NA	4	NA	NA
226607	NA	NA	4	1	1	NA	NA	4	2	NA	3	NA	NA
226701	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
226702	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
226703	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA	1	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
226704	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	NA	NA	5	NA
226705	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	4	NA
226706	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
226707	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
226901	5	NA	4	NA	5	5	5	3	1	NA	4	5	4
226902	5	NA	1	NA	5	1	2	4	5	NA	5	5	4
226903	1	NA	4	NA	5	1	5	4	5	NA	5	5	4
226904	1	NA	1	NA	1	5	1	3	1	NA	5	5	1
226905	4	NA	1	NA	5	1	1	4	1	NA	1	5	1
226906	4	NA	4	NA	1	4	5	4	1	NA	5	5	1
226907	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	5	1	1	NA	5	1	1
226908	1	NA	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
231001	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	1
231002	3	1	1	2	5	5	5	3	1	5	3	4	1
231003	4	4	1	2	1	4	4	5	1	1	5	5	1
231004	1	3	1	3	2	4	5	4	1	2	3	4	1
231005	4	3	1	3	1	3	3	3	1	1	1	1	1
231006	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
231007	1	2	5	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	5	5	5
231008	2	2	1	5	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	3
231009	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	4	3
232001	NA	3	4	NA	2	1	2	2	4	2	4	2	1
232002	NA	5	4	NA	2	3	1	3	2	5	1	2	5
232003	NA	5	5	NA	5	1	5	2	5	5	5	NA	5
232004	NA	5	1	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	3	1
232005	NA	5	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
232006	NA	4	2	NA	5	3	5	3	3	4	5	5	5
232007	NA	4	5	NA	5	3	3	3	5	5	5	3	5
232008	NA	1	5	NA	1	1	4	3	5	1	5	5	1
232009	NA	4	4	NA	4	1	4	5	4	4	5	5	5
232010	NA	4	1	NA	2	1	2	4	1	1	5	5	5
233001	2	NA	3	5	2	2	2	4	2	2	3	2	2
233002	5	NA	3	2	5	3	5	5	1	1	5	5	5
233003	5	NA	3	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
233004	5	NA	4	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5
233005	4	NA	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
233006	5	NA	4	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5
233007	5	NA	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
233008	4	NA	3	5	5	3	5	3	3	5	5	5	4
233009	3	NA	3	5	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
233010	3	NA	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	1	3
233011	3	NA	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
234101	5	NA	5	1	5	3	5	4	4	NA	4	5	5
234102	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
234103	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
234104	2	NA	2	5	3	4	3	3	3	NA	5	5	3
234105	5	NA	5	4	5	5	5	5	4	NA	5	5	5
234106	3	NA	4	5	5	5	5	3	5	NA	4	5	3
234107	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
234108	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
234109	3	NA	4	5	4	4	3	3	4	NA	4	1	4
234110	3	NA	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	NA	3	3	3
234201	3	5	4	3	5	3	3	4	4	NA	5	NA	NA
234202	5	5	4	5	5	1	1	3	5	NA	5	NA	NA
234203	4	4	4	5	1	4	1	3	5	NA	5	NA	NA
234204	5	5	4	5	5	5	1	5	3	NA	5	NA	NA
234205	5	5	4	5	1	4	1	3	4	NA	4	NA	NA
234206	5	3	3	5	5	5	1	5	5	NA	5	NA	NA
234207	5	5	4	5	5	5	1	5	5	NA	5	NA	NA
234208	3	5	3	5	1	4	3	3	4	NA	3	NA	NA
234209	4	3	1	3	1	1	2	1	3	NA	1	NA	NA
235101	1	NA	2	1	5	1	5	3	1	1	4	2	3
235102	1	NA	2	1	5	2	2	4	1	2	1	4	3
235103	1	NA	2	1	1	1	1	5	1	2	3	1	5
235104	1	NA	2	1	2	1	1	2	3	1	4	1	2
235105	1	NA	3	1	4	1	1	2	1	2	4	1	5
235106	2	NA	2	1	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	3
235107	1	NA	3	1	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	2
235108	1	NA	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
235109	1	NA	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
235110	1	NA	3	1	3	1	3	3	1	1	3	1	5
235201	2	NA	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	2	5	NA	NA
235202	2	NA	1	4	5	2	5	3	5	2	4	NA	NA
235203	2	NA	1	1	5	1	5	5	5	2	5	NA	NA
235204	2	NA	1	4	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	NA	NA
235205	3	NA	1	4	5	5	5	4	2	3	5	NA	NA
235206	2	NA	1	3	1	5	1	4	1	1	5	NA	NA
235207	2	NA	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	NA	NA
235208	2	NA	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	1	4	NA	NA
235209	2	NA	4	1	4	3	3	3	5	2	5	NA	NA
235210	2	NA	4	1	5	5	5	5	3	1	5	NA	NA
235211	2	NA	3	1	3	5	4	3	4	NA	5	NA	NA
235301	NA	NA	NA	2	3	4	5	5	4	3	5	3	4
235302	NA	NA	NA	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	3	5	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
235303	NA	NA	NA	1	1	2	1	4	5	2	4	4	4
235304	NA	NA	NA	3	3	NA	5	5	4	1	4	4	4
235305	NA	NA	NA	5	1	5	1	5	5	1	4	5	1
235306	NA	NA	NA	5	1	2	1	1	1	1	4	1	1
235307	NA	NA	NA	1	2	4	1	3	2	3	4	3	4
235308	NA	NA	NA	5	3	4	5	3	4	1	4	3	3
235401	5	5	NA	2	5	1	3	3	1	5	NA	5	NA
235402	5	1	NA	2	2	1	2	3	4	5	NA	3	NA
235403	5	2	NA	3	2	4	5	1	2	5	NA	5	NA
235404	5	5	NA	4	5	4	5	5	2	5	NA	5	NA
235405	3	5	NA	4	5	4	5	5	2	5	NA	5	NA
235406	5	5	NA	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	NA	5	NA
235407	5	5	NA	4	5	1	5	3	2	5	NA	5	NA
235408	2	5	NA	4	4	1	2	1	2	2	NA	5	NA
235409	5	2	NA	3	3	1	3	3	2	3	NA	5	NA
235410	2	1	NA	2	2	1	2	1	2	3	NA	1	NA
235411	5	2	NA	1	3	4	3	2	2	3	NA	5	NA
235501	4	NA	NA	NA	5	4	5	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA
235502	2	NA	NA	NA	1	4	5	NA	5	5	NA	4	NA
235503	2	NA	NA	NA	1	4	5	NA	5	2	NA	4	NA
235504	4	NA	NA	NA	5	1	4	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA
235505	4	NA	NA	NA	5	1	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA
235506	3	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA
235507	3	NA	NA	NA	2	2	2	NA	4	2	NA	4	NA
235508	3	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	4	3	NA	3	NA
235509	2	NA	NA	NA	3	1	3	NA	3	3	NA	3	NA
235510	2	NA	NA	NA	3	1	2	NA	2	3	NA	3	NA
235601	1	NA	2	3	5	1	5	4	3	1	4	3	1
235602	5	NA	3	4	1	2	2	2	3	3	4	4	4
235603	1	NA	3	5	1	2	2	1	5	4	3	4	2
235604	5	NA	3	2	1	2	1	2	3	3	2	1	4
235605	5	NA	3	2	1	1	3	1	3	3	4	2	1
235606	3	NA	3	2	1	1	3	1	2	4	3	3	5
235901	3	5	5	4	5	2	5	3	5	3	5	5	5
235902	1	5	4	4	5	4	2	5	5	4	5	5	5
235903	1	5	5	4	5	4	2	4	5	3	5	5	4
235904	1	5	5	4	3	4	2	4	5	3	5	5	1
235905	1	5	NA	5	4	4	5	5	5	3	5	4	4
235906	1	5	NA	1	5	4	3	3	5	3	5	5	5
235907	1	3	NA	5	2	4	2	4	4	3	4	3	3
235908	1	5	NA	1	2	3	2	3	5	3	4	5	1
235909	1	1	NA	5	5	2	1	3	4	1	5	4	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
235910	1	1	NA	5	5	2	5	5	4	1	5	5	1
235911	1	4	NA	1	5	3	5	3	4	4	5	4	1
241101	1	5	3	3	5	1	5	3	4	3	3	3	3
241102	1	1	3	4	3	1	3	3	3	1	3	3	1
241103	1	1	2	4	3	1	3	3	1	3	3	1	1
241104	1	3	2	3	3	1	2	1	3	1	3	3	1
241105	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
241106	5	3	3	5	2	3	3	5	1	3	5	3	5
241107	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1
241108	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
241201	5	NA	5	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
241202	5	NA	5	NA	NA	1	3	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
241203	5	NA	5	NA	NA	1	5	4	5	NA	5	NA	5
241204	1	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
241205	5	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA	5	1	NA	5	NA	NA
241206	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	5	1	NA	1	NA	5
241301	1	NA	5	1	3	5	3	4	2	3	3	3	2
241302	2	NA	1	3	5	5	2	5	3	2	3	4	3
241303	1	NA	2	3	5	1	3	3	5	4	3	4	4
241304	3	NA	1	3	1	5	3	5	1	3	3	1	1
241305	1	NA	1	1	4	3	3	1	1	3	1	1	1
241306	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
241307	3	NA	1	1	2	4	2	3	2	3	1	3	1
241308	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
241309	3	NA	1	1	3	5	1	1	1	2	4	3	4
242101	5	3	4	1	NA	3	4	4	3	NA	5	5	3
242102	3	3	4	5	NA	1	3	3	4	NA	3	1	3
242103	3	3	3	2	NA	3	5	3	3	NA	4	1	3
242104	5	4	3	4	NA	1	4	5	4	NA	4	1	4
242105	3	2	3	1	NA	3	1	5	4	NA	4	1	4
242106	3	2	4	1	NA	2	1	1	3	NA	5	1	1
242107	3	3	4	3	NA	2	1	3	3	NA	3	1	3
242108	3	3	4	5	NA	2	5	5	3	NA	4	1	1
242109	3	3	3	2	NA	1	5	3	3	NA	3	1	3
242201	4	NA	4	1	NA	4	1	1	4	5	1	NA	5
242202	5	NA	1	1	NA	3	1	5	1	3	2	NA	3
242203	2	NA	2	3	NA	1	1	3	3	1	4	NA	3
242204	5	NA	5	3	NA	1	1	5	4	1	3	NA	2
242205	5	NA	3	3	NA	1	1	1	3	1	1	NA	2
242206	2	NA	4	3	NA	1	1	4	3	1	3	NA	4
242207	5	NA	3	3	NA	1	1	5	3	2	2	NA	4
242301	4	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
242302	5	1	1	4	3	4	4	3	2	3	3	5	3
242303	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	1	2	1	1	2	1
242304	3	3	4	1	5	5	1	3	3	2	3	5	5
242305	1	1	1	4	1	3	5	3	3	1	1	3	3
242401	2	NA	4	3	3	3	2	5	3	NA	2	2	5
242402	2	NA	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	NA	5	2	4
242403	3	NA	3	3	2	3	3	4	4	NA	2	2	5
242404	4	NA	4	5	3	3	3	3	1	NA	3	3	5
242405	4	NA	1	5	3	3	4	3	2	NA	2	3	5
242406	4	NA	2	3	NA	3	5	3	3	NA	3	3	5
242407	4	NA	1	4	5	3	1	5	3	NA	2	2	4
242408	3	NA	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	NA	3	1	5
243101	3	5	4	5	3	1	3	1	5	1	3	5	4
243102	3	4	4	3	1	1	1	4	4	1	3	5	5
243103	1	5	1	5	4	1	1	5	1	1	1	5	1
243104	4	3	1	1	3	3	1	3	4	4	3	3	4
243105	1	3	1	5	1	3	1	3	3	1	1	3	1
243106	4	3	1	3	1	3	1	4	1	1	3	3	1
243107	3	3	3	1	1	3	1	3	3	1	3	1	4
243108	1	2	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	1
243109	2	3	1	1	1	3	3	3	3	1	3	1	1
243201	1	NA	5	NA	4	1	2	3	4	3	5	4	5
243202	5	NA	5	NA	1	3	3	4	1	4	4	2	4
243203	1	NA	2	NA	1	3	2	3	1	4	1	3	1
243204	2	NA	2	NA	3	1	3	3	2	1	3	2	2
243205	1	NA	4	NA	1	1	2	5	1	4	5	1	3
243206	1	NA	3	NA	4	1	1	3	2	1	2	2	1
243207	5	NA	3	NA	4	1	3	4	4	3	4	3	1
243208	1	NA	4	NA	4	1	5	4	5	5	4	1	4
243301	1	NA	2	1	1	1	4	1	3	4	5	3	5
243302	1	NA	3	5	3	1	5	4	3	4	3	2	5
243303	4	NA	4	5	1	5	4	4	3	5	5	3	1
243304	3	NA	4	5	4	5	4	5	3	4	5	3	5
243305	1	NA	5	5	1	5	4	4	3	3	5	4	NA
243306	1	NA	4	1	1	1	4	4	4	4	3	3	1
243307	1	NA	3	1	1	1	4	1	4	3	5	5	1
243308	5	NA	3	1	5	1	4	4	3	4	5	5	4
243309	1	NA	4	5	1	1	4	4	4	3	5	5	1
243310	1	NA	3	3	4	1	4	4	4	4	5	5	1
243311	4	NA	3	5	5	5	4	3	3	NA	4	3	4
243312	1	NA	3	4	4	1	4	4	3	NA	5	5	2
243401	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	NA	5	1	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
243402	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	3	NA	1	NA	5	5	3
243403	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	2	NA	5	5	5
243404	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	NA	5	5	1
243405	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	2	NA	1	NA	5	5	5
243406	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	4	NA	5	1	1
243407	NA	NA	5	NA	4	NA	4	NA	1	NA	1	5	3
251101	4	5	4	1	1	1	4	1	4	3	5	4	3
251102	4	5	5	1	3	5	3	3	4	3	5	4	3
251103	4	5	4	1	2	5	3	5	4	1	4	3	4
251104	5	5	4	3	3	5	3	5	4	3	4	5	4
251105	5	1	4	5	4	4	4	1	3	3	3	5	3
251106	3	4	5	5	2	3	3	5	3	3	4	3	3
251107	1	5	5	5	1	5	1	1	3	1	4	3	2
251201	3	NA	4	2	1	5	1	5	4	1	4	4	4
251202	5	NA	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
251203	1	NA	3	5	1	1	1	3	1	1	3	3	1
251204	4	NA	3	1	1	5	1	4	4	1	4	5	5
251205	4	NA	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
251206	5	NA	3	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5
251207	3	NA	1	4	3	5	5	5	1	1	4	5	5
251208	3	NA	1	4	1	5	1	3	4	1	4	1	3
251301	1	4	5	1	5	1	5	5	5	1	5	5	3
251302	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	2
251303	1	5	3	3	3	4	3	4	3	1	1	4	1
251304	4	4	5	5	3	1	1	5	5	1	5	5	1
251305	4	5	3	5	1	1	1	5	4	3	5	5	2
251401	1	NA	5	4	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	1
251402	5	NA	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1
251403	5	NA	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1
251404	3	NA	2	3	4	3	3	3	3	1	4	4	4
251405	5	NA	4	3	3	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	1
251901	5	NA	3	5	1	3	1	4	3	3	3	5	4
251902	2	NA	3	3	5	3	3	3	3	4	1	3	3
251903	5	NA	5	1	5	4	5	3	5	4	5	5	5
251904	5	NA	4	5	5	4	5	5	5	3	5	5	5
251905	5	NA	4	5	3	5	5	5	5	1	5	4	3
252101	5	NA	3	2	3	1	2	4	5	3	4	3	5
252102	4	NA	1	4	4	1	4	4	3	4	4	4	5
252103	3	NA	3	4	1	1	2	5	4	3	2	5	3
252104	2	NA	3	5	3	1	1	1	4	3	2	2	3
252105	2	NA	1	4	4	3	2	1	3	1	2	5	4
252106	1	NA	1	5	3	5	3	1	4	1	4	2	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
252201	5	NA	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
252202	3	NA	4	5	3	3	3	3	4	3	4	4	4
252203	5	NA	5	3	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
252204	5	NA	2	5	5	1	3	1	4	4	3	4	3
252205	5	NA	3	5	5	1	1	5	1	5	5	4	4
252301	5	NA	3	2	NA	1	1	5	3	2	4	5	3
252302	4	NA	3	2	NA	1	1	5	5	2	3	1	4
252303	3	NA	4	3	NA	5	3	5	3	2	3	4	5
252304	5	NA	3	1	NA	2	3	4	4	3	5	4	5
252305	4	NA	4	1	NA	5	4	5	3	2	4	3	5
252306	4	NA	3	5	NA	3	4	3	4	2	3	1	3
252307	4	NA	5	1	NA	5	1	5	5	4	5	1	5
252901	2	NA	2	1	1	5	2	2	3	2	4	3	1
252902	1	NA	1	1	1	5	3	3	3	3	5	4	1
252903	1	NA	1	5	3	3	4	3	4	3	5	3	3
252904	1	NA	1	5	1	4	4	2	1	1	5	5	1
252905	1	NA	3	5	1	3	5	2	1	1	5	3	3
252906	1	NA	1	4	1	3	5	3	3	3	5	3	1
252907	3	NA	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	2	4	1	1
252908	1	NA	1	4	1	5	1	5	1	1	5	5	1
261101	5	NA	5	1	5	NA	5	5	5	4	4	5	NA
261102	5	NA	5	5	3	NA	4	5	5	5	2	4	NA
261103	4	NA	5	4	1	NA	1	5	5	1	1	1	NA
261104	4	NA	5	4	1	NA	3	5	5	5	1	3	NA
261105	1	NA	3	4	1	NA	3	5	3	1	1	1	NA
261106	1	NA	3	4	1	NA	1	1	3	1	1	1	NA
261107	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA
261108	5	NA	4	1	1	NA	3	5	4	1	2	4	NA
261109	1	NA	1	3	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA
261110	5	NA	3	1	5	NA	4	5	5	5	1	5	NA
261201	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA							
261202	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA							
261203	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA							
261204	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA							
261205	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA							
261206	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA							
261207	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA							
261901	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
261902	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1
261903	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	3	1	4	1	1	1
261904	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
262101	4	NA	5	1	2	5	NA	5	1	NA	2	NA	2

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
262102	1	NA	5	4	1	4	NA	5	1	NA	3	NA	2
262103	1	NA	5	1	2	1	NA	1	1	NA	5	NA	2
262104	1	NA	5	4	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	3	NA	2
262105	1	NA	1	5	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	5	NA	2
262106	4	NA	5	5	1	5	NA	1	1	NA	4	NA	1
262107	1	NA	5	2	3	3	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
262108	4	NA	5	2	1	1	NA	3	1	NA	3	NA	1
262109	1	NA	1	3	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	2	NA	1
262110	1	NA	5	1	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	2	NA	2
262201	5	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	2	4	1	5	NA	1
262202	1	NA	NA	5	2	2	1	5	1	2	3	NA	1
262203	5	NA	NA	5	5	3	3	5	1	4	5	NA	5
262204	1	NA	NA	5	1	5	1	1	4	1	5	NA	1
262205	5	NA	NA	5	1	5	1	1	1	4	5	NA	5
262206	1	NA	NA	5	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1
262207	3	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	3
262208	1	NA	NA	4	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	NA	1
262209	1	NA	NA	1	5	1	5	1	1	4	5	NA	5
263101	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	4	3	1	5	2	NA
263102	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	4	1	1	1	2	NA
263103	1	NA	NA	3	1	NA	1	5	1	3	5	3	NA
263104	1	NA	NA	4	3	NA	3	5	1	1	1	3	NA
263105	1	NA	NA	3	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	3	NA
263106	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	3	1	3	NA
263107	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	NA
263108	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	5	1	3	1	1	NA
263109	1	NA	NA	4	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	2	NA
263110	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	4	1	1	1	1	NA
263111	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA
263112	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	4	1	1	1	1	NA
263201	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	5	2	3	1	5
263202	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
263203	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
263204	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
263205	3	NA	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	2	2	3	1
263206	3	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	3	1	1
263207	5	NA	1	1	4	2	2	5	3	2	3	5	3
263208	4	NA	1	5	5	3	3	1	1	4	3	1	4
263209	3	NA	1	2	4	3	1	1	2	5	1	1	1
263301	5	NA	5	NA	1	NA	4	3	4	NA	2	NA	3
263302	1	NA	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	3	NA	1	NA	2
263303	5	NA	5	NA	1	NA	4	5	1	NA	1	NA	4

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
263304	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	5	3	NA	1	NA	4
263305	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	5	4	NA	1	NA	5
263306	1	NA	3	NA	1	NA	2	3	4	NA	3	NA	5
263307	5	NA	2	NA	1	NA	2	5	2	NA	1	NA	5
263308	5	NA	3	NA	1	NA	2	1	4	NA	1	NA	5
263401	2	NA	3	1	3	5	4	5	4	3	3	1	NA
263402	3	NA	4	3	1	3	1	5	5	2	1	1	NA
263403	5	NA	1	1	4	4	5	5	5	1	1	5	NA
263404	5	NA	4	4	3	3	1	3	1	3	1	1	NA
263405	1	NA	1	1	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA
263406	1	NA	1	1	5	4	2	3	1	1	1	2	NA
263407	1	NA	3	1	2	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA
263408	2	NA	3	1	4	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA
263501	5	4	5	5	2	2	4	5	5	5	1	4	3
263502	5	4	5	5	2	2	2	5	5	4	4	4	5
263503	4	4	1	4	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1
263504	5	1	1	1	2	3	1	5	5	5	4	4	4
263505	3	4	1	3	2	1	1	4	5	4	5	1	2
263506	4	2	1	3	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
263507	1	1	1	2	2	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1
263508	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
263509	3	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3
263510	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	2
263511	4	5	3	4	1	2	1	3	5	2	5	3	5
263601	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	4	NA	NA
263602	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	4	NA	NA
263603	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	5	NA	NA
263604	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	4	NA	NA
263605	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
263606	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	1	NA	NA
263607	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	2	NA	NA
263608	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	4	NA	NA
263609	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	2	NA	NA
264101	1	NA	1	NA	5	5	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1
264102	1	NA	4	NA	1	1	NA	1	3	NA	5	5	4
264103	1	NA	2	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1
264104	5	NA	3	NA	1	3	NA	5	1	NA	1	4	4
264105	4	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	4	2	2
264106	1	NA	4	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	4	1
264201	5	1	5	5	1	5	4	5	5	5	5	1	1
264202	5	3	1	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	1	5	5
264203	5	5	4	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	1	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
264204	1	1	1	5	1	1	4	1	1	3	1	1	1
264205	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	3	1	1	1
264206	1	1	1	4	1	1	3	1	1	4	1	1	3
264207	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
264208	5	5	1	1	5	1	4	5	5	5	5	5	5
264209	1	5	1	5	4	1	4	1	1	1	5	1	5
264210	5	1	1	5	1	1	2	1	4	5	1	1	5
264301	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1
264302	1	1	3	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	5	3
264303	3	4	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5
264304	1	2	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	5	5
264305	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	2	1
264306	5	3	3	1	5	5	5	1	3	4	1	3	5
265101	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	3	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
265102	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	3	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
265103	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	4	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
265104	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
265105	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	2	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
265106	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
265107	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
265108	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	2	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
265201	5	NA	5	NA	5	2	2	3	5	5	5	3	NA
265202	3	NA	2	NA	5	3	1	5	5	5	3	2	NA
265203	4	NA	3	NA	1	1	3	4	1	4	3	3	NA
265204	4	NA	2	NA	1	1	4	4	1	1	NA	4	NA
265205	2	NA	2	NA	5	1	1	5	4	1	3	4	NA
265206	5	NA	5	NA	5	4	3	4	5	5	4	5	NA
265207	1	NA	1	NA	1	4	4	5	1	4	NA	5	NA
265208	5	NA	5	NA	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	5	NA
265301	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
265302	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	3	NA	5	NA	NA	NA
265303	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA
265304	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	4	NA	5	NA	NA	NA
265305	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	2	NA	3	NA	NA	NA
265306	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
265401	1	NA	1	NA	5	4	1	1	1	NA	1	1	NA
265402	3	NA	1	NA	3	5	5	1	1	NA	1	1	NA
265403	5	NA	4	NA	2	5	5	4	4	NA	1	2	NA
265404	3	NA	4	NA	3	5	5	1	4	NA	1	2	NA
265405	1	NA	1	NA	2	3	5	1	1	NA	1	1	NA
265406	1	NA	5	NA	5	4	5	5	3	NA	1	1	NA
265407	3	NA	5	NA	1	3	5	1	3	NA	1	1	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
265501	NA	2	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
265502	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA	4	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
265503	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA	4	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
265504	NA	4	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
265505	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA	5	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
265506	NA	3	NA	NA	5	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
265507	NA	3	NA	NA	5	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
265601	5	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA
265602	5	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA
265603	5	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA
265604	4	NA	NA	NA	2	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	NA
265605	5	NA	NA	NA	2	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA
265901	NA	3											
265902	NA	1											
265903	NA	4											
265904	NA	1											
311101	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2
311102	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3
311103	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1
311104	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5
311105	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1
311106	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1
311201	1	NA	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1
311202	4	NA	5	1	3	5	5	2	3	3	5	4	1
311203	1	NA	5	5	5	5	1	1	5	3	5	5	5
311204	4	NA	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	2	5	4	5
311205	4	NA	1	5	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	3	1
311206	1	NA	3	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311207	5	NA	5	1	4	5	1	1	5	1	5	4	1
311301	4	NA	5	1	1	1	1	3	5	1	5	2	1
311302	3	NA	1	1	1	1	1	3	5	3	1	4	1
311303	3	NA	1	5	1	1	1	4	1	3	1	3	1
311304	4	NA	5	1	5	5	2	5	4	2	5	4	1
311305	3	NA	5	5	1	1	2	5	4	1	5	4	1
311306	3	NA	1	5	5	3	5	5	3	1	5	5	1
311401	5	5	3	4	3	1	1	5	2	1	4	4	3
311402	1	5	2	5	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	3	3
311403	1	3	2	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1
311404	4	4	3	5	3	5	5	5	1	5	3	5	3
311405	2	5	2	5	2	1	2	1	1	5	3	5	1
311406	5	4	1	5	2	1	5	1	1	1	3	5	1
311407	5	5	4	5	1	5	3	5	1	1	5	5	2

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
311501	2	NA	1	1	1	1	1	5	5	NA	4	1	2
311502	1	NA	4	3	1	1	1	5	5	NA	3	1	2
311503	4	NA	5	3	5	2	5	5	1	NA	5	1	4
311504	4	NA	5	2	5	2	5	5	1	NA	5	1	5
311505	2	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
311506	4	NA	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	NA	3	1	1
311507	1	NA	1	1	4	1	3	5	1	NA	3	1	1
311508	1	NA	5	3	1	1	5	1	4	NA	5	4	2
311601	1	NA	4	NA	5	NA	1	2	5	1	3	1	3
311602	1	NA	2	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311603	2	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	2	2	1	3	1	1
311604	2	NA	2	NA	1	NA	3	2	5	5	1	1	1
311605	3	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	4	3	1	5	3	3
311701	1	NA	NA	1	5	1	3	3	4	5	NA	NA	5
311702	1	NA	NA	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1
311703	1	NA	NA	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1
311704	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1
311705	1	NA	NA	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1
311706	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	3	1	4	NA	NA	1
311707	5	NA	NA	1	1	1	5	1	1	5	NA	NA	5
311708	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	NA	NA	5
311801	5	4	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	2	5
311802	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
311803	5	1	1	5	1	1	1	5	1	1	5	1	1
311804	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	1
311805	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311806	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311807	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	5	1
311808	5	5	5	1	5	1	5	4	5	5	5	5	5
311901	1	NA	5	5	1	1	5	1	5	5	5	1	5
311902	5	NA	2	1	1	5	3	1	3	3	4	3	5
311903	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	4
311904	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
311905	1	NA	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	3
312101	NA	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA
312102	NA	NA	NA	1	1	3	5	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA
312103	NA	NA	NA	1	5	4	5	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA
312104	NA	NA	NA	5	1	3	1	NA	NA	5	4	NA	NA
312105	NA	NA	NA	4	1	3	1	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA
312201	4	5	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	NA	5	1	4
312202	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	4	1
312203	4	4	4	5	3	1	3	5	4	5	1	4	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
312204	5	4	4	5	1	1	3	5	5	4	5	1	1
312205	4	5	5	5	1	5	1	5	5	1	5	4	5
312206	1	5	3	5	1	1	1	3	5	3	3	2	2
312301	5	5	4	1	4	4	4	4	1	4	5	5	4
312302	5	5	5	3	3	1	5	5	5	1	5	5	5
312303	5	4	5	3	4	1	5	5	4	1	5	5	5
312304	3	4	4	5	5	1	5	1	1	1	4	1	1
312305	5	4	5	5	5	1	5	5	1	3	5	4	1
312306	5	4	5	5	5	1	5	5	1	1	5	4	1
313101	NA	NA	5	3	1	5	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1
313102	NA	NA	5	4	4	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1
313103	NA	NA	5	5	1	5	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1
313104	NA	NA	5	5	5	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1
313105	NA	NA	5	5	1	5	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	2
313106	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	1
313201	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA
313202	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA
313203	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA
313204	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA
313205	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	1	NA
313206	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	1	NA
313207	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA
313208	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA
313301	NA	NA	5	NA	1	3	4	NA	5	NA	NA	1	5
313302	NA	NA	4	NA	1	3	1	NA	5	NA	NA	1	1
313303	NA	NA	5	NA	5	3	5	NA	5	NA	NA	1	4
313304	NA	NA	5	NA	1	2	5	NA	5	NA	NA	1	4
313305	NA	NA	5	NA	1	2	5	NA	5	NA	NA	1	1
313306	NA	NA	5	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	NA	NA	1	1
313401	5	NA	1	NA	5	NA	2	1	5	NA	1	NA	NA
313402	3	NA	1	NA	5	NA	3	4	4	5	5	NA	NA
313403	5	NA	1	NA	2	NA	3	4	5	4	NA	NA	NA
313404	3	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	4	5	4	NA	NA
313405	5	NA	1	NA	5	NA	4	5	5	5	5	NA	NA
313501	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	4	1	5	NA	NA
313502	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA
313503	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	5	NA	4	1	5	NA	NA
313504	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA
313505	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	4	NA	1	1	3	NA	NA
313506	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA
313507	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	NA
314101	4	NA	4	1	5	1	4	5	3	NA	1	2	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
314102	3	NA	3	1	5	2	1	5	4	NA	5	4	NA
314103	5	NA	1	3	5	4	1	4	5	NA	5	1	NA
314104	5	NA	1	5	5	3	3	4	5	NA	5	3	NA
314105	5	NA	1	5	5	1	2	5	5	NA	5	1	NA
314106	4	NA	4	5	5	3	2	5	5	NA	5	3	NA
314107	3	NA	1	5	1	1	1	5	1	NA	4	3	NA
314108	5	NA	1	5	5	3	5	5	5	NA	5	1	NA
314109	1	NA	1	5	5	5	2	4	1	NA	5	2	NA
314110	1	NA	1	5	5	2	2	5	5	NA	5	4	NA
314111	2	NA	1	1	1	3	2	1	1	NA	1	4	NA
314112	4	NA	3	1	5	1	2	5	4	NA	1	4	NA
314113	4	NA	4	3	1	1	2	5	5	NA	1	1	NA
314201	NA	NA	4	4	1	1	5	2	1	4	4	1	1
314202	NA	NA	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	4	3	1	1
314203	NA	NA	1	1	2	1	1	3	1	2	3	1	1
314204	NA	NA	3	1	1	1	1	3	1	2	4	1	1
314205	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	4	5	5
314206	NA	NA	1	4	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1
314207	NA	NA	3	1	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	1
314208	NA	NA	3	1	1	3	1	4	1	1	2	1	5
314209	NA	NA	1	4	1	1	5	3	2	1	2	1	1
314301	1	NA	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	5	NA
314302	2	NA	NA	NA	4	3	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	4	NA
314303	2	NA	NA	NA	2	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA
314304	4	NA	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA
314305	4	NA	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	3	NA
314306	4	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	5	NA
314307	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA
314308	4	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	2	NA
314309	2	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	3	NA
314310	2	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	4	NA
315101	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA							
315102	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
315103	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA							
315104	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA							
315105	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
315202	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
315203	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	2	1	4	NA	NA	5	NA
315204	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
315205	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	4	NA
315206	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	3	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
315207	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	4	1	3	NA	NA	3	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
315208	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	3	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
315301	5	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5
315302	5	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	3	NA	NA	4
315303	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	4
315304	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	4
315305	4	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	5
315306	1	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5
315307	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5
315401	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
315402	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
315403	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	4	NA	1
315404	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
315405	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	2	NA	5
315406	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	4	NA	5
315407	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	5	NA	5
315408	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
315501	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA						
315502	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
315503	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
315504	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
315505	NA	1	NA	NA	2	NA	NA						
315506	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
315507	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
315508	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
315509	NA	5	NA	NA	2	NA	NA						
321101	NA	NA	5	NA	1	3	1	5	5	NA	1	NA	5
321102	NA	NA	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	NA	3	NA	5
321103	NA	NA	5	NA	5	3	5	5	5	NA	1	NA	5
321104	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	1	5	5	NA	1	NA	5
321105	NA	NA	5	NA	5	1	5	1	5	NA	1	NA	5
321106	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
321107	NA	NA	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
321108	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
321201	5	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	NA	4	NA	NA
321202	5	1	5	5	5	1	1	1	4	NA	4	NA	NA
321203	5	4	5	1	5	1	5	5	1	NA	4	NA	NA
321204	5	1	5	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	3	NA	NA
321205	4	5	5	5	5	5	4	3	4	NA	4	NA	NA
321206	5	1	4	5	1	5	1	1	4	NA	4	NA	NA
321207	4	1	5	5	1	5	1	1	4	NA	3	NA	NA
321208	5	1	1	5	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	NA
321209	5	1	1	5	5	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
321210	5	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
321301	1	NA	5	1	1	5	1	1	5	NA	1	1	1
321302	1	NA	5	1	5	5	4	5	5	NA	1	1	1
321303	5	NA	5	1	5	5	4	5	5	NA	1	5	1
321305	1	NA	4	5	4	1	4	5	5	NA	1	1	1
321306	1	NA	5	1	5	5	4	5	5	NA	5	5	5
321307	1	NA	5	1	5	5	4	1	1	NA	1	5	5
321308	1	NA	5	1	1	3	4	5	5	NA	1	5	4
321309	5	NA	5	1	1	5	1	5	5	NA	1	4	1
321401	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
321402	4	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
321403	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
321404	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
321405	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
321406	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
321407	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
321408	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
321409	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
321410	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
322101	5	NA	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	NA
322102	5	NA	5	5	1	4	5	5	5	1	5	1	NA
322103	4	NA	5	5	5	3	5	5	4	1	1	1	NA
322104	4	NA	1	5	1	5	1	4	5	1	1	1	NA
322105	5	NA	5	5	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	1	NA
322106	5	NA	4	5	1	5	5	5	3	1	5	1	NA
322201	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA							
322202	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA							
322203	NA	NA	5	NA	3	NA							
322204	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA							
324001	4	NA	NA	5	3	NA	NA	NA	5	5	2	5	NA
324002	3	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	4	5	2	5	NA
324003	3	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	5	2	1	NA
324004	3	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	5	5	3	5	NA
324005	2	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	2	1	NA
324006	2	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	5	2	1	NA
324007	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	5	5	2	1	NA
324008	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	5	1	2	1	NA
324009	2	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	5	1	5	1	NA
324010	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	4	5	1	1	NA
325101	1	NA	4	1	3	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	NA
325102	1	NA	1	1	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA
325103	1	NA	1	1	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
325104	5	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA
325105	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	NA
325106	5	NA	5	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA
325107	4	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	3	5	NA
325108	3	NA	5	5	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	5	NA
325201	NA	NA	5	5	5	5	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA
325202	NA	NA	1	3	1	5	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA
325203	NA	NA	5	5	1	5	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA
325204	NA	NA	1	1	1	4	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA
325205	NA	NA	5	5	1	5	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA
325206	NA	NA	5	1	1	5	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA
325301	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	4	NA	5	4	4	5	1
325302	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	5	1	2	2	1
325303	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	5	1	2	1	1
325304	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	2	1	1
325305	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	5	1	1
325306	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	2	2	1
325401	4	NA											
325402	5	NA											
325403	5	NA											
325404	4	NA											
325501	NA	NA	5	1	5	5	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA
325502	NA	NA	5	5	4	1	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA
325503	NA	NA	5	4	4	5	NA	NA	3	5	NA	NA	NA
325504	NA	NA	4	1	3	1	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA
325505	NA	NA	5	1	3	1	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA
325506	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA
325601	3	NA	3	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1
325602	5	NA	1	1	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5
325603	5	NA	3	1	5	5	4	5	5	5	1	1	1
325604	5	NA	1	1	5	5	1	5	5	3	1	5	1
325605	3	NA	5	5	1	5	1	3	4	1	2	1	1
325606	5	NA	5	1	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5
325607	4	NA	1	5	1	5	1	5	5	3	5	1	1
325608	5	NA	5	5	5	1	1	5	5	5	1	5	5
325609	4	NA	3	5	5	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	4
325610	5	NA	1	5	1	5	1	5	5	3	5	5	4
325701	5	NA	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	NA	2	1	1
325702	4	NA	1	1	5	1	5	4	3	NA	3	2	5
325703	4	NA	1	3	1	5	5	3	1	NA	3	1	1
325704	4	NA	1	3	2	1	5	3	4	NA	3	4	5
325705	4	NA	1	2	1	5	5	3	3	NA	3	4	4

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
325706	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
325707	4	NA	1	2	1	1	1	4	1	NA	1	2	4
325708	4	NA	5	2	1	1	5	1	1	NA	3	3	1
325709	4	NA	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	NA	1	1	1
325710	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	2	1
325901	1	NA	1	1	5	1	5	4	5	5	NA	5	4
325902	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	5	1
325903	5	NA	1	5	5	1	1	1	5	5	NA	4	5
325904	1	NA	NA	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	NA	4	5
325905	1	NA	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	NA	3	5
331101	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	5	5	NA	5	2	NA
331102	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	5	5	5	5	NA	5	1	NA
331103	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	5	NA	5	1	NA
331104	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	4	NA	1	1	NA
331105	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	5	5	1	4	NA	5	1	NA
331201	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
331202	3	NA	3	1	5	5	1	5	5	NA	4	5	5
331203	2	NA	4	3	5	5	5	5	5	NA	3	1	1
331204	3	NA	2	1	5	1	5	5	5	NA	1	NA	5
331205	1	NA	4	1	5	5	1	1	5	NA	1	1	5
331301	5	NA	5	1	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	1	5
331302	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5
331303	3	NA	3	5	3	1	3	3	1	3	3	1	3
331304	5	NA	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	1	5
331305	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5
331306	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
331401	5	NA	5	NA	NA	5	1	3	5	NA	1	4	NA
331402	1	NA	2	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	NA	1	1	NA
331403	1	NA	4	NA	NA	4	5	2	1	NA	1	4	NA
331404	3	NA	5	NA	NA	4	1	4	1	NA	1	4	NA
331405	5	NA	5	NA	NA	3	5	3	5	NA	1	5	NA
331406	3	NA	4	NA	NA	4	1	3	5	NA	1	5	NA
331407	5	NA	3	NA	NA	5	1	2	5	NA	1	5	NA
331408	1	NA	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	NA	2	5	NA
331501	1	1	4	5	5	5	1	1	5	1	1	4	1
331502	5	5	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	4	5
331503	1	1	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	3	1
331504	1	1	4	5	5	5	5	5	1	1	1	3	1
331505	1	1	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	3	1
332101	5	NA	5	1	1	5	1	NA	5	1	5	5	5
332102	5	NA	5	5	4	1	5	NA	5	5	5	5	1
332103	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	NA	4	4	5	5	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
332104	5	NA	5	5	4	5	5	NA	5	3	5	5	1
332105	4	NA	1	5	1	5	5	NA	1	1	1	2	1
332106	4	NA	5	5	1	1	5	NA	3	1	1	1	1
332201	1	5	1	1	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	1	1
332202	5	5	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	5	5	5	5
332203	5	1	4	1	1	5	1	1	3	3	4	5	1
332204	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
332205	5	5	5	5	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	1	5
332206	5	1	4	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	4
332207	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5
332301	5	NA	3	1	5	4	5	5	5	3	5	5	4
332302	5	NA	5	1	5	4	5	5	5	3	5	5	5
332303	5	NA	4	5	5	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	3
332304	5	NA	5	5	2	4	1	5	5	1	5	5	4
332305	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	5
332306	1	NA	2	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	3
332307	5	NA	3	1	5	4	5	5	3	1	5	5	5
332308	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5
332309	5	NA	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	1	5	5	5
332310	5	NA	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	1	5	5	5
332401	5	1	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	1	1	NA	3	1	1
332402	5	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	3	NA	2	5	1
332403	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1
332404	1	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	5
332405	1	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	1
332406	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	5
333101	5	NA	5	1	4	1	4	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA
333102	5	NA	3	1	1	2	4	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
333103	1	NA	5	5	4	1	4	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
333104	5	NA	5	5	4	1	1	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA
333105	5	NA	2	5	4	1	4	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA
333201	2	5	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	4
333202	1	5	NA	1	1	1	NA	5	3	5	5	5	4
333203	1	5	4	1	4	1	4	5	3	5	4	5	4
333204	5	5	4	4	5	1	NA	4	5	3	4	5	1
333205	3	1	NA	5	1	1	NA	2	4	3	4	5	4
333206	3	5	4	5	2	1	5	2	3	1	4	5	1
333207	3	4	1	1	1	1	5	4	1	1	3	5	1
333301	NA	NA	5	1	1	3	1	5	5	5	5	5	1
333302	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	1
333303	NA	NA	1	3	1	4	1	3	5	3	1	3	1
333304	NA	NA	1	1	1	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
333305	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	5	1
333306	NA	NA	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1
333401	5	NA	NA	NA	4	4	NA	NA	3	3	1	NA	4
333402	3	NA	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	4	5	1	NA	4
333403	1	NA	NA	NA	5	2	NA	NA	4	1	5	NA	1
333404	4	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	3	5	1	NA	1
333405	1	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	1	5	3	NA	1
333406	3	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	3	1	NA	1
333407	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	3	1	NA	1
333901	4	NA	2	1	5	4	4	1	3	1	4	4	5
333902	1	NA	5	1	4	4	1	1	3	1	5	4	5
333903	1	NA	4	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	3	1
333904	1	NA	4	5	5	1	1	1	1	1	5	4	5
333905	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
334101	5	5	4	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
334102	5	5	1	1	1	5	1	4	5	3	5	1	1
334103	5	3	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	1
334104	3	3	3	3	3	1	1	4	3	1	1	4	1
334105	2	3	1	4	3	1	1	1	2	5	1	3	1
334106	2	2	1	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1
334201	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	5	5	4	5
334202	4	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	5	4
334203	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	5	5
334204	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	3	5	5	5
334205	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	5	5	5
334206	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	1	5	1
334207	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	1	5	1
334301	5	3	1	1	1	4	1	5	4	3	5	5	5
334302	5	5	4	1	1	5	1	5	5	3	5	5	5
334303	5	4	1	5	1	5	5	5	4	3	5	5	5
334304	1	1	3	5	1	1	1	1	4	1	3	5	1
334305	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
334306	5	4	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	5
334307	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
334308	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1
334401	5	5	5	1	1	1	5	1	5	NA	5	NA	5
334402	5	5	5	1	1	1	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
334403	5	5	1	5	1	1	5	1	1	NA	5	NA	1
334404	1	3	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	NA	4	NA	1
334405	5	5	5	1	1	3	1	5	1	NA	5	NA	5
334406	3	5	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	NA	5	NA	1
334407	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
334408	1	5	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	NA	5	NA	1
335101	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1
335102	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	5
335103	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1
335104	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	5	5	1	NA	NA	NA	1
335105	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1
335106	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	3	4	NA	NA	NA	1
335107	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	5	NA	NA	NA	1
335108	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	2	1	2	NA	NA	NA	1
335201	3	NA	NA	4	4	4	4	1	5	4	1	4	NA
335202	5	NA	NA	1	5	3	1	1	1	5	1	4	NA
335203	5	NA	NA	5	4	1	2	1	1	4	1	4	NA
335204	5	NA	NA	3	3	3	5	2	4	4	5	4	NA
335301	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	1	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
335302	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	3	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
335303	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
335304	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
335401	5	NA	5	5	4	5	5	NA	5	4	4	NA	NA
335402	1	NA	4	3	1	3	1	NA	4	4	3	NA	NA
335403	1	NA	1	5	4	1	1	NA	1	1	2	NA	NA
335404	5	NA	4	5	3	2	1	NA	1	4	2	NA	NA
335405	1	NA	1	1	1	2	1	NA	1	1	2	NA	NA
335501	NA	NA	4	NA	5	NA	1	3	5	5	5	1	NA
335502	NA	NA	3	NA	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	4	5	NA
335503	NA	NA	3	NA	5	NA	1	4	5	NA	5	5	NA
335504	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	2	4	1	5	4	1	NA
335505	NA	NA	2	NA	3	NA	1	4	2	5	4	5	NA
335506	NA	NA	3	NA	1	NA	2	2	1	3	4	2	NA
335901	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
335902	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	1	1
335903	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
335904	5	NA	5	1	2	5	3	5	3	NA	5	5	5
341101	5	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	4	3	5	4	1	5
341102	4	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	1	1
341103	1	NA	NA	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
341104	5	NA	NA	4	1	1	1	5	3	5	5	1	5
341105	5	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	5	3	1	5	1	5
341106	5	NA	NA	5	1	1	5	5	1	5	5	1	5
341107	1	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	5	1	1
341108	1	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
341201	1	NA	4	1	1	5	5	3	5	3	3	5	4
341202	5	NA	2	1	5	1	5	1	1	5	3	5	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
341203	1	NA	4	4	1	5	5	2	4	5	3	5	5
341204	5	NA	4	4	4	1	5	4	4	5	3	5	5
341205	1	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1
341206	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	5	1
341207	2	NA	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1
341208	5	NA	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	3	1	5
341209	1	NA	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	3	5	5
341210	1	NA	4	5	1	1	5	3	5	1	3	5	5
341301	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
341302	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
341303	NA	3	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
341304	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
341305	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA
341306	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
342101	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA							
342102	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA							
342103	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA							
342105	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA							
342106	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA							
342107	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA							
342108	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA							
342201	5	5	NA	3	1	NA	5	4	3	NA	5	3	NA
342202	5	5	NA	4	1	NA	3	3	3	NA	5	3	NA
342203	1	5	NA	3	3	NA	2	2	1	NA	3	1	NA
342204	5	5	NA	5	1	NA	1	4	1	NA	5	5	NA
342205	1	1	NA	3	1	NA	1	4	1	NA	1	5	NA
342206	3	5	NA	3	3	NA	1	5	4	NA	5	1	NA
342207	5	1	NA	5	1	NA	1	5	4	NA	5	5	NA
342208	1	1	NA	5	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	3	1	NA
342209	1	5	NA	5	1	NA	1	2	1	NA	1	1	NA
342210	1	1	NA	3	1	NA	1	2	1	NA	5	3	NA
342211	1	1	NA	3	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	5	1	NA
342301	1	NA	4	NA	1	4	2	1	3	3	4	5	NA
342302	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	2	5	2	NA
342303	5	NA	2	NA	1	5	1	1	4	1	5	4	NA
342304	5	NA	2	5	1	5	1	5	1	4	5	5	NA
342305	5	NA	2	3	4	5	2	5	1	4	5	5	NA
342306	5	NA	2	5	2	5	2	5	1	3	5	2	NA
343101	3	NA	5	4	3	1	3	4	3	NA	5	5	5
343102	2	NA	1	1	4	4	4	4	1	NA	3	3	4
343103	3	NA	5	4	1	3	4	5	3	NA	1	4	3
343104	3	NA	5	4	5	5	4	4	5	NA	5	5	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
343105	1	NA	1	5	1	5	2	5	1	NA	5	5	4
343106	4	NA	5	5	5	3	5	4	5	NA	5	5	5
343107	1	NA	5	4	1	5	2	5	1	NA	5	4	5
343108	1	NA	5	5	1	5	1	1	5	NA	5	5	4
343201	2	NA	4	4	1	NA	4	4	1	5	3	1	5
343202	3	NA	4	5	4	NA	5	5	1	5	3	4	5
343203	3	NA	3	5	1	NA	5	5	1	4	4	1	2
343204	5	NA	4	5	1	NA	5	5	1	4	5	5	3
343205	1	NA	4	5	5	NA	4	4	3	4	5	1	3
343206	1	NA	4	5	1	NA	5	5	1	2	5	1	1
343207	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	4	5	1	2	5	5	1
343208	1	NA	3	5	1	NA	5	5	5	2	5	1	5
343209	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	2
343210	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	3	4	1	2	1	1	5
343301	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
343302	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
343303	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
343304	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
343305	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
343306	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
343307	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
343308	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
343309	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
343401	5	NA	5	1	NA	1	NA	3	4	NA	3	5	1
343402	5	NA	5	1	NA	1	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	5
343403	5	NA	3	5	NA	1	NA	3	5	NA	4	3	5
343404	5	NA	5	5	NA	1	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	5
343405	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	3	5	1
343406	5	NA	5	5	NA	1	NA	3	5	NA	5	5	5
343407	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA	3	5	NA	5	5	4
343408	1	NA	1	5	NA	1	NA	3	5	NA	5	3	1
343409	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	5
343410	5	NA	5	1	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	4	5	5
351101	NA	5	NA	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA
351102	NA	5	NA	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA
351103	NA	5	NA	5	5	5	1	1	5	5	5	1	NA
351104	NA	4	NA	5	3	4	1	1	5	5	5	5	NA
351105	NA	5	NA	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	NA
351106	NA	1	NA	5	4	4	1	2	1	2	5	1	NA
351107	NA	1	NA	5	3	5	1	1	1	4	4	1	NA
351108	NA	1	NA	5	5	3	1	4	1	5	5	1	NA
351201	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
351202	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5
351203	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	1
351204	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4
351205	5	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	4	5	1	1
351206	1	4	1	1	5	5	5	5	1	1	5	5	5
351207	5	5	4	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
351208	5	5	5	5	1	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
351301	3	NA	5	3	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5
351302	4	NA	3	4	5	4	4	4	1	5	5	5	5
351303	2	NA	4	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	4	5	5
351304	4	NA	4	5	4	2	5	5	5	3	5	5	3
351305	2	NA	4	5	4	5	5	4	1	4	1	3	2
351401	NA	NA	5	3	1	5	3	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
351402	NA	NA	4	1	2	3	1	5	3	NA	NA	3	NA
351403	NA	NA	3	5	1	1	1	5	3	NA	NA	2	NA
351404	NA	NA	4	1	3	2	1	3	3	NA	NA	3	NA
351405	NA	NA	5	1	5	5	1	5	4	NA	NA	1	NA
351406	NA	NA	4	3	1	1	3	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA
351407	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	2	4	1	NA	NA	3	NA
352101	5	NA	1	1	4	1	1	1	5	5	5	5	5
352102	5	NA	1	1	4	1	1	5	3	1	1	5	5
352103	5	NA	1	5	1	1	1	5	5	1	1	5	5
352104	5	NA	1	5	5	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	1
352105	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
352106	5	NA	1	4	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
352107	1	NA	2	1	2	2	1	1	4	1	3	1	2
352201	1	NA	1	5	5	1	5	1	1	2	1	1	5
352202	5	NA	2	3	5	1	3	1	1	5	5	5	1
352203	1	NA	1	4	3	1	2	1	1	2	1	3	1
352204	5	NA	1	3	1	5	5	5	1	2	5	1	1
352205	5	NA	1	1	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5
411001	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
411002	5	5	1	1	1	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5
411003	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
411004	5	3	4	5	1	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5
411005	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
411006	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
411007	5	5	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	5
411008	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
412001	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5
412002	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
412003	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
412004	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
412005	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	5
412006	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
412007	1	NA	5	1	5	5	5	1	5	1	5	1	5
412008	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
413101	5	NA	NA	3	5	5	1	5	5	3	5	5	4
413102	1	NA	NA	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5
413103	1	NA	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	4
413104	1	NA	NA	5	5	5	1	4	5	5	5	5	5
413105	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
413106	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
413107	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
413201	3	NA	NA	1	4	5	1	NA	1	NA	5	NA	5
413202	5	NA	NA	1	5	5	1	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5
413203	4	NA	NA	NA	5	4	1	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5
413204	1	NA	NA	5	5	3	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1
413205	1	NA	NA	5	5	2	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1
421101	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	NA	5	5	4
421102	5	5	5	1	5	5	1	1	1	NA	1	1	4
421103	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	1	5	NA	1	3	4
421104	1	5	1	5	5	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
421105	5	1	3	5	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	3	1
421106	5	1	5	1	5	5	1	1	1	NA	5	5	1
421201	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	5	NA
421202	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA
421203	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA
421204	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA
421205	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA
421301	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
421302	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
421303	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
421304	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
421305	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
421401	5	NA	1	1	1	5	1	1	5	1	5	1	5
421402	5	NA	1	1	3	4	3	3	5	3	5	5	5
421403	5	NA	2	1	3	5	3	3	5	1	5	1	5
421404	3	NA	1	3	1	1	1	3	5	3	3	1	4
421405	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4
422101	5	NA	5	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
422102	5	NA	5	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
422103	5	NA	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5
422104	5	NA	5	1	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
422105	5	NA	5	5	5	5	3	1	5	4	1	5	1
422106	1	NA	1	1	5	5	4	5	5	1	5	5	1
422107	4	NA	5	3	3	3	3	4	1	2	1	1	1
422201	5	4	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
422202	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
422203	5	1	5	1	1	5	1	5	5	4	5	5	5
422204	1	3	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
422205	1	3	4	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	5	5	5
422206	1	3	4	1	5	1	5	5	5	4	5	5	5
422301	5	NA	5	1	NA	1	1	5	5	NA	5	1	NA
422302	1	NA	4	1	NA	1	1	1	5	NA	5	1	NA
422303	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	5	5	NA	5	1	NA
422304	5	NA	5	1	NA	1	5	5	5	NA	5	5	NA
422305	1	NA	1	5	NA	1	1	4	1	NA	3	1	NA
422401	5	NA	5	5	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	4	1	1
422402	5	NA	5	1	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	1	5
422403	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	1	5
422404	5	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	1	5
422405	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
422406	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	1	4
422407	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	4	5	NA	5	1	5
422408	1	NA	5	5	1	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
422409	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	5	1
422501	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	NA
422502	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	5	5	NA	4	5	NA
422503	5	NA	NA	5	4	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	NA
422504	1	NA	NA	5	4	NA	NA	5	3	NA	1	5	NA
422505	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	3	NA
422601	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5
422602	5	4	5	1	5	1	4	1	5	1	5	5	5
422603	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
422604	1	5	1	5	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
422701	5	NA	5	2	1	5	3	1	3	2	3	5	1
422702	5	NA	1	1	5	5	3	1	5	2	3	5	1
422703	5	NA	5	1	5	5	4	1	5	1	4	5	1
422704	1	NA	5	1	5	4	1	3	1	1	3	1	5
422705	5	NA	5	1	4	4	3	2	3	1	4	1	5
422901	NA	NA	1	5	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1
422902	NA	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1
422903	NA	NA	5	1	5	5	3	3	5	5	NA	NA	5
422904	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	5
422905	NA	NA	1	5	1	5	1	3	5	NA	NA	NA	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
422906	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	3	1	NA	NA	NA	1
431101	5	NA	5	1	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	1	5
431102	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
431103	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
431104	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4
431105	3	NA	3	5	3	5	3	3	1	3	1	5	3
431201	5	5	5	5	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
431202	1	5	4	5	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	5
431203	5	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	1	5	5	5	5
431204	5	3	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	5	5	1	1
431205	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
431301	5	NA	NA	3	1	NA	1	5	5	3	3	1	4
431302	4	NA	NA	1	4	NA	3	1	3	1	3	5	1
431303	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	3	4	3	1	3	3	3
431304	4	NA	NA	5	3	NA	3	5	4	4	4	1	4
431305	4	NA	NA	5	3	NA	3	1	1	3	4	1	1
432101	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
432102	5	5	5	1	1	5	5	5	5	1	5	4	5
432103	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	1
432104	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	5	1	1	1
432105	1	1	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
432201	5	5	1	1	1	3	1	3	1	4	5	1	5
432202	4	5	1	1	3	5	1	1	1	4	5	3	1
432203	5	5	4	1	5	3	2	1	5	5	5	5	1
432204	5	4	1	1	3	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	1
432205	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	4	5	5	5	5	1
432301	1	NA	5	5	4	1	1	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
432302	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
432303	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
432304	1	NA	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	NA	1	NA	5
432305	4	NA	1	1	1	1	5	5	1	NA	5	NA	1
432306	1	NA	1	5	5	4	5	3	1	NA	3	NA	4
441101	NA	NA	4	NA	2	3	NA	NA	4	1	3	NA	NA
441102	NA	NA	4	NA	4	3	NA	NA	4	1	4	NA	NA
441103	NA	NA	5	NA	5	4	NA	NA	1	5	4	NA	NA
441104	NA	NA	1	NA	2	3	NA	NA	1	1	4	NA	NA
441105	NA	NA	4	NA	3	5	NA	NA	1	1	4	NA	NA
441106	NA	NA	5	NA	3	5	NA	NA	1	1	4	NA	NA
441201	2	NA	5	1	1	NA	3	NA	1	1	3	5	5
441202	1	NA	1	1	5	NA	1	NA	5	1	1	5	1
441203	3	NA	1	5	1	NA	5	NA	1	5	1	5	1
441204	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	4	3	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
441301	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA						
441302	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA						
441303	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA						
441304	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA	NA						
441305	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA						
441401	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	3	NA
441402	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA
441403	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	2	4	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA
441501	1	NA	1	NA	3	4	5	1	4	5	5	3	5
441502	1	NA	4	NA	1	5	2	4	4	5	5	1	5
441503	3	NA	1	NA	4	4	5	1	3	5	2	1	5
441504	1	NA	1	NA	4	5	5	1	1	5	5	1	5
441505	5	NA	5	NA	4	5	5	5	1	3	4	NA	4
441601	3	NA	3	5	3	1	1	1	3	2	4	5	3
441602	5	NA	3	5	3	5	5	4	1	4	5	4	3
441603	1	NA	1	5	3	1	5	4	1	3	1	1	1
441604	5	NA	4	5	1	5	1	1	1	5	5	4	4
441605	5	NA	1	1	3	1	3	5	1	3	1	1	1
441606	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	5	1
441607	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4
441901	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
441902	5	1	5	5	5	3	5	5	4	5	5	5	4
441903	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
441904	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
511101	NA	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	5	NA	4	NA	NA
511102	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	3	NA	4	NA	NA
511103	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
511104	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
511105	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	1	4	NA	4	NA	NA
511106	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	4	NA	4	NA	NA
511107	NA	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	4	NA	1	NA	NA
511108	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	2	5	NA	1	NA	NA
511109	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
511110	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	4	NA	1	NA	NA
511111	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	5	5	4	NA	4	NA	NA
511201	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
511202	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
511203	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
511204	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
511205	NA	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
511206	NA	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
511207	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
511208	NA	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
511209	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
511210	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
511301	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	1	1	3	NA	1	NA
511302	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	3	NA	1	1	5	NA	1	NA
511303	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	3	1	5	NA	5	NA
511304	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	2	NA	1	1	5	NA	1	NA
511305	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	1	5	NA	1	NA
511306	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	4	4	NA	5	NA
511307	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	1	1	4	NA	5	NA
511308	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	3	NA	1	1	4	NA	1	NA
511309	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	5	4	NA	5	NA
512001	5	NA	5	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	1	5
512002	5	NA	5	1	1	1	5	1	1	5	5	1	1
512003	5	NA	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
512004	5	NA	5	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	4	5	5
512005	5	NA	4	5	5	1	5	5	5	4	4	1	4
512006	1	NA	4	5	5	1	1	1	5	4	4	1	5
513101	5	NA	5	1	3	3	1	NA	4	NA	1	NA	1
513102	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	NA	4	NA	5	NA	5
513103	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	5
513104	5	NA	1	5	5	5	5	NA	4	NA	5	NA	1
513105	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	NA	4	NA	5	NA	5
513106	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5
513107	1	NA	1	5	5	5	1	NA	5	NA	5	NA	1
513201	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	5	5
513202	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	5	5
513203	1	NA	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	5	5
513204	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	5	5	5
513205	1	NA	5	NA	1	NA	1	1	5	NA	1	1	5
513206	5	NA	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	5	5
513207	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	4	1	4	NA	5	5	2
513208	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	3	NA	5	1	1
513209	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	1	1	1	NA	5	5	5
513210	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	4	1	5	NA	5	5	5
514101	5	5	5	1	5	3	4	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5
514102	5	4	1	5	1	5	4	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1
514103	5	5	5	5	5	3	4	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	4
514104	5	3	1	5	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1
514105	5	5	5	5	4	1	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5
514106	5	5	2	5	4	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1
514107	4	5	5	5	1	1	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
514108	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5
514201	NA	NA	5	4	1	4	1	5	5	1	5	5	5
514202	NA	NA	5	5	1	1	1	5	5	1	5	5	5
514203	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
514204	NA	NA	5	5	1	1	1	5	1	5	5	4	3
514205	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	3
514206	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	5	5	1	5	1	1
514207	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
514208	NA	NA	5	5	5	1	1	5	5	1	5	1	1
515101	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	3	5	1	1
515102	5	NA	NA	1	1	3	NA	1	1	1	1	4	1
515103	5	NA	NA	1	1	1	5	1	1	5	5	4	1
515104	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	5	1	1
515105	1	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	1	5
515106	1	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	1	1	3	5	1	5
515107	1	NA	NA	3	1	4	5	1	1	3	1	1	1
515108	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	4	1	1	4	1	1	1
515201	1	NA	1	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
515202	1	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
515203	1	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
515204	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
515205	5	NA	4	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
515206	5	NA	4	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
515207	NA	NA	1	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA
515208	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
515209	5	NA	4	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
515301	1	NA	1	1	1	5	5	NA	1	NA	NA	2	NA
515302	1	NA	5	1	2	5	5	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA
515303	1	NA	5	1	1	1	5	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
515305	4	NA	5	1	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
515306	1	NA	5	1	1	1	5	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
515307	1	NA	1	1	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA
515308	1	NA	5	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
516301	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	5	NA
516302	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	3	NA
516303	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	5	NA
516304	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	3	NA
516305	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	5	NA
516306	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	5	NA
516401	3	5	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	5	NA
516402	5	4	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	3	NA	5	5	NA
516403	5	4	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	5	5	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
516404	1	5	5	NA	1	NA	1	3	1	NA	5	5	NA
516405	4	3	4	NA	1	NA	1	4	1	NA	5	5	NA
516406	4	4	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	5	NA
516407	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	3	5	5	NA	5	5	NA
516408	1	2	1	NA	1	NA	1	4	5	NA	4	1	NA
516409	1	4	4	NA	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	5	NA
516501	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
516502	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
516503	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
516504	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA
516505	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
516506	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA
516901	NA	NA	3	3	1	NA	3	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	5
516902	NA	NA	4	3	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	1
516903	NA	NA	1	1	5	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	1
521101	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	2	NA	1	NA	NA
521102	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
521103	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	4	NA	1	NA	NA
521104	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	1	1	2	NA	3	NA	NA
521105	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	NA	NA
521106	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	5	4	NA	5	NA	NA
521107	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
521201	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
521202	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	4	NA	4	NA	NA	NA
521203	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
521204	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
521205	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	3	NA	NA	NA
522101	1	NA	5	5	5	1	5	4	5	NA	4	5	5
522102	1	NA	5	1	1	1	4	3	1	NA	4	5	3
522103	1	NA	1	1	1	1	3	1	5	NA	3	5	3
522104	1	NA	1	1	5	1	3	5	5	NA	4	5	5
522105	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5	5	4
522106	5	NA	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	NA	4	1	2
522107	5	NA	3	5	3	1	3	4	5	NA	5	1	2
522201	5	NA	1	5	3	1	3	5	4	NA	5	5	5
522202	4	NA	4	3	4	5	5	5	5	NA	4	1	5
522203	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
522204	1	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	2	1	1
522205	5	NA	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
522206	4	NA	1	5	3	5	3	4	5	NA	5	4	5
522207	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
522208	5	NA	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
522301	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
522302	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
522303	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5
522304	1	3	5	5	3	5	3	1	1	3	5	2	4
522305	5	4	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
523001	5	5	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	4	5	5	5
523002	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	4	5	1	5
523003	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
523004	5	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	1	3	5	1	1
523005	1	1	1	1	5	5	5	5	1	1	1	1	5
523006	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	4	5	5	5
523007	1	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	5	1	5	1	5
523008	1	1	1	5	5	1	1	1	4	4	5	1	5
524201	5	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	4
524202	5	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	5	4
524203	1	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	4
524204	5	NA	NA	5	NA	3	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	1
524205	1	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	5	4
524301	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA							
524302	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
524303	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
524304	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
524305	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
524306	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
524307	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
524401	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	4	2	5	5	5	5	5
524402	1	NA	1	1	5	NA	1	1	5	5	1	1	1
524403	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	4	3	1	1	1	1	1
524404	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
524405	1	NA	1	1	5	NA	1	3	1	5	5	1	5
524406	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1
524407	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	1	3	5	5	5	5	1
524408	5	NA	3	1	5	NA	1	3	1	5	1	5	1
524501	NA	NA	5	1	5	NA	4	NA	4	NA	5	NA	NA
524502	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA
524503	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	3	NA	NA
524504	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
524505	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
524506	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
524507	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
524508	NA	NA	5	1	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA
524601	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	1	NA	4	NA	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
524602	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
524603	4	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
524604	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
524605	3	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	NA	5
524606	3	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	5	NA	5
524607	4	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	4	NA	5	NA	4
524608	4	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA	5
531101	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
531102	1	NA	5	1	5	4	5	5	5	1	5	2	1
531103	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5
531104	1	NA	5	5	5	3	5	1	5	1	5	5	4
531105	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
531106	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
531107	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
531108	5	NA	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	1	1	5	1
531201	NA	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	1	1	2	NA	1	5
531202	NA	NA	4	4	2	NA	3	1	5	2	NA	3	4
531203	NA	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	1	5	3	NA	5	5
531204	NA	NA	1	5	5	NA	5	2	5	4	NA	5	5
531205	NA	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	2	5	3	NA	5	5
531206	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	5	2	5	1	NA	5	5
531207	NA	NA	4	1	5	NA	5	2	5	2	NA	4	5
532101	1	NA	5	1	5	1	5	4	5	5	5	5	5
532102	5	NA	5	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	2	5	5
532103	1	NA	5	5	1	5	1	5	5	5	1	5	5
532104	1	NA	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	1	5	5
532105	1	NA	1	5	1	5	1	4	1	1	1	1	1
532106	5	NA	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5
532201	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	5	5
532202	1	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	1	5
532203	1	NA	2	5	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	5	5
532204	1	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	1	1	5
532205	5	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	4	5	5
532206	1	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	4	1	5
532207	1	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	5	4	5
532208	1	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	1	1	1
532209	1	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	3	1	1
532901	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	5	1	1
532902	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	1	1	1	1	3	1	1
532903	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	5	1	5	1	1	5	5
532904	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	5	1	1	1	5	5	1
532905	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
532906	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
541101	NA	NA	3	NA	5	NA	3	NA	4	5	NA	4	NA
541102	NA	NA	3	NA	1	NA	3	NA	4	3	NA	4	NA
541103	NA	NA	3	NA	5	NA	3	NA	2	2	NA	5	NA
541104	NA	NA	3	NA	1	NA	2	NA	2	1	NA	2	NA
541105	NA	NA	2	NA	5	NA	3	NA	1	1	NA	5	NA
541106	NA	NA	4	NA	5	NA	4	NA	1	1	NA	5	NA
541201	3	5	5	3	5	NA	5	5	5	4	5	3	NA
541202	3	4	5	5	3	NA	1	5	5	5	4	3	NA
541203	1	3	3	5	1	NA	1	4	4	1	1	2	NA
541204	1	3	2	5	1	NA	1	5	5	1	4	2	NA
541301	NA	NA	5	1	4	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	1	4
541302	NA	NA	5	2	4	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	1	4
541303	NA	NA	1	4	4	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	5
541304	NA	NA	5	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	1	5
541305	NA	NA	5	1	4	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	1	4
541306	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	4	1	5
541307	NA	NA	3	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	1	4
541401	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
541402	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
541403	5	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
541404	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
541405	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
541406	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
541901	2	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1
541902	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5
541903	1	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5
541904	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5
611101	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
611102	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA
611103	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA
611104	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	2	3	NA	NA	NA
611105	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	NA
611106	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
611107	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
611108	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
611109	3	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
611110	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
611111	4	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
611201	NA	1	NA	2	1	NA							
611202	NA	1	NA	4	1	NA							
611203	NA	2	NA	1	1	NA							

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
611204	NA	2	NA	2	1	NA							
611205	NA	1	NA	3	1	NA							
611206	NA	1	NA	2	1	NA							
611207	NA	4	NA	1	1	NA							
611208	NA	2	NA	1	1	NA							
611209	NA	3	NA	1	1	NA							
611210	NA	1	NA	4	5	NA							
611211	NA	1	NA	3	NA	NA							
611301	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	2	1	1	1	NA	1
611302	5	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	3	1	1	1	NA	1
611303	3	NA	3	5	2	NA	NA	3	1	2	2	NA	1
611304	2	NA	4	1	2	NA	NA	3	1	1	3	NA	1
611305	3	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	2	1	1	1	NA	1
611306	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	NA	4	1	3	3	NA	4
611307	3	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	4	1	1	1	NA	1
611308	1	NA	1	1	2	NA	NA	3	1	3	1	NA	1
611309	5	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1
611310	1	NA	1	1	2	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1
611311	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1
611312	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	3	1	1	1	NA	3
611401	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	4	1
611402	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	3	NA	NA	NA	3	5
611403	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	2	NA	NA	NA	3	5
611404	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	3	NA	NA	NA	3	5
611405	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	1	NA	NA	NA	3	5
611406	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	3	5						
611407	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	2	NA	NA	NA	3	5
611408	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	3	5
611409	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	3	5
611410	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	3	5
611411	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	3	5
612101	5	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	3	1	NA	3	2	NA
612102	5	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	5	4	NA	5	5	NA
612103	5	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	4	5	NA	5	5	NA
612104	3	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	3	3	NA	5	5	NA
612105	5	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	3	5	NA	5	5	NA
612106	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	5	NA	1	1	NA
612107	5	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	4	5	NA	5	5	NA
612108	5	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	2	5	NA	1	5	NA
612109	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	5	NA	5	5	NA
612110	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	4	1	NA	1	1	NA
612111	1	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
612112	1	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	4	1	NA	5	3	NA
612113	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	3	1	NA	5	5	NA
612201	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612202	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612203	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612204	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612205	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612206	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612207	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA							
612208	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612209	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612210	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA							
612211	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612212	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
612901	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	3	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
612902	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
612903	4	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
612904	5	NA	NA	1	1	NA	2	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
612905	4	NA	NA	4	1	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
612906	5	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
612907	4	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
612908	3	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
612909	1	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
612910	1	NA	NA	3	1	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
613001	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
613002	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
613003	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
613004	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
613005	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
613006	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
613007	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
613008	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
613009	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
613010	2	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
621001	NA	4	3	NA	2	1	2	2	3	1	2	NA	NA
621002	NA	4	2	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
621003	NA	4	1	NA	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
621004	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
621005	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
621006	NA	2	1	NA	1	1	5	2	1	1	2	NA	NA
621007	NA	4	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	NA	NA
621008	NA	4	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
621009	NA	4	1	NA	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
621010	NA	4	1	NA	1	2	1	2	1	1	3	NA	NA
622101	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	2	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA
622102	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	4	NA	NA	3	5	NA	NA
622103	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	4	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA
622104	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	4	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA
622105	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	4	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA
622106	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA
622107	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
622108	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	1	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA
622109	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA
622110	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	4	5	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA
622201	NA	5	NA	NA	NA								
622202	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
622203	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
622204	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
622205	NA	5	NA	NA	NA								
622206	NA	5	NA	NA	NA								
622208	NA	5	NA	NA	NA								
622209	NA	5	NA	NA	NA								
622210	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
622301	NA	4	3	NA	NA	NA							
622302	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA							
622303	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA							
622304	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA							
622305	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA							
622306	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA							
622307	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA							
622308	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA							
622309	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA							
631001	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA							
631002	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
631003	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
631004	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
631005	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
631006	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
632001	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
632002	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
632003	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
632004	5	NA											
632005	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
632006	3	NA											

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
632007	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
632008	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
632009	4	NA											
632010	1	NA											
632011	5	NA											
632012	1	NA											
633001	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
633002	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
633003	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
633004	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
633005	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
633006	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
633007	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
633008	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
633009	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
711101	NA	NA	NA	4	1	NA	2	2	1	1	1	NA	NA
711102	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	3	NA	NA
711103	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	3	1	3	NA	NA
711104	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	2	2	1	1	1	NA	NA
711105	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	2	1	2	2	3	NA	NA
711106	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	2	2	1	1	5	NA	NA
711107	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	1	2	4	1	5	NA	NA
711201	5	NA	5	1	4	NA	1	5	5	NA	4	4	NA
711202	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	3	1	NA	2	2	NA
711203	4	NA	5	5	1	NA	1	3	1	NA	3	5	NA
711301	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
711302	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
711303	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
711304	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
711305	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
711306	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
711307	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
711401	NA	NA	NA	1	4	4	NA	NA	1	4	NA	1	NA
711402	NA	NA	NA	3	4	1	NA	NA	3	5	NA	4	NA
711403	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	5	NA	4	NA
711404	NA	NA	NA	5	3	1	NA	NA	2	5	NA	4	NA
711405	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	4	5	NA	1	NA
711501	5	5	5	3	5	NA	1	NA	3	5	4	1	5
711502	1	5	3	5	5	NA	1	NA	2	1	3	1	1
711503	5	5	2	5	5	NA	3	NA	5	1	3	2	1
711504	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1
711505	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
711901	3	NA	1	5	NA	2	5	1	1	NA	3	3	NA
711902	4	NA	2	1	NA	1	3	1	3	NA	3	2	NA
711903	3	NA	2	4	NA	2	2	1	1	NA	4	2	NA
712101	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA
712102	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA
712103	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA
712104	NA	NA	5	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA
712105	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
712106	NA	NA	2	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA
712201	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	1	NA	2	NA	4	NA	NA
712202	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	3	NA	5	NA	4	NA	NA
712203	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	1	NA	3	NA	4	NA	NA
712204	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA
712301	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	2	NA	5	2	NA	NA	NA
712302	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	2	NA	2	2	NA	NA	NA
712303	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	2	NA	2	2	NA	NA	NA
712304	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA
712401	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA
712402	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	2	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA
712403	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
712404	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	2	NA
712405	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
712406	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
712501	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	5	NA
712502	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	5	NA
712503	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
712504	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	5	NA
712601	NA	NA	4	NA	5	3	5	5	5	5	4	5	NA
712602	NA	NA	1	NA	3	3	1	5	1	1	4	5	NA
712603	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	4	1	2	1	2	NA
712604	NA	NA	5	NA	4	1	5	3	1	1	3	4	NA
712701	1	5	NA	1	2	5	NA	3	1	NA	NA	1	NA
712702	5	5	NA	4	3	3	NA	3	5	NA	NA	1	NA
712703	5	4	NA	4	3	1	NA	1	5	NA	NA	1	NA
712704	5	5	NA	5	3	3	NA	5	5	NA	NA	1	NA
713101	5	NA	5	4	5	NA	5	5	5	1	2	5	2
713102	4	NA	5	5	1	NA	4	5	1	5	1	5	3
713103	4	NA	4	5	3	NA	3	3	5	5	3	5	3
713104	4	NA	1	5	1	NA	3	5	1	2	1	1	2
713105	4	NA	5	5	5	NA	3	5	5	5	3	5	2
713201	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5							
713202	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA							

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
713203	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
713301	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	4	NA	5	NA	NA
713302	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
713303	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
721101	NA	NA	5	1	2	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1
721102	NA	NA	2	1	1	NA	1	1	2	NA	NA	NA	1
721103	NA	NA	3	5	1	NA	3	1	3	NA	NA	5	1
721104	NA	NA	3	5	2	NA	1	4	3	NA	NA	5	5
721105	NA	NA	4	5	2	NA	1	1	4	NA	NA	5	NA
721106	NA	NA	4	4	2	NA	1	1	3	NA	NA	5	5
721107	NA	NA	4	5	2	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	5	1
721201	5	5	5	2	5	5	5	NA	5	5	1	5	5
721202	5	4	1	2	1	5	1	NA	5	1	1	1	3
721203	1	4	1	5	1	4	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1
721204	5	4	5	NA	1	1	1	NA	5	1	1	5	1
721205	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	NA	1	2	1	4	2
721206	5	5	5	5	1	5	1	NA	1	1	1	4	1
721207	5	5	1	5	1	1	5	NA	5	1	5	3	1
721208	5	5	4	NA	5	1	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5
721301	NA	NA	1	1	5	2	1	1	5	1	5	NA	NA
721302	NA	NA	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
721303	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	NA	NA
721304	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	5	1	NA	NA
721305	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	5	NA	NA
721306	NA	NA	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	5	5	NA	NA
721307	NA	NA	1	1	1	3	1	4	1	5	5	NA	NA
721401	NA	NA	NA	1	4	5	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
721402	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
721403	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
721404	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
721405	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
721406	NA	NA	NA	1	4	1	1	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA
721501	NA	5	NA	NA	NA								
721502	NA	3	NA	NA	NA								
721503	NA	2	NA	NA	NA								
721504	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
721505	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
722101	1	NA	NA	1	1	3	5	5	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
722102	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	5	5	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
722103	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
722104	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	3	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
722105	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
722106	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
722107	1	NA	NA	5	1	3	1	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
722108	1	NA	NA	1	1	4	NA						
722201	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	1	5	2	NA	NA	4
722202	5	NA	NA	1	1	NA	5	1	1	3	NA	NA	3
722203	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	1	1	5	NA	NA	4
722204	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	1	4	4	NA	NA	5
722205	5	NA	NA	5	5	NA	5	1	3	3	NA	NA	3
722206	5	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	1	1	4	NA	NA	5
722207	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1
722208	NA	NA	NA	4	1	NA	1	1	1	4	NA	NA	1
722209	5	NA	NA	4	1	NA	1	1	1	3	NA	NA	1
722210	5	NA	NA	4	1	NA	1	1	1	4	NA	NA	1
722211	5	NA	NA	4	5	NA	5	4	1	4	NA	NA	4
722301	4	NA	5	1	5	1	1	4	5	1	5	4	1
722302	1	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	1	4	5
722303	1	NA	2	5	1	1	1	3	1	1	4	5	2
722304	3	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1	4	5	5
722305	5	NA	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
722306	2	NA	1	5	5	1	1	4	3	4	4	4	4
722401	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
722402	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
722403	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
722404	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
722405	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
722406	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
722407	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
723101	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
723102	5	NA	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	1	4	5	5
723103	5	NA	4	5	2	1	5	3	3	3	4	5	1
723104	5	NA	5	5	5	1	5	4	5	5	5	5	1
723105	5	NA	5	5	1	5	1	1	5	5	4	4	1
723106	5	NA	4	5	1	4	1	1	4	1	4	4	1
723107	1	NA	5	1	3	5	5	4	5	5	3	4	5
723108	1	NA	5	1	1	1	1	4	5	4	5	1	1
723201	NA	NA	NA	5	1	5	NA	NA	5	NA	1	5	1
723202	NA	NA	NA	5	1	4	NA	NA	4	NA	1	1	1
723203	NA	NA	NA	5	1	5	NA	NA	5	NA	3	5	1
723204	NA	NA	NA	5	1	4	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	1
723205	NA	NA	NA	5	5	4	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	1
723206	NA	NA	NA	4	5	1	NA	NA	5	NA	1	4	5
723207	NA	NA	NA	4	5	2	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
723208	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	1
723209	NA	NA	NA	5	5	3	NA	NA	5	NA	5	1	1
723210	NA	NA	NA	5	5	3	NA	NA	5	NA	5	1	1
723301	4	NA	4	1	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
723302	4	NA	5	1	5	5	5	2	1	4	4	1	1
723303	4	NA	1	5	3	4	2	3	4	3	3	5	1
723304	4	NA	5	5	5	3	4	2	5	3	4	1	1
723305	4	NA	5	5	5	3	5	3	5	2	4	5	1
723306	5	NA	4	5	5	3	5	3	5	1	5	1	1
723307	5	NA	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	1
723401	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
723402	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
723403	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
723404	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
723405	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
723406	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
731101	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA	4	3	NA	NA
731102	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA	1	2	NA	NA
731103	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	5	NA	1	4	NA	NA
731104	NA	5	NA	1	2	NA	NA						
731105	NA	5	NA	5	4	NA	NA						
731106	NA	5	NA	5	3	NA	NA						
731107	NA	5	NA	5	4	NA	NA						
731108	NA	5	NA	1	2	NA	NA						
731109	NA	5	NA	5	2	NA	NA						
731110	NA	5	NA	5	3	NA	NA						
731111	NA	1	NA	1	3	NA	NA						
731112	NA	5	NA	5	2	NA	NA						
731201	NA	2	NA	NA	2	NA							
731202	NA	4	NA	NA	3	NA							
731203	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA							
731204	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA							
731205	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA							
731206	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA							
731207	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA							
731208	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA							
731209	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA							
731210	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA							
731211	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA							
731301	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
731302	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
731303	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
731304	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
731305	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
731306	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA
731307	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
731308	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
731309	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
731310	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
731311	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
731401	NA	3											
731402	NA	1											
731403	NA	3											
731404	NA	1											
731405	NA	1											
731406	NA	2											
731407	NA	2											
731408	NA	3											
731409	NA	2											
731410	NA	2											
731411	NA	5											
731501	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731502	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731503	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731504	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731505	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731506	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
731507	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731508	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731509	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731510	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731511	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731512	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731513	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
731601	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA						
731602	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731603	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA						
731604	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA						
731605	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA						
731606	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731607	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA						
731608	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731609	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731610	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
731611	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731612	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731613	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA						
731614	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731701	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA
731702	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA
731703	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA
731704	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA
731705	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	2	NA
731706	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	3	NA
731707	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731708	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA
731709	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731710	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731711	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA						
731801	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731802	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA							
731803	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731804	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731805	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731806	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731807	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731808	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731809	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731810	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731811	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731812	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731813	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
731814	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
732101	2	NA	1	1	3	1	1	5	1	4	1	NA	NA
732102	5	NA	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	NA	NA
732103	3	NA	1	4	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	NA	NA
732104	5	NA	5	5	2	5	1	1	5	3	1	NA	NA
732105	1	NA	1	5	3	5	1	1	1	2	1	NA	NA
732106	5	NA	3	4	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	NA
732107	2	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
732201	1	NA	4	1	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5
732202	1	NA	4	1	1	1	4	1	5	5	5	NA	1
732203	1	NA	4	1	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	NA	5
732204	4	NA	1	1	5	5	1	1	1	5	5	NA	4
732205	1	NA	4	1	1	1	1	1	5	5	1	NA	1
732206	5	NA	4	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
732207	4	NA	4	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	5
732208	1	NA	2	3	5	5	4	1	5	5	4	NA	5
732209	5	NA	1	5	1	1	5	1	1	1	5	NA	1
732301	NA	NA	2	5	NA	1	1	NA	1	4	NA	5	NA
732302	NA	NA	5	1	NA	1	2	NA	1	5	NA	5	NA
732303	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	5	5	NA	4	NA
732304	NA	NA	4	1	NA	5	5	NA	1	1	NA	3	NA
732305	NA	NA	1	5	NA	3	1	NA	1	5	NA	3	NA
732306	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	5	1	NA	4	NA
732307	NA	NA	1	1	NA	5	5	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA
741101	5	NA	5	1	4	5	5	3	5	5	1	5	5
741102	3	NA	1	1	4	1	1	4	1	5	1	5	1
741103	3	NA	4	5	5	1	4	4	5	5	5	4	5
741104	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	3	4	5	5	5	5
741105	5	NA	4	5	5	4	5	3	5	5	1	5	2
741106	4	NA	1	5	5	1	3	3	1	4	5	5	1
741107	4	NA	1	5	1	1	3	3	1	4	1	3	2
741108	5	NA	4	5	4	4	4	3	3	5	1	5	2
741201	5	1	1	1	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5	5
741202	3	1	4	3	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	1
741203	1	1	4	4	5	1	5	1	1	1	3	1	4
741204	5	5	5	4	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	4
741205	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1
741206	5	3	3	4	5	1	5	5	1	5	5	5	2
741207	4	2	3	3	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	4
741301	3	NA	1	4	5	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	1
741302	3	NA	1	4	3	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1
741303	5	NA	1	4	5	2	5	5	4	1	5	1	4
741304	3	NA	3	1	3	1	5	1	2	5	5	5	3
741305	1	NA	1	5	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
741306	4	NA	3	5	1	1	5	1	1	5	5	5	4
742101	NA	NA	5	1	4	1	NA	3	5	NA	NA	4	NA
742102	NA	NA	5	3	4	1	NA	3	5	NA	NA	5	NA
742103	NA	NA	5	5	3	1	NA	3	5	NA	NA	4	NA
742104	NA	NA	2	4	1	1	NA	3	4	NA	NA	5	NA
742105	NA	NA	4	5	1	5	NA	1	1	NA	NA	3	NA
742106	NA	NA	4	1	2	1	NA	1	5	NA	NA	3	NA
742107	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	NA	3	4	NA	NA	4	NA
742108	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA
742109	NA	NA	5	3	4	5	NA	3	5	NA	NA	1	NA
742201	5	NA	3	1	1	1	5	5	1	1	1	1	NA
742202	3	NA	2	5	1	1	1	4	3	1	1	5	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
742203	5	NA	4	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	5	NA
742204	5	NA	3	5	3	5	4	5	1	5	5	1	NA
742205	5	NA	5	3	4	1	5	1	4	5	1	1	NA
742206	3	NA	5	4	4	1	5	1	5	4	1	1	NA
742207	1	NA	1	5	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA
751101	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	1	3
751102	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	1	5
751103	5	NA	1	1	1	2	5	5	1	NA	5	1	1
751104	5	NA	1	2	1	1	5	1	1	NA	1	1	1
751105	5	NA	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	NA	4	1	5
751106	5	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
751107	5	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	NA	5	1	1
751108	5	NA	5	1	1	1	5	5	1	NA	5	5	1
751201	5	NA	2	5	1	2	5	5	5	1	1	1	5
751202	1	NA	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
751203	5	NA	3	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	5
751204	1	NA	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
751205	5	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4
751206	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
751207	5	NA	5	5	5	5	1	1	5	5	5	5	5
751208	5	NA	4	5	1	1	1	5	1	1	5	5	5
751301	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
751302	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
751303	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
751304	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
751305	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
751306	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
751307	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
751308	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
751401	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA							
751402	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
751403	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
751404	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
751405	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
751501	5	NA	NA	1	5	1	4	2	1	5	5	5	1
751502	5	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	5	4	5	4	1
751503	3	NA	NA	1	1	5	4	4	1	5	5	4	1
751504	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	3	4	5	4	4
751505	4	NA	NA	5	5	1	1	1	5	4	1	3	1
752101	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
752102	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
752103	NA	NA	3	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
752104	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
752105	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
752106	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
752201	NA	5	4	1	5	NA	5	4	4	NA	5	5	NA
752202	NA	5	2	1	5	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	5	NA
752203	NA	5	4	5	5	NA	3	3	5	NA	5	5	NA
752204	NA	4	4	5	3	NA	4	5	5	NA	5	4	NA
752205	NA	4	4	5	2	NA	3	3	2	NA	1	3	NA
752206	NA	3	4	5	5	NA	4	5	1	NA	5	4	NA
752301	NA	NA	NA	5	5	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA
752302	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA
752303	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
752304	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA
752305	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA
752306	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA
753101	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753102	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753103	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753104	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753105	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753106	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753107	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753108	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753109	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753110	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753111	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
753201	4	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA
753202	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA
753203	5	NA	NA	5	5	1	1	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA
753204	4	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA
753205	4	NA	NA	5	1	5	4	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA
753206	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	3	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA
753207	1	NA	NA	4	1	5	1	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA
753208	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	5	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA
753209	5	NA	NA	2	1	1	5	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA
753210	4	NA	NA	1	1	1	4	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA
753211	5	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA
753212	5	NA	NA	1	1	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA
753301	1	3	NA	1	3	NA	1	3	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
753302	1	3	NA	1	5	NA	4	4	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
753303	1	4	NA	1	5	NA	5	4	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
753304	1	3	NA	5	1	NA	1	3	2	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
753305	1	1	NA	5	1	NA	1	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
753306	1	5	NA	1	5	NA	5	1	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
753307	3	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	3	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
753308	1	5	NA	5	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753309	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753310	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753311	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753312	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	3	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753401	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
753402	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
753403	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA
753404	4	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
753405	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
753406	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	3	NA
753407	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
753408	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	2	NA	NA	1	NA
753409	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
753410	4	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
753411	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
753412	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
753501	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA
753502	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA
753503	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA
753504	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA
753505	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA
753506	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA
753507	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA
753508	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA
753509	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA
753510	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA
753511	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA
753512	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA
753513	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA
753601	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
753602	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
753603	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753604	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753605	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753606	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
753607	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753608	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753609	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
753610	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753611	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
753612	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
753613	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754101	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754102	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
754103	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754104	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754105	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754106	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754107	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754108	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754109	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754110	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754111	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
754301	5	NA	4	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5
754302	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
754303	5	NA	4	5	5	5	1	5	5	1	1	5	1
754304	5	NA	5	1	1	5	1	5	5	5	4	5	1
754305	5	NA	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5
754306	1	NA	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	1	5
754307	5	NA	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5
754308	5	NA	1	5	1	1	5	1	1	5	1	5	5
754309	5	NA	2	5	1	4	5	5	1	5	5	5	5
754401	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA
754402	5	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	3	NA
754403	5	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	1	NA
754404	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA
754405	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	2	NA
754406	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	3	NA
754407	4	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	4	NA
811101	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
811102	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
811103	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
811104	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
811105	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA
811106	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA
811107	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA
811108	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	5	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA
811109	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
811201	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	4	NA	5	3	NA	NA
811202	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
811203	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	5	1	NA	NA
811204	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	NA	1	1	NA	NA
811205	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	4	NA	1	1	NA	NA
811206	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	NA	1	1	NA	NA
811207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	4	NA	5	1	NA	NA
811208	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
811209	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	3	NA	5	NA	NA	NA
811210	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	3	NA	NA
811301	1	NA	5	5	1	1	4	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
811302	1	NA	1	1	1	1	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
811303	1	NA	1	1	1	1	5	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
811304	5	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
811305	1	NA	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
811306	1	NA	5	1	1	5	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
811307	NA	NA	5	1	1	5	5	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA
811308	1	NA	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
811309	1	NA	1	1	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
811310	1	NA	1	1	1	4	1	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
811401	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
811402	NA	5	NA	NA	NA								
811403	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
811404	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
811405	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
811406	NA	1	NA	NA	NA								
811407	NA	5	NA	NA	NA								
812101	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
812102	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
812103	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
812104	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
812105	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
812106	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	5	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
812107	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	NA	NA
812108	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
812201	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	5	NA	NA	5	3	1	NA
812202	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA
812203	NA	NA	NA	1	1	4	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA
812204	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA
812205	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	4	1	NA
812206	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA
812207	NA	NA	NA	1	5	4	1	NA	NA	1	5	5	NA
812208	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA
813101	1	NA	5	1	4	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
813102	5	NA	1	1	4	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
813103	5	NA	1	4	5	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
813104	5	NA	1	1	5	NA	NA	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
813105	1	NA	1	1	3	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
813106	3	NA	1	5	4	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	NA	NA
814101	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	5	1	NA	5	NA	NA
814102	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	1	NA	5	NA	NA
814103	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	5	1	NA	5	NA	NA
814104	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
814105	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	5	5	NA	1	NA	NA
814106	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	NA
814201	5	NA	NA	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	NA	1	NA
814202	5	NA	NA	1	5	1	4	5	1	5	NA	5	NA
814203	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA
814204	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA
814205	5	NA	NA	1	5	5	1	5	5	5	NA	5	NA
814206	5	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	NA	NA	NA
814207	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	NA
814301	5	NA	5	1	NA	5	NA						
814302	1	NA	1	3	NA	1	NA						
814303	5	NA	1	1	NA	5	NA						
815101	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA						
815102	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815103	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815104	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815105	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815106	NA	4	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815107	NA	4	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815108	NA	4	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815109	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815110	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815111	NA	4	NA	NA	1	NA	NA						
815201	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815202	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	3	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815203	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
815204	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	3	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
815205	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815206	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815207	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815208	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815209	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815210	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
815211	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
815212	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
815213	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
815301	5	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
815302	5	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
815303	5	NA	NA	1	1	5	4	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815304	1	NA	NA	1	1	5	4	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
815305	1	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815306	1	NA	NA	5	1	4	1	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815307	5	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
815308	5	NA	NA	1	5	5	4	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
815406	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815412	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815601	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815602	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
815603	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
815701	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815702	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815703	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815704	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815705	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815706	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815707	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815708	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815709	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
815901	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	4	1	NA	1	5	NA
815902	NA	NA	NA	4	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA
815903	NA	NA	NA	1	2	1	NA	1	5	NA	5	1	NA
815904	NA	NA	NA	3	1	2	NA	1	1	NA	1	1	NA
815905	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	NA
816001	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
816002	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
816003	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
816004	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
816005	NA	NA	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	5	5
816006	NA	NA	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	5
816007	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1
817101	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
817102	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
817103	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA
817104	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
817105	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
817201	1	NA	1	1	4	1	NA	1	3	NA	5	NA	1
817202	1	NA	1	4	4	4	NA	3	5	NA	1	NA	1
817203	5	NA	1	5	5	5	NA	1	1	NA	4	NA	5
817204	1	NA	1	NA	1	5	NA	1	1	NA	1	NA	1
817205	1	NA	1	1	4	5	NA	1	3	NA	1	NA	4
818101	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818102	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818103	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818104	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818105	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818106	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818107	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818108	5	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818109	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818110	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818111	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA						
818112	1	NA	NA	4	NA	1	NA						
818113	5	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA						
818201	5	NA	NA	1	3	5	3	5	1	5	NA	NA	NA
818202	4	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	4	4	5	NA	NA	NA
818203	5	NA	NA	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	NA	NA	NA
818204	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	1	1	2	NA	NA	NA
818205	4	NA	NA	5	5	1	1	4	1	1	NA	NA	NA
818206	1	NA	NA	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA
818207	5	NA	NA	4	5	5	2	3	1	1	NA	NA	NA
818301	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
818302	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
818303	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
821101	1	NA	3	NA	5	4	1	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
821102	2	NA	4	NA	4	3	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
821103	3	NA	5	NA	4	3	4	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
821104	4	NA	5	NA	5	3	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
821105	4	NA	5	NA	5	4	1	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
821201	5	NA	NA	5	2	4	5	1	5	NA	1	5	5
821202	4	NA	NA	1	1	5	5	5	5	NA	5	5	5
821203	3	NA	NA	5	1	5	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	5
821204	NA	NA	NA	1	1	3	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1
821205	4	NA	NA	5	1	5	5	1	5	NA	5	5	5
821901	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	5	5	5	NA	5
821902	NA	NA	NA	1	4	4	1	1	1	5	4	NA	3
821903	NA	NA	NA	1	1	4	5	5	5	1	5	NA	1
821904	NA	NA	NA	3	5	1	1	4	5	5	5	NA	4

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
821905	NA	NA	NA	3	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	NA	5
831101	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
831102	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
831103	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	4	NA	NA
831104	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	1	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
831105	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	1	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
831201	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA	3	NA
831202	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA	1	NA	3	NA
831203	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA
831204	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA
831205	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA
832101	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA						
832102	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA						
832103	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	5	NA						
832104	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	3	NA						
832105	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	4	NA						
832201	1	1	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	NA	3	5	1
832202	5	5	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	NA	5	1	5
832203	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	NA	3	1	1
832204	4	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	5	NA	1	1	1
832205	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	5	1	1
832206	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	1	5	NA	5	5	5
832207	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
832208	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
833101	5	NA	5	1	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	5	5	NA
833102	5	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1	1	1	5	NA
833103	5	NA	5	1	5	NA	1	NA	5	5	5	5	NA
833104	5	NA	3	1	1	NA	1	NA	1	5	5	1	NA
833105	4	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	5	5	NA
833106	5	NA	5	5	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	5	5	NA
833107	1	NA	1	5	5	NA	1	NA	5	5	1	1	NA
833201	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
833202	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5
833203	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5
833204	1	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	3	1	5	5
833205	1	3	1	5	4	1	5	3	1	3	3	1	1
833206	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
834101	NA	NA	4	1	5	NA	2	NA	2	NA	3	NA	NA
834102	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	2	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
834103	NA	NA	1	5	5	NA	2	NA	4	NA	4	NA	NA
834104	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	4	NA	4	NA	NA
834105	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
834106	NA	NA	1	4	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
834107	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
834108	NA	NA	3	1	4	NA	2	NA	4	NA	5	NA	NA
834201	5	5	3	1	NA	1	5	NA	5	NA	4	5	NA
834202	3	5	1	1	NA	2	5	NA	1	NA	5	5	NA
834203	1	5	2	1	NA	3	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	NA
834204	1	5	1	1	NA	4	5	NA	1	NA	3	5	NA
834205	1	4	1	1	NA	5	5	NA	1	NA	1	5	NA
834206	1	3	1	1	NA	1	5	NA	1	NA	2	5	NA
834207	1	3	1	1	NA	2	4	NA	1	NA	3	4	NA
834301	NA	NA	5	1	5	NA	NA	3	5	5	NA	5	NA
834302	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	5	NA
834303	NA	NA	1	4	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	5	NA
834304	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	5	NA	1	NA
834305	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA
834306	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA
834307	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	1	NA
834401	1	NA	NA	1	4	5	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	5
834402	5	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA	1	5	5
834403	1	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	1	NA	5	1	5
834404	1	NA	NA	1	4	1	NA	NA	1	NA	5	3	1
834405	5	NA	NA	1	4	3	NA	NA	1	NA	5	1	1
835001	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA
835002	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
835003	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	3	NA	NA	NA
835004	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA
835005	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA
835006	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	3	NA	NA	NA
911101	5	NA	1	1	NA	NA	5	4	5	NA	5	5	5
911102	4	NA	1	1	NA	NA	2	4	4	NA	5	5	1
911103	5	NA	1	5	NA	NA	5	4	5	NA	5	NA	3
911104	1	NA	5	1	NA	NA	1	4	5	NA	1	5	1
911105	1	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	4	4	NA	1	4	1
911106	5	NA	5	1	NA	NA	5	4	5	NA	5	5	5
911107	5	NA	5	1	NA	NA	5	4	3	NA	3	5	4
911201	5	NA	5	5	5	1	5	1	5	5	1	5	5
911202	1	NA	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	5	1
911203	5	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	NA
911204	5	NA	4	1	5	5	5	4	1	5	5	5	5
912101	NA	NA	5	NA	5	4	5	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA
912102	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	4	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
912103	NA	NA	1	NA	4	1	5	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
912104	NA	NA	1	NA	1	1	5	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA
912201	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
912202	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
912203	NA	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
912204	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA
912205	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
912206	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
912301	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
912302	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
912303	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	5	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
912901	5	NA	5	1	1	4	3	1	1	NA	1	1	1
912902	5	NA	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1
912903	4	NA	3	1	1	5	4	3	1	NA	5	1	1
912904	1	NA	4	5	1	5	1	1	1	NA	NA	5	1
921101	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	1	NA	NA
921102	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA
921103	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
921104	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
921105	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
921106	NA	NA	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
921107	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	2	NA	NA
921108	NA	NA	NA	1	2	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	2	NA	NA
921201	NA	3	1	NA	NA	NA	NA						
921202	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	4	4	NA	NA	NA	NA
921203	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
921204	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
921205	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
921206	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	3	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
921207	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921208	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921209	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA							
921210	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA							
921301	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921302	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921303	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921304	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	NA	NA
921305	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921306	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921307	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921308	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921309	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921310	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
921311	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
921401	3	NA	1	NA	1	4	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA
921402	5	NA	1	NA	5	4	NA	NA	4	NA	1	NA	NA
921403	5	NA	1	NA	5	3	NA	NA	4	NA	1	NA	NA
921404	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
921405	5	NA	2	NA	1	4	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	NA
921406	5	NA	1	NA	5	3	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
921407	5	NA	1	NA	5	3	NA	NA	5	NA	1	NA	NA
921408	1	NA	1	NA	5	3	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
921409	1	NA	2	NA	1	3	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	NA
921501	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
921502	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
921503	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA							
921504	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	NA							
931101	5	NA	NA	1	5	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5
931102	5	NA	NA	1	3	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5
931103	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1
931104	1	NA	NA	4	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3
931105	1	NA	NA	4	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1
931106	1	NA	NA	4	5	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5
931107	1	NA	NA	1	5	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5
931201	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	4	1	NA	4	5	NA	1	NA
931202	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	5	5	NA	1	NA
931203	NA	NA	NA	NA	4	1	1	NA	1	4	NA	1	NA
931204	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	1	5	NA	5	NA
931205	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	5	NA
931301	1	NA	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	NA	2	1	1
931302	1	NA	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	NA	3	3	2
931303	5	NA	4	3	1	1	1	1	4	NA	4	1	1
931304	5	NA	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	NA	4	1	1
931305	1	NA	5	3	4	2	5	1	5	NA	4	1	NA
931306	5	NA	5	1	4	3	1	3	4	NA	4	5	1
932101	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	5	5	5	5	NA	NA	5	NA
932102	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	4	NA	NA	4	NA
932103	NA	NA	2	NA	NA	1	5	1	1	NA	NA	4	NA
932901	1	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5
932902	4	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	4
932903	5	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	5
932904	4	NA	NA	5	1	3	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	5
933301	1	5	1	5	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	5
933302	5	5	5	5	5	1	5	NA	5	3	5	5	1
933303	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	NA	1

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
933304	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	1	1	1	1	1
933305	5	5	4	5	5	1	5	NA	5	5	5	5	5
933306	4	4	5	5	5	1	5	5	5	5	1	5	5
933401	4	NA	5	5	5	5	4	NA	4	NA	NA	4	5
933402	5	NA	5	5	5	1	4	NA	5	NA	NA	5	5
933403	3	NA	5	5	4	1	5	NA	5	NA	NA	5	5
933404	5	NA	5	5	5	5	4	NA	5	NA	NA	5	5
933405	5	NA	5	5	5	5	1	NA	1	NA	NA	5	4
933406	5	NA	5	5	5	5	1	NA	5	NA	NA	5	1
933407	5	NA	1	5	1	5	1	NA	5	NA	NA	5	2
933408	5	NA	5	1	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	NA	5	5
941101	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5
941102	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	4	5	NA	NA	5
941103	1	NA	NA	NA	4	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	1
941104	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	4	NA	1	5	NA	NA	5
941105	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5
941106	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	1	NA	4	4	NA	NA	5
941107	5	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	1	5	NA	NA	1
941108	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	5
941109	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA	NA	1
941110	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	5
941201	1	NA	3	5	4	NA	5	NA	5	5	5	5	NA
941202	1	NA	3	5	1	NA	5	NA	1	5	5	5	NA
941203	1	NA	1	5	1	NA	1	NA	5	NA	5	5	NA
941204	4	NA	3	4	1	NA	1	NA	1	NA	5	3	NA
941205	4	NA	3	5	4	NA	1	NA	5	1	1	5	NA
941206	1	NA	3	4	1	NA	1	NA	1	5	5	5	NA
941207	1	NA	3	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	5	NA	NA
952001	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA							
952002	NA	NA	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA	NA
952003	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
952004	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
952005	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
961101	NA	NA	NA	4	5	NA	NA	NA	5	NA	NA	5	NA
961102	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
961103	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
961104	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA
961201	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
961202	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
961203	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
961204	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	5	NA	NA	NA	NA
961205	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA

Task	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NET	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
961206	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA
961301	NA	NA	NA	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	NA	5	NA
961302	NA	NA	NA	1	5	1	2	1	1	5	NA	1	NA
961303	NA	NA	NA	1	1	4	1	3	1	1	NA	1	NA
961304	NA	NA	NA	1	5	5	5	5	1	5	NA	5	NA
962101	5	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	5	1	NA
962102	5	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	4	1	NA
962103	5	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	5	1	NA
962104	4	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	3	1	NA
962105	1	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	NA	5	1	NA
962106	5	NA	NA	NA	5	1	1	1	5	NA	5	5	NA
962107	1	NA	NA	NA	4	2	3	1	1	NA	1	5	NA
962201	NA	NA	4	NA	1	5	NA	NA	3	3	4	2	NA
962202	NA	NA	4	NA	1	5	NA	NA	5	1	3	3	NA
962203	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	NA	NA	3	1	2	2	NA
962204	NA	NA	5	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	2	3	2	NA
962205	NA	NA	3	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA
962206	NA	NA	3	NA	2	4	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	NA
962207	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	NA
962301	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	4	5	NA	1	1	NA
962302	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	3	1	NA	1	1	NA
962303	NA	4	NA	NA	3	NA	1	5	4	NA	3	5	NA
962304	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	3	1	NA	5	NA	NA
962305	NA	4	NA	NA	5	NA	1	4	4	NA	1	5	NA
962306	NA	1	NA	NA	1	NA	1	4	4	NA	1	5	NA
962307	NA	1	NA	NA	5	NA	5	4	5	NA	1	1	NA
962901	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	2	1
962902	NA	NA	5	1	1	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	5	5
962903	NA	NA	5	4	4	NA	NA	5	1	NA	NA	3	5
962904	NA	NA	5	1	4	NA	NA	5	4	NA	NA	3	5
962905	NA	NA	1	3	5	NA	NA	2	1	NA	NA	3	1
962906	NA	NA	1	5	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	5	1
962907	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	3	1
962908	NA	NA	1	1	1	NA	NA	1	1	NA	NA	1	4

appendix 5 Ratio of valid answers on total respondents identified in each occupation, by task and country

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
111101	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
111102	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
111103	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
111104	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0.67	0	0	0	0	0
111105	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
111106	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
111107	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
111108	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
111201	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
111202	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
111203	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
111204	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
111205	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
111206	1	0	0	1	0.75	1	1	1	1	0	0.67	1	1
111207	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
111208	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	0.88	1	1	0	1	1	1
111209	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	0	1	1	1
111401	0	0	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
111402	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0	0
111403	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0	0
111404	0	0	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
111405	0	0	1	1	1	0.67	0.67	1	1	1	1	0	0
111406	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
111407	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0	0
111408	0	0	1	1	1	0.67	0.33	1	1	1	1	0	0
111409	0	0	1	1	1	0.67	0.33	1	1	1	1	0	0
112001	0.98	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.96
112002	1	1	1	1	0.98	0.98	0.93	1	0.97	1	0.97	1	0.96
112003	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.9	1	0.98	1	0.99	1	0.96
112004	0.98	0.67	1	1	0.98	0.98	0.9	1	0.96	1	0.99	0.97	0.96
112005	1	0.67	1	1	0.98	1	0.93	0.98	0.96	1	0.97	1	1
112006	0.98	1	0.97	0.91	0.93	1	0.93	0.98	0.95	1	0.99	0.97	0.96
112007	1	1	0.97	1	0.95	1	1	0.93	0.97	1	0.99	1	0.96

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
112008	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	0.93	0.98	0.93	1	0.96	0.97	0.96
112009	0.98	1	1	1	0.93	1	0.9	0.95	0.95	1	0.97	1	0.92
112010	0.98	1	1	1	0.89	0.95	0.93	0.98	0.92	1	1	1	0.96
112011	1	1	1	1	0.95	0.95	0.97	0.98	0.96	1	1	1	0.96
121101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.92
121102	0.96	0	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	1
121103	0.92	0	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	1	1
121104	1	0	1	1	1	0.97	0.96	1	0.97	1	0.98	1	1
121105	1	0	1	1	0.91	1	0.82	1	0.97	1	0.98	1	1
121106	1	0	1	0.89	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	0.92	1	1
121107	1	0	1	1	1	0.97	0.93	1	1	1	0.95	1	1
121108	0.96	0	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	0.95	1	1
121201	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	0.98	1	1
121202	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.98	1	1	1	1	1
121203	1	1	1	0.96	0.89	0.99	0.93	0.92	1	1	1	0.91	1
121204	1	1	1	0.96	0.89	1	0.97	0.96	1	1	1	1	1
121205	1	1	1	0.96	0.78	0.99	0.9	0.94	1	1	0.98	1	1
121206	1	1	1	0.96	0.89	0.97	0.93	0.98	1	1	0.98	1	1
121207	1	1	1	0.92	0.78	0.97	0.93	0.94	1	0.89	0.98	0.91	1
121208	1	1	1	0.92	0.67	0.97	0.97	0.96	1	1	0.94	1	0.9
121209	1	1	1	0.96	0.89	0.99	0.93	0.96	0.97	1	0.94	1	1
121210	0.97	1	1	0.96	0.89	0.93	1	0.96	1	1	0.98	1	1
121211	1	1	1	0.92	0.89	0.97	1	0.94	1	1	0.94	1	1
121301	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
121302	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
121303	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
121304	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
121305	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
121306	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
121307	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
121308	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
121901	1	1	1	0.95	0.94	1	0.93	0.99	0.97	1	1	1	1
121902	0.98	1	1	1	0.92	1	0.85	0.99	0.95	1	1	1	0.94
121903	1	0.9	1	0.95	0.94	0.96	0.93	0.99	0.98	1	0.99	0.97	0.97
121904	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	0.98	0.95	1	0.97	1	1
121905	0.93	1	1	1	0.94	0.93	0.85	0.96	0.97	1	0.97	0.97	1
121906	0.93	1	0.95	0.95	0.92	1	0.88	0.99	0.97	1	0.95	1	1
121907	0.95	1	1	0.95	0.92	1	0.88	0.99	0.95	1	0.96	1	0.97
121908	0.95	1	1	0.95	0.89	1	0.88	0.98	0.98	1	0.98	0.97	1
121909	1	0.9	1	0.95	0.86	1	0.88	0.98	0.99	1	1	1	1
121910	0.95	0.9	1	0.9	0.81	1	0.85	0.98	0.98	1	0.99	1	1
122101	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.99	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
122102	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0.98	1	0.96	1	1
122103	0.96	1	0.95	1	0.95	1	0.98	0.97	0.98	1	1	1	0.96
122104	1	1	1	1	0.95	0.95	0.98	1	0.96	0.89	0.96	1	0.96
122105	1	1	0.95	0.96	0.98	0.95	0.97	1	0.98	0.94	0.96	1	1
122106	0.96	1	1	1	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.94	0.96	1	1
122107	0.91	1	0.95	1	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.93	0.94	0.96	1	0.96
122108	0.96	1	1	1	0.95	0.92	0.95	1	0.97	0.89	0.98	1	1
122201	1	1	1	0	0.91	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	0.5
122202	1	1	0.75	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	0.75
122203	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.77	1	1	1	1	0.75	1
122204	1	1	0.75	0	0.91	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	1
122205	1	1	0.75	0	0.91	1	0.92	1	1	0.75	1	1	1
122206	1	1	1	0	0.91	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
122207	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.86	1	1
122208	1	1	0.75	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
122301	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1
122302	0.75	0	0.9	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1
122303	0.75	0	1	1	1	0.92	0.6	1	1	1	0.91	1	1
122304	1	0	0.9	1	1	1	0.8	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
122305	1	0	1	1	1	0.92	0.8	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
122306	0.75	0	1	1	1	0.92	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1
122307	1	0	0.9	1	1	0.92	0.8	1	1	0.67	0.91	1	1
122308	1	0	0.9	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1
131101	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.67	0	1
131102	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
131103	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
131104	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
131105	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
131106	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
131107	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
131108	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.67	0	1
131109	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
131110	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
131111	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
131112	0.67	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
131201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131202	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131203	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131204	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131205	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131206	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131207	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
131208	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131209	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131211	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131212	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
131213	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
132101	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
132102	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
132103	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1
132104	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1
132105	1	0	1	1	0.86	0	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1
132106	1	0	1	1	0.86	0	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1
132107	1	0	1	1	0.86	0	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1
132108	1	0	0.5	1	0.86	0	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1
132109	1	0	1	1	0.86	0	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1
132110	1	0	1	1	0.86	0	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	1
132111	1	0	1	1	0.86	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
132112	1	0	1	1	0.86	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
132201	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
132202	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	0
132203	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	0
132204	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	0
132205	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
132206	1	0	0	1	0	1	0.75	1	1	0	1	1	0
132207	1	0	0	1	0	0.91	1	1	1	0	1	0.5	0
132208	1	0	0	1	0	1	0.75	1	1	0	1	1	0
132209	1	0	0	1	0	0.91	0.75	1	1	0	1	1	0
132210	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
132301	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
132302	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
132303	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
132304	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.88	1	1
132305	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
132306	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
132307	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
132308	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
132309	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
132310	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
132311	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
132401	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	0.95	0.8	1	1	1
132402	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
132403	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	0.95	0.8	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
132404	0.92	1	1	1	0.75	1	1	0.95	0.97	1	0.96	1	1
132405	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	0.91	1
132406	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
132407	1	1	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	0.87	0.8	1	1	1
132408	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	0.9	0.95	0.97	0.8	1	1	1
132409	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	0.9	1	1	1	1	1	1
132410	0.92	1	1	0.93	1	0.94	0.9	1	1	0.8	0.96	1	1
132411	1	1	1	1	0.88	0.94	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
133001	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1
133002	0.92	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
133003	1	0	0.92	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.96	1	1
133004	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.96	1	1
133005	1	0	1	0.83	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.96	1	1
133006	0.83	0	0.83	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.98	1	1	0.9	1
133007	0.92	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.96	0.9	1
133008	0.92	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.96	0.9	0.9
133009	0.92	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.96	0.9	1
133010	0.92	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	0.9	1
133011	0.92	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.91	0.9	1
134101	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
134102	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
134103	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
134104	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
134105	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
134106	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
134107	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
134108	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
134109	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
134201	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	1
134202	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	1
134203	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	1
134204	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
134205	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
134206	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	1
134207	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	1
134208	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	1
134209	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.5	0	0	1	1
134210	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.5	0	0	1	1
134301	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
134302	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
134303	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
134304	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
134305	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
134306	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
134307	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
134308	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
134309	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
134310	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
134401	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
134402	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
134403	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
134404	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0.5	0	1
134405	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0.83	0	1	0	1
134406	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
134407	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
134408	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
134409	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	1	0.83	0	1	0	1
134410	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
134411	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
134501	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0.75
134502	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
134503	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134504	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134505	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
134506	1	0	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134507	1	0	1	0.67	1	0.83	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
134508	1	0	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
134509	1	0	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
134510	1	0	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
134511	1	0	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
134601	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134602	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	1
134603	1	1	0.67	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134604	1	1	1	0.86	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134605	1	1	1	0.71	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134606	1	1	1	0.86	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134607	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134608	1	1	1	0.86	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134609	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134610	1	1	1	0.71	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134611	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
134901	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.89	0	1	1	0	1	1
134902	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.89	0	1	1	0	1	1
134903	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.89	0	1	0.75	0	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
134904	1	0	1	0.5	1	0	0.89	0	1	0.75	0	1	1
134905	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.89	0	1	1	0	1	1
134906	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
134907	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
134908	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.89	0	1	1	0	1	1
134909	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
141101	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141102	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141103	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141104	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141105	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141106	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141107	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.75
141108	0.8	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141109	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141110	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141201	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0.86	0.94	1	1	1	1
141202	1	0	1	0	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
141203	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
141204	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
141205	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.94	1	1
141206	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.94	1	1
141207	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.94	1	1
141208	1	0	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1
141209	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.94	1	1
141210	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0.86	0.97	1	0.94	1	1
142001	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1
142002	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.94	1	1
142003	1	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	0.91
142004	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1
142005	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1
142006	1	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
142007	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	1	1
143101	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
143102	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.92	0	1	1	0
143103	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0.8	1	0	1	1	0
143104	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
143105	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
143106	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
143107	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
143108	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.67	1	0
143109	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0.8	1	0	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
211101	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211102	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211103	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211104	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211105	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211106	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211107	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211108	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211109	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211110	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
211111	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
211201	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211202	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211203	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211204	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211205	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211206	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211207	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211208	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211209	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211210	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
211301	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.89	1	1	1	1
211302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.89	1	1	1	1
211303	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.78	1	1	1	1
211304	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.78	1	1	1	1
211305	0.5	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.78	1	0.5	1	1
211306	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	0.5	1	1
211307	0.5	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	0.5	1	1
211308	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	0.5	1	1
211309	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1
211401	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
211402	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.75	1	1	1
211403	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
211404	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.75	1	1	1
211405	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.75	1	1	1
211406	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.75	1	1	1
211407	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	0.95	1	1	0.75	1	1	1
211408	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.75	1	1	1
211409	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1
211410	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.75	1	1	1
211411	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.75	1	1	1
211412	1	0	0	0.8	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.75	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
212001	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
212002	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
212003	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
212004	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
212005	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
212006	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
212007	1	1	1	0.5	0	0	1	0.92	0.9	0	1	1	1
212008	1	1	1	1	0	0	0.67	1	1	0	1	1	1
212009	1	1	1	1	0	0	0.67	1	1	0	1	1	1
213101	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
213102	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
213103	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
213104	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
213105	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
213106	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
213107	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
213108	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
213201	1	0	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.67	1
213202	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
213203	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
213204	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
213205	1	0	0.5	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.85	0	0.88	1	1
213206	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
213207	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
213208	1	0	1	1	0.9	1	0.75	1	0.85	0	1	1	1
213209	1	0	1	1	0.9	1	0.75	1	0.85	0	0.88	1	1
213210	1	0	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	0.85	0	0.88	1	1
213211	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.88	1	1
213301	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
213302	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
213303	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0.86	1	1	0	0
213304	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0.93	1	1	0	0
213305	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0.93	1	1	0	0
213306	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.67	0	1	1	1	0	0
213307	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
214101	1	1	0.92	1	0.96	1	1	0.99	0.96	0.87	0.96	1	1
214102	1	1	0.92	1	0.95	1	0.97	1	0.96	0.87	0.96	1	1
214103	0.87	1	0.92	0.9	0.94	1	0.94	0.97	0.96	0.87	1	1	1
214104	0.93	1	0.92	0.8	0.97	1	0.98	0.94	0.96	0.87	1	1	1
214105	0.87	1	0.92	0.9	0.93	1	0.97	0.99	0.96	0.73	1	1	1
214106	0.87	1	0.92	1	0.91	1	0.92	0.99	1	0.8	1	0.97	1
214107	0.8	1	0.92	1	0.94	1	0.95	0.96	1	0.87	0.96	0.95	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
214108	0.8	1	0.92	0.9	0.91	0.96	0.92	0.97	0.96	0.8	0.96	0.92	1
214109	0.8	1	0.92	0.9	0.92	0.96	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.8	1	0.97	1
214110	0.8	1	1	0.9	0.93	0.96	0.97	0.99	1	0.8	1	0.97	1
214201	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.67
214202	1	0	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
214203	1	0	1	1	1	0.93	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1
214204	1	0	1	1	0.94	1	0.88	1	0.94	1	1	0.91	1
214205	1	0	1	1	0.97	0.93	0.88	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
214206	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	0.88	1	0.88	1	1	1	1
214207	1	0	1	1	0.94	0.86	0.94	1	0.88	1	1	1	0.67
214301	1	0	0	1	1	0	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1
214302	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
214303	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
214304	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
214305	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
214306	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1
214307	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
214308	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1
214309	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1
214401	0.86	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.75	1	1	1
214402	0.93	1	0.89	1	1	1	0.86	0.92	0.93	0.75	0.94	1	1
214403	0.93	1	0.89	1	1	1	0.86	0.97	1	1	0.97	1	1
214404	0.86	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.93	0.75	0.88	1	1
214405	0.79	1	0.89	1	0.89	1	0.86	0.89	0.93	0.75	0.88	1	1
214406	1	1	1	0.92	0.89	1	0.86	0.97	0.93	0.75	0.97	1	1
214407	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.94	1
214501	1	0	1	1	0.5	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
214502	1	0	1	1	0.5	0	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	0
214503	1	0	1	1	0.5	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	0
214504	1	0	1	1	0.5	0	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	0
214505	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	0
214506	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	0
214507	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	0
214508	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	0
214601	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.63	1	1	1	1	1	0
214602	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	0
214603	0	0	0	1	0.91	1	0.63	1	1	0	1	1	0
214604	0	0	0	0	0.91	1	0.38	1	1	0	1	1	0
214605	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.63	1	1	0	1	1	0
214606	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.63	0.67	1	0	1	1	0
214607	0	0	0	1	0.91	1	0.38	0.67	1	0	1	1	0
214608	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.88	0.67	1	0	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
214609	0	0	0	1	0.91	0	0.75	0.67	1	0	1	1	0
214901	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.82	1	0	1	1
214902	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.91	1	0.82	1	0	1	1
214903	1	0	1	0	1	0	0.91	1	0.91	1	0	1	1
214904	0.5	0	1	1	1	0	0.82	1	0.82	1	0	1	1
214905	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.91	1	0.82	1	0	1	1
214906	1	0	1	0.5	1	0	0.91	1	0.82	1	0	1	1
214907	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.91	0.93	0.82	1	0	1	1
214908	1	0	1	0.5	1	0	0.91	1	0.82	1	0	1	1
214909	1	0	1	0.5	1	0	1	1	0.91	1	0	1	1
215101	0.78	1	1	1	1	0	0.9	1	1	0.67	1	1	1
215102	0.89	1	1	1	0.88	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
215103	0.89	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67
215104	1	1	1	1	0.88	0	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	1
215105	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1
215106	1	1	1	0.89	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1
215201	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
215202	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	1
215203	1	0	1	1	0.93	0	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	1
215204	1	0	1	1	0.93	0	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	1
215205	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1
215206	1	0	0.83	1	0.93	0	1	0.96	1	1	1	0.67	1
215207	1	0	1	1	0.93	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
215208	1	0	1	1	0.87	0	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	1
215301	1	0	1	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
215302	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	0.95	1
215303	1	0	1	1	0.9	1	0.97	1	1	0.83	1	0.95	1
215304	0.86	0	1	1	0.9	0.5	0.9	1	1	1	1	1	1
215305	1	0	1	1	0.9	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1
215306	0.71	0	1	1	0.9	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1
215307	0.86	0	1	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
216101	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.94	0.5	1	1	0
216102	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.98	0.94	1	1	1	0
216103	0.95	1	1	1	0.93	1	0	0.97	0.88	1	1	1	0
216104	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.95	0.88	1	1	1	0
216105	0.95	1	1	0.5	0.86	1	0	0.93	0.82	1	1	1	0
216106	0.89	1	1	1	0.86	0.95	0	0.93	0.82	1	1	1	0
216107	0.95	1	1	1	0.93	1	0	0.93	0.94	1	1	1	0
216108	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	0	0.97	0.82	1	1	1	0
216109	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	0	0.97	0.88	1	1	1	0
216201	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
216202	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
216203	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
216204	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
216205	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
216206	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0.8	0	0	0	0
216207	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0.8	0	0	0	0
216208	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0.8	0	0	0	0
216209	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0.8	0	0	0	0
216301	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1
216302	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
216303	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
216304	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
216305	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
216306	1	0	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
216307	1	0	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
216308	1	0	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
216309	0.83	0	1	0.8	0.88	0.88	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1
216401	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
216402	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
216403	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
216404	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
216405	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
216406	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
216407	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
216408	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
216409	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
216501	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
216502	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
216503	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.67	1	1	0	1	1	0
216504	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.67	0	1	1	0
216505	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
216506	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
216507	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
216508	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
216601	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	0.99	1	0.97	1	1
216602	0.97	1	1	1	0.92	0.95	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
216603	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	0.8	1	0.96	1	0.97	1	1
216604	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.96	1	0.86	1	1	0.95
216605	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.8	0.98	0.95	1	0.97	1	1
216606	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	0.98	1	0.92	1	1
216607	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.7	1	0.99	1	0.97	1	1
216608	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	0.8	0.98	0.96	1	0.97	0.88	1
216609	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.94	0.95	1	0.95	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
216610	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	0.8	0.98	0.99	1	0.97	1	0.95
221101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
221102	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
221103	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
221104	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
221105	1	0	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
221106	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
221107	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0
221108	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	0
221109	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	0
221110	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	0
221111	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	0.75	0
221201	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
221202	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.89	1	0	1
221203	1	0	0	1	0.93	0	0.93	1	1	1	0.8	0	1
221204	1	0	1	1	0.95	0	0.97	0.93	1	1	1	0	1
221205	1	0	1	1	0.98	0	0.93	1	0.92	1	1	0	1
221206	1	0	1	1	0.98	0	0.97	0.93	0.92	1	1	0	1
221207	1	0	1	0.67	0.98	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	0	1
221208	1	0	1	1	0.95	0	1	0.93	0.92	1	1	0	1
221209	1	0	1	1	0.93	0	0.97	1	1	0.78	0.6	0	1
221210	1	0	1	1	0.9	0	0.93	0.93	0.92	0.78	0.8	0	1
221211	1	0	1	1	0.88	0	0.9	1	1	0.78	0.8	0	1
221212	1	0	1	1	0.93	0	0.9	1	1	0.78	0.8	0	1
222101	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	0.98	0.9	1	1	1
222102	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	0.85	1	0.99	0.9	1	1	1
222103	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.85	1	0.98	0.9	1	1	1
222104	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1
222105	1	0	0.96	1	0.96	0.94	0.95	1	0.98	0.9	1	1	1
222106	1	0	0.96	1	0.91	0.94	0.9	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
222107	1	0	0.96	1	0.96	1	0.9	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
222108	1	0	0.98	1	0.96	1	0.75	1	0.99	0.9	1	1	1
222109	0.93	0	0.98	1	0.91	1	0.75	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
222110	1	0	0.98	1	0.87	1	0.75	1	0.98	0.9	1	1	1
222201	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
222202	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
222203	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
222204	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
222205	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
222206	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
222207	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
222208	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
223001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
223002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
223003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
223004	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
223005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
223006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
223007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
224001	1	0	1	0	0.89	1	1	1	0.95	0	1	0	0
224002	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.86	0	1	0	0
224003	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	0.91	0	1	0	0
224004	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.91	0	1	0	0
224005	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	0.91	0	1	0	0
224006	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.95	0	1	0	0
224007	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
224008	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.91	0	1	0	0
224009	1	0	1	0	0.89	1	1	1	0.91	0	1	0	0
224010	0	0	0	0	0.33	0.33	0.4	0	0.32	0	0.5	0	0
225001	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
225002	1	0	0.5	0	1	0	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
225003	1	0	1	0	0.95	0	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
225004	1	0	1	0	0.95	0	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
225005	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
225006	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
225007	1	0	1	0	0.95	0	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
225008	1	0	1	0	0.95	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
225009	1	0	1	0	0.95	0	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
226101	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226102	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226103	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226104	0	0	0	1	0.86	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226105	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226106	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226107	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226108	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226109	0	0	0	1	0.86	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226110	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226111	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226112	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
226201	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	0.75	1	0
226202	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	0
226203	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
226204	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.33	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
226205	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	0
226206	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
226207	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
226208	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0
226209	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	1	0.75	1	0
226210	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	1	1	1	0
226211	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
226212	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
226213	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	1	0.8	1	1	0.75	1	0
226301	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226302	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226303	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226304	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226305	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226306	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226307	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226308	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226309	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226310	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
226401	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
226402	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
226403	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
226404	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
226405	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
226406	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
226407	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0.83	1
226501	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
226502	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.86	0	0	0	0
226503	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.86	0	0	0	0
226504	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
226505	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
226506	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
226507	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
226601	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
226602	0	0	1	1	0.5	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
226603	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
226604	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0.83	0	1	0	0
226605	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
226606	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
226607	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
226701	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
226702	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
226703	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.95	0	0	1	0
226704	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
226705	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.95	0	0	1	0
226706	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
226707	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
226901	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.67	1
226902	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
226903	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
226904	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
226905	0.67	0	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	1	1	1
226906	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	1	1	1
226907	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	0.94	0	1	1	1
226908	1	0	1	0	1	0.5	0.5	1	0.94	0	1	1	1
231001	1	1	0.93	0.91	0.94	1	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.95	0.97	0.94	1
231002	0.93	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.97	0.98	0.97	0.95	0.93	1	1
231003	0.86	1	0.93	0.91	0.96	1	0.91	0.94	0.99	0.95	1	1	1
231004	0.93	1	1	0.91	0.94	1	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.95	1	1	1
231005	0.93	1	1	0.91	0.94	1	0.93	1	0.99	0.95	0.93	1	0.92
231006	0.79	1	1	0.91	0.88	1	0.9	0.99	0.93	0.86	0.97	1	0.92
231007	0.93	1	0.93	0.82	0.99	1	0.9	0.99	1	0.95	1	1	0.92
231008	0.93	1	1	0.73	0.97	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.92
231009	0.93	1	1	0.91	0.99	0.94	0.98	0.96	1	0.95	1	1	0.92
232001	0	1	1	0	1	1	0.97	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
232002	0	1	1	0	0.95	1	0.88	1	0.98	0.75	1	1	1
232003	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.98	0.88	0.86	0	1
232004	0	1	1	0	0.95	1	0.94	1	0.98	0.88	0.86	1	1
232005	0	1	1	0	0.89	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.86	1	1
232006	0	1	1	0	0.95	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.86	1	1
232007	0	1	1	0	0.95	1	0.88	1	0.96	1	0.71	1	1
232008	0	1	1	0	0.79	1	0.91	1	0.93	0.88	0.71	1	1
232009	0	1	1	0	0.89	1	0.97	1	0.98	0.88	0.86	1	1
232010	0	1	1	0	0.89	1	0.94	1	0.96	0.88	0.71	1	1
233001	0.93	0	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
233002	1	0	0.5	1	0.94	1	0.98	1	0.95	0.93	1	1	1
233003	1	0	1	1	0.99	1	0.99	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
233004	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	0.97	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
233005	1	0	1	1	0.99	1	0.98	1	1	1	1	1	1
233006	1	0	0.5	1	0.96	1	0.95	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
233007	1	0	1	1	0.98	1	0.95	1	0.98	0.93	1	1	1
233008	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	0.95	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
233009	1	0	1	1	0.97	1	0.96	1	0.93	1	1	1	1
233010	1	0	1	1	0.96	0.93	0.96	1	0.98	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
233011	1	0	1	1	0.96	0.93	0.95	1	0.98	0.93	1	1	1
234101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
234102	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	0.93	1	1	0	1	1	1
234103	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	0.96	1	0	1	1	1
234104	1	0	1	0.92	0.88	1	0.95	1	0.98	0	1	1	1
234105	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	0.95	1	0.96	0	1	1	1
234106	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	0.93	1	0.96	0	1	1	1
234107	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	0.93	1	0.96	0	0.89	0.8	1
234108	1	0	1	1	0.88	0.91	0.95	0.96	0.94	0	1	1	1
234109	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	0.96	0.96	0	1	1	1
234110	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	0.93	1	0.96	0	1	1	1
234201	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
234202	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
234203	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
234204	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
234205	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.86	0	0
234206	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
234207	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
234208	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
234209	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
235101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235102	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1
235103	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235104	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	1
235105	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235106	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	0.95	1	1	1	0.92	1	1
235107	1	0	1	0.88	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	0.92	1	1
235108	0.67	0	0.5	0.88	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	0.92	1	1
235109	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.93	1	1	0.92	1	1
235110	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.93	1	1	0.92	1	1
235201	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	0	0
235202	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
235203	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	0.94	0.88	1	1	1	0	0
235204	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	0	0
235205	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	0.81	0.75	1	1	1	0	0
235206	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	0.81	0.75	1	1	1	0	0
235207	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	0.94	0.75	1	1	1	0	0
235208	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	0.75	1	1	1	0	0
235209	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	0.81	0.75	1	1	1	0	0
235210	1	0	1	1	0.79	0.9	0.81	0.75	1	1	1	0	0
235211	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	0.75	1	0	1	0	0
235301	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
235302	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235303	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235304	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	1
235305	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235306	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	1
235307	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235308	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235401	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
235402	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
235403	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	0	0.5	0
235404	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
235405	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.5	0
235406	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
235407	1	1	0	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
235408	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.75	1	1	0	1	0
235409	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
235410	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	0	1	0
235411	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.5	0
235501	1	0	0	0	0.9	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
235502	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
235503	1	0	0	0	1	1	0.75	0	1	1	0	1	0
235504	1	0	0	0	1	1	0.5	0	1	0	0	1	0
235505	1	0	0	0	0.8	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
235506	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
235507	1	0	0	0	1	1	0.5	0	1	1	0	1	0
235508	1	0	0	0	0.9	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
235509	1	0	0	0	0.9	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
235510	1	0	0	0	1	1	0.75	0	1	1	0	1	0
235601	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235602	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235603	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	1	1
235604	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235605	0.5	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235606	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235901	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
235902	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1
235903	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	0.88
235904	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	0.92	0.96	1	1	1	0.88
235905	1	1	0	1	0.94	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1
235906	1	1	0	1	0.94	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	0.75
235907	1	1	0	1	0.94	1	1	0.92	1	0.5	1	1	1
235908	1	1	0	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
235909	1	1	0	1	0.94	1	1	0.85	0.96	1	0.94	1	0.88
235910	1	1	0	1	0.94	1	1	0.92	0.96	1	1	1	0.88
235911	1	1	0	1	0.94	1	1	0.92	0.96	1	1	1	0.88
241101	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.97	1	1	1	0.98	1	1
241102	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1
241103	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	0.98	0.98	1	0.99	1	1
241104	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.97	0.97	1	1	0.98	0.96	1
241105	1	1	1	1	0.94	0.98	0.92	1	0.94	1	0.97	1	0.97
241106	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	0.97	1	0.97	0.86	0.97	1	1
241107	0.97	1	0.93	1	0.93	0.98	0.84	0.97	0.98	1	0.94	1	1
241108	0.97	1	0.93	1	0.96	0.97	0.95	0.98	0.95	1	0.96	1	0.97
241201	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
241202	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.94	0	1	0	1
241203	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0.83	0	1
241204	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
241205	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0.94	0	1	0	0
241206	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0.67	0	1
241301	1	0	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
241302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
241303	1	0	1	0.95	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
241304	1	0	1	0.95	0.75	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.88	1	1
241305	1	0	1	0.95	0.75	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.88	1	1
241306	1	0	1	0.95	0.75	0.8	0.93	0.94	0.91	1	0.88	1	1
241307	1	0	1	0.95	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.88	0.9	1
241308	1	0	1	0.95	0.75	1	0.93	1	0.91	1	0.88	1	1
241309	1	0	1	0.95	0.75	0.8	0.93	1	0.91	1	0.75	1	1
242101	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
242102	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
242103	0.89	1	1	1	0	1	0.8	0.93	1	0	1	1	1
242104	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.8	1	1	0	1	1	1
242105	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.6	1	1	0	1	1	1
242106	0.89	1	1	1	0	1	0.6	1	1	0	0.92	1	1
242107	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.6	1	0.95	0	0.92	1	1
242108	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.8	0.93	1	0	0.85	1	1
242109	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.8	1	0.95	0	0.92	1	1
242201	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0	1
242202	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.67	1	0.97	1	1	0	1
242203	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0	1
242204	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
242205	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	0	1
242206	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0	1
242207	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
242301	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.98	1	1	1	1	1	1
242302	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.97	0.96	0.97	0.95	0.8	0.98	1	1
242303	1	1	0.96	1	0.96	0.96	0.98	0.94	0.97	1	1	1	1
242304	0.93	1	0.96	1	0.92	0.87	0.98	1	1	1	0.98	1	1
242305	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.9	0.95	1	0.99	1	1	1	0.93
242401	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
242402	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
242403	1	0	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
242404	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	0	1	1	1
242405	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
242406	1	0	1	0.88	0	1	1	0.9	1	0	1	1	1
242407	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	0	1	1	1
242408	1	0	1	1	1	0.93	1	0.9	1	0	1	1	1
243101	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.98	0.99	0.99	1	0.99	1	1
243102	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.91	0.98	0.99	0.93	1	1	1
243103	0.95	1	1	1	0.93	0.94	0.93	1	0.98	0.93	0.97	1	1
243104	1	1	0.91	1	0.97	0.94	0.93	0.99	0.98	0.93	0.99	1	1
243105	0.95	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.91	0.99	0.95	0.93	1	0.95	0.97
243106	0.9	1	1	1	0.96	0.94	0.89	0.99	0.96	0.93	0.95	0.98	0.97
243107	0.95	1	1	1	0.89	0.88	0.91	0.99	0.96	0.93	0.99	0.98	1
243108	1	1	1	1	0.91	0.88	0.84	0.99	0.97	0.93	0.97	0.98	1
243109	0.95	1	1	1	0.89	0.94	0.95	0.99	0.99	0.93	1	0.98	1
243201	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5
243202	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243203	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243204	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243205	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243206	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243207	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243208	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	0.5
243301	1	0	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
243302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243303	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243304	1	0	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243305	1	0	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	0
243306	1	0	0.75	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
243307	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	0.92	1	0.75	1	1
243308	1	0	1	1	0.82	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
243309	1	0	1	0.8	0.88	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1
243310	1	0	1	0.8	0.88	1	1	0.92	0.96	1	0.75	1	1
243311	1	0	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.96	0	1	1	1
243312	1	0	1	1	0.82	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
243401	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
243402	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
243403	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0.92	0	1	1	1
243404	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
243405	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0.92	0	1	1	1
243406	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.8
243407	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
251101	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1
251102	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	0.96	0.99	0.94
251103	0.96	1	0.97	0.97	0.92	1	0.92	0.97	0.98	1	0.98	0.99	1
251104	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.92	0.97	0.97	1	0.96	0.99	1
251105	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0.92	0.97	0.99	1	1	0.99	1
251106	0.98	1	0.97	1	1	1	0.92	0.97	0.99	1	1	0.96	1
251107	0.98	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	0.97	0.99	1	1	0.97	1
251201	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
251202	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	1
251203	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.93	1	1
251204	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	0.89	0.94	0.93	1	0.95
251205	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
251206	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
251207	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	0.94	1	1	1
251208	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	0.94	1	1	1
251301	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	1
251302	1	1	1	1	0.82	1	1	1	0.96	1	0.9	1	1
251303	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	0.96	1	0.9	1	1
251304	1	1	1	1	0.91	0.75	1	1	0.96	0.75	0.9	1	1
251305	1	1	1	1	0.82	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
251401	1	0	0.97	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	0.95	1
251402	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
251403	0.96	0	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
251404	1	0	0.93	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	0.98	1
251405	1	0	0.97	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1
251901	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
251902	0.92	0	1	0.88	0.94	1	1	1	0.99	1	0.96	1	1
251903	1	0	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.99	1	0.96	1	1
251904	1	0	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.96	1	1
251905	1	0	0.92	1	1	0.91	1	1	0.95	0.9	1	1	1
252101	0.88	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1
252102	1	0	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
252103	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
252104	1	0	1	1	0.8	0.89	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1
252105	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.88	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
252106	1	0	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	0.78
252201	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
252202	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1
252203	1	0	1	1	0.83	0.75	1	0.94	1	1	0.92	1	1
252204	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.88	1
252205	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
252301	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	1
252302	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1
252303	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.67	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
252304	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
252305	0.8	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
252306	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
252307	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.95	0.67	1	1	1
252901	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
252902	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	1	1
252903	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	0.91	0.89	1	1	1	1	1
252904	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	1
252905	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	1	0.89	0.97	1	1	1	1
252906	1	0	1	1	1	0.9	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	1
252907	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	1
252908	1	0	1	1	1	0.9	1	0.89	0.97	1	1	1	1
261101	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
261102	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
261103	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
261104	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	0
261105	1	0	1	1	0.89	0	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	0
261106	1	0	1	1	0.78	0	1	1	1	0.89	1	1	0
261107	1	0	1	1	0.89	0	1	0.96	1	0.89	1	1	0
261108	1	0	1	1	0.89	0	0.93	0.96	1	0.78	1	1	0
261109	1	0	1	1	0.89	0	0.86	0.93	1	0.89	1	1	0
261110	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.89	1	1	0
261201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
261202	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
261203	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
261204	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
261205	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
261206	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
261207	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
261901	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1
261902	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
261903	1	0	1	1	0.98	0.94	0.95	1	0.95	1	0.89	1	1
261904	1	0	1	1	0.97	0.94	0.98	1	0.91	1	0.89	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
262101	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262102	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262103	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262104	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262105	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262106	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262107	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262108	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262109	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262110	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
262201	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
262202	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	0	1
262203	1	0	0	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
262204	1	0	0	1	0.82	1	0.89	0.67	1	1	1	0	1
262205	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	0.89	0.67	1	1	1	0	1
262206	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	0.89	0.67	1	1	1	0	1
262207	1	0	0	0.75	0.76	1	0.89	0.67	1	1	1	0	1
262208	1	0	0	1	0.82	1	0.89	0.67	1	1	1	0	1
262209	1	0	0	1	0.88	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	0	1
263101	1	0	0	1	0.95	0	0.97	1	1	0.83	1	1	0
263102	1	0	0	1	0.94	0	0.91	1	1	0.83	1	1	0
263103	1	0	0	1	0.93	0	0.94	1	1	0.83	0.5	1	0
263104	1	0	0	1	0.91	0	1	1	0.78	1	1	1	0
263105	1	0	0	1	0.93	0	0.97	1	0.67	0.83	1	1	0
263106	1	0	0	1	0.9	0	0.94	1	0.78	1	1	1	0
263107	1	0	0	1	0.94	0	0.91	1	0.78	1	1	1	0
263108	1	0	0	1	0.95	0	0.89	1	0.67	0.83	1	1	0
263109	1	0	0	1	0.85	0	0.86	1	0.67	0.83	1	1	0
263110	1	0	0	1	0.9	0	0.89	1	0.67	0.83	1	1	0
263111	1	0	0	1	0.86	0	0.89	1	0.67	0.83	1	0.8	0
263112	1	0	0	0.83	0.84	0	0.89	1	0.67	0.83	1	1	0
263201	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
263202	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.83	1	1
263203	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.5	0.83	1	1
263204	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0.89
263205	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.92	1	1
263206	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0	1	1	0.89
263207	1	0	0.8	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1
263208	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	0.89
263209	1	0	1	1	1	0.75	1	0.88	1	0.5	1	1	1
263301	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
263302	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
263303	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
263304	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
263305	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
263306	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
263307	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
263308	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
263401	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	0
263402	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.33	1	0
263403	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0.33	1	0
263404	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0.33	1	0
263405	1	0	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.33	1	0
263406	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	0
263407	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.33	0.8	0
263408	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.67	1	0
263501	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
263502	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
263503	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
263504	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
263505	1	1	1	1	1	0.75	0.75	1	0.98	1	1	1	0.83
263506	1	1	1	0.67	1	0.75	0.75	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
263507	1	1	1	0.67	1	0.75	0.75	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
263508	1	1	1	0.67	1	0.75	0.75	0.86	0.92	1	0.86	0.75	1
263509	1	1	1	0.67	1	0.75	0.75	0.71	0.94	1	1	1	1
263510	1	1	0.92	0.67	1	0.75	0.75	0.86	0.95	1	1	1	0.83
263511	1	1	1	0.67	1	0.75	0.75	0.86	0.98	1	1	1	1
263601	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.75	0	0
263602	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.5	0	0
263603	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	0.75	0	0
263604	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.75	0	0
263605	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.75	0	0
263606	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.75	0	0
263607	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.75	0	0
263608	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
263609	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
264101	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.89	1	1
264102	1	0	0.5	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
264103	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.85	0	0.89	1	1
264104	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.92	0	1	1	1
264105	1	0	1	0	0.75	1	0	1	0.92	0	1	1	1
264106	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
264201	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
264202	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.98	1	0.96	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
264203	1	1	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.97	0.96	1	0.96	1	1
264204	1	1	1	0.9	0.94	1	0.88	1	0.96	1	0.98	1	1
264205	1	1	1	0.86	0.94	1	0.94	1	0.98	1	0.96	1	1
264206	1	1	1	0.9	0.94	0.95	0.75	1	0.92	1	1	1	1
264207	1	1	1	0.86	0.94	0.95	0.81	1	0.98	0.9	0.98	1	1
264208	1	1	1	0.9	0.94	0.9	0.69	1	0.98	0.9	1	1	1
264209	0.95	1	1	0.9	0.94	0.9	0.69	1	0.92	1	0.91	1	1
264210	0.95	0.5	1	0.86	0.94	0.9	0.75	1	0.96	1	0.98	1	1
264301	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.7	1	1	0.5	1
264302	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.95	1	0.8	1	1	0.5	1
264303	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	1	1	1
264304	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	0.9	1	1	0.5	1
264305	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.9	1	1	0.5	1
264306	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.9	1	1	1	1
265101	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
265102	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
265103	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
265104	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
265105	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
265106	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
265107	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
265108	0	0	0	0	0.67	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
265201	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
265202	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
265203	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
265204	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
265205	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
265206	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0
265207	1	0	1	0	0.9	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
265208	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
265301	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
265302	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
265303	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
265304	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
265305	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
265306	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
265401	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
265402	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
265403	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
265404	1	0	1	0	0.8	0.5	1	1	1	0	0.67	1	0
265405	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.89	0	0.67	1	0
265406	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
265407	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
265501	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
265502	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
265503	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
265504	0	1	0	0	0.83	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
265505	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
265506	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
265507	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
265601	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
265602	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
265603	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
265604	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
265605	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
265901	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
265902	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
265903	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
265904	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
311101	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
311102	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
311103	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
311104	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
311105	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
311106	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
311201	0.75	0	1	1	0.77	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
311202	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311203	0.75	0	1	1	0.92	1	0.82	1	1	1	1	1	1
311204	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311205	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.73	1	0.9	1	1	1	1
311206	1	0	1	1	0.85	1	0.73	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
311207	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	0.82	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
311301	1	0	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311303	0.89	0	1	0.92	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311304	0.89	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311305	0.89	0	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311306	0.89	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
311401	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1
311402	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311403	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0.71	1	1
311404	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1
311405	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311406	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
311407	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311501	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
311502	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
311503	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	0	1	1	1
311504	0.8	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
311505	0.8	0	1	1	0.88	1	0.8	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
311506	0.8	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	0.95	0	1	1	1
311507	1	0	1	0.86	0.75	1	1	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
311508	1	0	1	1	0.75	0.8	0.8	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
311601	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1
311602	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311603	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311604	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311605	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
311701	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
311702	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
311703	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	1
311704	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	1
311705	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
311706	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	1
311707	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	1
311708	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	1
311801	1	1	0.97	1	0.96	1	0.98	1	0.97	1	0.96	1	1
311802	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.96	1	1
311803	1	1	0.92	1	0.89	1	0.86	1	0.97	1	0.92	1	1
311804	1	1	0.92	1	0.89	1	0.84	1	0.99	1	0.92	1	1
311805	1	1	0.95	0.97	0.85	1	0.82	0.86	0.94	0.91	0.85	1	1
311806	1	1	0.97	0.97	0.91	1	0.8	1	0.94	0.82	0.85	1	1
311807	1	1	0.92	0.97	0.91	1	0.86	1	0.93	1	0.92	1	1
311808	1	1	0.95	1	0.94	1	0.9	1	1	0.91	0.96	1	1
311901	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
311902	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	1
311903	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.85	1	1	1	1
311904	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
311905	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
312101	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.83	0	0	1	1	0	0
312102	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.67	0	0	1	1	0	0
312103	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
312104	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
312105	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.83	0	0	1	1	0	0
312201	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
312202	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
312203	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
312204	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
312205	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
312206	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	0.9	1	1	1	1
312301	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
312302	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
312303	1	1	0.96	1	0.95	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
312304	1	1	1	1	0.95	0.97	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
312305	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.99	1	1	1	0.75
312306	1	1	1	1	0.91	0.9	1	0.97	0.98	1	0.94	1	0.88
313101	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
313102	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
313103	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
313104	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
313105	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
313106	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
313201	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
313202	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
313203	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
313204	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
313205	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
313206	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
313207	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
313208	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
313301	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
313302	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.86	0	0	1	1
313303	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
313304	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
313305	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.91	0	0	1	1
313306	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
313401	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
313402	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.86	1	1	0	0
313403	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
313404	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
313405	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
313501	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	1	1	1	0	0
313502	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
313503	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	1	1	1	0	0
313504	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	1	1	0	0	0
313505	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
313506	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	1	1	0	0	0
313507	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
314101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314102	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314103	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314104	1	0	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314105	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314106	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314107	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	0	1	1	0
314108	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314109	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314110	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.86	0	1	1	0
314111	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314112	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314113	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
314201	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1
314202	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1
314203	0	0	1	1	0.33	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1
314204	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1
314205	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1
314206	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1
314207	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1
314208	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
314209	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
314301	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0.5	0	1	0
314302	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
314303	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
314304	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
314305	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0.5	0	1	0
314306	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
314307	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
314308	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
314309	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
314310	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
315101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
315102	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
315103	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
315104	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
315105	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
315202	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
315203	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0.9	0	0	1	0
315204	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
315205	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
315206	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
315207	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
315208	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
315301	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
315302	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
315303	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
315304	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
315305	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
315306	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
315307	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
315401	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
315402	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
315403	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
315404	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
315405	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
315406	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
315407	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
315408	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
315501	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
315502	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
315503	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
315504	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
315505	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
315506	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
315507	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
315508	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
315509	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
321101	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
321102	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	0	1	0	1
321103	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	0	1	0	1
321104	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
321105	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	0	1	0	1
321106	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.63	0	1	0	1
321107	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	0	1	0	1
321108	0	0	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	0.88	0	1	0	1
321201	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
321202	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	0	1	0	0
321203	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
321204	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	0	1	0	0
321205	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
321206	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	0	1	0	0
321207	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
321208	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
321209	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
321210	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
321301	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
321302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
321303	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
321305	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
321306	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.5	1
321307	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.5	1
321308	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.5	1
321309	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.89	0	1	0.5	1
321401	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
321402	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
321403	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
321404	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
321405	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	0
321406	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	0
321407	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	0
321408	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	0
321409	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	0
321410	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	0
322101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
322102	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0
322103	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	0
322104	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	0.98	1	0.83	1	0
322105	1	0	1	0.92	1	1	0.71	1	0.98	1	1	1	0
322106	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	0.75	1	1	0
322201	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
322202	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
322203	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
322204	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
324001	1	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
324002	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
324003	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
324004	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
324005	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
324006	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
324007	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
324008	1	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
324009	1	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
324010	1	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
325101	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.97	0	1	1	0
325102	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
325103	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.97	0	1	1	0
325104	1	0	0.89	1	1	0	0	0	0.97	0	1	1	0
325105	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.93	0	1	1	0
325106	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.97	0	1	1	0
325107	1	0	1	1	0.67	0	0	0	0.97	0	1	1	0
325108	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.97	0	1	1	0
325201	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325202	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325203	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325204	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325205	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0.88	1	0	0	0
325206	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325301	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
325302	0	0	0	0	0.8	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
325303	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
325304	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.75
325305	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
325306	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
325401	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
325402	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
325403	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
325404	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
325501	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325502	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325503	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325504	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325505	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325506	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
325601	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
325602	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
325603	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
325604	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
325605	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
325606	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
325607	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
325608	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
325609	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
325610	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1
325701	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.78	1	1
325702	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	0	1	1	1
325703	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	0.96	0	1	1	1
325704	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.77	0.96	0	0.89	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
325705	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	0	1	1	1
325706	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	0.75	0.92	0.96	0	1	1	1
325707	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	0.75	0.85	0.96	0	1	1	1
325708	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.85	0.96	0	1	1	1
325709	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.75	0.85	0.96	0	1	1	1
325710	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.75	0.85	0.91	0	1	1	1
325901	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
325902	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	0	1	1
325903	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
325904	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	0	1	1
325905	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
331101	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
331102	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
331103	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
331104	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
331105	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
331201	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
331202	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
331203	1	0	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
331204	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.8	0	1
331205	1	0	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
331301	1	0	1	1	0.97	1	0.97	1	0.95	0.93	0.97	1	0.78
331302	1	0	1	0.97	0.98	1	0.98	1	0.96	1	0.97	1	1
331303	1	0	1	1	0.99	1	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.98	0.97	1	1
331304	1	0	0.97	1	0.96	1	0.94	0.91	0.97	0.98	0.95	0.83	1
331305	0.96	0	1	0.97	0.98	0.9	0.96	0.94	0.99	0.95	0.97	1	0.89
331306	1	0	1	1	0.94	0.9	0.92	0.94	0.91	0.91	0.94	1	1
331401	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
331402	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
331403	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
331404	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
331405	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
331406	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
331407	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
331408	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.6	0	1	1	0
331501	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1
331502	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.85	1	1	1	1
331503	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1
331504	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.85	1	1	1	1
331505	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
332101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
332102	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
332103	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
332104	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
332105	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.92	1	1	1	1
332106	0.67	0	1	1	1	0.8	0.88	0	0.92	1	1	1	1
332201	0.98	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	0.98	0.98	1	0.98	1	1
332202	0.98	1	0.97	1	0.91	1	0.92	0.97	0.96	1	0.96	1	1
332203	0.98	1	0.97	0.95	0.91	1	0.96	0.97	0.99	1	1	1	1
332204	0.98	1	0.95	0.95	0.95	1	0.94	0.98	0.99	1	1	1	0.93
332205	0.98	1	0.97	0.95	0.98	1	0.96	0.98	0.99	1	0.98	1	1
332206	0.93	1	0.97	0.95	0.98	0.96	0.94	0.97	0.98	1	0.98	1	1
332207	1	1	0.97	0.95	0.98	0.92	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.67	0.98	1	1
332301	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
332302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	0.97	1	1
332303	0.89	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	1
332304	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1
332305	0.94	0	1	0.97	0.85	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
332306	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	0.94	0.96	0.99	0.8	1	1	0.8
332307	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	0.94	0.96	0.97	0.8	1	1	1
332308	0.94	0	1	1	0.92	1	0.94	0.96	1	0.8	1	0.93	1
332309	0.94	0	1	0.97	0.92	1	0.94	0.96	1	0.8	1	0.93	1
332310	1	0	0.91	1	0.92	1	0.89	0.96	1	0.8	1	0.93	1
332401	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
332402	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.83	1
332403	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
332404	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
332405	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
332406	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
333101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
333102	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
333103	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
333104	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
333105	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
333201	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0.88	1	0.92	1	1
333202	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.92	1	1
333203	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
333204	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
333205	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.8	0.94	1	1	1	1
333206	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	1
333207	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
333301	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
333302	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
333303	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
333304	0	0	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	0.75
333305	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
333306	0	0	1	1	1	0.92	0.86	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
333401	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1
333402	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1
333403	0.5	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.93	1	0.5	0	1
333404	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.93	1	1	0	1
333405	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.93	1	1	0	1
333406	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.93	1	1	0	1
333407	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.93	1	1	0	1
333901	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.6	1	1	1	1
333902	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
333903	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
333904	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1
333905	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.6	1	1	1	1
334101	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.87	0.96	1	1	1	1	1
334102	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
334103	0.89	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
334104	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	1
334105	0.94	1	1	1	0.89	0.97	0.8	0.96	1	1	1	1	1
334106	1	1	1	1	0.89	0.93	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	1
334201	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.97	1	1	1	1
334202	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.89	1	1
334203	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
334204	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.97	1	1	1	1
334205	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.97	1	1	1	1
334206	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
334207	1	0	0.92	0	0	0	0	0	0.97	1	1	1	1
334301	1	1	0.97	0.99	0.98	1	0.96	0.97	0.99	1	0.99	1	1
334302	0.97	1	1	0.99	1	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.99	0.92	0.99	1	1
334303	0.97	1	1	0.99	0.98	1	0.96	0.97	1	1	0.98	1	1
334304	1	1	1	1	0.98	0.96	0.96	1	0.99	1	0.98	1	1
334305	0.95	1	1	0.99	1	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.98	1	0.96	0.94	1
334306	0.95	1	0.97	0.95	1	0.98	0.96	0.94	0.99	1	0.99	1	1
334307	0.97	1	1	0.95	0.98	0.92	0.93	0.92	0.94	1	0.96	0.94	0.98
334308	0.97	1	1	0.95	0.98	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.96	1	0.97	0.94	0.98
334401	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.9	0	1
334402	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.91	0	1	0	1
334403	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
334404	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
334405	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.9	0	1
334406	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
334407	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
334408	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.91	0	1	0	1
335101	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
335102	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
335103	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.67	0	0	0	1
335104	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
335105	0	0	0	0	0.83	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
335106	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
335107	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
335108	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.67	1	1	0	0	0	1
335201	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
335202	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
335203	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0
335204	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
335301	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
335302	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	0	0
335303	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
335304	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
335401	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.88	1	1	0	0
335402	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
335403	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.88	1	1	0	0
335404	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.88	1	1	0	0
335405	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
335501	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
335502	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
335503	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
335504	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
335505	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
335506	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
335901	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
335902	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
335903	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	0	1	1	1
335904	1	0	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
341101	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.94	1	1
341102	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	0.95	1	0.94	1	1
341103	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.94	0.95	0.75	0.78	1	1
341104	1	0	0	1	0.86	1	1	0.94	0.95	1	1	1	1
341105	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1
341106	0.89	0	0	1	0.86	0.83	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.8
341107	1	0	0	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.94	1	1
341108	1	0	0	1	0.86	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1
341201	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
341202	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
341203	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	0.92	1	1	1
341204	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
341205	1	0	1	0.83	0.87	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
341206	1	0	1	0.67	0.93	1	0.9	1	0.94	0.83	1	1	0.8
341207	1	0	1	0.83	0.87	1	0.9	1	1	0.92	1	1	0.8
341208	1	0	1	0.83	0.87	1	0.9	1	1	0.92	1	0.67	1
341209	1	0	1	0.83	0.93	1	0.9	0.83	1	0.83	1	1	1
341210	1	0	1	0.83	0.93	0.75	0.9	1	1	0.83	1	1	1
341301	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
341302	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
341303	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
341304	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
341305	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
341306	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
342101	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
342102	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
342103	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
342105	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
342106	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
342107	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
342108	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
342201	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.89	1	0.93	0	1	1	0
342202	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
342203	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.83	1	0	1	1	0
342204	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.83	1	0	1	1	0
342205	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.89	0.83	1	0	1	1	0
342206	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.83	1	0	1	1	0
342207	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0.83	1	0	1	1	0
342208	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.89	0.83	1	0	1	1	0
342209	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.89	0.83	1	0	1	1	0
342210	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.89	0.83	1	0	1	1	0
342211	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.89	0.83	0.93	0	1	1	0
342301	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	0
342302	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	0.92	1	1	1	0
342303	1	0	1	0	0.8	1	0.5	1	0.9	1	1	1	0
342304	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	0.92	1	1	1	0
342305	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	0
342306	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	0
343101	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
343102	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
343103	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.67	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
343104	1	0	1	1	1	0.75	1	0.88	1	0	1	1	1
343105	1	0	0.67	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	0	1	1	1
343106	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
343107	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	0.88	1	0	1	0.67	1
343108	1	0	1	1	0.75	0.75	1	0.75	1	0	1	1	1
343201	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
343202	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
343203	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
343204	1	0	1	0.86	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1
343205	1	0	1	0.71	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
343206	1	0	1	0.86	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
343207	1	0	1	0.71	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1
343208	1	0	1	0.71	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	1
343209	1	0	1	0.86	1	0	1	1	0.92	0	1	1	1
343210	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
343301	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
343302	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
343303	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
343304	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
343305	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
343306	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
343307	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
343308	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
343309	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
343401	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0.67	1	1
343402	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
343403	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
343404	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
343405	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
343406	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
343407	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
343408	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0.94	0	0.67	1	1
343409	0.86	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
343410	0.86	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
351101	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
351102	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
351103	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	0
351104	0	1	0	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
351105	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
351106	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
351107	0	1	0	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
351108	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
351201	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
351202	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.89	0.98	0.98	0.93	1	1	1
351203	1	1	0.86	1	0.95	0.95	0.97	0.98	0.95	1	0.98	1	0.95
351204	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.91	0.98	0.95	1	0.98	1	0.95
351205	0.97	1	0.93	1	0.86	0.95	0.94	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.95
351206	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.95	0.94	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
351207	1	1	1	1	0.86	0.95	0.94	1	0.98	1	0.97	1	1
351208	1	1	0.93	1	0.9	0.9	0.94	1	0.98	1	0.98	1	1
351301	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
351302	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	1	1
351303	1	0	1	1	0.95	1	0.96	1	0.95	1	0.92	1	1
351304	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	0.92	1	1	1
351305	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	1	1
351401	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	0	0	1	0
351402	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
351403	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
351404	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
351405	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	0	0	1	0
351406	0	0	1	1	1	0.92	1	0	0.95	0	0	1	0
351407	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
352101	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
352102	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
352103	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
352104	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	1
352105	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	0.74	1	1	1	1
352106	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	0.8	1	0.89	1	1	1	1
352107	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
352201	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
352202	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	0.88	1	1
352203	1	0	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
352204	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
352205	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
411001	0.99	1	1	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.98	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
411002	0.99	1	0.98	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.99	0.97	0.98	0.98	1	1
411003	1	1	0.97	0.99	0.95	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.97	1	0.98	1	1
411004	1	1	0.97	0.99	0.97	0.99	0.96	0.99	0.97	0.98	1	0.98	1
411005	0.96	1	0.97	0.99	0.9	0.98	0.93	0.97	0.95	0.98	0.95	0.98	0.98
411006	1	1	0.99	0.98	0.95	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.98	1	0.96	0.98	1
411007	0.99	1	0.98	0.96	0.95	0.98	0.93	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.97	1	1
411008	1	1	0.98	0.99	0.96	0.97	0.97	0.99	0.98	1	0.97	1	1
412001	0.99	0	0.98	1	1	1	1	0.99	0.98	1	1	1	1
412002	1	0	1	0.98	1	1	0.95	1	0.99	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
412003	1	0	1	0.98	1	1	1	0.99	0.99	1	1	1	1
412004	0.97	0	0.95	0.93	1	1	1	0.98	0.98	1	1	0.97	1
412005	1	0	0.98	0.98	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0.97	1
412006	0.95	0	0.95	0.97	1	1	0.95	0.99	0.93	1	1	1	1
412007	0.97	0	0.98	0.98	1	1	0.95	0.99	0.97	0.75	0.98	1	0.89
412008	0.99	0	0.98	0.97	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	0.97	1
413101	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
413102	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
413103	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
413104	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
413105	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
413106	1	0	0	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
413107	1	0	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
413201	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0.75	0	1	0	1
413202	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
413203	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
413204	1	0	0	1	0.75	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
413205	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
421101	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
421102	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.92	1	1
421103	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.92	1	1
421104	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.92	1	1
421105	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
421106	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.92	1	1
421201	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
421202	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
421203	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
421204	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
421205	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
421301	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
421302	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
421303	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
421304	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
421305	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
421401	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1
421402	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1
421403	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	1
421404	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1
421405	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
422101	1	0	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	0.8	1
422102	1	0	1	1	0.94	1	0.91	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
422103	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	0.95	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
422104	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	0.95	1	0.86	1	1
422105	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
422106	1	0	1	0.67	0.94	1	0.91	0.83	1	1	1	1	1
422107	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	0.9	1	1	1	1
422201	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
422202	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.97	1	1
422203	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
422204	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.94	1	1
422205	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.97	1	0.96
422206	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
422301	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
422302	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
422303	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
422304	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.92	0	0.83	1	0
422305	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
422401	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.5	1
422402	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.89	0	1	1	1
422403	1	0	1	0.93	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
422404	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
422405	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
422406	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
422407	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
422408	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
422409	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.89	1	1	0	1	1	1
422501	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
422502	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
422503	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
422504	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
422505	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
422601	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
422602	0.97	1	1	1	1	0.93	0.91	1	0.98	1	0.98	1	1
422603	0.97	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
422604	1	1	1	0.99	1	0.93	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
422701	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
422702	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
422703	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
422704	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
422705	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
422901	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0.88
422902	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0.88
422903	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
422904	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	0	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
422905	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
422906	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
431101	1	0	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1
431102	0.99	0	1	0.97	0.98	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.97	1	1
431103	0.99	0	0.89	0.92	0.98	1	0.98	0.98	0.98	1	1	1	1
431104	0.99	0	0.89	1	0.98	0.88	0.96	0.99	1	1	1	1	1
431105	0.99	0	0.95	0.97	1	0.88	0.98	0.98	0.98	1	1	1	1
431201	0.96	1	0.94	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	0.95	1	1
431202	0.96	1	1	1	1	0.96	0.97	1	0.98	1	0.93	1	1
431203	1	1	1	1	0.96	0.98	1	0.93	0.98	1	0.95	1	1
431204	0.96	1	1	0.97	0.96	1	0.94	0.97	0.97	1	0.93	1	1
431205	0.96	1	1	1	0.92	0.96	0.91	1	0.97	1	0.91	1	1
431301	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
431302	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
431303	0	0	0	1	0.84	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
431304	1	0	0	1	0.95	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	1
431305	1	0	0	1	0.95	0	0.88	0.9	1	1	1	1	1
432101	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.93
432102	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.9	0.99	1	1	1	1
432103	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
432104	0.9	1	1	0.98	1	0.97	1	0.9	0.96	1	0.92	1	1
432105	0.9	1	0.96	0.98	0.97	0.94	0.97	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
432201	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1
432202	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
432203	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
432204	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	0.75	0.9	0.96	1	1	1	1
432205	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1
432301	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
432302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	0	1	0	1
432303	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	0	1	0	1
432304	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	0	1
432305	1	0	0.8	0.86	1	1	1	1	0.78	0	1	0	1
432306	1	0	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	0.95	0	1	0	1
441101	0	0	1	0	0.86	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
441102	0	0	1	0	0.86	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
441103	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
441104	0	0	1	0	0.86	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
441105	0	0	1	0	0.86	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
441106	0	0	1	0	0.86	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
441201	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
441202	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
441203	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.5	0	1	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
441204	1	0	1	0.67	1	0	0.5	0	1	1	1	1	1
441301	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
441302	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
441303	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
441304	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
441305	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
441401	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
441402	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
441403	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
441501	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
441502	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
441503	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
441504	1	0	0.88	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1
441505	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
441601	1	0	0.95	0.98	1	1	0.97	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
441602	1	0	1	0.98	1	0.96	1	0.97	0.99	1	1	1	1
441603	1	0	1	0.98	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
441604	1	0	1	0.94	0.95	0.94	0.97	0.95	0.96	1	1	0.89	1
441605	1	0	1	0.98	0.95	0.91	0.97	0.98	0.94	1	1	1	0.83
441606	1	0	1	0.94	1	0.91	1	0.98	0.97	1	1	1	1
441607	1	0	1	0.96	1	0.91	0.97	1	0.97	1	0.92	1	0.83
441901	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
441902	1	1	1	0.97	0.94	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
441903	0.96	1	0.94	1	0.94	0	0.96	0.98	0.99	1	0.92	0.92	1
441904	0.96	1	1	1	1	0	0.96	1	0.96	1	0.96	1	1
511101	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511102	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511103	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511104	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511105	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511106	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511107	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511108	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.89	0	1	0	0
511109	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511110	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511111	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
511201	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
511202	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
511203	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	0	0
511204	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
511205	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
511206	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.75	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
511207	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
511208	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
511209	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	0	0
511210	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
511301	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
511302	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
511303	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.8	1	0	1	0
511304	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
511305	0	0	0	0	0.67	1	0	0.5	1	1	0	1	0
511306	0	0	0	0	0.67	1	0	0.5	1	1	0	1	0
511307	0	0	0	0	0.67	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
511308	0	0	0	0	0.67	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
511309	0	0	0	0	0.67	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
512001	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
512002	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
512003	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	0.75
512004	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
512005	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
512006	1	0	1	1	1	0.8	0.8	1	0.93	1	1	1	1
513101	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	0	0.99	0	1	0	1
513102	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.99	0	1	0	1
513103	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	0	0.96	0	0	0	1
513104	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.98	0	1	0	1
513105	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.96	0	1	0	1
513106	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.99	0	1	0	1
513107	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	0	0.98	0	1	0	1
513201	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
513202	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
513203	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
513204	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
513205	1	0	1	0	0.67	0	1	1	0.97	0	0.86	1	1
513206	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
513207	1	0	1	0	0.67	0	1	1	0.89	0	1	1	1
513208	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.95	0	1	1	1
513209	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.89	0	1	1	1
513210	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0.92	0	1	1	1
514101	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
514102	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	0	0.92	0	0	0	1
514103	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
514104	1	1	1	1	0.64	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
514105	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
514106	1	1	1	1	0.79	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
514107	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
514108	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
514201	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
514202	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1
514203	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
514204	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
514205	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
514206	0	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
514207	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
514208	0	0	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
515101	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.98	1	1	0.89	1
515102	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.93	1	1	0.89	1
515103	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1
515104	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.93	1	1	0.89	1
515105	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
515106	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.83	0.9	1	1	1	1
515107	1	0	0	1	0.67	1	1	0.83	0.95	1	1	1	1
515108	1	0	0	1	0.67	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
515201	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	1	0	0
515202	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	1	0	0
515203	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	0.67	0	0
515204	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	1	0	0
515205	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
515206	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
515207	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.67	0	0
515208	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
515209	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
515301	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.93	0	0	1	0
515302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
515303	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	0	0.87	0	0	1	0
515305	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	0	0.87	0	0	1	0
515306	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	0	0.87	0	0	1	0
515307	1	0	1	0.8	1	1	1	0	0.87	0	0	1	0
515308	1	0	1	0.8	1	1	0.8	0	0.93	0	0	1	0
516301	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
516302	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
516303	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
516304	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.8	0	0	1	0
516305	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
516306	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
516401	1	1	1	0	0.88	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
516402	1	1	1	0	0.88	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
516403	0.5	1	1	0	0.94	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
516404	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
516405	1	1	1	0	0.94	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
516406	1	1	1	0	0.88	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
516407	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
516408	1	1	1	0	0.81	0	1	1	0.94	0	1	1	0
516409	1	1	1	0	0.88	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
516501	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
516502	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
516503	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
516504	0	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
516505	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
516506	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
516901	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
516902	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
516903	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
521101	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
521102	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
521103	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
521104	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
521105	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
521106	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
521107	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
521201	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
521202	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
521203	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
521204	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
521205	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
522101	0.95	0	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	0.95	0	0.83	1	1
522102	0.95	0	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	0.95	0	1	1	1
522103	0.89	0	1	1	0.82	0.94	0.92	0.89	0.97	0	0.83	1	1
522104	0.89	0	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	0.95	0	0.5	1	1
522105	0.89	0	1	1	0.91	0.94	0.92	1	1	0	0.83	0.67	1
522106	1	0	1	0.95	1	1	0.85	0.89	0.98	0	0.5	1	1
522107	1	0	1	0.95	1	1	0.92	0.89	1	0	0.83	1	1
522201	1	0	1	1	0.96	0.8	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
522202	1	0	1	1	0.91	1	0.95	0.96	0.99	0	1	1	1
522203	1	0	1	0.88	1	1	1	0.96	0.99	0	1	1	1
522204	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	0.95	0.92	0.95	0	1	1	1
522205	1	0	1	1	0.96	1	0.95	0.96	0.99	0	1	1	1
522206	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.95	0.92	1	0	1	1	1
522207	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	0.99	0	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
522208	1	0	1	1	0.96	0.6	0.95	0.92	1	0	1	0.8	1
522301	1	1	0.97	1	0.99	1	1	1	0.98	1	0.91	1	1
522302	1	1	0.97	1	0.99	1	0.9	1	0.98	1	0.91	1	1
522303	1	1	0.95	1	0.96	1	0.97	0.93	0.97	1	1	0.94	1
522304	1	1	0.97	0.98	0.99	1	0.97	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
522305	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
523001	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
523002	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	0.78	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
523003	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	0.78	0.9	0.9	1	1	1	1
523004	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
523005	0.92	1	1	0.91	0.95	1	0.89	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
523006	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.89	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
523007	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.78	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
523008	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.78	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
524201	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
524202	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
524203	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
524204	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
524205	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
524301	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
524302	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
524303	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
524304	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
524305	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
524306	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
524307	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
524401	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	0.75
524402	0.83	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.75
524403	1	0	0.8	1	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.75
524404	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	0.75
524405	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.75
524406	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1
524407	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1
524408	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.75
524501	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
524502	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
524503	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
524504	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
524505	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
524506	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
524507	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0
524508	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
524601	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0.5	0	1
524602	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
524603	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0.5	0	1
524604	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0.5	0	1
524605	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0.5	0	1
524606	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0.5	0	1
524607	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0.5	0	1
524608	0.5	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
531101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
531102	1	0	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1
531103	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
531104	0.95	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.98	1	0.86	1	1
531105	0.95	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
531106	0.95	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.98	1	0.86	1	1
531107	0.95	0	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
531108	0.95	0	1	0.83	1	1	0.88	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
531201	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
531202	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.97	1	0	1	1
531203	0	0	1	1	0.98	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
531204	0	0	1	1	1	0	0.91	1	0.91	1	0	1	1
531205	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.97	1	0	1	1
531206	0	0	1	1	1	0	0.91	1	1	1	0	1	1
531207	0	0	1	1	0.98	0	0.82	1	0.94	1	0	1	1
532101	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
532102	1	0	0.96	1	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
532103	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.98	1	1	0.91	1
532104	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0.91	1
532105	1	0	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1
532106	1	0	0.96	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	0.91	1
532201	0.83	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
532202	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0.96	0	1	1	1
532203	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0.98	0	1	1	1
532204	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0.98	0	1	1	0.88
532205	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0.96	0	1	1	0.88
532206	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0.98	0	0.67	1	0.88
532207	1	0	0.83	1	0	0	0	1	0.96	0	1	1	0.88
532208	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0.94	0	0.67	1	1
532209	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0.96	0	1	1	0.88
532901	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1
532902	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
532903	0	0	0	1	0.8	0	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	1
532904	0	0	0	1	0.8	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
532905	0	0	0	1	0.8	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
532906	0	0	0	1	0.8	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
541101	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0.5	0	1	0
541102	0	0	1	0	0.75	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
541103	0	0	1	0	0.75	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
541104	0	0	1	0	0.75	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
541105	0	0	1	0	0.75	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
541106	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
541201	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
541202	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
541203	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
541204	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
541301	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
541302	0	0	1	0.5	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
541303	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
541304	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
541305	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.9	0	1	1	1
541306	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.8	0	1	1	1
541307	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0.9	0	1	1	1
541401	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
541402	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
541403	1	1	1	1	0.93	0.97	1	1	0.97	1	0.91	1	1
541404	1	1	1	1	0.93	0.97	1	0.92	0.98	1	0.91	1	1
541405	0.91	1	1	1	0.9	0.91	1	1	0.89	1	0.82	1	1
541406	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.91	1	1	0.91	1	0.82	1	1
541901	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
541902	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
541903	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
541904	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
611101	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.91	0	0	0	0
611102	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
611103	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.91	1	0	0	0
611104	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.91	1	0	0	0
611105	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0.91	1	0	0	0
611106	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0.91	0	0	0	0
611107	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0.82	0	0	0	0
611108	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0.91	0	0	0	0
611109	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0.91	0	0	0	0
611110	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0.91	0	0	0	0
611111	1	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0.91	0	0	0	0
611201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
611202	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.5	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
611203	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
611204	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
611205	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
611206	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
611207	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
611208	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.67	0	1	1	0
611209	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.67	0	1	1	0
611210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
611211	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
611301	0.5	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.98	1	1	0	1
611302	0.5	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.95	1	1	0	1
611303	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0.94	1	1	0	1
611304	1	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.95	1	1	0	1
611305	1	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.95	1	1	0	1
611306	0.5	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0.96	1	1	0	1
611307	0.5	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.96	1	1	0	1
611308	0.5	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.98	1	1	0	1
611309	0.5	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.98	1	1	0	1
611310	1	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.95	1	1	0	1
611311	0.5	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.96	1	1	0	0.75
611312	0.5	0	1	1	0.75	0	0	1	0.96	1	1	0	1
611401	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
611402	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
611403	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
611404	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
611405	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
611406	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
611407	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
611408	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
611409	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
611410	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
611411	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
612101	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.88	0	1	1	0
612102	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.88	0	1	1	0
612103	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
612104	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
612105	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
612106	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.88	0	1	1	0
612107	1	0	0	0	0.88	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
612108	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
612109	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
612110	1	0	0	0	0.88	1	0	1	0.88	0	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
612111	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.88	0	1	1	0
612112	1	0	0	0	0.88	1	0	1	0.75	0	1	1	0
612113	1	0	0	0	0.88	1	0	1	0.88	0	1	1	0
612201	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612202	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612203	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612204	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612205	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612206	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612207	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612208	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612209	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612210	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612211	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612212	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
612901	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
612902	1	0	0	1	0.83	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
612903	1	0	0	1	0.83	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
612904	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
612905	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
612906	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0.9	0	0	0	0
612907	1	0	0	1	0.83	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
612908	1	0	0	1	0.83	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
612909	1	0	0	1	0.83	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
612910	1	0	0	1	0.83	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
613001	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
613002	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
613003	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
613004	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
613005	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
613006	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
613007	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
613008	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
613009	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
613010	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
621001	0	1	1	0	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
621002	0	1	1	0	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0	0
621003	0	1	1	0	0.88	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0	0
621004	0	0	1	0	0.82	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0	0
621005	0	0	1	0	0.71	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0	0
621006	0	1	0.75	0	0.82	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
621007	0	1	1	0	0.76	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
621008	0	1	1	0	0.76	1	1	1	0.86	1	0.5	0	0
621009	0	1	1	0	0.82	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0	0
621010	0	1	1	0	0.76	1	1	1	0.86	1	0.5	0	0
622101	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
622102	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
622103	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
622104	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
622105	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
622106	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
622107	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
622108	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
622109	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
622110	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
622201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
622202	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
622203	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
622204	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
622205	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
622206	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
622208	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
622209	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
622210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
622301	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
622302	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
622303	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
622304	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
622305	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
622306	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
622307	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
622308	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
622309	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
631001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
631002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
631003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
631004	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
631005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
631006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
632001	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
632002	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
632003	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
632004	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
632005	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
632006	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
632007	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
632008	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
632009	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
632010	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
632011	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
632012	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
633001	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
633002	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
633003	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
633004	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
633005	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
633006	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
633007	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
633008	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
633009	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
711101	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0.6	1	1	0	0
711102	0	0	0	1	1	0	0.67	1	0.8	1	1	0	0
711103	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	0	0
711104	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
711105	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
711106	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
711107	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	0	0
711201	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
711202	1	0	0.75	1	0.89	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
711203	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.95	0	1	1	0
711301	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
711302	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
711303	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
711304	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
711305	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
711306	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
711307	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
711401	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
711402	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
711403	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
711404	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
711405	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
711501	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
711502	1	1	0.75	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
711503	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.98	1	1	1	1
711504	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.93	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
711505	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.93	1	1	1	1
711901	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.89	0	1	1	0
711902	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.95	0	1	1	0
711903	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
712101	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
712102	0	0	1	0	0.8	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
712103	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
712104	0	0	1	0	0.8	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
712105	0	0	1	0	0.8	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
712106	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
712201	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
712202	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
712203	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
712204	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
712301	0	0	0	0	0.92	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
712302	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
712303	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
712304	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
712401	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
712402	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
712403	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
712404	0	0	1	0	0.67	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
712405	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
712406	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0.67	0	0	1	0
712501	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
712502	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	1	0
712503	0	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
712504	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
712601	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
712602	0	0	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	0
712603	0	0	1	0	1	1	0.8	1	0.93	1	1	1	0
712604	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
712701	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.92	0	0	1	0
712702	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
712703	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
712704	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
713101	1	0	1	1	0.96	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
713102	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
713103	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
713104	1	0	1	1	0.92	0	1	1	0.97	0.5	1	1	1
713105	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
713201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.88	0	0	0	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
713202	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
713203	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0
713301	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
713302	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
713303	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
721101	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
721102	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
721103	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
721104	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
721105	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
721106	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
721107	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
721201	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
721202	1	1	1	1	0.93	0.5	0.93	0	0.97	1	1	1	1
721203	1	1	0.8	1	0.86	1	0.93	0	0.95	1	1	1	1
721204	1	1	0.8	0	0.83	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
721205	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
721206	1	1	0.8	1	0.79	1	0.93	0	0.95	1	1	1	1
721207	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	1	0	0.89	1	1	1	1
721208	1	1	1	0	0.93	1	1	0	0.97	1	1	1	1
721301	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
721302	0	0	1	1	0.8	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
721303	0	0	1	1	0.8	0.75	1	1	0.96	1	1	0	0
721304	0	0	1	1	0.8	0.75	1	1	0.96	1	1	0	0
721305	0	0	1	1	1	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
721306	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	0	0
721307	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
721401	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
721402	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
721403	0	0	0	1	0.8	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
721404	0	0	0	1	0.8	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
721405	0	0	0	1	0.8	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
721406	0	0	0	1	0.8	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
721501	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
721502	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
721503	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
721504	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
721505	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
722101	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
722102	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
722103	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
722104	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
722105	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
722106	0.5	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
722107	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
722108	0.5	0	0	1	0.33	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
722201	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
722202	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	0	0	1
722203	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0.88	1	0	0	1
722204	1	0	0	1	0.89	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
722205	1	0	0	1	0.78	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
722206	1	0	0	1	0.78	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
722207	1	0	0	1	0.78	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
722208	0	0	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
722209	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
722210	1	0	0	1	0.89	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
722211	1	0	0	1	0.78	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
722301	1	0	1	0.8	0.93	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
722302	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
722303	1	0	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1
722304	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
722305	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
722306	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
722401	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
722402	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
722403	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
722404	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
722405	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
722406	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
722407	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
723101	0.83	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
723102	0.83	0	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
723103	1	0	1	1	0.95	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.8	1	1
723104	0.83	0	1	1	0.95	1	0.9	0.8	0.97	1	0.8	1	1
723105	1	0	0.93	1	0.95	1	0.9	1	0.97	0.88	0.8	1	1
723106	0.67	0	0.93	1	0.9	1	0.85	1	0.95	0.88	0.8	0.8	1
723107	1	0	0.8	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.99	1	0.6	1	1
723108	0.83	0	0.93	1	0.9	1	0.9	1	0.96	0.75	0.6	1	1
723201	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
723202	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
723203	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0.67	1	1
723204	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
723205	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
723206	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
723207	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
723208	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
723209	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
723210	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
723301	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.99	1	1	1	1
723302	1	0	1	0.88	0.88	1	1	1	0.96	1	0.83	1	1
723303	1	0	0.9	0.88	0.92	1	0.95	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
723304	1	0	1	0.88	0.92	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
723305	1	0	1	0.88	0.88	1	0.95	1	0.98	1	0.83	1	1
723306	1	0	0.9	0.88	0.8	1	0.91	1	0.98	1	1	1	1
723307	1	0	0.9	0.88	0.8	1	0.91	1	0.99	1	0.83	1	1
723401	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
723402	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
723403	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
723404	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
723405	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
723406	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731101	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731102	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731103	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731104	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731105	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731106	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731107	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731108	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731109	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731111	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731112	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
731201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731202	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731203	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731204	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731205	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731206	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731207	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731208	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731209	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731211	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
731301	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731302	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
731303	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731304	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731305	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731306	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731307	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731308	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731309	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731310	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731311	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
731401	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731402	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731403	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731404	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731405	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731406	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731407	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731408	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731409	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731410	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731411	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
731501	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731502	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731503	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731504	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731505	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731506	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731507	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731508	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731509	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731510	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731511	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731512	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731513	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
731601	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731602	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731603	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731604	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731605	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731606	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731607	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731608	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731609	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
731610	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731611	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731612	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731613	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731614	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731701	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731702	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731703	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731704	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731705	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731706	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731707	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731708	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731709	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731710	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731711	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
731801	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731802	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731803	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731804	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731805	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731806	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731807	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731808	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731809	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731810	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731811	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731812	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731813	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
731814	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
732101	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
732102	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
732103	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.8	0	0
732104	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
732105	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
732106	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.8	0	0
732107	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.8	0	0
732201	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	0.8	1	0.91	1	1	0	1
732202	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	0	1
732203	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
732204	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	0	1
732205	1	0	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	0	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
732206	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	0	1
732207	1	0	1	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
732208	1	0	1	1	0.92	0.89	1	1	0.91	1	1	0	1
732209	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	0	1
732301	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.86	1	0	1	0
732302	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.67	0	0.86	1	0	1	0
732303	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.67	0	0.86	1	0	1	0
732304	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
732305	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.67	0	0.86	1	0	1	0
732306	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
732307	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.86	1	0	1	0
741101	1	0	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
741102	1	0	1	1	0.93	0.8	0.89	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
741103	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	0.97	0.8	1	1	1
741104	1	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	0.97	0.8	1	1	1
741105	1	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	0.67
741106	1	0	1	0.9	0.93	0.6	0.89	1	0.83	1	0.75	1	1
741107	1	0	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	0.93	0.8	1	1	1
741108	1	0	1	1	1	0.6	0.89	1	0.97	1	1	1	0.67
741201	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	1	1
741202	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.96	1	1	0.92	1	0.83	1
741203	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	0.96	1	0.98	0.92	1	0.83	1
741204	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	0.98	1	0.88	0.83	1
741205	1	1	1	1	0.89	1	0.96	1	0.95	1	1	0.83	1
741206	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.96	1	0.97	1	0.88	0.67	1
741207	1	1	1	1	0.95	1	0.96	1	1	1	1	1	1
741301	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
741302	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1
741303	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
741304	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1
741305	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	1	1
741306	1	0	1	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
742101	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
742102	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
742103	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
742104	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
742105	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
742106	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
742107	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
742108	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
742109	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
742201	0.89	0	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
742202	0.89	0	1	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0
742203	1	0	1	1	0.83	1	0.71	1	0.9	1	1	1	0
742204	0.89	0	1	1	0.83	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0
742205	0.89	0	1	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
742206	1	0	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	0.9	1	1	1	0
742207	1	0	1	1	0.83	1	0.86	1	0.8	1	1	1	0
751101	1	0	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	0	1	1	1
751102	1	0	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	0	1	1	1
751103	1	0	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	0.5
751104	1	0	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
751105	1	0	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	0.5	1
751106	1	0	0.86	1	0.78	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
751107	1	0	1	1	0.89	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
751108	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	0	1	1	1
751201	1	0	0.83	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
751202	1	0	0.83	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	0.8	0.75	1
751203	1	0	0.83	1	1	1	0.75	1	0.97	1	1	0.75	1
751204	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	0.8	1	1
751205	1	0	0.83	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.87	1	1	0.5	1
751206	1	0	1	1	0.95	1	0.75	0.86	0.97	1	1	1	1
751207	1	0	0.83	1	0.95	1	1	0.86	0.97	1	1	0.75	1
751208	1	0	0.83	1	0.95	1	0.75	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
751301	0	0	0	0	0.75	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
751302	0	0	0	0	0.75	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
751303	0	0	0	0	0.75	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
751304	0	0	0	0	0.75	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
751305	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
751306	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
751307	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
751308	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
751401	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
751402	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
751403	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
751404	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
751405	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
751501	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
751502	1	0	0	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
751503	1	0	0	1	0.83	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	1
751504	1	0	0	1	0.83	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	1
751505	1	0	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
752101	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
752102	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0.8	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
752103	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
752104	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	0	0	0	0
752105	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
752106	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
752201	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
752202	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
752203	0	1	1	0.5	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
752204	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
752205	0	1	1	0.5	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
752206	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
752301	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
752302	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
752303	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
752304	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
752305	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
752306	0	0	0	1	0.88	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
753101	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753102	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753103	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753104	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753105	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753106	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753107	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753108	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753109	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753110	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753111	1	0	0	0	0.88	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
753201	1	0	0	1	0.91	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
753202	1	0	0	0.67	0.91	1	1	0	0	0	0.67	1	0
753203	1	0	0	1	0.82	1	0.5	0	0	0	1	1	0
753204	1	0	0	1	0.91	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
753205	1	0	0	1	0.91	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
753206	1	0	0	1	0.73	1	0.5	0	0	0	1	1	0
753207	1	0	0	0.67	0.82	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
753208	1	0	0	1	0.82	1	0.5	0	0	0	0.67	1	0
753209	1	0	0	0.67	0.82	1	0.5	0	0	0	1	1	0
753210	1	0	0	1	0.73	1	0.5	0	0	0	0.67	1	0
753211	1	0	0	0.67	0.64	1	0.5	0	0	0	1	1	0
753212	1	0	0	1	0.64	1	0.5	0	0	0	1	1	0
753301	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753302	1	1	0	0.8	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753303	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
753304	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753305	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753306	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753307	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753308	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753309	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753310	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
753311	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753312	1	1	0	1	0.83	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
753401	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753402	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753403	0.67	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753404	0.67	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753405	0.67	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753406	0.67	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0.89	0	0	1	0
753407	0.33	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753408	0.67	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753409	0.67	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0.89	0	0	1	0
753410	0.67	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753411	0.67	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753412	0.67	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
753501	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753502	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753503	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753504	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753505	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753506	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753507	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753508	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753509	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753510	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753511	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753512	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753513	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
753601	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
753602	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
753603	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
753604	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
753605	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0
753606	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
753607	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
753608	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
753609	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0
753610	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0
753611	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0
753612	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0
753613	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0
754101	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754102	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754103	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754104	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754105	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754106	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754107	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754108	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754109	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754110	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754111	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
754301	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
754302	1	0	1	1	0.85	0.9	1	1	0.93	1	0.8	0.83	0.83
754303	1	0	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
754304	1	0	1	1	0.85	0.95	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
754305	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1
754306	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
754307	1	0	0.75	1	1	0.9	1	1	0.86	1	1	1	1
754308	1	0	1	1	0.92	0.9	0.86	0.95	0.9	1	1	1	1
754309	1	0	1	1	1	0.95	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1
754401	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
754402	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
754403	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
754404	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
754405	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
754406	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
754407	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
811101	0	0	0	0	0.8	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
811102	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
811103	0	0	0	0	0.8	1	1	0	0	0.67	0	0	0
811104	0	0	0	0	0.6	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
811105	0	0	0	0	0.8	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
811106	0	0	0	0	0.6	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
811107	0	0	0	0	0.6	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
811108	0	0	0	0	0.8	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
811109	0	0	0	0	0.8	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
811201	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
811202	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
811203	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
811204	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
811205	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
811206	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
811207	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
811208	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
811209	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
811210	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
811301	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
811302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
811303	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
811304	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
811305	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
811306	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
811307	0	0	1	1	1	0.67	0.83	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
811308	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.83	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
811309	1	0	1	1	1	0.67	0.83	0	0.75	0	0	0	0
811310	1	0	1	1	1	0.67	0.83	0	1	0	0	0	0
811401	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
811402	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
811403	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
811404	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
811405	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
811406	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
811407	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
812101	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	0	0	0
812102	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
812103	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	0	0	0
812104	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
812105	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	0	0	0
812106	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
812107	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
812108	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0.67	0	0	0	0
812201	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
812202	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
812203	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
812204	0	0	0	1	0.67	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
812205	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
812206	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
812207	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
812208	0	0	0	1	0.67	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
813101	1	0	1	0.5	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
813102	1	0	1	0.5	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
813103	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
813104	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
813105	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
813106	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
814101	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
814102	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
814103	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
814104	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
814105	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
814106	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
814201	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	0	1	0
814202	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	0	1	0
814203	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	0	1	0
814204	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	0	1	0
814205	1	0	0	1	1	0.8	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
814206	1	0	0	0.86	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
814207	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.83	1	0	1	0
814301	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
814302	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
814303	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
815101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815102	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815103	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815104	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815105	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815106	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815107	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815108	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815109	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815111	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
815201	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815202	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815203	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815204	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815205	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815206	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815207	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815208	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815209	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
815210	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815211	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0
815212	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0
815213	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0
815301	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
815302	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
815303	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
815304	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
815305	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
815306	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
815307	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
815308	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
815406	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815412	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815601	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815602	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815603	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815701	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815702	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815703	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815704	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
815705	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0
815706	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0
815707	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0
815708	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0
815709	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0
815901	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	0
815902	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
815903	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
815904	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.67	0	1	1	0
815905	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.67	0	0	1	0
816001	0	0	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	0.82	1	1	1	1
816002	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1
816003	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.91	0.5	1	1	1
816004	0	0	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	0.82	0.5	1	1	1
816005	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
816006	0	0	1	1	1	0.83	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
816007	0	0	1	1	0.88	0.67	0.5	0.5	0.91	0.5	0.5	1	1
817101	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
817102	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
817103	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
817104	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
817105	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0
817201	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
817202	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
817203	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.83	0	1	0	1
817204	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
817205	1	0	1	1	1	0.5	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
818101	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818102	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818103	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818104	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818105	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818106	1	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818107	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818108	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818109	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818110	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818111	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818112	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818113	1	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
818201	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
818202	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
818203	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
818204	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
818205	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.67	0	0	0
818206	1	0	0	1	0.67	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
818207	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
818301	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
818302	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
818303	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
821101	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
821102	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
821103	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
821104	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
821105	1	0	1	0	1	0.5	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
821201	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
821202	1	0	0	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
821203	1	0	0	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
821204	0	0	0	1	0.71	1	0.8	1	0.9	0	0	1	1
821205	1	0	0	1	0.86	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
821901	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	0	1
821902	0	0	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	0	1
821903	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
821904	0	0	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	0	1
821905	0	0	0	1	0.9	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	0	1
831101	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
831102	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
831103	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
831104	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
831105	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
831201	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
831202	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
831203	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
831204	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
831205	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
832101	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
832102	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
832103	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
832104	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
832105	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
832201	1	1	1	1	0.96	1	1	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
832202	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.93	1	0.95	0	1	1	1
832203	1	1	1	1	0.88	0.91	1	1	0.92	0	1	1	1
832204	1	1	1	1	0.84	0.91	0.86	1	0.95	0	1	1	1
832205	1	1	1	1	0.88	0.91	0.93	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
832206	1	1	1	1	0.92	0.91	0.86	1	0.93	0	1	1	1
832207	1	1	1	1	0.8	0.91	0.93	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
832208	1	1	1	1	0.8	0.82	0.79	1	0.92	0	1	1	1
833101	1	0	1	1	0.86	0	1	0	0.95	1	1	1	0
833102	1	0	1	1	0.86	0	1	0	0.95	1	1	1	0
833103	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
833104	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.9	1	1	1	0
833105	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
833106	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
833107	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
833201	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
833202	1	1	0.8	1	0.88	1	0.91	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
833203	1	1	1	1	0.91	0.8	0.82	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
833204	1	1	1	1	0.91	0.8	0.82	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
833205	1	1	0.9	1	0.97	0.8	0.91	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
833206	1	1	1	1	0.91	0.8	0.91	1	0.96	1	1	1	1
834101	0	0	1	1	0.89	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
834102	0	0	1	1	0.67	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
834103	0	0	1	1	0.78	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
834104	0	0	1	1	0.67	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
834105	0	0	0.5	1	0.67	0	1	0	0.9	0	1	0	0
834106	0	0	0.5	1	0.67	0	1	0	0.9	0	1	0	0
834107	0	0	0.5	1	0.67	0	1	0	0.9	0	1	0	0
834108	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
834201	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
834202	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
834203	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
834204	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
834205	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
834206	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
834207	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
834301	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
834302	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0.92	1	0	1	0
834303	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0.92	1	0	1	0
834304	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0.92	1	0	1	0
834305	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0.92	1	0	1	0
834306	0	0	1	1	0.67	0	0	0.5	0.92	1	0	1	0
834307	0	0	1	1	0.67	0	0	1	0.92	1	0	1	0
834401	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
834402	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0.94	0	1	1	1
834403	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0.94	0	1	1	1
834404	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
834405	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
835001	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
835002	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.94	0	0	0	0
835003	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
835004	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.94	1	0	0	0
835005	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
835006	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.94	1	0	0	0
911101	0.9	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
911102	0.95	0	1	0.91	0	0	0.6	1	0.99	0	0.96	1	1
911103	0.95	0	1	1	0	0	0.8	1	0.97	0	1	0	1
911104	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0.88	0	0.92	1	1
911105	0.95	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0.95	0	0.92	1	1
911106	0.95	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0.97	0	1	1	1
911107	0.95	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0.97	0	0.96	1	1
911201	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
911202	1	0	0.86	1	1	0.8	1	1	0.97	1	1	1	1
911203	1	0	0.71	0.88	0.95	1	1	0.88	0.93	0.83	1	0.9	0
911204	1	0	1	0.88	1	1	1	1	0.88	1	1	1	1
912101	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
912102	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
912103	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
912104	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
912201	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
912202	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
912203	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
912204	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
912205	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
912206	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
912301	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
912302	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
912303	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
912901	1	0	1	0.89	0.82	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
912902	1	0	1	0.89	0.82	1	1	1	0.9	0	1	1	1
912903	1	0	1	1	0.91	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
912904	1	0	1	0.89	1	1	1	1	0.9	0	0	1	1
921101	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0.86	0	1	0	0
921102	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921103	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0.86	0	1	0	0
921104	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0.86	0	1	0	0
921105	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0.86	0	1	0	0
921106	0	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	0	0.86	0	1	0	0
921107	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921108	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.83	0	0	0	0
921202	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
921203	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
921204	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
921205	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
921206	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
921207	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921208	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921209	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921301	0	0	0	0	0.89	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921302	0	0	0	0	0.89	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921303	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921304	0	0	0	0	0.89	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921305	0	0	0	0	0.89	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921306	0	0	0	0	0.78	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921307	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921308	0	0	0	0	0.89	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921309	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
921310	0	0	0	0	0.89	0	0	0	0.67	0	0	0	0
921311	0	0	0	0	0.89	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
921401	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921402	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921403	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921404	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921405	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921406	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921407	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921408	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921409	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
921501	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
921502	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
921503	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
921504	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
931101	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
931102	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
931103	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
931104	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
931105	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
931106	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
931107	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
931201	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
931202	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
931203	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
931204	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
931205	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0.5	0
931301	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
931302	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
931303	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
931304	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
931305	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
931306	1	0	1	1	0.93	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
932101	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
932102	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
932103	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
932901	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0.94	1	0	0	1
932902	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0.88	1	0	0	1
932903	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0.88	1	0	0	1
932904	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
933301	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.94	1	1	1	1
933302	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.95	1	1	1	1

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
933303	0.82	1	1	1	1	1	0.88	0	0.92	1	1	0	1
933304	0.82	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.94	0.67	1	0.33	1
933305	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.99	1	1	0.67	1
933306	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.95	0.67	1	1	1
933401	0.67	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.98	0	0	1	1
933402	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
933403	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0.98	0	0	1	1
933404	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.98	0	0	1	1
933405	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.98	0	0	1	1
933406	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
933407	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.98	0	0	1	1
933408	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
941101	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
941102	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
941103	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
941104	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
941105	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
941106	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
941107	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
941108	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
941109	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0.95	1	0	0	1
941110	0.5	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0.38	1	0	0	1
941201	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.98	1	1	1	0
941202	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.94	1	1	1	0
941203	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.98	0	1	1	0
941204	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.96	0	1	1	0
941205	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.98	1	1	1	0
941206	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.9	1	1	1	0
941207	0.5	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	0	0.38	0	1	0	0
952001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
952002	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
952003	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
952004	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
952005	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
961101	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
961102	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0.75	0	0	1	0
961103	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
961104	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
961201	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
961202	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
961203	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
961204	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0

Code	ARG	AUS	BEL	BRA	BLR	IND	KAZ	MEX	NDL	RUS	ZAF	ESP	GBR
961205	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
961206	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
961301	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.67	1	1	1	0	1	0
961302	0	0	0	1	0.92	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
961303	0	0	0	1	0.85	1	0.67	1	1	1	0	1	0
961304	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
962101	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.83	0	1	1	0
962102	1	0	0	0	1	0.5	1	1	0.83	0	1	1	0
962103	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.92	0	1	1	0
962104	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.67	0	1	1	0
962105	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.75	0	1	1	0
962106	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.92	0	1	1	0
962107	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
962201	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
962202	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0.92	1	1	1	0
962203	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
962204	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
962205	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
962206	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0.92	1	1	1	0
962207	0	0	0	0	0.43	1	0	0	0.54	0.67	0	0	0
962301	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
962302	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
962303	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
962304	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
962305	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
962306	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
962307	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0.8	0	1	1	0
962901	0	0	1	1	0.5	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	1	1
962902	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0.75	0	0	1	1
962903	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
962904	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
962905	0	0	1	1	0.5	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
962906	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
962907	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
962908	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1

appendix 6 Estimated market value of tasks in the Netherlands (EUR)

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Leading and managing the activities of research and development staff	122303	35.36	33.82
Consulting with engineering staff to evaluate interface between hardware and software	251203	33.84	32.50
Representing the organisation at official occasions and board meetings in negotiations at conventions seminars public hearings and forums	112009	33.68	35.90
Planning and directing daily operations	122306	33.20	32.85
Directing the selection and installation of ICT resources and the provision of user training	133003	33.20	29.68
Conducting research and improving or developing concepts instruments theories and operational methods related to chemistry	211301	32.86	35.59
Directing software programming and development of documentation	251206	32.71	32.13
Representing the enterprise or organisation in dealings with outside bodies	121108	32.70	36.42
Planning the overall research and development programme of an enterprise or organisation specifying goals and budgetary requirements	122302	32.33	31.28
Researching analysing and evaluating requirements for software applications and operating systems	251201	32.29	31.15
Selecting or approving the selection of senior staff	112010	32.26	34.59
Consulting with customers concerning maintenance of software systems	251208	32.06	26.69
Consulting with the chief executive and with managers of other departments or sections	121103	32.04	32.75
Developing and directing software testing and validation procedures	251204	31.22	27.87
Planning directing and coordinating research and development activities in-house or commissioned from external research organisations to develop new or improved technical processes products knowledge or utilisation of materials	122301	30.89	30.83
Planning and organizing negotiations and procedures for determination of wage structures and level and for consultation with workers on conditions of employment	121203	30.60	29.60
Establishing and managing budgets controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources	122304	30.16	28.87
Overseeing safety health and related programmes and activities	121204	30.06	29.96
Providing overall leadership and management to the enterprise or organisation	112004	30.02	33.81
Conducting logical analyses of management problems especially in terms of input-output effectiveness and formulating mathematical models of each problem usually for programming and solution by computer	212003	29.97	28.18
Ensuring compliance with standards and legislation relating to employees rights health and safety equal opportunity and related concerns	121208	29.33	29.31
Representing the enterprise or organisation in dealings with outside bodies	121211	29.33	30.43
Applying mathematics statistics probability and risk theory to assess potential financial impacts of future events	212004	29.16	28.11
Overseeing the selection training and performance of staff for the entire enterprise or organisation	121209	29.04	28.42

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Researching designing and developing computer software systems	251202	28.93	28.66
Directing research of post-graduate students or other members of department	231006	28.88	29.10
Reporting to sales management on sales made and the marketability of goods and services	243311	28.87	26.83
Planning directing and coordinating the financial operations of an enterprise or organisation	121101	28.64	29.82
Assessing the financial situation of the enterprise or organisation preparing budgets and overseeing financial operations	121102	28.64	30.43
Establishing and managing budgets controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources	122106	28.51	29.15
Consulting with clients after sale to ensure satisfaction resolve any problems and provide ongoing support	243312	28.29	24.84
Overseeing the selection training and performance of staff	121107	27.80	26.92
Providing information and support for the preparation of financial reports and budgets	121905	27.53	27.37
Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures	121206	27.51	28.20
Consulting with senior management and with managers of other departments	121210	27.51	29.19
Drawing up legal documents such as contracts real estate transactions and wills and preparing statements of legal opinions	261110	27.34	29.55
Providing leadership and guidance to teaching academic and administrative staff as well as to students	134505	27.33	26.62
Overseeing the security of ICT systems	133005	26.99	27.28
Arranging delivery of goods installation of equipment and the provision of services	243310	26.94	26.15
Controlling administrative operations such as budget planning report preparation expenditure on supplies equipment and services	134504	26.58	26.51
Reviewing the operations and results of the enterprise or organisation and reporting to boards of directors and governing bodies	112002	26.47	30.70
Reviewing operations and programs to ensure consistency with policies of the organisation	242207	26.15	25.00
Planning and organizing procedures for recruitment training promotion transfer and dismissal of staff	121202	25.98	28.38
Overseeing the development and implementation of management information systems	121207	25.98	28.22
Overseeing the selection training and performance of staff	133010	25.98	25.43
Formulating and directing information and communication technology (ICT) strategies policies and plans	133002	25.67	26.61
Assigning reviewing managing and leading the work of systems analysts programmers and other computer- related workers	133006	25.67	25.93
Evaluating the organisation's technology use and needs and recommending improvements such as hardware and software upgrades	133007	25.67	25.95
Quoting and negotiating prices and credit terms and preparing and administering sales contracts	243309	25.59	25.37
Giving clients legal advice on a wide variety of subjects and undertaking legal business on clients' behalf	261101	25.40	26.30
Planning directing and coordinating the personnel and industrial relations activities policies and practices of an enterprise or organisation	121201	25.33	27.61
Overseeing the recording of purchase storage and distribution transactions	132407	25.19	25.38
Planning directing and coordinating the general functioning of an enterprise or organisation	112001	25.15	28.64

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Conducting physical examinations of patients and interviewing them and their families to determine their health status	221201	25.02	27.72
Considering medical information provided by a referring doctor or other health care provider	221202	25.02	27.72
Prescribing administering and monitoring patients' responses to treatments medications anaesthetics psychotherapies physical rehabilitation programmes and other preventive and curative measures	221204	25.02	27.72
Recording patients' medical information and exchanging information with other health professionals to ensure the provision of comprehensive care	221207	25.02	27.33
Establishing and managing budgets controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources	132408	25.01	24.03
Representing the enterprise or organisation in negotiations and at conventions seminars public hearings and forums	121907	24.92	30.28
Establishing and managing budgets controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources	121908	24.92	24.61
Ordering specialized diagnostic tests to determine the nature of disorders or illnesses	221203	24.78	27.52
Providing information to patients and families and communities about preventive measures treatment and care for specific ailments	221209	24.78	27.66
Planning and directing daily operations	121106	24.63	25.82
Establishing and managing budgets controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources	121205	24.61	26.31
Training users and promoting security awareness to ensure system security and to improve server and network efficiency	252902	24.54	26.89
Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures	133009	24.53	25.24
Establishing and managing budgets controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources	121104	24.46	25.01
Advising on and designing machinery and tools for manufacturing mining construction agricultural and other industrial purposes	214401	24.38	27.62
Consulting with senior subordinate staff and reviewing recommendations and reports	112008	24.35	29.84
Conducting threat and risk assessments and developing responses	242206	24.30	23.40
Liaising with other departments and customers concerning requirements for outward goods and associated forwarding transportation	132406	24.25	22.63
Modifying existing software to correct errors to adapt it to new hardware or to upgrade interfaces and improve performance	251205	24.25	26.43
Modifying computer security files to incorporate new software correct errors or change individual access status	252905	24.25	27.45
Monitoring use of data files and regulate access to safeguard information in computer files	252906	24.25	24.60
Performing risk assessments and executing tests of data processing system to ensure functioning of data processing activities and security measures	252907	24.25	24.86
Preparing or reporting on profit forecasts and budgets	241104	24.00	26.03
Providing administrative strategic planning and operational support research and advice to senior management on matters such as the management of building facilities and administrative services	121901	23.90	24.38
Leading and managing the activities of sales and marketing staff	122104	23.68	25.43
Advising on planning and installing budgetary accounts controlling and other accounting policies and systems	241101	23.67	24.07
Determining objectives strategies policies and programs for the enterprise or organisation	112003	23.63	28.81

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Monitoring and evaluating performance of the organisation or enterprise against established objectives and policies	112007	23.49	27.17
Ensuring the organisation complies with relevant legislation and regulations	112011	23.48	27.93
Assisting in implementing approved recommendations issuing revised instructions and procedure manuals and drafting other documentation	242108	23.46	25.20
Reviewing operating procedures and advising of departures from procedures and standards	242109	23.46	24.17
Directing ICT operations analysing workflow establishing priorities developing standards and setting deadlines	133004	23.38	24.18
Establishing and managing budgets controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources	112005	23.35	26.78
Liaising and consulting with program administrators and other interested parties to identify policy needs	242201	23.11	23.30
Leading managing and developing administrative staff to ensure smooth business operations and the provision of accurate and timely information	121906	23.09	24.44
Planning and directing daily operations	122105	23.09	24.86
Authorising material human and financial resources to implement organisational policies and programs	112006	23.07	26.52
Evaluate findings and develop strategies and arguments in preparation for presentation of cases	261104	23.05	25.42
Organizing maintenance and repairs	311206	23.05	21.92
Representing the enterprise or organisation at sales and marketing conventions trade exhibitions and other forums	122108	22.82	27.25
Conferring with users to discuss issues such as computer data access needs security violations and programming changes	252903	22.81	23.77
Encrypting data transmissions and erecting firewalls to conceal confidential information as it is being transmitted and to keep out tainted digital transfers	252908	22.81	23.89
Planning and directing daily operations	121909	22.81	23.90
Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures related to sales and marketing activities	122103	22.68	23.73
Developing and managing the organisation's administrative and physical resources	121902	22.47	22.13
Advising on and designing: hulls superstructures and propulsion systems of ships mechanical plant and equipment for the release control and utilisation of energy heating ventilation and refrigeration systems steering gear pumps and other mechanical equipment	214403	22.45	25.87
Counselling students to help them understand and overcome personal social or behavioural problems affecting their education	235910	22.29	21.97
Formulating and implementing purchasing and marketing policies and setting prices	142002	22.27	19.31
Determining price lists discount and delivery terms sales promotion budgets sales methods special incentives and campaigns	122102	22.25	23.09
Conducting investigations and advising management on financial aspects of productivity stockholdings sales new products etc.	241107	22.15	22.96
Devising and controlling a system to determine unit cost of products and services	241108	22.15	24.04
Researching legal principles statutes and previous court decisions related to specific cases	261102	22.08	26.17
Operating electronic or computerized control panel from a central control room to monitor and optimize physical and chemical processes for several processing units	313301	22.06	23.06
Directing clients towards more efficient organisation and developing solutions to organisational problems	242104	22.04	22.76

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Conducting counselling or therapeutic interviews with individuals and groups and providing follow-up services	263403	22.00	21.39
Analysing the effect of heredity social occupational and other factors on individual thought and behaviour	263402	21.99	20.17
Coordinating and linking the computer systems within an organisation to increase compatibility	251107	21.94	24.60
Preparing and certifying financial statements for presentation to management shareholders and statutory or other bodies	241102	21.76	23.32
Developing reports and proposals as part of sales presentation to demonstrate benefits from use of good or service	243306	21.74	22.75
Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures	132409	21.73	23.12
Planning and directing daily operations	132410	21.73	22.46
Preparing administering and marking tests assignments and examinations to evaluate pupils' progress	233008	21.72	23.15
Monitoring current reports of computer viruses to determine when to update virus protection systems	252904	21.68	22.86
Formulating and analysing policy options preparing briefing papers and recommendations for policy changes and advising on preferred options	242204	21.68	22.36
Consulting with users management vendors and technicians to assess computing needs and system requirements and specifying technology to meet those needs	133001	21.65	23.26
Establishing and managing budgets controlling expenditure and ensuring the efficient use of resources	133008	21.65	23.80
Stimulating and developing students' confidence interests abilities manual skills and coordination	235207	21.61	21.70
Preparing and maintaining student data and other records and submitting reports	235209	21.61	21.70
Overseeing the selection training and performance of staff	132411	21.36	21.43
Planning and organizing special sales and marketing programmes based on sales records and market assessments	122101	21.27	23.99
Overseeing the selection training and performance of staff	122107	21.27	22.90
Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures	121105	21.25	24.54
Supervising where appropriate experimental and practical work undertaken by students	231004	21.16	22.25
Examining applications and other relevant documents to determine type and amount of benefit which individuals are eligible to receive	335302	21.07	21.16
Assessing documentation and interviewing benefit recipients to ensure eligibility for continuing benefits or services	335303	21.07	21.16
Performing related administrative tasks to maintain client records and prepare reports on determinations regarding eligibility referral decisions termination of benefits and abuse or fraud	335304	21.07	21.16
Analysing complex resource management issues and initiatives that affect the organisation and preparing associated reports correspondence and submissions	121904	20.99	21.76
Conducting research on nursing practices and procedures and disseminating findings such as through scientific papers and reports	222110	20.93	21.83
Developing and implementing administrative and procedural statements and guidelines for use by staff in the organisation	121903	20.85	21.98
Overseeing the selection training and performance of staff	121910	20.85	21.44
Operating recording systems to track all movements of goods and ensuring re-ordering and re-stocking at optimal times	132405	20.79	22.90
Preparing and giving lessons discussions and demonstrations in one or more subjects	233003	20.79	19.82

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Establishing clear objectives for all lessons units and projects and communicating those objectives to students	233004	20.79	20.11
Preparing materials and classrooms for class activities	233005	20.79	19.81
Adapting teaching methods and instructional materials to meet students' varying needs and interests	233006	20.79	21.22
Participating in meetings concerning the school's educational or organisational policies	233010	20.79	20.20
Installing configuring testing maintaining and administering new and upgraded networks software database applications servers and workstations	252305	20.79	18.81
Verifying equipment for malfunctions carrying out routine operating tests and arranging for maintenance	313305	20.70	21.20
Visiting regular and prospective client businesses to establish and act on selling opportunities	243303	20.57	22.71
Selecting and preparing paints to required colours by mixing pigments and additives	713102	20.53	26.03
Ensuring that equipment operation and maintenance comply with design specifications and safety standards	214407	20.53	23.86
Preparing and maintaining procedures and documentation for network inventory and recording diagnosis and resolution of network faults enhancements and modifications to networks and maintenance instructions	252306	20.50	19.70
Setting financial objectives and developing and implementing strategies for achieving the financial objectives	241203	20.39	21.80
Auditing accounts and bookkeeping records	241106	20.38	18.96
Assisting in research on and development of industrial chemical processes plant and equipment or testing prototypes	311601	20.36	24.69
Observing and evaluating students' performance and behaviour	233007	20.35	20.04
Monitoring technical aspects of the manufacture installation utilisation maintenance and repair of electrical systems and equipment to ensure satisfactory performance and compliance with specifications and regulations	311304	20.32	21.37
Estimating costs of installing and maintaining equipment	243307	20.31	22.41
Monitoring customers' changing needs and competitor activity and reporting these developments to sales management	243308	20.31	23.22
Researching analysing evaluating and monitoring network infrastructure to ensure networks are configured to operate at optimal performance	252302	20.21	18.92
Monitoring network traffic and activity capacity and usage to ensure continued integrity and optimal network performance	252307	20.21	19.33
Negotiating with customers to determine type and degree of risk for which insurance is required	332102	20.21	21.37
Explaining details of insurance and conditions risk coverage premiums and benefits to customers	332103	20.21	21.37
Assisting clients to determine the type and level of coverage required calculating premiums and establishing method of payment	332104	20.21	21.37
Advising on and performing personnel functions relating to employee recruitment placement training promotion compensation and employee-management relations or other areas of personnel policy	242301	20.13	19.83
Studying and analysing jobs performed in an establishment by various means including interviews with workers supervisors and management and writing detailed position job or occupation descriptions from information obtained	242302	20.13	19.81
Providing input to product design where goods or services must be tailored to suit clients' needs	243305	20.06	21.40
Determining implementing and monitoring purchasing storage and distribution strategies policies and plans	132401	19.92	20.99

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Determining the quality or value of raw materials real estate industrial equipment personal and household effects works of art gems and other objects	331501	19.92	16.67
Preparing reports of value outlining the estimation factors and methods used	331505	19.92	17.20
Supervising independent or group projects field placements laboratory work or other training	232008	19.86	18.06
Providing individualized instruction and tutorial or remedial instruction	232009	19.86	17.32
Controlling process start-up and shut-down troubleshooting and monitoring outside process equipment	313303	19.79	18.51
Controlling process start-up and shut-down troubleshooting and monitoring outside process equipment	313304	19.79	18.51
Developing functional specifications for use by systems developers	251105	19.69	21.32
Investigating cases of abuse or neglect and taking action to protect children and other at risk persons	263506	19.68	19.40
Recording and analysing organisations' work flow charts records reports manuals and job descriptions	242106	19.67	18.52
Preparing and delivering lectures and conducting tutorials seminars and laboratory experiments	231002	19.63	21.28
Participating in departmental and faculty meetings and in conferences and seminars	231009	19.63	20.87
Advising and working on the foregoing and other aspects of job and occupation analyses in such fields as personnel administration workforce research and planning training or occupational information and vocational guidance	242304	19.63	19.17
Studying and advising individuals on employment opportunities career choices and further education or training that may be desirable	242305	19.63	19.11
Designing constructing modifying integrating implementing and testing database management systems	252102	19.58	19.65
Performing the operational establishment and preventive maintenance of backups recovery procedures and enforcing security and integrity controls	252106	19.58	20.47
Arranging property transfers	261903	19.55	20.76
Organising and managing project labour and the delivery of materials plant and equipment	214105	19.52	16.70
Analysing developing interpreting and evaluating complex system design and architecture specifications data models and diagrams in the development configuration and integration of computer systems	252301	19.49	18.83
Assessing and recommending improvements to network operations and integrated hardware software communications and operating systems	252303	19.49	19.01
Providing specialist skills in troubleshooting network problems and emergencies	252304	19.49	19.47
Maintaining and administering computer networks and related computing environments including computer hardware systems software applications software and all configurations	252201	19.44	18.91
Diagnosing hardware and software problems	252203	19.44	18.90
Performing data backups and disaster recovery operations	252204	19.44	18.74
Operating master consoles to monitor the performance of computer systems and networks and to coordinate computer network access and use	252205	19.44	18.45
Identifying and evaluating inefficiencies and recommending optimal business practices and system functionality and behaviour	251103	19.42	21.79
Identifying and analysing business processes procedures and work practices	251102	19.34	21.87
Quoting prices and credit terms recording orders and arranging deliveries	332205	19.34	19.56
Stimulating discussion and independent thought among students	231003	19.28	19.59
Treating animals medically and surgically and administering and prescribing drugs analgesics and general and local anaesthetics	225002	19.22	29.89

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Organizing and planning the daily work with regard to plans economy staff and environment	312202	19.11	21.70
Ensuring safety of workers	312205	19.11	21.70
Administering evaluating and marking examination papers and tests	231005	19.09	18.60
Training and instructing employees in job duties safety procedures and company policies or arranging for training to be provided	334104	19.08	19.09
Evaluating employees' job performance and conformance to regulations and recommending appropriate personnel action	334105	19.08	20.31
Preparing and implementing plans to maintain required stock levels at minimum cost	132402	19.05	21.47
Advising on and designing structures such as bridges dams docks roads airports railways canals pipelines waste-disposal and flood-control systems and industrial and other large buildings	214202	19.05	20.71
Determining and specifying construction methods materials and quality standards and directing construction work	214203	19.05	21.59
Preparing occupational information or working on occupational classification systems	242303	19.05	19.30
Taking responsibility for deploying functional solutions such as creating adopting and implementing system test plans	251104	19.05	22.37
Adjusting equipment valves pumps controls and process equipment	313302	19.03	19.77
Analysing sample products performing tests recording data and writing production logs	313306	19.03	18.58
Ensuring that mechanical engineering designs and finished work are within specifications regulations and contract provisions	311508	18.98	19.94
Assisting in planning and managing the care of individual patients	322105	18.96	19.18
Supervising the work of physiotherapy assistants and others	226407	18.95	15.19
Soliciting orders and selling goods to retail industrial wholesale and other establishments	332201	18.93	19.32
Providing technical assistance connected with the construction of buildings and other structures and with surveys or the preparation of survey reports	311202	18.89	17.82
Consulting with users to formulate and document requirements and with management to ensure agreement on systems principles	251101	18.85	21.54
Researching into and developing concepts theories and operational methods for application in industrial and other fields	231007	18.82	21.76
Providing nursing and personal care and treatment and health advice to patients as per care plans established by health professionals	322101	18.80	18.77
Updating information on patients' condition and treatments received in records-keeping systems	322104	18.80	19.10
Assessing clients' needs and resources and recommending appropriate goods or services	243304	18.76	22.04
Negotiating settlements in matters which involve legal disputes	261108	18.76	24.27
Developing and implementing care plans for the biological social and psychological treatment of patients in collaboration with other health professionals	222103	18.75	18.58
Planning and providing personal care treatments and therapies including administering medications and monitoring responses to treatment or care plan	222104	18.75	18.69
Assessing students and offering advice criticism and encouragement	235906	18.74	19.53
Preparing students for examinations and assessments	235908	18.74	20.00
Counselling students regarding educational issues such as course and program selection class scheduling school adjustment truancy study habits and career planning	235909	18.74	17.68
Conducting tests of mechanical systems collecting and analysing data and assembling and installing mechanical constructions in support of mechanical engineers	311507	18.72	19.72

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Expanding or modifying systems to improve work flow or serve new purposes	251106	18.71	22.52
Supervising and coordinating the work of other nursing health and personal care workers	222109	18.69	18.37
Developing plans to safeguard computer files against accidental or unauthorized modification destruction or disclosure and to meet emergency data processing needs	252901	18.68	21.01
Assembling installing testing calibrating modifying and repairing electrical equipment and installations to conform with regulations and safety requirements	311306	18.62	20.41
Scheduling and accompanying clients for appointments with medical doctors and other health professionals or performing other errands	532209	18.62	22.57
Answering questions from patients and families and providing information about prevention of ill-health treatment and care	222108	18.59	18.36
Monitoring pain and discomfort experienced by patients and alleviating pain using a variety of therapies including the use of pain-killing drugs	222106	18.59	18.00
Monitoring technical aspects of manufacture utilisation maintenance and repair of machines and mechanical installations facilities and components to ensure satisfactory performance and compliance with specifications and regulations	311504	18.53	19.43
Planning preparing and delivering programs of study lessons and workshops for individual students and groups	235902	18.51	20.27
Providing technical assistance in research on and development of machines and mechanical installations facilities and components or testing prototypes	311501	18.48	18.96
Establishing control standards and procedures to ensure efficient functioning and safety of machines machinery tools motors engines industrial plant equipment or systems	214406	18.46	20.22
Providing technical advice and support services to organisations on how best to deal with environmental problems in order to reduce environmental damage and minimize financial loss	213306	18.45	18.11
Inspecting places of work and by interviews observations and other means obtaining information about work practices and accidents to determine compliance with safety rules and regulations	325704	18.42	17.92
Responding to program error messages by finding and correcting problems referring the problem to other staff or terminating the program	351105	18.41	27.29
Monitoring technical aspects of manufacture utilisation maintenance and repair of machines and mechanical installations facilities and components to ensure satisfactory performance and compliance with specifications and regulations	311503	18.35	19.41
Assembling and installing new and modified mechanical assemblies components machine tools and controls and hydraulic power systems	311506	18.35	17.22
Coordinating the care of patients in consultation with other health professionals and members of health teams	222102	18.35	18.17
Assisting in giving first-aid treatment in emergencies	322106	18.34	18.88
Administering medications and other treatments to patients monitoring patients' condition and responses to treatment and referring patients and their families to a health professional for specialised care as needed	322102	18.34	18.60
Liaising with materials buying storing and controlling departments to ensure a steady flow of supplies	214110	18.32	17.61
Assessing recording and reporting on students' progress	235308	18.29	18.79
Planning providing and evaluating nursing care for patients according to the practice and standards of modern nursing	222101	18.28	18.32
Recommending changes to improve systems and network configurations and determining hardware or software requirements related to such changes	252202	18.28	19.08
Obtaining and updating knowledge of market conditions and of employer's and competitors' goods and services	332203	18.26	18.69

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Installing software and hardware and configuring operating system software in preparation for testing	251902	18.23	18.66
Examining equipment and construction sites to ensure that health and safety requirements are met	312304	18.23	19.69
Preparing scholarly books papers or articles	231008	18.21	20.52
Providing prospective customers with information about the characteristics and functions of the products and equipment for sale and demonstrating its use or qualities	332204	18.18	18.43
Reporting customers' reactions and requirements to suppliers and manufacturers	332206	18.18	18.91
Controlling process start-up and shut-down troubleshooting and monitoring outside process equipment	313403	18.16	20.56
Designing and preparing layouts of machines and mechanical installations facilities and components according to the specifications given	311502	18.15	18.94
Negotiating contracts with suppliers to meet quality cost and delivery requirements	132403	18.13	20.06
Retrieving separating and sorting program output as needed and sending data to specified users	351107	18.13	32.47
Compiling case records or reports for courts and other legal proceedings	263503	18.12	18.91
Maintaining contact with other social service agencies educational institutions and health care providers involved with clients to provide information and obtain feedback on clients' overall situation and progress	263511	18.12	17.94
Computing quantities qualities and types of materials required by production programme	432201	18.11	21.97
Planning and implementing programs of assistance for clients including crisis intervention and referral to agencies that provide financial assistance legal aid housing medical treatment and other services	263505	18.08	18.41
Observing and evaluating children's performance and behaviour	234107	18.04	18.16
Maintaining technical liaison and consultancy with other relevant specialists	216109	18.02	16.99
Establishing work schedules and procedures and co-coordinating activities with other work units or departments	334102	18.00	18.40
Coordinating assigning and reviewing the work of clerks engaged in word processing record keeping and filing operating telephones and switchboards data entry desktop publishing and other activities involving general office and administrative skills	334101	17.96	19.15
Resolving work-related problems and preparing and submitting progress and other reports	334103	17.96	19.29
Determining or negotiating contract terms and conditions awarding supplier contracts or recommending contract awards for the purchase of equipment raw materials products services and the purchasing of merchandise for resale	332301	17.89	18.32
Selecting the merchandise or products that best fit the establishment's requirements	332307	17.87	17.75
Studying market reports trade periodicals and sales promotion materials and visiting trade shows showrooms factories and product design events	332306	17.86	17.96
Instructing and demonstrating practical aspects of the subject area being studied	235904	17.85	19.28
Assigning exercises and work relevant to students' level of ability interests and aptitude	235905	17.85	19.09
Preparing students for later educational experiences by encouraging them to explore learning opportunities and to persevere with challenging tasks	235911	17.85	19.64
Laying stone brick and similar building blocks to construct or repair walls partitions fireplaces and other structures such as smokestacks furnaces converters kilns and ovens piers and abutments	711201	17.84	23.86
Instructing children individually and in groups using various teaching methods and materials (eg computers books games) adapting to children's varying needs	234102	17.84	17.57

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Supervising children during classes and at other times in the school day including the playground during breaks	234108	17.84	17.57
Participating in staff meetings and other sessions and conferring with other teachers concerning educational issues	234109	17.84	18.16
Assessing impacts financial implications interactions with other programs and political and administrative feasibility of policies	242205	17.80	21.87
Inspecting places of work to ensure that the working environment machinery and equipment conform to government and other rules regulations and standards related to sanitation and/or occupational and environmental health and safety	325702	17.78	17.46
Instructing patients and their families in procedures to be continued outside clinical settings	226404	17.77	16.83
Operating and controlling peripheral and related computer equipment	351101	17.77	24.83
Monitoring systems for equipment failure or errors in performance	351103	17.77	17.39
Purchasing general and specialized equipment materials or business services for use or for further processing by their establishment	332303	17.65	17.41
Instructing and monitoring students in the use of tools equipment and materials and the prevention of injury and damage	232004	17.64	19.35
Observing and evaluating students' work to determine progress provide feedback and make suggestions for improvement	232005	17.64	19.44
Interviewing clients individually in families or in groups to assess their situation and problems and determine the types of services required	263501	17.64	17.81
Interviewing clients to determine financial status and objectives risk tolerance and other information needed to develop financial plans and investment strategies	241202	17.62	20.17
Preparing and presenting material on the theory of the subject area being studied	235903	17.62	18.83
Aiding in the identification of potential hazards and introducing safety procedures and devices	311902	17.61	18.79
Performing web server backup and recovery operations	351407	17.61	16.63
Laying bricks or other masonry to build patios garden walls and other decorative installations	711203	17.59	24.53
Analysing the client's situation and presenting alternative approaches to resolving problems	263502	17.58	16.88
Planning and carrying out tests to measure mental physical and other characteristics such as intelligence abilities aptitudes potentialities etc. interpreting and evaluating results and providing advice	263401	17.55	20.54
Entering commands using computer terminal and activating controls on computer and peripheral equipment to integrate and operate equipment	351102	17.54	17.73
Notifying supervisor or maintenance technician of equipment malfunctions	351104	17.54	16.59
Developing and implementing programmes for screening and prevention of common physical ailments and disorders	226406	17.53	16.30
Determining product mix stock levels and service standards	142001	17.48	19.69
Acquiring and updating knowledge of employers' and competitors' goods and services and market conditions	243302	17.44	21.51
Overseeing distribution of merchandise to outlets and maintaining adequate stock levels	332309	17.44	16.64
Maintaining discipline and good working habits in the classroom	234103	17.39	17.37
Assisting and encouraging the development of objectives strategies and plans aimed at achieving customer satisfaction and the efficient use of organisations' resources	242101	17.38	22.66
Discussing current systems with staff and observing systems at all levels of organisation	242103	17.38	22.47

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Undertaking and reviewing work studies by analysing existing and proposed methods and procedures such as administrative and clerical procedures	242105	17.38	21.99
Determining training needs of students or workers and liaising with individuals industry and other education sectors to ensure provision of relevant education and training programs	232002	17.33	16.33
Preparing medications and other pharmaceutical compounds under the guidance of a pharmacist or other health professional	321301	17.32	17.30
Leading and managing the activities of advertising and public relations staff	122204	17.32	19.77
Establishing and directing operational and administrative procedures	122206	17.32	20.12
Planning and directing daily operations	122207	17.32	18.58
Overseeing the selection training and performance of staff	122208	17.32	19.23
Planning and organizing special functions	141202	17.32	16.81
Assessing the likely impact that potential or proposed activities projects and developments may have on the environment and recommending whether such developments should proceed	213302	17.32	17.60
Screening requests for meetings scheduling and organizing meetings and travel arrangements	334303	17.32	17.79
Establishing treatment goals with patients and designing treatment programs to reduce physical pain strengthen muscles improve cardiothoracic cardiovascular and respiratory functions restore joint mobility and improve balance and coordination	226402	17.29	16.87
Recording information on patients' health status and responses to treatment in medical records-keeping systems and sharing information with other health professionals as required to ensure continuing and comprehensive care	226405	17.29	16.85
Assisting users with network and data communications problems	351303	17.26	17.12
Acting as advocates for client groups in the community and lobbying for solutions to problems affecting them	263509	17.25	16.07
Maintaining proper storage and security conditions for drugs	321303	17.24	17.01
Filling and labelling containers with prescribed medications	321305	17.24	17.01
Cleaning and preparing equipment and containers used to prepare and dispense medicines and pharmaceutical compounds	321309	17.24	17.01
Supervising construction sites and coordinating work with other construction projects	312305	17.21	19.49
Researching social economic and industrial trends and client expectations of programs and services provided	242203	17.17	14.96
Assessing students' level of ability and determining learning needs	235901	17.16	19.07
Administering muscle nerve joint and functional ability tests to identify and assess physical problems of patients	226401	17.13	16.54
Advising employers' and workers' representatives on the implementation of government and other rules and regulations concerning occupational safety and the working environment	325701	17.08	16.70
Establishing contacts and sources of information about crimes planned or committed in order to prevent crimes or identify suspected offenders	335501	17.08	17.45
Undertaking budgeting for the establishment	142005	17.07	20.45
Ensuring compliance with occupational health and safety regulations	142007	17.07	20.33
Giving advice on legal aspects of various personal business and administrative problems	261901	17.03	19.23
Planning installation methods checking completed installation for safety and controls or undertaking the initial running of the new electrical equipment or systems	311305	17.03	17.62
Executing analysing and documenting results of software application tests and information and telecommunication systems tests	251904	17.03	18.27

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Preparing production requirements schedules ensuring that materials are available when needed and keeping relevant records	432202	17.03	19.80
Recording and coordinating the flow of work and materials	432205	17.03	18.83
Conducting on-the-job training sessions to teach and demonstrate principles techniques procedures or methods of designated subjects	232010	17.02	17.13
Negotiating arrangements with clients and suppliers	141209	17.02	15.87
Ordering and stocking laboratory supplies	314112	17.00	17.62
Presenting lectures and conducting discussions to increase students' knowledge and competence	232003	16.99	16.52
Preparing daily and longer term lesson plans in accordance with curriculum guidelines	234101	16.98	15.83
Preparing reports and maintaining records such as student grades attendance rolls and training activity details	232007	16.96	17.15
Working with offenders during and after sentence to help them to integrate into the community and to change attitudes and behaviour in order to reduce further offending	263507	16.95	16.08
Drafting administrative correspondence and minutes	334301	16.94	17.50
Driving and tending motor bus trolley bus or motor coach to transport local or long-distance passengers mail or goods	833101	16.91	25.33
Inspecting areas of production processing transport handling storage and sale of products to ensure conformity with government and other rules regulations and standards	325705	16.90	17.22
Supervising prisoners at work meals or during recreation periods	541303	16.88	17.81
Observing the conduct and behaviour of prisoners to prevent disturbances and escapes	541304	16.88	17.81
Preparing project documentation including sketches and scale drawings and integrating structural mechanical and aesthetic elements in final designs	216104	16.87	16.70
Selling equipment supplies and related services to business establishments or individuals	332202	16.86	17.41
Conducting research and providing advice on the selection application and implementation of database management tools	252103	16.79	17.88
Ensuring compliance with design specifications relevant legislation and regulations and maintenance of desired standards of materials and work	311203	16.77	17.64
Inspecting buildings and structures during and after construction to ensure that they comply with building grading zoning and safety laws and approved plans specifications and standards as well as with other rules concerning quality and safety of buildings	311207	16.77	17.51
Building and maintaining a client base	241201	16.74	19.02
Verifying that programmes function according to user requirements and established guidelines	251903	16.74	18.73
Developing and implementing software and information system testing policies procedures and scripts	251905	16.74	18.00
Organizing and coordinating the material and human resources required to complete jobs	312302	16.74	18.01
Examining and inspecting work progress	312303	16.74	18.31
Supervising the activities of building trades workers labourers and other construction workers	312306	16.74	19.59
Analysing and evaluating current systems and structures	242102	16.73	19.92
Arranging the purchasing and pricing of goods according to budget	141203	16.71	16.11
Cleaning wounds and applying surgical dressings and bandages	222105	16.69	17.02
Operating maintaining and troubleshooting network systems	351301	16.62	16.80

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Assessing students' progress	235304	16.62	18.55
Obtaining and verifying evidence by examining crime and accident scenes for clues and physical evidence interviewing witnesses and suspects and analysing documents and computer files	335502	16.61	16.73
Preparing or assisting in the preparation of production operation schedules on the basis of customers' orders and production capacity and performance	432203	16.60	18.45
Cleaning wounds and applying surgical dressings	322103	16.60	16.72
Obtaining and compiling statistical or actuarial data based on routine or special sources of information	431202	16.60	17.60
Liaising with other staff about a range of matters relating to the organisation's operations	334305	16.59	17.47
Opening and closing doors before or after passengers board or alight	833103	16.55	20.84
Controlling lighting heating and ventilation on buses and trams	833105	16.55	20.26
Supervising the work of clerical support workers	334308	16.54	17.72
Assisting in the development of environmental pollution remediation devices under the direction of an engineer	311904	16.45	16.94
Reading specifications to determine construction requirements and planning procedures	312301	16.45	18.94
Developing implementing and monitoring programs and treatments using the therapeutic properties of exercise heat cold massage manipulation hydrotherapy electrotherapy ultraviolet and infra-red light and ultrasound in the treatment of patients	226403	16.44	15.70
Writing and answering business or technical letters and other similar correspondence	334306	16.41	17.43
Revising repairing or expanding existing programs to increase operating efficiency or adapt to new requirements	251402	16.41	16.53
Conducting trial runs of programs and software applications to confirm that they will produce the desired information	251403	16.41	16.46
Assessing the level of ability and the extent of language difficulties of students and establishing students' needs and learning goals	235301	16.37	17.74
Planning preparing and delivering lessons and workshops for groups and individuals with content and rate of progression adapted to students' abilities and needs	235302	16.37	18.24
Assigning and correcting work and preparing and grading exams	235307	16.37	16.24
Getting patients ready for examination and treatment including explaining procedures and showing them to examination rooms	325603	16.37	18.50
Preparing and handling medical instruments and supplies sterilizing instruments and disposing of contaminated supplies in accordance with safety procedures	325604	16.37	16.94
Applying technical knowledge of building and civil engineering principles and practices in order to identify and solve problems arising	311204	16.36	16.43
Designing and producing teaching materials and adapting existing materials	235303	16.35	17.58
Assisting students in classroom settings where subjects are taught in a language other than the students' native language	235305	16.35	16.86
Following up clients to ensure satisfaction with products purchased	332207	16.34	18.06
Researching potential demand and market characteristics for new goods and services and collecting and analysing data and other statistical information	243106	16.34	16.69
Giving advice on environmental sanitary problems and techniques	325703	16.32	15.18
Inviting tenders consulting with suppliers and reviewing quotations	332304	16.30	17.52
Assigning and grading class work and homework	234105	16.28	15.61
Preparing administering and grading tests and assignments to evaluate children's progress	234106	16.28	15.61

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Formulating design concepts for clothing textiles industrial commercial and consumer products and jewellery	216302	16.26	16.76
Inspecting and testing new machinery and mechanical equipment for conformity with standards and specifications	723303	16.24	19.48
Sharing information with other health care providers when required to ensure continuing and comprehensive care	325905	16.24	16.88
Obtaining proposing and monitoring deadlines and follow-up dates	334302	16.24	17.32
Disassembling machinery and equipment to remove parts and make repairs	723304	16.23	18.84
Maintaining records of client care changes in condition and responses to care and treatment and reporting concerns or providing referrals to a health or social services professional	532202	16.21	21.40
Operating newly repaired machinery and equipment to verify the adequacy of repairs	723306	16.18	19.13
Writing and maintaining program code outlined in instructions and specifications in accordance with quality accredited standards	251401	16.17	16.18
Assisting in designing setting up and conducting experiments	314101	16.17	17.42
Developing and maintaining documentation policies and instructions recording operational procedures and system logs	351402	16.17	16.35
Examining parts for defects such as breakage and excessive wear	723305	16.16	19.09
Preparing wiring diagrams circuit board assembly diagrams and layout drawings used for manufacture installation and repair of electrical equipment in factories power plants and buildings	311806	16.16	15.19
Analysing evidence in order to solve crimes identify criminal activity and gather information for court cases	335503	16.15	16.05
Recording information on patients' medical history diagnostic testing and treatment procedures and results and other relevant information in medical records-keeping systems	325609	16.14	19.01
Assisting clients with personal and therapeutic care needs such as personal hygiene feeding dressing physical mobility and exercise communication taking oral medications and changing dressings usually as per care plans established by a health professional	532201	16.13	21.03
Maintaining clients' environmental hygiene standards such as changing bed linen washing clothes and dishes and cleaning living quarters	532205	16.13	22.78
Planning purchasing preparing or serving meals to meet nutritional requirements or prescribed diets	532207	16.13	18.20
Using standard computer software packages to perform accounting and related calculations	331305	16.13	17.41
Assisting in the preparation of budgets monitoring of expenditures drafting of contracts and purchasing or acquisition orders	334304	16.09	17.74
Marking items with details such as grade and acceptance or rejection status	754307	16.09	15.84
Collecting information relevant to clients' needs and assessing their relevant skills strengths and deficits	341201	16.09	13.78
Advising managers and clients on strategies and campaigns to reach target markets creating consumer awareness and effectively promoting the attributes of goods and services	243102	16.09	16.66
Maintaining records of stock levels and financial transactions	142004	16.08	17.69
Providing counselling therapy and mediation services and facilitating group sessions to assist clients to develop skills and insights needed to deal with and resolve their social and personal problems	263504	16.08	16.05
Negotiating with suppliers on prices discounts credit terms and transportation arrangements	332308	16.08	17.18
Drawing up legal documents and contracts	261902	16.04	18.34

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Analysing and interpreting blueprints data manuals and other materials to determine specifications inspection and testing procedures	754304	16.00	15.76
Initiating action to maintain or improve hygiene and prevent pollution of water air food or soil	325708	15.96	15.81
Identifying and communicating technical problems processes and solutions	251405	15.95	16.28
Providing information regarding designs materials and estimated building times	216103	15.94	16.31
Positioning and lifting clients with physical mobility challenges and helping transport them in wheelchairs and motor vehicles	532203	15.94	18.29
Reviewing and proofreading documents and correspondence to ensure compliance with legal procedures	334202	15.93	21.43
Selecting specifying and recommending functional and aesthetic materials production methods and finishes for manufacture	216306	15.93	16.43
Obtaining information about requirements and stock and developing specifications for quantity and quality to be purchased costs delivery dates and other contract conditions	332302	15.91	16.50
Assisting medical doctors and other health professionals to examine and treat patients including measuring and recording vital signs administering medications and performing routine clinical procedures such as giving injections and removing sutures	325602	15.90	18.74
Purchasing merchandise for resale by retail or wholesale establishments	332305	15.88	16.79
Developing curricula and planning course content and methods of instruction	232001	15.79	15.27
Setting one or more types of machine tool for production of metal articles in standardised series	722301	15.77	13.91
Operating and monitoring metalworking machines such as lathes milling planing boring drilling grinding or honing machines including multi-purpose numerically controlled machines	722302	15.77	13.91
Observing machine operations to detect work piece defects or machine malfunctions adjusting machines as necessary	722304	15.77	14.15
Establishing delivery schedules monitoring progress and contacting clients and suppliers to resolve problems	332310	15.73	16.44
Advising patients and families on diet exercise and other habits which aid prevention or treatment of disease and disorders	224007	15.72	15.53
Verifying stocks arranging deliveries and investigating delays	432204	15.70	18.94
Measuring dimensions of products using instruments such as rulers calipers gauges or micrometers	754308	15.70	15.41
Steering ship according to instructions	835002	15.66	16.18
Supervising the work of accounts and bookkeeping clerks	331306	15.66	16.32
Installing maintaining and repairing electrical wiring systems and related equipment in various buildings such as schools hospitals commercial establishments residential buildings and other structures	741101	15.65	16.41
Interviewing patients and their families to obtain information on their health status and medical history	325601	15.62	16.50
Installing computer hardware network software operating system software and applications software	351304	15.60	15.04
Determining the objectives and constraints of the design brief by consulting with clients and stakeholders	216301	15.59	16.70
Harmonizing aesthetic considerations with technical functional ecological and production requirements	216303	15.59	16.35
Preparing sketches diagrams illustrations plans samples and models to communicate design concepts	216304	15.59	15.89
Designing and preparing blueprints of electrical installations and circuitry according to the specifications given	311302	15.59	19.57

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Preparing detailed estimates of quantities and costs of materials and labour required for manufacture and installation according to the specifications given	311303	15.59	17.13
Examining blueprints wiring diagrams and specifications to determine sequences and methods of operation	741102	15.59	17.84
Planning layout and installation of electrical wiring equipment and fixtures based on job specifications and relevant standards	741103	15.59	17.41
Compiling recording and reviewing medical charts reports documents and correspondence	334402	15.57	15.77
Notifying supervisors and other personnel of production problems and assisting in identifying and correcting these problems	754305	15.55	15.52
Collecting blood tissue or other specimens and preparing them for laboratory testing	325605	15.54	16.39
Receiving and answering inquiries about employment entitlements and conditions	441604	15.51	17.42
Installing monitoring and supporting the reliability and usability of Internet and Intranet websites or web server hardware or software	351401	15.50	16.25
Providing information to patients and families on health care topics including medications prescribed by a medical doctor or other health professional	325606	15.45	17.54
Commissioning and undertaking market research to identify market opportunities for new and existing goods and services	243108	15.44	15.96
Scheduling and confirming medical appointments and communicating messages for medical staff and patients	334401	15.43	15.18
Installing gas appliances dishwashers and water heaters sinks and toilets using hand and power tools	712602	15.42	26.52
Providing crisis intervention and emergency shelter services	341207	15.40	19.13
Maintaining contact with other social service agencies schools and health care providers involved to provide information and obtain feedback on clients' overall situation and progress	341210	15.40	18.36
Demonstrating and teaching body movements concepts and skills used in fitness routines and recreational activities	342304	15.40	21.70
Planning and carrying out recreational and fitness activities	342301	15.39	21.15
Evaluating and monitoring clients' abilities and fitness and recommending activities	342303	15.38	21.25
Providing clients and families with emotional support and information and advice on topics such as nutrition hygiene exercise caring for infants or adapting to disability or illness	532204	15.38	16.69
Providing psychological support to clients such as through conversation or reading aloud	532206	15.38	20.91
Preparing financial documents and calculating interest or brokerage charges and stamp duties payable	431204	15.38	15.20
Advising on all elements of marketing such as product mix pricing advertising and sales promotion selling and distribution channels	243109	15.37	16.22
Analysing data regarding consumer patterns and preferences	243104	15.30	15.76
Developing and documenting software testing plans	251901	15.30	17.73
Preparing reports for management	432306	15.30	20.06
Preparing and processing legal documents and papers such as deeds wills affidavits and briefs	334201	15.27	18.29
Keeping records of operational aspects and coordinating the timing of passenger and freight transport	432301	15.26	16.92
Modifying web pages	351406	15.25	15.78
Scheduling appointments with patients and preparing documentation required for billing reporting and insurance purposes	325610	15.21	14.29
Ensuring that facilities are kept clean and in good condition	143102	15.19	13.64

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Checking and keeping custody of all cash receipts and making regular stock checks	143105	15.19	14.14
Planning and directing daily operations	143107	15.19	14.30
Ensuring compliance with health and safety regulations	143109	15.19	13.88
Submitting periodic reports on telemarketing activities and results	524408	15.19	14.59
Preparing financial statements and reports for specified periods	331303	15.16	15.85
Interpreting and predicting current and future consumer trends	243105	15.14	15.94
Arranging for completed drawings to be reproduced for use as working drawings	311808	15.13	15.06
Controlling selection training and supervision of staff	142006	15.13	18.30
Observing traffic to ensure safe progress	833106	15.11	19.53
Applying bookkeeping principles and practices in order to identify and solve problems arising in the course of their work	331304	15.10	17.14
Organizing and maintaining documents case files and law libraries	334204	15.09	15.41
Processing insurance enrolments cancellations claims transactions policy changes and payments	431201	15.07	14.66
Verifying accuracy of documents and records relating to payments receipts and other financial transactions	331302	15.02	16.36
Collecting data and providing technical assistance regarding efficient safe and economic utilisation of personnel material and equipment methods of work and sequence of operations and supervision of their implementation and efficient layout of plant or establishment	311901	15.01	14.94
Maintaining complete records of all financial transactions of an undertaking according to general bookkeeping principles with guidance from accountants	331301	15.01	15.59
Arranging and coordinating services such as conference facilities catering signage displays audio-visual and computer equipment accommodation transport and social events for participants logistical arrangements for presenters	333204	15.01	14.44
Cutting metal pieces using gas flame or an electric arc	721205	15.00	13.83
Fitting installing examining servicing and repairing engines machinery and mechanical equipment	723301	15.00	17.37
Discarding or rejecting products materials and equipment not meeting specifications	754303	14.97	14.72
Planning developing and organizing advertising policies and campaigns to support sales objectives	243101	14.97	16.32
Inspecting electrical systems equipment and components to identify hazards defects and the need for adjustment or repair	741104	14.92	16.08
Greasing stationary engines and machinery	723302	14.92	19.79
Recording repairs and maintenance performed	723307	14.92	18.06
Monitoring patients' progress through treatment plans and identifying signs and symptoms requiring referral to a medical doctor or other health professional	325903	14.91	15.87
Providing technical assistance in research on and development of electrical equipment and facilities or testing prototypes	311301	14.88	18.56
Compiling and writing documentation of program development	251404	14.87	15.77
Preparing and revising working drawings from sketches and specifications from engineers and designers for the manufacture installation and erection of machinery and equipment or for the construction modification maintenance and repair of buildings dams bridges roads and other architectural and civil engineering projects	311801	14.80	14.72
Operating computer-aided design and drafting equipment to create modify and generate hard-copy and digital representations of working drawings	311802	14.80	15.11
Screening requests for meetings scheduling and organizing meetings	334205	14.80	15.96
Providing prescription and drug refill information to pharmacies	325607	14.75	17.58

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Combining measured ingredients in bowls of mixing blending or cooking machinery	751203	14.74	14.32
Supporting business growth and development through the preparation and execution of marketing objectives policies and programs	243107	14.72	15.82
Monitoring experiments to ensure adherence to correct laboratory quality control procedures and health and safety guidelines	314105	14.72	15.22
Recommending legal action or discontinuation of service when payment cannot be otherwise obtained	421404	14.72	18.11
Classifying recording and summarizing numerical and financial data to compile and keep financial records using journals and ledgers or computers	431103	14.72	14.87
Selecting set staff work schedules training and supervising waiting and kitchen staff	141207	14.71	17.71
Analysing and making recommendations to enhance performance including upgrading and acquiring new systems	351404	14.69	15.68
Liaising with and providing guidance to clients and users	351405	14.69	15.41
Installing testing connecting commissioning maintaining and modifying electrical equipment wiring and control systems	741204	14.69	14.70
Maintaining patients' environmental hygiene standards such as cleaning patient rooms and changing bed- linen	532104	14.69	16.58
Positioning lifting and turning patients and transporting them in wheelchairs or on movable beds	532103	14.69	16.13
Inspecting and testing products parts and materials for conformity with specifications and standards	754301	14.69	14.74
Serving statements of claims summons warrants subpoenas and other court orders	341102	14.64	14.73
Entering data from analysis of laboratory tests and clinical results into records-keeping systems and reporting results to medical practitioners and other health professionals	321203	14.64	15.41
Mailing faxing or arranging for delivery of legal correspondence to clients witnesses and court officials	334203	14.61	17.58
Telephoning visiting or writing to customers to collect money or arrange for later payments	421402	14.60	16.81
Updating information on employment history salaries performance evaluations qualifications and training and leave taken and accumulated	441601	14.59	18.95
Interviewing and examining patients to obtain information on their health status and the nature and extent of injury illness or other physical or mental health problem	325901	14.59	14.27
Replacing and repairing defective parts	741207	14.59	14.29
Planning and developing recipes and menus estimating food and labour costs and ordering food supplies	343401	14.59	15.34
Monitoring quality of dishes at all stages of preparation and presentation	343402	14.58	15.13
Performing start up and close down as well as backup and disaster recovery operations for computer networks	351305	14.58	14.74
Inspecting supplies equipment and work areas to ensure conformance to established standards	343405	14.57	15.05
Instructing cooks and other workers in the preparation cooking garnishing and presentation of food	343407	14.57	15.05
Explaining and enforcing hygiene and food safety regulations	343410	14.57	15.05
Fitting adjusting and repairing electrical parts in domestic appliances industrial machines and other appliances	741202	14.56	14.41
Identifying defective sectionalizing devices circuit breakers fuses voltage regulators transformers switches relays or wiring using wiring diagrams and electrical-testing instruments	741306	14.55	14.21
Handling ropes and wires and operating mooring equipment	835003	14.54	14.47

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Maintaining and in some cases operating ship's equipment cargo gear rigging life-saving and fire- fighting appliances	835004	14.54	13.73
Breaking out rigging and stowing cargo-handling gear stationary rigging and running gear	835006	14.54	14.08
Advising clients on legal matters	341106	14.53	14.48
Keeping records on individual children including daily observations and information about activities meals served and medications administered	531108	14.53	14.43
Checking figures postings and documents for correct entry mathematical accuracy and proper codes	431101	14.52	14.42
Compiling statistical financial accounting or auditing reports and tables pertaining to such matters as cash receipts expenditures accounts payable and receivable and profits and losses	431105	14.52	14.94
Coordinating and keeping records of operational activities concerning road transport such as allocation and scheduling of vehicles and drivers loading and unloading of vehicles and storage of goods in transit	432304	14.47	15.36
Planning and participating in health education programmes health promotion and nurse education activities in clinical and community settings	222107	14.47	14.66
Developing and implementing treatment plans for injuries illnesses and other physical and mental impairments	226902	14.46	21.31
Advising on training schemes	333306	14.44	14.89
Planning directing and coordinating the advertising and public relations activities of an enterprise or organisation	122201	14.43	18.08
Writing advertising copy and media scripts and arranging television and film production and media placement	243103	14.43	15.18
Assisting clients to identify and access community resources including legal medical and financial assistance housing employment transportation assistance with moves day care and other referral services	341204	14.43	13.38
Screening requests for meetings or appointments and helping to organize meetings	412005	14.43	14.11
Analysing laboratory findings to check the accuracy of the results	321206	14.43	14.88
Maintaining cleanliness of patient waiting and examination rooms	325608	14.43	16.46
Reading newspapers magazines press releases and other publications to locate and file articles of interest to staff and clients	441904	14.43	20.50
Documenting court proceedings and judgements	341101	14.41	15.02
Performing deck and hull cleaning scraping painting and other maintenance duties as required	835005	14.39	12.83
Supervising general welfare and conduct of housekeeping staff in institutions	515104	14.37	18.47
Facilitating negotiations with tenants and owners on rents and fees	333403	14.37	16.36
Paying bills and making money transfers on clients' behalf	421103	14.35	14.08
Operating computers programmed with accounting software to record store and analyse information	431102	14.33	14.65
Detailing and documenting the selected design for production	216307	14.29	16.02
Dealing with routine correspondence on their own initiative	412008	14.29	14.13
Recording information on patients' health status and responses to treatment in medical records-keeping systems	325904	14.28	15.26
Supervising and coordinating the activities of cooks and other workers engaged in food preparation	343404	14.28	14.91
Preparing verbatim reports of proceedings in legislative assemblies courts of law or other places using shorthand or specialized office equipment	334307	14.27	14.66

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Measuring cutting threading bending jointing assembling installing maintaining and repairing pipes fittings and fixtures of drainage heating water supply and sewerage systems	712601	14.26	19.41
Providing care support and treatment to patients and residents of medical rehabilitative and residential care facilities as per treatment plans established by medical nursing and other health professionals	532101	14.25	16.19
Controlling the selection supervision and performance of staff	143108	14.24	13.86
Assisting in analysing specifying and developing Internet strategies web-based methodologies and development plans	251305	14.15	15.50
Welding metal parts using gas flame or an electric arc thermite compound or other methods	721201	14.11	14.99
Operating resistance-welding machines	721202	14.11	14.99
Brazing metal parts together	721204	14.11	14.99
Examining work pieces for defects and measuring work pieces with straight edges or templates to ensure conformance with specifications	721208	14.11	15.53
Assisting in the preparation of materials and equipment for children's education and recreational activities	531104	14.11	13.22
Inspecting work pieces for defects and measuring work pieces to determine accuracy of machine operation using rules templates or other measuring instruments	722305	14.09	12.98
Assisting clients to identify options and develop plans of action while providing necessary support	341203	14.09	12.98
Assisting patients with personal and therapeutic care needs such as personal hygiene feeding dressing physical mobility and exercise communication taking oral medications and changing dressings	532102	14.08	15.91
Processing applications for employment and promotions and advising applicants of results	441603	14.08	14.81
Tracing and locating debtors	421401	14.08	13.75
Selecting cutting and connecting wire and cable to terminals and connectors	741105	14.05	16.65
Checking the quality of raw materials to ensure that standards and specifications are met	751204	14.04	14.57
Analysing designing and developing Internet sites applying a mixture of artistry and creativity with software programming and scripting languages and interfacing with operating environments	251301	14.03	14.42
Fitting assembling and altering internal and external fixtures of buildings such as walls doors door and window frames facings and panelling	711503	14.00	15.61
Calculating totals averages percentages and other details and presenting them in the required tabular form	431203	14.00	14.90
Discussing food preparation issues with managers dieticians kitchen and waiting staff	343403	13.98	14.85
Determining how food should be presented and creating decorative food displays	343406	13.98	14.93
Preparing seasoning and cooking speciality foods and complex dishes	343409	13.98	14.80
Selecting material for publication checking style grammar and accuracy of content arranging for any necessary revisions and checks of proof copies before printing	264106	13.97	15.40
Determining product mix stock and price levels for goods to be sold	522101	13.97	17.34
Budgeting and maintaining records of stock levels and financial transactions	522103	13.97	18.13
Making altering and repairing structural and other woodwork at a work-bench and on a construction site	711501	13.95	15.16
Responding to alarms investigating disturbances and contacting superiors police or fire-fighters as appropriate	541404	13.94	14.14
Maintaining records of daily data communication transactions problems and remedial actions taken or installation activities	351206	13.91	13.72

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Preparing legal documents including trial briefs pleadings appeals wills and contracts and preparing papers summarising legal positions or setting out conditions of loans or insurance	341104	13.91	13.57
Promoting and advertising the establishment's goods and services	142003	13.86	16.67
Creating detailed working diagrams of machinery and mechanical devices including dimensions fastening methods and other engineering information	311807	13.86	13.67
Developing coordinating implementing and monitoring security measures	351403	13.86	15.67
Maintaining and updating manual and computerized filing and registration systems and compiling and preparing reports and documents relating to personnel activities	441606	13.86	16.40
Storing and retrieving personnel records and files on request	441607	13.86	16.30
Operating and monitoring excavating machinery equipped with moveable shovel grab-bucket or dragline bucket to excavate and move earth rock sand gravel or similar materials	834201	13.86	18.19
Operating calibrating and maintaining equipment used in quantitative and qualitative analysis such as spectrophotometers calorimeters flame photometers and computer-controlled analysers	321202	13.86	15.15
Checking formatting and transcribing correspondence minutes and reports from dictation electronic documents or written drafts to conform to office standards using typewriter personal computer or other word processing equipment	412001	13.85	13.81
Dealing with incoming or outgoing mail	412003	13.85	13.99
Consulting user guides technical manuals and other documents to research and implement solutions	351208	13.85	13.90
Purchasing and ordering goods for sale from markets wholesalers and other suppliers	522102	13.81	17.75
Performing routine field and laboratory tests	314104	13.81	15.18
Making observations of tests and analysing calculating recording and reporting test results using appropriate scientific methods	314106	13.81	15.18
Keeping detailed logs of worked performed	314108	13.81	15.18
Obtaining information about properties to be sold or leased the circumstances of their owner and the needs of prospective buyers or tenants	333401	13.80	13.46
Scanning recording and distributing mail correspondence and documents	412004	13.75	13.93
Using various computer software packages including spreadsheets to provide administrative support	412002	13.75	13.90
Fitting adjusting and repairing various kinds of electrical machinery and motors generators switchgear and control apparatus instruments or electrical parts of elevators and related equipment	741201	13.74	13.97
Recording inspection or test data such as weights temperatures grades or moisture content and quantities inspected or graded	754306	13.74	13.81
Circulating among visitors patrons or employees to preserve order protect property from theft or vandalism and enforce the regulations of the establishment	541403	13.72	14.03
Preparing reports including amounts collected and maintain records and files related to collection work	421403	13.71	16.89
Setting up equipment for employee use performing or ensuring proper installation of cables operating systems or appropriate software	351205	13.70	14.27
Providing fluoride treatments cleaning and removing deposits from teeth preparing cavities and placing fillings administering local anaesthesia and performing other types of basic or routine clinical dental procedures	325105	13.69	18.37
Selling goods to customers and advising them on product use	522105	13.67	16.88
Taking inventory of goods in stock	522107	13.67	17.65
Observing patients' condition responses and behaviour and reporting changes to a health professional	532106	13.66	15.87

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Entering commands and observing system functioning to detect errors	351202	13.65	13.67
Installing and performing minor repairs to hardware software or peripheral equipment following design or installation specifications	351203	13.65	13.62
Collecting and preparing specimens and samples chemical solutions and slides and growing cultures for use in experiments	314103	13.62	14.82
Maintaining relevant databases	314113	13.62	16.32
Patrolling premises and checking doors windows and gates to prevent and detect signs of unauthorised entry	541401	13.61	13.98
Photocopying and faxing documents	411003	13.60	14.68
Supervising the work of office support workers	334207	13.59	16.78
Participating in the recruitment of kitchen staff and monitoring their performance	343408	13.57	14.05
Overseeing the daily performance of communications and computer systems	351204	13.57	13.74
Answering user inquiries regarding software or hardware operation to resolve problems	351201	13.57	14.48
Crediting and debiting clients' accounts	421102	13.51	13.22
Receiving mail selling postage stamps and conducting other post office counter business such as bill payments money transfers and related business	421104	13.51	13.05
Matching jobseekers with vacancies	333301	13.49	14.41
Discussing with enterprises/organisations the needed skills and other characteristics of the workers to be employed or contracted	333303	13.49	14.55
Identifying cases of patients with poor oral health or oral disease requiring referral to a dentist or other health professional	325103	13.48	16.19
Process customer cash deposits and withdrawals cheques transfers bills credit card payments money orders certified cheques and other related banking transactions	421101	13.47	14.16
Observing and monitoring children's play activities	531107	13.47	12.97
Setting up calibrating operating and maintaining laboratory instruments and equipment	314102	13.43	14.96
Using complex and high-powered equipment to perform work	314110	13.43	14.39
Examining returned goods and deciding on appropriate action	522106	13.42	16.85
Operating and maintaining data communications systems other than networks	351302	13.38	14.41
Detecting and diagnosing faults in engines and parts	723101	13.37	12.59
Reproducing technical problems encountered by users	351207	13.37	13.54
Applying or spraying paint varnish and similar materials to surfaces fixtures and fittings of buildings	713103	13.37	12.90
Operating digitising table or similar equipment to transfer hard-copy representation of working drawings maps and other curves to digital form	311803	13.36	13.70
Recording preparing sorting classifying and filing information	411001	13.34	14.59
Assisting children to wash dress and feed themselves	531101	13.33	12.68
Controlling access to establishments monitoring and authorizing the entrance or departure of employees and visitors checking identification and issuing security passes	541402	13.32	13.65
Finding workers with appropriate skills and undertaking the necessary formalities according to national or international regulations and requirements	333304	13.32	14.17
Curing meat fish and other foods	751105	13.32	13.38
Collecting reporting and commenting on news and current affairs for publication in newspapers and periodicals or for broadcasting by radio television or webcast media	264202	13.31	16.42
Transcribing information onto computers and proofreading and correcting copy	411008	13.30	14.27
Screening and recording leave and other staff-members' entitlements	412006	13.30	13.32

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Preparing indoor and outdoor areas for learning and recreational activities	531202	13.30	12.22
Checking figures preparing invoices and recording details of financial transactions made	411007	13.30	14.66
Organizing and supervising filing systems	412007	13.29	13.01
Responding to telephone or electronic enquiries or forwarding to appropriate person	411006	13.28	14.33
Finding workers for vacant posts against a commission from the employer or worker	333302	13.28	13.66
Consulting with and referring patients to ophthalmologists or other health professionals if additional medical treatment is necessary	226704	13.25	16.81
Analysing samples of biological material for chemical content or reaction	321204	13.23	13.96
Setting up cleaning and maintaining laboratory equipment	321205	13.23	14.38
Preparing and revising illustrations for reference works brochures and technical manuals dealing with the assembly installation operation maintenance and repair of machinery and other equipment and goods	311804	13.21	13.73
Calculating preparing and issuing bills invoices account statements and other financial statements according to established procedures	431104	13.21	14.79
Maintaining records of stock levels and financial transactions	141204	13.20	15.10
Ensuring dining kitchen and food storage facilities comply with health regulations and are clean functional and of suitable appearance	141205	13.20	16.49
Ensuring compliance with occupational health and safety regulations	141210	13.19	14.54
Playing games with children or entertaining them by reading or storytelling	531103	13.19	12.59
Managing children's behaviour and guiding their social development	531105	13.19	12.59
Disciplining children and recommending or initiating other measures to control behaviour such as caring for own clothing and picking up toys and books	531106	13.19	12.59
Directing and overseeing reservation reception room service and housekeeping activities	141101	13.16	14.01
Supervising security arrangements and garden and property maintenance	141102	13.16	14.01
Observing liquor gaming and other laws and regulations	141104	13.16	14.01
Ensuring compliance with occupational health and safety regulations	141109	13.16	14.01
Providing guests with local tourism information and arranging tours and transportation	141110	13.16	14.01
Conferring with customers to assess their satisfaction with meals and service	141206	13.14	13.41
Copying drawings and paintings onto stone or metal plates for printing	311805	13.14	12.79
Constructing erecting and installing heavy-framed wooden structures on building sites	711502	13.12	11.24
Testing systems diagnosing faults and performing routine maintenance or servicing	712704	13.12	14.01
Applying paints varnishes and stains to surfaces using brushes rollers and sprays	713105	13.11	13.42
Inspecting and testing manufactured electrical products	741203	13.09	13.06
Operating and monitoring log in-feed and conveyor systems	817202	13.08	17.36
Connecting electrical systems to power supply	741206	13.06	13.30
Analysing test data and making computations as necessary to determine test results	754309	13.04	14.27
Cleaning and preparing walls and other surfaces of buildings for painting or wallpapering	713101	13.04	13.63
Recording production and operational data on specified forms	821903	13.03	13.32
Inspecting and testing components and completed assemblies	821904	13.03	13.67
Driving and tending cars vans or small trucks to deliver mail or goods	832202	13.02	17.59
Determining prices and displaying goods for sale	522104	13.02	16.49

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Ensuring that the employment contracts meet legal requirements and signing them	333305	13.01	14.91
Designing developing and integrating computer code with other specialised inputs such as image files audio files and scripting languages to produce maintain and support websites	251304	12.99	13.12
Evaluating and documenting patients' progress through treatment plans and referring patients and families to medical doctors or other health care providers for specialized rehabilitative or other care services as needed	226903	12.94	19.02
Establishing and monitoring programs to ensure the accuracy of laboratory results and developing standardizing evaluating and modifying procedures techniques and tests used in the analysis of specimens	321207	12.86	15.58
Sorting opening and sending mail	411002	12.79	14.28
Advising on the facilities available and promoting publicity in relation to events shows and activities	143104	12.79	12.57
Using computer applications to generate images text layouts and impositions for print and other visual media displays	732102	12.78	13.59
Reassembling engines and parts after being repaired	723108	12.76	12.39
Taking reservations greeting guests and assisting in taking orders	141208	12.75	13.60
Receiving analysing and verifying news and other copy for accuracy	264203	12.72	16.61
Creating two-dimensional and three-dimensional images depicting objects in motion or illustrating a process using computer animation or modelling programs	216606	12.70	13.38
Controlling equipment to record sound	352101	12.70	12.49
Preparing reports and correspondence of a routine nature	411004	12.70	13.99
Arranging and controlling receipt and dispatch of goods and keeping relevant records	432101	12.70	13.19
Maintaining stock records verifying issue of goods estimating needs and making requisitions of new stocks	432102	12.70	13.44
Weighing goods received issued produced or dispatched and maintaining relevant records	432104	12.70	13.90
Initiating records for newly appointed workers and checking records for completeness	441602	12.70	14.97
Compiling inventories of furniture and other items received for storage	432105	12.69	12.35
Making appointments for clients	422602	12.67	13.44
Preparing cleaning and sterilizing dental instruments equipment and materials used in the examination and treatment of patients	325106	12.64	16.55
Communicating with network specialists regarding web-related issues such as security and hosting web sites to control and enforce Internet and web server security space allocation user access business continuity web site backup and disaster recovery planning	251303	12.62	12.53
Selecting assembling and preparing publicity material about business or other organisations for issue through press radio television and other media	264210	12.62	15.76
Assisting with preparing teaching materials and copying and collating written and printed material	531205	12.60	12.02
Installing adjusting servicing and replacing mechatronics components of motor vehicles	723106	12.59	11.54
Testing continuity of circuit	741108	12.58	12.83
Evaluating printed proofs checking and correcting them for quality	732106	12.58	13.20
Supervising or carrying out production in the chosen media	216610	12.51	13.32
Assembling installing and repairing components for air conditioning and refrigeration systems	712702	12.51	13.73
Participating in and providing advice to managers on interviewing hiring training evaluating promoting and dismissing staff and resolving staff grievances	522204	12.48	12.89

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Sending out job applications and announcements of job openings and job examinations	441605	12.48	14.09
Operating computer screen-based equipment for scanning colour separation colour correction masking creative design combining imposing retouching and other processes used to transfer copy to film and produce film for plate digital output and cylinder productions	732104	12.46	12.99
Determining project requirements including scope assembly sequences and required methods and materials according to blueprints drawings and written or verbal instructions	721306	12.45	13.92
Inspecting product quality and installation to ensure conformance to specifications	721307	12.45	14.01
Collecting local national and international news through interviews investigation and observation attending public events seeking out records reviewing written work attending film and stage performances	264201	12.43	17.71
Selecting material for publication checking style grammar accuracy and legality of content and arranging for any necessary revisions	264208	12.43	15.37
Examining patients' eyes and conducting diagnostic tests to assess ocular health and determine the nature and extent of vision problems and abnormalities	226701	12.42	16.20
Testing visual function using specialized instruments and equipment for measuring visual acuity and refractive error function of visual pathways visual fields eye movements freedom of vision and intraocular pressure	226702	12.42	16.20
Prescribing corrective eyeglasses contact lenses and other vision aids and checking optical devices for performance safety comfort and lifestyle	226706	12.42	16.20
Advising on visual health matters such as contact lens care vision care for the elderly optics visual ergonomics and occupational and industrial eye safety	226707	12.42	16.20
Detailing and documenting the selected design for production	216609	12.42	12.85
Operating telecommunications equipment to report location and availability and follow directions of control centre	832205	12.41	12.15
Determining most appropriate route	832206	12.41	13.90
Undertaking research and analysing functional communication requirements	216602	12.41	13.91
Receiving and welcoming visitors guests or clients	422601	12.40	12.96
Recording notes for follow-up action and updating marketing databases to reflect changes to the status of each customer	524405	12.39	16.16
Operating switchboards and consoles to connect hold transfer and disconnect telephone calls	422301	12.38	12.81
Dealing with telephone inquiries and recording messages	422303	12.38	12.72
Determining the objectives and constraints of the design brief by consulting with clients and stakeholders	216601	12.32	13.32
Engaging training discharging organizing and supervising helpers cleaners and other housekeeping staff	515101	12.32	13.34
Writing business and government correspondence such as replies to requests for information and assistance damage claims credit and billing enquiries and service complaints	441902	12.31	12.26
Converting blueprints into shop drawings to be followed in the construction and assembly of sheet metal products	721305	12.27	13.79
Advising communities and individuals on dental hygiene diet and other preventive measures to reduce potential risks to oral health	325101	12.23	13.45
Conducting visual and physical examinations of patients' mouths teeth and related structures to assess oral health status	325102	12.23	14.98
Getting patients ready for examination or treatment including explaining procedures and correct positioning	325107	12.23	14.21
Taking impressions of the mouth and dental radiographs to support diagnosis and fitting of dental prosthetics	325108	12.23	12.95

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Dealing with telephone requests for information or appointments	422603	12.21	13.01
Driving and tending a heavy motor vehicle such as a lorry with or without trailer to transport goods liquids or heavy materials over short or long distances	833201	12.21	12.99
Determining the most appropriate routes	833202	12.21	13.33
Ensuring goods are stowed and securely covered to prevent loss and damage	833203	12.17	12.80
Assisting with or carrying out loading or unloading operations using various lifting or tipping devices	833204	12.17	12.87
Cooking or in other ways preparing meat fish and related food items for sale	751107	12.15	12.30
Recording issue of equipment to staff	411005	12.14	13.70
Assisting dentists during complex dental procedures	325104	12.13	14.46
Monitoring the fitting burning and welding processes to avoid overheating of parts or warping shrinking distortion or expansion of material	721207	12.12	11.90
Estimating weights to comply with load limitations and ensuring the safe distribution of weights	833206	12.12	12.72
Making connections for outgoing calls	422302	12.05	12.51
Conducting examinations of animals to make diagnoses or refer more difficult cases to veterinarians when needed	324002	12.03	12.15
Carrying out minor maintenance to vehicles and arranges major maintenance and repairs	833205	12.02	13.47
Installing or adjusting motors and brakes and adjusting steering or other parts of motor vehicles	723105	12.00	11.33
Arranging delivery of goods installation of equipment and the provision of services	243406	11.98	12.49
Marking sheet metal for cutting and shaping	721301	11.95	14.11
Selling meat or fish to customers including wrapping weighing and labelling products and receiving payment	751108	11.95	11.74
Fitting examining testing and servicing motor vehicle and motorcycle engines	723102	11.92	11.36
Assembling component parts and positioning aligning and fastening units to assemblies sub-assemblies or frames using hand or power tools soldering and micro-welding equipment	821901	11.91	13.52
Rejecting faulty products	821905	11.91	13.37
Assisting children individually to learn social skills	531204	11.90	12.22
Inspecting equipment to identify wear and damage	834403	11.84	18.62
Performing routine maintenance on vehicles and equipment	834404	11.84	20.68
Fitting examining adjusting dismantling rebuilding and replacing defective parts of motor vehicles	723104	11.84	11.29
Negotiating design solutions with clients management sales and production staff	216607	11.84	14.12
Setting adjusting and monitoring substrate-feed mechanisms delivery mechanisms inking systems and other printing machine functions	732201	11.82	11.30
Monitoring evaluating and determining press to check print quality standards against proofs and detect malfunctions	732203	11.82	11.30
Loading paper into feeding mechanisms	732206	11.82	11.30
Monitoring machine operations and quality of printing	732207	11.82	11.30
Maintaining adjusting repairing and cleaning machines	732208	11.82	12.02
Forwarding messages to staff or clients	422304	11.80	12.44
Receiving storing and issuing tools spare parts or various equipment and maintaining relevant records	432103	11.77	11.90

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Performing scheduled maintenance services such as oil changes lubrications and engine tune-ups to achieve smoother running of vehicles and ensure compliance with pollution regulations	723107	11.74	11.25
Assisting children with intellectual physical behavioural and other learning difficulties with their studies	531203	11.74	11.80
Distributing and collecting lesson material	531207	11.74	11.64
Checking the cleanliness of equipment and operation of premises before production runs to ensure compliance with occupational health and safety regulations	751206	11.71	12.46
Helping customers in obtaining necessary travel documents such as visas	422105	11.71	16.11
Issuing tickets and vouchers	422104	11.67	15.23
Monitoring oven temperatures and product appearance	751207	11.66	12.42
Coordinating the forming loading baking unloading de-panning and cooling of batches of bread rolls pastry and confectionary products	751208	11.66	12.42
Obtaining information about the availability cost and convenience of different types of transport and accommodation ascertaining customer's requirements and advising them on travel arrangements	422101	11.64	14.92
Preparing itineraries	422102	11.64	11.23
Making and confirming reservations	422103	11.64	14.92
Instructing staff on sales procedures including how to handle difficult or complex cases	522202	11.62	12.39
Assisting in the preparation of periodicals advertisements catalogues directories and other material for publication	441903	11.62	12.33
Preparing bills and receiving payments	422106	11.60	11.43
Replacing engine components or complete engines	723103	11.60	11.59
Operating audio-visual equipment computers and other teaching aides	531206	11.59	11.34
Helping with preparation cooking and serving of meals and refreshments	911104	11.56	11.67
Formulating design concepts for the subject to be communicated	216603	11.55	12.63
Dispatching tasks to other units when relevant	422203	11.55	12.15
Sending letters information sheets and other documents to clients	422205	11.55	12.34
Collecting fares payments for deliveries or documents certifying deliveries	832204	11.55	11.11
Washing ironing and mending linen and other textiles	911102	11.55	11.20
Purchasing food and various other household supplies	911105	11.55	11.55
Identifying requirements and entering events into a computer system	422202	11.50	12.10
Preparing sketches diagrams illustrations and layouts to communicate design concepts	216604	11.48	12.43
Planning and preparing work schedules and assigning staff to specific duties	522201	11.46	12.16
Dealing with incoming calls and messages from clients whether to answer queries handle calls for service or sort out complaints	422201	11.45	11.96
Performing routine animal dental procedures and assisting veterinarians with animal dentistry	324010	11.42	11.34
Selecting specifying or recommending functional and aesthetic materials and media for publication delivery or display	216608	11.40	12.15
Receiving customers' orders for classified advertising writing and editing copy calculating advertising rates and billing customers	441901	11.40	10.43
Providing information regarding hotel services and services available in the community	422403	11.39	12.33
Responding to guests' requests for housekeeping and maintenance services as well as complaints	422405	11.39	12.33

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Compiling and checking guest accounts for charges using computerized or manual systems	422407	11.39	12.33
Receiving and forwarding messages in person or using telephone or telephone switchboard	422408	11.39	12.33
Sweeping vacuum-cleaning polishing and washing floors and furniture or washing windows and other fixtures	911101	11.38	11.28
Cleaning disinfecting and deodorising kitchens bathrooms and toilets	911106	11.38	11.25
Ensuring that customers receive prompt service	522203	11.37	11.99
Taking inventory of goods for sale and ordering new stock	522206	11.30	11.92
Ensuring that safety procedures are enforced	522208	11.30	12.01
Examining returned goods and deciding on appropriate action	522205	11.23	11.87
Making bread cakes biscuits pastries pies and other flour products	751201	11.22	11.46
Advising communities and individuals on the treatment of animals and their diseases and injuries	324001	11.19	11.25
Advising clients of additional products or services	422206	11.19	11.73
Driving and tending vans cars or taxis to transport passengers	832201	11.19	14.37
Connecting piping and equipment by bolting riveting or welding	712703	11.16	13.45
Mixing ink and solvents to standard and regulating paper and ink supply during print runs	732202	11.13	11.07
Maintaining statistics of calls made and successes achieved	524407	11.09	14.66
Ensuring that goods and services are correctly priced and displayed	522207	11.07	11.77
Operating and monitoring lifting-truck and similar equipment to load and unload transport lift and stack goods and pallets in terminals harbours ware-houses factories and other establishments	834401	11.02	14.85
Supplying information pamphlets brochures or forms	422604	11.01	12.73
Positioning lifting devices under over or around loaded pallets skids and boxes and securing material or products for transport to designated areas	834402	10.99	15.75
Making beds cleaning bathrooms supplying towels soap and related items	515106	10.98	14.25
Cleaning and sterilising examination tables and instruments and preparing materials used in the examination and treatment of animals	324004	10.95	11.16
Getting animals ready for examination or treatment and restraining or holding them during treatment	324006	10.95	11.16
Assisting veterinarians to administer anaesthetics and oxygen during treatment	324007	10.95	11.16
Placing animals in cages for recovery from operations and monitoring their condition	324008	10.95	11.16
Producing radiographs collecting samples and performing other laboratory tests to assist in diagnosis of animal health problems	324009	10.95	11.16
Taking children to and from school or outdoors for recreation	531102	10.89	11.48
Maintaining buildings greenhouses and other structures equipment and water supply systems	611309	10.86	11.28
Counting and recording money received or paid out and balancing against cash register sales records	523004	10.85	11.22
Assisting passengers with handling of luggage	832203	10.83	14.89
Operating equipment to facilitate the loading and unloading of physically challenged passengers	832208	10.83	10.95
Assisting physically challenged passengers	832207	10.74	10.80
Receiving incoming cash checking it against sales slips and other documents and preparing it for deposit at bank	523005	10.74	10.98

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Operating large volume cooking equipment such as grills deep-fat fryers or griddles	512006	10.73	10.69
Planning supervising and coordinating the work of kitchen helpers	512002	10.68	11.05
Making emergency repairs to equipment	352107	10.68	11.39
Arranging appointments for sales representatives	524404	10.67	17.53
Regulating the temperature of ovens grills roasters and other cooking equipment inspecting and cleaning the kitchen kitchen equipment serving areas to ensure safe and sanitary food handling practices	512005	10.64	11.48
Checking the quality of food	512003	10.64	10.86
Installing and repairing sheet-metal parts of vehicles and aircraft	721304	10.55	11.02
Installing and repairing cabling for computer radio telephone and television transmission	742205	10.54	17.40
Weighing measuring and mixing ingredients according to recipes and personal judgement	512004	10.52	11.61
Producing saplings bulbs and seeds and raising plants from seeds or cuttings	611307	10.51	11.61
Carrying and stacking goods in warehouses and similar establishments	933305	10.51	11.43
Sorting cargo prior to loading and unloading	933306	10.51	11.77
Demonstrating supervising and participating in activities that enhance the physical social emotional and intellectual development of children in schools and preschools	531201	10.50	10.90
Treating ill or injured animals especially for common diseases and disorders	324003	10.48	11.08
Planning meals preparing and cooking foodstuffs	512001	10.40	10.86
Sweeping or vacuum-cleaning washing and polishing floors furniture and other fixtures	515105	10.39	13.19
Picking up rubbish emptying garbage containers and taking contents to waste areas to removal	911204	10.38	11.41
Pruning and trimming trees shrubs and hedges installing plant supports and protection and rolling mowing aerating and edging lawns	611304	10.34	9.67
Operating large-volume cooking equipment such as grills deep-fat fryers or griddles	941109	10.34	14.75
Cleaning kitchens and generally helping with kitchen work including dishwashing	515107	10.32	14.33
Making beds cleaning bathrooms supplying towels soap and related items	911202	10.30	10.73
Carrying goods to be loaded on or unloaded from vans trucks wagons ships or aircraft	933302	10.29	11.75
Assisting with the ongoing management of stock such as product inventories and participating in stock takes	522304	10.27	11.20
Promoting goods and services by telephone or electronic mail following scripts and working form lists of contacts	524401	10.26	13.19
Creating interest in goods and services and seeking a sale or agreement to see sales representatives	524402	10.25	14.38
Purchasing or controlling the purchase of supplies	515102	10.24	12.22
Checking the health of plants and trees identifying and treating weeds pests and diseases and applying mulch and fertilizers	611306	10.23	12.10
Designing complex graphics and animation to satisfy functional aesthetic and creative requirements of the design brief	216605	10.22	12.51
Giving scalp treatment	514103	10.18	17.69
Giving change and issuing receipts	523002	10.17	11.27
Explaining and enforcing safety procedures rules and regulations	342306	10.16	12.86
Sweeping or vacuum-cleaning washing and polishing floors furniture and other fixtures in buildings coaches buses trams trains and aircraft	911201	10.14	10.57

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Packing office or household furniture machines appliances and related goods to be transported from one place to another	933301	9.98	11.60
Demonstrating and explaining to customers the establishment's goods and services	522302	9.91	10.40
Advising on food and beverage choices	513103	9.87	9.42
Collecting payments from customers for purchases	524506	9.86	9.70
Cleaning petrol pumps and surrounding driveway shop and facilities	524507	9.86	9.70
Invoicing or handling payments where necessary	422204	9.82	10.08
Cleaning and applying creams lotions and related products to face and parts of body	514201	9.81	12.08
Arranging appointments and collecting payments	514208	9.81	12.08
Researching and reporting on developments in specialized fields such as medicine science and technology	264205	9.78	10.15
Receiving and verifying payment by cash cheque credit card our automatic debit in stores ticket offices or similar establishments	523001	9.73	10.79
Washing dishes	911103	9.71	10.71
Greeting customers and presenting them with menus and beverage lists	513102	9.67	9.32
Scanning weighing and recording prices of goods	523007	9.67	10.73
Checking identification of customers to verify age requirements for purchase of alcohol	513207	9.65	9.51
Preparing ingredients and making sausages and similar products using chopping mixing and shaping machines	751104	9.64	10.21
Stacking and displaying goods for sale and wrapping and packing goods sold	522305	9.62	10.05
Planting trees hedges garden plants grass	611303	9.60	9.60
Training and supervising workers in production maintenance duties and health and safety precautions and hiring and discharging workers and contractors	611312	9.60	11.81
Selling goods and services accepting payment by a variety of payment methods preparing sales invoices and recording sales using cash registers	522303	9.59	9.76
Determining customer requirements and advising on product range price delivery warranties and product use and care	522301	9.57	10.48
Participating in cleaning simple repairs and maintenance of building interiors	515302	9.53	9.48
Presenting bills accepting payment and operating point of sales machines and cash registers	513107	9.51	8.91
Operating large-volume single-process cooking equipment such as grills deep-fat fryers or griddles	941103	9.49	11.52
Providing advice on hair care beauty products and hairstyles	514105	9.36	14.81
Cleaning windows and other glass surfaces	911107	9.34	9.65
Cleaning work areas and sanitizing instruments	514108	9.33	13.80
Sorting and delivering mail to private houses and businesses	441202	9.26	10.55
Taking beverage orders from serving staff or directly from patrons	513201	9.25	10.52
Tapping kegs and attaching supply lines	513205	9.25	11.04
Assisting in keeping bar properly stocked and arranging bottles and glasses	513206	9.25	10.79
Wrapping and placing merchandise in bags	523008	9.12	9.67
Operating cash register to calculate total to be paid from or to clients	523006	9.11	9.57
Examining servicing and repairing bicycles and other non-motorized transport equipment	723401	8.99	9.81
Cleaning and lubricating bearings and other moving parts	723402	8.99	9.81

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Replacing and repairing components and accessories such as brakes driving chain mechanism wheels handle bars etc.	723403	8.99	9.81
Changing tyres and controlling air pressure	723404	8.99	9.81
Assembling new bicycles wheelchairs and similar non-motorized equipment	723406	8.99	9.64
Applying knowledge of principles and practices of image and sound recording and editing in order to identify and solve problems	352103	8.98	9.39
Cutting washing tinting and waving hair	514101	8.98	14.24
Arranging appointments and collecting payments	514107	8.98	14.07
Unpacking checking weighing and storing supplies in refrigerators cupboards and other storage areas	941204	8.87	12.19
Bathing and feeding animals	516401	8.87	16.54
Cleaning organizing and disinfecting animal quarters such as pens stables cages and yards and animal equipment such as saddles and bridles	516406	8.87	16.54
Preparing and serving alcoholic and non-alcoholic drinks at a bar	513202	8.86	10.36
Washing used glassware cleaning and maintaining bar service areas tea and coffee-making areas and equipment such as espresso machines	513203	8.86	10.36
Collecting payment for sales operating cash registers and balancing cash receipts	513204	8.86	10.36
Serving snacks or other food items to customers at the bar	513210	8.86	11.14
Performing mail-handling duties in public post offices or privately owned delivery establishments	441201	8.81	8.51
Serving food and beverages to clients at tables	513105	8.80	8.52
Collecting and recording animal information such as weight size physical condition treatments received medications given and food intake	516407	8.66	15.07
Grooming animals by performing tasks such as washing brushing clipping and trimming coats cutting nails and cleaning ears	516409	8.66	15.07
Maintaining sanitation health and safety standards in work areas	941108	8.65	11.92
Setting tables with clean linen cutlery crockery and glassware	513101	8.59	8.78
Taking orders for food and drinks and passing order to kitchen or bar staff	513104	8.59	8.52
Clearing tables and returning dishes and cutlery to kitchen	513106	8.59	8.83
Preparing simple or pre-prepared foods and beverages such as sandwiches hamburgers pizzas fish and chips salads and coffee	941101	8.57	11.24
Taking and serving food and beverage orders in eating places that specialize in fast service and carry-out food	941106	8.57	10.82
Conveying goods material equipment etc. to work area removing finished pieces	932901	8.53	8.68
Carrying out manual sorting of products or components	932904	8.36	8.74
Assembling dishes for service	941203	8.34	13.30
Constructing features and facilities within gardens such as paths or paved areas walls rockeries garden beds ponds and water features sheds and fences	611305	8.26	7.91
Cleaning kitchens and generally helping with kitchen work including dishwashing	911203	7.96	9.54
Cleaning food preparation areas cooking surfaces and utensils	941105	7.66	7.73
Instructing in the use of equipment	342305	7.56	16.94
Washing dishes and cooking utensils and putting them away	941205	7.18	10.17
Assisting cooks and chefs in preparation of food by washing peeling chopping cutting up measuring and mixing ingredients	941202	7.13	11.68
Checking transferring weighing and storing supplies in refrigerators cupboards and other storage areas	941206	5.96	6.12
Washing cutting measuring and mixing foods for cooking	941102	5.93	6.72

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Cleaning kitchens food preparation areas and service areas	941201	5.75	9.14
Noting what has been sold and collecting goods needed from the stockroom	933405	5.09	6.24
Receiving opening unpacking and inspecting for damage merchandise from manufacturer or distributor	933408	5.09	6.76
Directing customers to location of articles sought	933407	4.26	5.81
Removing goods with past due use-by dates	933403	4.12	6.06
Filling shelves with goods ensuring goods with the earliest use-by dates are at the front of shelves	933402	4.11	4.97
Maintaining shelf order by removing stock belonging in a different location	933404	4.11	5.72
Obtaining articles for customers from shelf or stockroom	933406	4.11	5.64
Placing goods neatly in bins and on racks and stacking bulky goods on floors	933401	3.61	5.86

appendix 7 Country abbreviations

Country	Abbreviation
Argentina	ARG
Australia	AUS
Belarus	BLR
Belgium	BEL
Brazil	BRA
Indonesia	IDN
Kazakhstan	KAZ
Mexico	MEX
Netherlands	NLD
Russian Federation	RUS
South Africa	ZAF
Spain	ESP
United Kingdom	GBR

Bibliography

- Acemoglu, D., Autor, D.** (2011). Skills, tasks and technologies: Implications for employment and earnings. In D. Card and O. Ashenfelter (eds.), *Handbook of Labor Economics*, Elsevier, 2011, Volume 4, Part B (pp. 1043-171).
- Autor, D., Levy, F., & Murnane, R.** (2003). The skill content of recent technological change: An empirical investigation. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118, 1279-1333.
- Commission of the European Communities** (2009). Commission Regulation (EC) No 1022/2009 of 29 October 2009 amending Regulations (EC) No 1738/2005, (EC) No 698/2006 and (EC) No 377/2008 as regards the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO). *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 283/3, 30.10.2009.
- Fabo B., & Tjeldens, K.** (2014). Using Web Data to Measure the Demand for Skills (Discussion Paper No. 21). Bratislava: Central European Labour Studies Institute, CELSI http://celsi.s3.amazonaws.com/media/discussion_papers/celsi-dp-021.pdf
- Gathmann, C., & Schonberg, U.** (2010). How General Is Human Capital? A Task-Based Approach. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 28, 1-49.
- Grossman, G.M., & Rossi-Hansberg, E** (2008). Trading tasks: a simple theory of offshoring. *American Economic Review*. 98(5), 1978-1997.
- Hunter, D.** (2014). *The design principles of ISCO-08: challenges for coding occupations globally*. ILO Geneva. Presentation given at Amsterdam, Ingrid Workshop, February 10, 2014. <https://inclusivegrowth.be/events/call6-ExpertWorkshop/programme-and-presentations>.
- ILO** (2012). *International Standard Classification of Occupations ISCO-08 Volume 1 Structure, Group Definitions And Correspondence Tables*. Geneva: International Labour Office (http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_172572.pdf, accessed 17-12-2015).
- Larson, M.S.** (1977). *The rise of professionalism: A sociological analysis*. London: University of California Press.
- Mihaylov, E., & Tjeldens, K.G.** (2014). *Routine and non-routine tasks and their impact on wages*. VU University Amsterdam/University of Amsterdam. Presentation given at TASK III: Changing Tasks - Consequences for Inequality, BIBB/IAB/ZEW Conference, IAB Nuremberg, May 26-28.
- Morgeson, F.P., & Dierdorff EC** (2011). Work analysis: from technique to theory. In S. Zedeck (ed.), *APA Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology, Vol 2*. Washington DC: American Psychological Association, pp. 3-41.
- Reskin, B.F.,** (ed. 1984). *Sex segregation in the Workplace*. Washington DC: The National Academies Press.
- Tjeldens, K.G.** (2014). Reviewing the measurement and comparison of occupations across Europe. Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam, AIAS Working Paper 149 (InGRID paper T21.1), www.uva-aias.net/publications/show/1964
- Tjeldens, K.G.** (2015). *The design of a tool for the measurement of occupations in web surveys using a global index of occupations* (InGRID paper T21.3, AIAS Working Paper XX). Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam.
- Tjeldens, K.G., De Ruijter, E., & De Ruijter, J.** (2011). *Codebook and explanatory note on the EurOccupations dataset about the job content of 150 occupations* (AIAS Working Paper 11-107). Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam, www.uva-aias.net/publications/show/1412
- Tjeldens, K.G., De Ruijter, E., & De Ruijter, J.** (2012). Measuring work activities and skill requirements of occupations: Experiences from a European pilot study with a web-survey. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 36(7), 751-763.
- Tjeldens, K.G., De Ruijter, E., & De Ruijter, J.** (2014). Comparing work tasks of 160 occupations across eight European countries. *Employee Relations*, 36(2), 110-127.
- Tjeldens, K.G., Van Zijl, S., Hughie-Williams, M., Van Klaveren, M. & Steinmetz, S.** (2010). *Codebook and explanatory note on the WageIndicator dataset: A worldwide, continuous, multilingual web-survey on work and wages with paper supplements* (AIAS Working Paper 10-102). Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam, www.uva-aias.net/uploaded_files/publications/WP102-Tjeldens,vanZijl,Hughie-Williams,vKlaveren,Steinmetz.pdf
- Visintin, S., Tjeldens, K.G., Pedraza, P., & Steinmetz, S.** (2015). Wage Dispersion and Job-tasks implementation. An exploratory analysis of tasks implementation heterogeneity and its relation with wages dispersion making use of web survey data. *IZA Journal of Labour Economics*, 4:20 doi: 10.1186/s40172 (5 November 2015), <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s40172-015-0036-2>

InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

InGRID is supported by the European Union’s Seventh Programme for Research, Technological Development and Demonstration under Grant Agreement No 312691.

More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

345

Co-ordinator

Guy Van Gyes
Monique Ramioul

Partners

TÁRKI Social Research Institute Inc. (HU)
Amsterdam Institute for Advanced labour Studies, Universiteit van Amsterdam (NL)
The Swedish Institute for Social Research, Stockholms Universitet (SE)
Fachbereich IV, Wirtschafts- und Sozialstatistik, Universität Trier (DE)
Centre d'Etudis Demogràfics, Campus de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (ES)
Centre d'Etudes de Population, de Pauvreté et de Politiques Socio-Economiques (LU)
Centre for Social Policy, Universiteit Antwerpen (BE)
Institute for Social & Economic Research, University of Essex (UK)
Bremen International Graduate School of Social Sciences, Universität Bremen (DE)
Department of Dynamics of Organisations of Work, Centre d'Etudes de l'Emploi (FR)
The Centre for European Policy Studies (BE)
Dipartimento di Economica e Management, Università di Pisa (IT)
Social Statistics Division, University of Southampton (UK)
Luxembourg Income Study, asbl (LU)
WageIndicator Foundation (NL)
School of Social Sciences, The University of Manchester (UK)

InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research
Infrastructure Diffusion
Contract No 312691

For further information about
the InGRID project, please contact
inclusive.growth@kuleuven.be
www.inclusivegrowth.be
p/a HIVA – Research Institute
for Work and Society
Parkstraat 47 box 5300
3000 Leuven
Belgium